

Dissertation

**LIMEN-AI: Łukasiewicz Interpretable Markov
Engine for Neuralized AI – A Differentiable
and Interpretable Framework for Probabilistic
Logical Reasoning**

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*to my life partner Rossella
and our daughter Stella Marie*

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Abstract

This thesis develops LIMEN-AI (Łukasiewicz Interpretable Markov Engine for Neuralized AI), a novel framework for Neuralized Markov Logic Networks combining weighted first-order rules with Łukasiewicz fuzzy semantics to create an interpretable reasoning engine for EU AI Act-compliant decision support. The research addresses the tension between machine learning’s predictive power and transparency requirements mandating human understanding and oversight of automated decisions.

The theoretical foundation exploits the piecewise linearity and differentiability of Łukasiewicz fuzzy logic operations, enabling integration of explicit logical structure with gradient-based optimisation. The thesis formalises Neuralized Markov Logic Networks under Łukasiewicz semantics, proves key regularity properties including convexity of the induction loss, and establishes convergence results. The thesis develops sampling-based inference algorithms tailored to continuous fuzzy interpretations, analysing importance and power sampling for variance and computational cost. A distinctive feature is structured explanation traces recording which rules contributed to conclusions with what satisfaction degrees, providing a basis for transparency and audit requirements. A template-based induction mechanism learns weighted clauses from labelled examples using differentiable scoring, enabling knowledge base growth while maintaining interpretability.

An open-source Python implementation validates the framework on the COLIEE legal entailment benchmark (11.67% precision on 400 queries, a 46% relative improvement over BM25) and a complementary statute retrieval task (76.7% precision, 83.7% F1). The implementation integrates large language models for document ingestion and rule proposal, and features formal verification of core Łukasiewicz operations in Isabelle/HOL with 55 mechanised theorems guaranteeing correctness-by-construction.

The regulatory analysis demonstrates that LIMEN-AI’s technical properties align with EU AI Act requirements (Articles 9–15) proposing workflow patterns satisfying regulatory obligations while supporting human-AI collaboration. By demonstrating that interpretability and computational effectiveness can be achieved together, the work opens possibilities for deploying AI in high-stakes domains where accuracy and accountability are essential.

Keywords: *Neuralized Markov Logic Networks, Łukasiewicz Fuzzy Logic, Interpretable AI, Explainable AI, EU AI Act, Neural-Symbolic Integration*

Affidavit

I hereby declare that I have complied with the principles of academic integrity and that I have written this thesis independently. I have used only the sources listed in the attached bibliography, and all content taken directly or indirectly from other works is clearly identified.

I further confirm that I have not submitted this thesis, in whole or in part, for the award of any academic degree at this or any other institution.

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Symbol	Description
Logical Foundations	
Σ	Signature consisting of predicates and constants
\mathcal{P}	Set of predicate symbols
\mathcal{C}	Set of constant symbols
\mathcal{V}	Set of variable symbols
$\text{ar}(p)$	Arity of predicate p
φ, ψ	First-order logic formulas
A	Ground atom
Łukasiewicz Fuzzy Semantics	
I	Fuzzy interpretation mapping atoms to $[0, 1]$
$I(A)$	Truth degree of atom A under interpretation I
$I(\varphi)$	Truth degree of formula φ under interpretation I
$\sigma(\varphi, I)$	Satisfaction degree of formula φ under I ; equivalent to $I(\varphi)$
$T_{\mathbb{L}}(a, b)$	Łukasiewicz t-norm: $\max(0, a + b - 1)$
$S_{\mathbb{L}}(a, b)$	Łukasiewicz t-conorm: $\min(1, a + b)$
$\rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}}$	Łukasiewicz implication: $\min(1, 1 - a + b)$
$\neg_{\mathbb{L}}a$	Łukasiewicz negation: $1 - a$
$\Delta_{\mathbb{L}}$	Łukasiewicz symmetric difference
\mathcal{I}_{Σ}	Set of all fuzzy interpretations over signature Σ
Knowledge Base and Energy	
\mathcal{K}	NMLN knowledge base (set of weighted formulas)
\mathcal{F}	Set of formulas in a knowledge base
\mathbf{w}	Vector of formula weights w_1, \dots, w_m
$E(I; \mathbf{w})$	Energy function: $\sum_{i=1}^m w_i \cdot \bar{I}(\varphi_i)$
$\bar{I}(\varphi)$	Ground satisfaction degree of formula φ

Symbol	Description
$\text{Gr}(\varphi)$	Set of all groundings of formula φ
N	Number of ground atoms in domain
N_{\max}	Intractability horizon for grounding (approx. 10^7)

Probabilistic Inference

$P(I; \mathbf{w})$	Gibbs distribution: $\frac{1}{Z(\mathbf{w})} \exp(E(I; \mathbf{w}))$
$Z(\mathbf{w})$	Partition function: $\int_{\mathcal{I}_{\Sigma}} \exp(E(I; \mathbf{w})) dI$
$\mathbb{E}_P[\cdot]$	Expectation under distribution P
$Q(I)$	Proposal distribution for importance sampling
$\hat{\mu}_N$	Importance sampling estimator with N samples
$W(I)$	Importance weight for interpretation I
β	Temperature parameter for power sampling

Inductive Rule Discovery

$\mathcal{L}^+, \mathcal{L}^-$	Positive and negative label sets
\mathcal{T}	Set of rule templates
$\ell(\mathbf{w})$	Induction loss function
θ	Parameters of neural truth functions
∇	Gradient operator
λ	Regularisation parameter (L^1 or L^2)

1 Introduction

Deep learning has, by most accounts, reshaped artificial intelligence more dramatically in the past decade than any single development since the field’s founding. Networks with billions of parameters now routinely match or exceed human performance on image classification (Krizhevsky et al., 2012), speech recognition, game playing, protein folding, and natural language tasks (Vaswani et al., 2017). The excitement is understandable. But alongside the enthusiasm runs an undercurrent of unease that I suspect anyone who has tried to debug a large neural model will recognise: these systems are extraordinarily capable, yet we have remarkably little insight into how they reach their conclusions. The complexity that makes deep learning powerful is the same complexity that makes it opaque, and that opacity is not just an inconvenience—it is, as I will argue throughout this thesis, a structural problem with far-reaching consequences.

Put bluntly, modern neural networks are “black boxes.” Data goes in, high-dimensional computation happens across layers of learned weights, and an output emerges—but whatever reasoning drives the result sits distributed across millions of parameters in ways no human can parse. A convolutional network trained to recognise faces carries no internal concept of “face”; what it has found are statistical regularities in pixel distributions that correlate with facial features in its training set. The system works, often impressively well, yet the gap between how it operates and how a domain expert would explain the same judgment is vast—and the gap has consequences that grow more serious once these systems begin making decisions that affect people’s lives.

Figure 1 shows what researchers call the “interpretability spectrum.” Deep neural networks and large language models sit at the opaque extreme; linear models and shallow decision trees sit near the transparent pole, their decision boundaries open to direct inspection—though at the price of limited representational capacity. Most real systems land somewhere in between. The question driving this thesis is whether the gap can be narrowed: can an architecture learn as flexibly as a neural network while remaining genuinely comprehensible to the domain experts who must trust and oversee it?

Opacity becomes acutely problematic when AI systems make decisions that affect people directly. A mortgage denied, an asylum claim rejected, a parole

Figure 1: The interpretability spectrum in machine learning. Traditional deep neural networks occupy the opaque end, while linear models and decision trees offer greater transparency. LIMEN-AI positions itself toward the transparent end by maintaining explicit logical structure while achieving the learning capabilities typically associated with neural approaches. Source: Author.

recommendation that goes unexplained—in each case, the person on the receiving end cannot understand the reasoning behind the outcome, let alone challenge it. I find this troubling as a concrete failure of accountability: if a system’s decision cannot be inspected, the affected individual is left with an algorithmic verdict delivered without reasons.

Take the seemingly mundane case of a loan rejection. The model behind the decision may perform well in aggregate, but the individual applicant sitting across from a bank officer cannot verify whether the assessment was fair in their particular circumstances. Perhaps erroneous data inflated their estimated risk. Perhaps a small change in their financial profile would have tipped the balance toward approval. Without access to the model’s reasoning, none of this can be ascertained, and the rejection feels—and may in fact be—arbitrary. Trust in the institution erodes, and the technology that was meant to make lending decisions more consistent instead makes them less legible.

Stakes rise sharply when AI systems make consequential errors. A diagnostic mistake in medicine demands investigation; clinicians must trace what went wrong to prevent recurrence. Hiring tools that systematically disadvantage particular demographic groups need scrutiny aimed at locating exactly where bias enters the pipeline. When an autonomous vehicle is involved in an accident, regulators must reconstruct a chain of computational decisions that unfolded in milliseconds. Across all these settings, opacity blocks the corrective feedback loops on which safe, fair deployment depends.

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) grew out of precisely this frustration. Over the past decade, researchers have assembled a broad—and still expanding—toolkit for prying open black-box models (Barredo Arrieta et al., 2020; Guidotti et al., 2019). Two post-hoc techniques have become especially prominent: LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations) and SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) (Lundberg and Lee, 2017; Ribeiro et al., 2016). Both construct simpler surrogate models that approximate how a complex classifier behaves near a particular input, but they go about it differently. LIME perturbs the input, watches how predictions shift, and fits a local linear model to those shifts, flagging the features whose perturbation matters most. SHAP takes a game-theoretic route, allocating to each feature a contribution score derived from its marginal effect on the prediction across every possible coalition of features.

These methods have undeniable practical value. Practitioners rely on them to gain at least partial visibility into opaque models, and they can surface genuine problems—a classifier latching onto a spurious background feature, or a risk model assigning disproportionate weight to a legally protected attribute. Even a rough indication of which factors drove a decision is better than none. Post-hoc explanation techniques have, however, attracted criticism that I find well-founded.

The fundamental problem is that post-hoc explanations approximate, rather than reproduce, the model’s actual reasoning. No guarantee ensures these approximations are faithful. LIME explanations can be unstable under small input perturbations, producing substantially different explanations for nearly identical inputs (Doshi-Velez and Kim, 2017; Rudin, 2019). SHAP values depend on the choice of background distribution and can shift under different selections. Attention weights in neural networks, suggestive as they are, need not reflect the causal importance of input features—a model may attend to certain inputs without relying on them for its predictions.

At a deeper level, any post-hoc explanation is a simplification—a story told about the model through the lens of the explanation method. That story may be locally accurate yet miss the broader decision landscape, and its intuitive appeal may owe more to the smoothing of genuine complexity than to fidelity. In the worst case, a clean explanation creates a false sense of understanding, convincing stakeholders they comprehend a system whose full behaviour is far more erratic than the narrative suggests. A tool meant to foster accountability can instead furnish a reassuring but

misleading gloss.

These shortcomings have not gone unnoticed. A growing camp of researchers—Cynthia Rudin most vocally among them—has argued that the entire post-hoc enterprise may be misguided for high-stakes settings. Her influential commentary, “Stop Explaining Black Box Machine Learning Models for High Stakes Decisions and Use Interpretable Models Instead” (Rudin, 2019), does not contend that neural networks are useless; they plainly are not. What it does contend is that practitioners too often reach for a complex model and then bolt on an explanation, when a natively interpretable model might have delivered comparable accuracy with none of the epistemological baggage. In domains where the marginal predictive gain from a black box is small, the loss of transparency is a poor trade.

I take the argument for inherent interpretability seriously. Instead of asking how to explain an opaque model after the fact, the thesis asks how to design reasoning systems that are transparent from the outset—systems whose structure directly encodes inference in a form experts can inspect, understand, and validate without post-hoc approximation. The answer draws on statistical relational learning and, specifically, on a reformulation of Markov Logic Networks using fuzzy semantics that achieves differentiability while preserving explicit logical structure.

1.1 The Regulatory Context: The EU AI Act

Until recently, the call for interpretability was largely an academic and ethical one. That changed in August 2024, when the European Union’s Artificial Intelligence Act entered into force (European Parliament and Council, 2024). The Act is, to date, the most ambitious legislative effort to regulate AI development and deployment anywhere in the world, and it goes well beyond generic disclosure mandates. What makes it particularly relevant to this thesis is its frank acknowledgment that the technical architecture of an AI system is not a neutral engineering choice—it has direct consequences for fundamental rights, public safety, and the accountability mechanisms on which democratic governance depends.

Figure 2 shows the Act’s risk tiers. At the apex, certain uses are banned outright—subliminal behavioural manipulation, exploitation of vulnerable groups, government-run social scoring, and, with narrow exceptions, real-time biometric identification in public spaces. The legislature’s reasoning is blunt: no conceivable

Figure 2: The EU AI Act’s risk-based classification framework. Systems at higher risk levels face more stringent regulatory requirements. High-risk systems, which include AI used in critical infrastructure, employment, and essential services, must satisfy comprehensive obligations for transparency, human oversight, accuracy, and documentation. Source: Author.

benefit justifies these applications. Below the outright prohibition, tiers impose progressively lighter obligations, from extensive transparency and oversight for high-risk systems down to essentially no restrictions for minimal-risk applications such as spam filters.

The high-risk tier is the one that matters here. The Act draws that category broadly, sweeping in critical infrastructure, educational gatekeeping, hiring tools, credit scoring, law-enforcement risk assessments, migration management, and the administration of justice. Different as these domains are, they share a defining trait: the decisions made within them are hard or impossible to undo, and the people affected have a pressing interest in knowing why the outcome went as it did. Accordingly, the Act imposes obligations that follow high-risk systems across their entire lifecycle, well beyond a one-time disclosure at deployment.

Article 13 spells out what transparency means in practice. High-risk systems “shall be designed and developed in such a way as to ensure that their operation is sufficiently transparent to enable users to interpret the system’s output and use it appropriately.” Notice the wording: the obligation is architectural, not informational. It is not enough to publish a data sheet or a model card; the system itself must be built so that its workings admit of interpretation. When a recommendation or decision touches an individual’s interests, there must be a genuine pathway by which the basis for that output can be reconstructed.

Article 14 pushes the point further with human oversight mandates. Oversight mechanisms must be baked into the design from the start and sustained throughout

operation. The people assigned to oversight roles must be able to “fully understand the capacities and limitations of the high-risk AI system,” “properly monitor its operation,” “remain aware of the possible tendency to automatically rely on or over-rely on the output,” “correctly interpret the high-risk AI system’s output,” and “decide, in any particular situation, not to use the high-risk AI system or otherwise disregard, override, or reverse the output.” In plain terms, the system must serve human judgment, not replace it, and its outputs must be legible enough to support genuine review rather than rubber-stamping.

Table 2: Key EU AI Act requirements for high-risk systems and their implications for system design. Source: Author.

Article	Requirement Summary	Design Implications
Art. 9: Risk Management	Continuous risk identification and mitigation throughout life-cycle	Architecture must support ongoing monitoring and intervention
Art. 10: Data Governance	Training data must be relevant, representative, and free from errors	Data provenance and quality must be documented and verifiable
Art. 11: Documentation	Technical documentation describing system logic and design choices	System reasoning must be expressible in documentable form
Art. 12: Record-Keeping	Automatic logging of events during operation	Inference process must generate auditable traces
Art. 13: Transparency	Operation sufficiently transparent for users to interpret outputs	Architecture must support meaningful explanation
Art. 14: Human Oversight	Humans must be able to understand, monitor, and override system	Outputs must be interpretable; interventions must be feasible
Art. 15: Accuracy & Robustness	Appropriate levels of accuracy and resilience to errors	Performance bounds must be characterisable and verifiable

Table 2 pulls these requirements together. Collectively, they amount to a mandate for interpretability by design. Post-hoc explanations grafted onto an opaque model may fall short of Article 13 if they do not faithfully reflect the system’s actual reasoning. The oversight provisions presuppose that operators can genuinely comprehend and, when necessary, override outputs—hard to guarantee when the model itself resists inspection. Even the record-keeping articles carry an implicit assumption: that the system’s logic can be expressed in terms an auditor could follow.

For the purposes of this thesis, the implication is direct: interpretable AI is now a binding legal obligation for any high-risk deployment within the European Union. That fact supplies both the motivation and the design constraint for LIMEN-AI, which must achieve a form of transparency that an auditor could credibly evaluate against Articles 9–15.

1.2 Statistical Relational Learning and the Promise of Logic

If interpretability is the goal, symbolic approaches to knowledge representation are the obvious place to look—and for good reason. During the first several decades of AI research, the dominant paradigm was precisely this: represent knowledge as logical formulas, production rules, or semantic networks, and reason over those representations using well-understood inference procedures. The appeal for interpretability is immediate. A lending rule that says “flag for review any applicant with a credit score below 600 and a debt-to-income ratio above 0.4” can be read, questioned, and revised by a domain expert without any specialised tooling. If the rule produces an undesirable outcome, the source of the problem is right there in the rule itself, and fixing it is a matter of editing or removing a single explicit statement.

The trouble, as decades of experience have made clear, is that classical symbolic AI comes with serious practical limitations. Extracting the necessary rules from human experts is laborious and expensive—the so-called knowledge acquisition bottleneck. Experts often know more than they can articulate, and what they do articulate may turn out to be incomplete or subtly inconsistent. Keeping a large rule base current as the domain evolves is itself a nontrivial engineering challenge. More fundamentally, classical logic is brittle in the face of real-world data. It operates in a binary world where propositions are either true or false, and a single missing fact or minor inconsistency can derail an entire chain of inference. Real data, of course, is noisy, partial, and uncertain—precisely the conditions under which rigid logical systems perform worst.

It was these shortcomings that pushed the field toward statistical and neural methods—systems that could learn from data and tolerate uncertainty without requiring every rule to be hand-written. The shift solved some problems but introduced others. Conventional machine learning algorithms operate on flat feature vectors, each example encoded as a fixed-length list of attribute values. That encoding works

poorly in domains whose structure is inherently relational: social networks, molecular graphs, knowledge bases, multi-agent systems—settings where the objects and the links between them vary from example to example.

Figure 3: Statistical Relational Learning emerges from the recognition that the strengths of classical logic (interpretability, compositionality, relational structure) and statistical learning (uncertainty handling, learning from data) are complementary. SRL frameworks like Markov Logic Networks combine these strengths. Source: Author.

Statistical Relational Learning (SRL) grew out of a pragmatic observation that Figure 3 makes visual: the weaknesses of symbolic AI and statistical learning happen to be complementary (De Raedt et al., 2016). Logic handles relational structure and compositionality well but chokes on noise; statistical models tolerate noise but flatten relational structure into feature vectors. SRL weaves the two together, pairing first-order logic’s expressiveness with probabilistic models’ capacity for uncertainty so that one framework can represent rich relational structures, learn from noisy data, and reason under genuine uncertainty.

Markov Logic Networks (MLNs), introduced by Richardson and Domingos (Richardson and Domingos, 2006) and rooted in earlier work on probabilistic logic (Nilsson, 1986), are the SRL framework most relevant to this thesis. The core idea can be stated in a sentence: attach a real-valued weight to each first-order formula, so that logic becomes soft rather than brittle. An MLN is then a collection of such weighted formulas. Given a finite set of constants (the objects in the domain), every formula is grounded—variables replaced by constants in all possible ways—yielding a set of ground formulas that serve as features in a log-linear model over possible

worlds.

The probability distribution defined by an MLN takes the form:

$$P(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{Z} \exp \left(\sum_i w_i n_i(\mathbf{x}) \right) \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x} is a possible world (an assignment of truth values to all ground atoms), w_i is the weight of the i -th formula, $n_i(\mathbf{x})$ is the number of true groundings of the i -th formula in world \mathbf{x} , and Z is a normalisation constant ensuring that probabilities sum to one. Higher weights indicate stronger constraints: a formula with infinite weight is a hard constraint that must be satisfied in all possible worlds, while a formula with finite weight is a soft constraint that can be violated with a penalty proportional to its weight.

$$P(\text{world}) \propto \exp(w_1 \cdot n_1 + w_2 \cdot n_2 + \dots)$$

Worlds satisfying high-weight formulas receive higher probability

Figure 4: Structure of a Markov Logic Network. Weighted first-order formulas (left) are grounded by substituting constants for variables, producing ground formulas (right) that define features in a log-linear model. The probability of each possible world depends exponentially on the weighted sum of satisfied formulas. Source: Author.

Figure 4 illustrates the structure. Logical and probabilistic reasoning reinforce each other here: worlds in which many high-weight formulas hold receive higher probability, and violating an important constraint incurs a cost proportional to its weight. Because the knowledge base consists of explicit logical formulas, a domain expert can inspect them, understand the relationships they encode, and judge whether those relationships are sensible. Weights add a quantitative dimension—they say which constraints matter and by how much. Inference can, at least in principle, be traced through the logical structure, so one can explain which rules supported a given conclusion.

Despite their conceptual appeal, classical MLNs have not achieved the widespread adoption one might expect—largely for computational reasons. The most immediate

obstacle is inference: computing the partition function Z in Equation 1 requires summing over 2^n possible worlds for a domain with n ground atoms. Even moderately sized domains make exact computation infeasible. Approximate methods such as Gibbs sampling and belief propagation help, but multimodal distributions arising from complex rule interactions can trap samplers in local modes, and convergence can be slow.

A second bottleneck is grounding. Before inference can proceed, every formula must be instantiated with all possible combinations of constants— $O(n^k)$ ground formulas for a formula with k variables over n constants. In richly relational domains, this count can explode, consuming both memory and computation. Lazy grounding and relevance-based pruning mitigate the problem but have not eliminated it.

Most fundamentally for the purposes of this thesis, classical MLNs use Boolean semantics: each ground atom is either true or false, creating discontinuities in the energy landscape that block gradient-based optimisation. Weight learning therefore falls back on pseudo-likelihood estimation, contrastive divergence, or gradient-based boosting (Khot et al., 2015)—methods with their own scalability and convergence limitations. Structure learning, discovering the formulas themselves from data, is harder still, typically demanding heuristic search through a combinatorially vast space of candidates.

1.3 Neural-Symbolic Integration: Bridging Two Paradigms

Neither purely symbolic nor purely neural approaches have proved sufficient on their own, and this recognition has fueled what is sometimes called a “third wave” in AI: neural-symbolic integration (Garcez and Lamb, 2023). The ambition is to fuse neural networks’ ability to discover patterns in raw, noisy data with the compositionality and transparency of symbolic representations—rules, abstract reasoning, structures a human can read and critique. Behind this ambition lies a simple intuition: human cognition appears to involve both fast perceptual pattern-matching and slow deliberate reasoning, and there is no obvious reason an artificial system should have to choose one or the other.

The design space is wide. Neural theorem provers learn to steer proof search; neural program synthesisers produce symbolic code. Logical constraints can be imposed on a neural model’s predictions, or symbolic knowledge can reshape the

training loss landscape. A third family pipelines the two modes, letting a neural front-end extract symbolic entities from raw input for downstream logical inference. These strategies differ sharply in transparency, scalability, and expressiveness, yet they share a conviction that the strongest, most trustworthy systems will draw on both traditions.

Figure 5: The landscape of neural-symbolic integration approaches. Each system makes different trade-offs between expressiveness, efficiency, and interpretability. LIMEN-AI distinguishes itself through its combination of Markov Logic foundations with Łukasiewicz fuzzy semantics, maintaining fully explicit rule structure. Source: Author.

Figure 5 surveys several of the most developed frameworks. Logic Tensor Networks (LTN) treat predicates as small neural networks—entity embeddings go in, fuzzy truth values come out (Serafini and Garcez, 2016). Differentiable fuzzy semantics let LTN optimise both neural predicates and logical parameters by gradient descent, capturing intricate non-linear relationships under logical guidance. The cost: what the network has learned stays locked inside weight matrices rather than surfacing as human-readable rules.

DeepProbLog extends probabilistic logic programming with neural predicates and compiles the resulting programs into differentiable arithmetic circuits (Manhaeve et al., 2018). Each ground atom carries a probability; the circuit structure enables efficient gradient computation, useful for tasks blending perception (e.g., recognising handwritten digits) with symbolic reasoning (e.g., checking arithmetic). Compilation,

however, transforms the program into a form that no longer resembles a logic program, making natural-language explanation hard.

Scallop couples Datalog-style logic with differentiable provenance semirings (Li et al., 2024, 2023b). Its compilation pipeline supports probabilistic, weighted, and top- k reasoning modes; the provenance mechanism records which facts contributed to each conclusion—a useful, if partial, form of explainability. Scallop has demonstrated strong compositional generalisation on visual question answering, knowledge graph completion, and program synthesis benchmarks.

On the inductive side, differentiable ILP systems learn logical rules directly from examples while keeping inference differentiable, so that rule learning can be integrated with neural perception modules (Shindo et al., 2023, 2024). By parsing visual scenes into symbolic objects and reasoning over them with learned rules, these systems show that logical structure can steer learning even in perceptual domains.

Relational neural machines occupy yet another corner of the design space, embedding entities and relations as neural vectors while enforcing logical constraints that channel the learning process (Marra et al., 2020). The resulting systems perform well on tasks requiring both perceptual grounding and relational reasoning, though the learned representations remain sub-symbolic.

The trade-offs deserve candid acknowledgment. LTN’s neural predicates capture rich relationships but hide them in opaque matrices. DeepProbLog’s circuit compilation buys speed at the cost of readability—the compiled form bears little resemblance to the original logic program. Scallop’s provenance tracking identifies which facts mattered yet cannot look inside the neural modules that produced those facts.

None of this is necessarily a flaw; for many applications, sacrificing some transparency for better scalability or richer expressiveness is entirely reasonable. But the applications I am most concerned with are those where the reasoning process must be transparent, auditable, and documentable. In high-stakes, regulated settings, a system that cannot explain its inferences in terms a human can follow may not be deployable at all.

LIMEN-AI is designed with this constraint front and centre. It maintains an explicit knowledge base of weighted first-order formulas throughout inference, rather than encoding predicates in neural networks or compiling logic into opaque circuits. Łukasiewicz fuzzy semantics supply the differentiability needed for gradient-based learning while leaving the symbolic structure intact and inspectable. The result is

a system whose reasoning can be traced, audited, and documented at every step—properties that, as I have argued, are indispensable for the domains this thesis addresses.

1.4 The LIMEN-AI Approach

LIMEN-AI—Łukasiewicz Interpretable Markov Engine for Neuralized AI—weds the weighted rules of Markov Logic Networks to Łukasiewicz fuzzy semantics. The result is a reasoning engine that is differentiable yet keeps its logical structure explicit from start to finish. The enabling insight is straightforward: Łukasiewicz logic operations are piecewise linear and therefore differentiable almost everywhere, so gradient-based optimisation can be applied directly without compressing the symbolic representation into an opaque numeric form.

In Łukasiewicz logic, first introduced in the 1920s (Łukasiewicz, 1920) and later formalised extensively by Hájek (Hájek, 1998), truth values range over the unit interval $[0, 1]$, providing a smooth generalisation of Boolean logic where 0 represents complete falsehood, 1 represents complete truth, and intermediate values represent partial or graded truth. The logical connectives are interpreted through continuous operations:

$$\text{Negation: } \neg_{\mathbb{L}} a = 1 - a \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Conjunction: } T_{\mathbb{L}}(a, b) = \max(0, a + b - 1) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Disjunction: } S_{\mathbb{L}}(a, b) = \min(1, a + b) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Implication: } a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b = \min(1, 1 - a + b) \quad (5)$$

Figure 6 visualises the conjunction and implication operations as surfaces over the unit square. The geometric structure of these surfaces reveals why Łukasiewicz logic is so well-suited to differentiable reasoning. Both surfaces are composed of flat planar regions that meet along edges. Within each planar region, the function is linear and hence differentiable with a constant gradient. The edges where regions meet form a set of measure zero where the function is continuous but not differentiable. For practical purposes, this means that gradients exist and can be computed at almost all points, enabling standard gradient-based optimisation techniques.

Figure 6: Łukasiewicz fuzzy operations visualised as surfaces over the unit square. The conjunction (top) achieves its maximum only when both inputs are fully true, dropping to zero along a diagonal where $a + b \leq 1$. The implication (bottom) is fully satisfied (value 1) whenever $a \leq b$, decreasing linearly as the antecedent exceeds the consequent. The piecewise linear structure ensures differentiability almost everywhere. Source: Author.

Piecewise linearity pays off at every nesting depth: composing piecewise linear maps yields another piecewise linear map, so the satisfaction degree of even deeply nested formulas remains piecewise linear in the atomic truth values. Gradients with respect to truth values or formula weights therefore exist almost everywhere and can be computed by automatic differentiation, much as one would back-propagate through a neural network.

Classical MLNs, bound to Boolean semantics, face discontinuities that block gradient-based learning. Under Łukasiewicz semantics those discontinuities vanish: the resulting Neuralized MLN admits end-to-end differentiable optimisation. Weights are learned by descending an energy function that quantifies how well the knowledge base is satisfied; truth values are adjusted to maximise consistency with observed evidence. Because the computation graph is standard, it slots into PyTorch or any comparable framework, and gradients flow without interruption between symbolic reasoning and any upstream neural perception module.

Figure 7: Architecture of the LIMEN-AI framework. A knowledge base comprises a signature, weighted first-order rules, and a truth assignment mapping atoms to fuzzy values. The energy function aggregates weighted satisfaction degrees using Łukasiewicz semantics. Automatic differentiation enables gradient computation, supporting weight learning, sampling-based inference, and inductive rule discovery. All components maintain explicit logical structure, enabling generation of human-readable explanations alongside predictions. Source: Author.

Figure 7 lays out how these pieces fit together. A domain signature (predicates and constants) pairs with a collection of weighted first-order formulas and a truth assignment ν that maps every ground atom to $[0, 1]$. An energy function aggregates the weighted satisfaction degrees of all formulas under ν ; because Łukasiewicz semantics keep everything differentiable, that energy can be differentiated with respect to both weights and truth values. Three capabilities follow: gradient-based weight learning, sampling-based inference for query probabilities, and an inductive rule discovery module that proposes and scores new formulas from labelled examples.

What sets LIMEN-AI apart from a purely neural system is that interpretability is built into the representation itself. The knowledge base consists of explicit weighted first-order formulas, each one readable by a domain expert without specialised visualisation tools. Knowledge sits in discrete rules whose individual contributions to a prediction can be isolated and examined. The inference engine produces structured traces recording which rules fired, to what degree, and how their contributions combined—a natural audit trail. Because truth values range continuously over $[0, 1]$, the system communicates both what it concluded and how strongly the evidence supported that conclusion.

The name LIMEN-AI encodes the approach: Łukasiewicz semantics for differentiability, Interpretability as a design principle, Markov Logic for probabilistic structure, and an Engine for Neuralized AI reasoning. “Limen”—Latin for threshold—signals the framework’s position at the boundary between symbolic and neural paradigms.

In practice, this means LIMEN-AI can work alongside neural perception modules without sacrificing its interpretability guarantees. A neural network might extract entities and relationships from unstructured text, for example, and feed those extracted facts into a LIMEN-AI knowledge base for downstream reasoning. The boundary between the two components is explicit and deliberate: the neural module handles perception, and LIMEN-AI handles inference. Everything on the inference side—the rules, their weights, and the traces they produce—remains fully transparent and auditable, even though the upstream perception may involve an opaque learned model.

This architectural separation has a practical payoff that goes beyond compliance. When a LIMEN-AI system produces an unexpected or questionable result, the debugging process can be decomposed cleanly. If the problem originates in perception—an entity missed, a relationship misclassified—then standard neural network diagnostics

apply. If the problem lies in the reasoning layer, one can inspect the rules directly, examine the inference trace, and identify which formulas contributed to the erroneous conclusion. I find this kind of principled decomposition difficult to achieve with end-to-end neural systems, where the source of an error can be anywhere in a monolithic computation graph.

1.5 Research Questions and Objectives

Building LIMEN-AI forces a series of interdependent decisions: the choice of truth-value semantics constrains which algorithms are feasible; algorithmic properties determine what the software can compute; and the software’s capabilities decide whether the framework meets regulatory requirements. The five research questions below organise these dependencies.

RQ1: Theoretical Foundations. How can Markov Logic Networks be formalised under Łukasiewicz fuzzy semantics in a way that preserves differentiability while maintaining interpretability? What are the regularity properties of the resulting energy function, and what convergence guarantees can be established for gradient-based learning? Chapter 3 answers with a formalisation establishing five key theorems: energy function properties (Theorem 3.1), piecewise linearity of Łukasiewicz operations (Theorem 3.2), piecewise linearity of the satisfaction degree (Theorem 3.3), gradients of the energy function (Theorem 3.4), and convergence of gradient ascent (Theorem 3.5). Differentiability follows as corollaries (Corollaries 3.1–3.2). Appendix B provides mechanised Isabelle/HOL proof certificates for 55 supporting lemmas and theorems.

RQ2: Inference Algorithms. What sampling-based inference algorithms suit Neuralized MLNs with fuzzy truth values, and how can they produce explanation traces supporting transparency and audit requirements? Chapter 4 develops two complementary algorithms: importance sampling (Algorithm 1) for unimodal energy landscapes, with variance bounds in Theorem 4.4, and power sampling with replica exchange (Algorithm 2) for multimodal distributions, whose convergence Theorem 4.3 guarantees via detailed balance. Both produce structured explanation traces (Algorithm 3) decomposing results into weighted rule contributions, directly addressing Article 13. Sample complexity analysis characterises the number of samples needed for specified confidence levels.

RQ3: Inductive Learning. How can new weighted rules be learned from labelled examples while preserving the explicit logical structure of the knowledge base? Chapter 5 introduces a template-based induction mechanism (Algorithm 4) that generates candidate rules from syntactic patterns encoding structures such as transitivity, symmetry, and composition. A differentiable scoring function (Section 5.4) measures how well candidates explain training data; convexity (Theorem 5.2) ensures efficient gradient-based optimisation. A beam search balances exploration against tractability, maintaining a priority queue of partially instantiated candidates. Integration with large language models lets domain experts propose candidate templates in natural language, which the system formalises, evaluates, and ranks.

RQ4: Practical Implementation. Can the theoretical framework be realised in software that demonstrates viability for real-world applications? Chapter 6 describes the open-source Python library implementing LIMEN-AI, with tensor-based energy computation leveraging PyTorch for automatic differentiation and GPU acceleration. Correctness is verified through unit tests comparing outputs against hand-calculated results for small knowledge bases; performance benchmarks validate the complexity analyses from the theoretical chapters. On the Competition on Legal Information Extraction/Entailment (COLIEE) legal entailment benchmark, LIMEN-AI achieved 11.67% precision—a 46% relative improvement over BM25’s 8.00%—on 400 queries, with every prediction accompanied by a logical justification trace. The complete codebase and documentation are publicly available.

RQ5: Regulatory Alignment. How do LIMEN-AI’s technical properties align with the EU AI Act, and what workflow patterns enable compliant integration into organisational decision processes? Chapter 7 maps each requirement of Articles 9–15 to specific LIMEN-AI capabilities. Explicit weighted rules address transparency (Art. 13); explanation traces support human oversight (Art. 14); formal verification in Appendix B contributes to accuracy and robustness documentation (Art. 15). Reference workflows for cybersecurity anomaly detection, financial risk assessment, and legal contract analysis illustrate integration with human review checkpoints, audit trails, and intervention protocols. The analysis also identifies areas where organisational measures must supplement the technical architecture.

The five questions form a chain: RQ1 feeds RQ2, whose algorithms ground the implementation in RQ4, which in turn enables the regulatory analysis of RQ5; RQ3 cuts across by extending the learning loop. The corresponding objectives translate

these questions into concrete deliverables:

O1. Develop a complete formal framework for Neuralized Markov Logic Networks under Łukasiewicz semantics, including syntax, semantics, energy functions, and probabilistic interpretation, with rigorous proofs of key properties, including piecewise linearity, differentiability, and convergence of gradient-based weight learning.

O2. Design and analyse sampling-based inference algorithms for fuzzy MLNs, including importance sampling and power sampling schemes, with a characterisation of their variance, sample complexity, computational cost, and explanation trace generation capabilities.

O3. Develop a mechanism for inductive rule discovery that uses template-based instantiation and differentiable scoring to learn new weighted clauses from labelled examples, along with an analysis of convergence properties and interpretability preservation.

O4. Implement the framework as an open-source Python library with integration capabilities for large language models and deep learning frameworks, demonstrating practical viability through comprehensive testing and documentation.

O5. Analyse the alignment between LIMEN-AI’s technical properties and EU AI Act requirements, propose reference workflow patterns for regulatory-compliant deployment, and identify both the strengths and limitations of the approach.

1.6 Research Methodology

Four methodological strands run through this thesis—theoretical analysis, algorithm design, software implementation, and regulatory analysis—and their interplay matters as much as any single strand.

Figure 8 shows the dependencies. Theory feeds algorithm design, which feeds implementation; all three feed the regulatory analysis. The arrows also run backwards: bugs uncovered during implementation have, on more than one occasion, forced revisions to an algorithm, and algorithms have sometimes exposed unstated assumptions in the theoretical development.

The theoretical work follows the conventions of mathematical logic and theoretical computer science: standard notation from first-order logic, probability, and optimisation; results formulated as theorems and proved in full; complexity bounds derived from established techniques. I build incrementally—each result rests only on

Figure 8: Research methodology combining four interconnected strands: theoretical development establishing mathematical foundations, algorithm design specifying computational procedures, software implementation demonstrating practical viability, and regulatory analysis connecting technical properties to legal requirements. Source: Author.

what has already been proved—and scatter hand-calculable pedagogical examples throughout, so that readers can verify each step against a concrete instance.

Algorithms are specified in precise pseudocode with explicit inputs, outputs, and preconditions. Correctness arguments link each algorithm back to mathematical definitions; time and space complexity are analysed as functions of the relevant problem parameters; for iterative procedures I prove convergence under stated assumptions and characterise the rate.

The Python implementation mirrors the theoretical structure in its module layout. Unit tests systematically compare computational outputs against hand-calculated examples from the theory chapters—an approach that has caught subtle bugs more than once. Performance benchmarks validate the complexity predictions; the entire codebase is released under an open-source licence.

Regulatory analysis, the last strand, differs in kind. It reads the EU AI Act and its emerging interpretive guidance closely, maps LIMEN-AI’s capabilities onto the specific obligations for high-risk systems, identifies where the mapping holds and where organisational measures must compensate, and proposes reference workflows for three illustrative domains.

A word on intellectual honesty. Throughout the thesis I have tried to keep the boundary between proof and experiment clearly marked. Theoretical claims rest on definitions, theorems, and complexity bounds that can be checked on paper (or, in

this case, mechanically in Isabelle). Practical viability is a separate matter: it is demonstrated through the software implementation (Chapter 6) and validated against the COLIEE legal entailment benchmark, where the framework delivered measurable improvements over baselines. The pedagogical examples scattered through the chapters are exactly what they claim to be—small, hand-calculable scenarios meant to build intuition, not to substitute for empirical evaluation.

I do not pretend that LIMEN-AI is a universal solution. It is a framework designed for settings where interpretability is non-negotiable, and it inherits the scalability constraints that come with logic-based reasoning. Those constraints, together with expressiveness trade-offs and the distance still remaining between the theoretical framework and full empirical validation, are discussed openly throughout the thesis. Where a limitation points toward a productive research direction, I say so.

1.7 Thesis Structure

Nine chapters and two appendices progress from foundational theory through algorithms and implementation to regulatory analysis. Each chapter builds on its predecessors; the outline below sketches the arc.

Chapter 2 surveys five areas—statistical relational learning (focusing on MLNs), neural-symbolic integration, Łukasiewicz fuzzy logic, explainable AI, and the EU AI Act—using the PRISMA systematic review methodology to map the landscape and pinpoint the research gaps LIMEN-AI addresses.

Chapter 3 builds the mathematical scaffolding. Starting from the syntax of Neuralized MLNs (signatures, terms, atoms, formulas, grounding), it introduces Łukasiewicz semantics and proves that the satisfaction degree of any formula is piecewise linear in atomic truth degrees (Theorem 3.3). The energy function is defined, its Boltzmann-distribution reading established, and further regularity results proved: energy function properties (Theorem 3.1), piecewise linearity of Łukasiewicz operations (Theorem 3.2), gradients of the energy function (Theorem 3.4), and convergence of gradient ascent (Theorem 3.5), with differentiability following as corollaries (Corollaries 3.1–3.2). Hand-calculable examples on small knowledge bases ground each concept; Appendix B confirms all results through 55 mechanically checked Isabelle/HOL theorems.

Chapter 4 shifts to computation. After showing that exact inference is in-

tractable even for small knowledge bases (Theorem 4.1), it develops two sampling algorithms: importance sampling (Algorithm 1, variance bounded by Theorem 4.4) and power sampling with replica exchange (Algorithm 2, convergence guaranteed by Theorem 4.3 via detailed balance). Both emit structured explanation traces (Algorithm 3) decomposing each answer into weighted rule contributions—directly addressing Article 13’s transparency mandate.

Chapter 5 tackles the harder learning problem: discovering new rules, not just tuning weights. Template-based generation constrains the search space to patterns such as transitivity, symmetry, and composition; a differentiable scoring function (Section 5.4) grades candidates against labelled data; beam search (Algorithm 4) explores the most promising candidates while pruning the rest. Convexity of the scoring landscape (Theorem 5.2) ensures gradient-based optimisation finds high-quality rules. An LLM-assisted pipeline lets domain experts propose candidate templates in natural language, which the system formalises, evaluates, and ranks.

Chapter 6 turns theory into software. The open-source Python library layers a `KnowledgeBase` core (signatures, formulas, interpretations) over scalar and tensor-based (PyTorch) energy modules, sampling-based inference with configurable proposals, and an orchestrator for LLM integration. Unit tests cross-check every module against hand-calculated examples. On the COLIEE legal entailment benchmark, LIMEN-AI achieved a 46% relative precision improvement over baselines on 400 queries, with every prediction accompanied by a logical justification trace.

Chapter 7 maps LIMEN-AI’s capabilities onto the EU AI Act’s requirements—transparency, oversight, documentation, record-keeping, risk management, accuracy, and robustness—and proposes deployment workflows for cybersecurity anomaly detection, financial risk assessment, and legal contract analysis, flagging areas where organisational measures must supplement the technical architecture.

Chapter 8 situates LIMEN-AI relative to LTN, DeepProbLog, Scallop, and classical MLNs, weighing trade-offs candidly and acknowledging scalability constraints, expressiveness limits, and the remaining gap to full empirical validation. Future directions—lifted inference, richer template languages, broader benchmarking—are laid out.

Chapter 9 synthesises the contributions and reflects on their implications for building AI systems that are both effective and accountable.

Appendix B reproduces the Isabelle/HOL formalisation in full: 19 theorems

on Łukasiewicz operations and well-formedness, 16 theorems on algebraic laws (commutativity, associativity, monotonicity, De Morgan), 15 theorems on formula satisfaction and energy-function properties, and 5 theorems on piecewise linearity—55 in total. The source files are provided for independent verification—an unusual level of formal assurance for neurosymbolic AI, and one that is particularly relevant for safety-critical deployments.

1.8 Contributions

The original contributions span theory, algorithms, software, and regulation.

The NMLN framework (Theoretical Contribution 1) is, to my knowledge, the first comprehensive formalisation of Neuralized Markov Logic Networks under Łukasiewicz fuzzy semantics, comprising 55 mechanically verified theorems in Isabelle/HOL (Appendix B). Novel results include piecewise linearity of Łukasiewicz operations (Theorem 3.2) and formula evaluation (Theorem 3.3), energy function properties (Theorem 3.1), and convergence of gradient-based weight learning (Theorem 3.5)—properties not previously established for this class of models.

Inference algorithms (Theoretical Contribution 2). Two sampling methods designed for fuzzy truth spaces—importance sampling with variance bounds (Theorem 4.4) and power sampling with replica exchange (Theorem 4.3)—include a formal specification of explanation trace generation (Algorithm 3). The traces make each inference auditable, advancing beyond prior work that treated explanation as an afterthought.

Inductive rule discovery (Theoretical Contribution 3). A template-based mechanism (Algorithm 4) lets knowledge bases grow structurally, not just adjust existing weights; convexity of the scoring landscape is proved (Theorem 5.2). Integration with large language models supports a human-in-the-loop workflow in which domain experts propose candidate rules in natural language and the system validates them against data.

Software and empirical validation (Practical Contribution). An open-source Python library implements the full framework, coupling tensor-based energy computation with PyTorch for automatic differentiation and GPU acceleration. Evaluation on the COLIEE legal entailment benchmark supplies empirical evidence of competitive performance in a real-world legal reasoning task.

Compliance analysis (Regulatory Contribution). A mapping of LIMEN-AI’s capabilities onto Articles 9–15 of the EU AI Act shows how explicit weighted rules address transparency (Art. 13) and how explanation traces support human oversight (Art. 14). Deployment workflows for cybersecurity, financial risk assessment, and legal contract analysis illustrate how the framework can be embedded in organisational decision processes with appropriate review checkpoints and audit trails.

1.9 Scope and Limitations

No thesis can do everything, and it is worth being explicit about what this one leaves out. The scope is deliberately confined to four strands—mathematical foundations, algorithms, software, and regulatory analysis—and the central bet is on *provable interpretability*: the mathematical guarantee that every inference can be traced to explicit logical rules. Empirical results on COLIEE (Chapter 6) confirm that transparency need not come at the expense of competitive performance, but the thesis’s distinctive value lies in the proofs, not the benchmarks. For high-stakes systems governed by the EU AI Act, being able to *demonstrate* interpretability may matter more than a few percentage points of accuracy.

Validation follows two complementary routes. Isabelle/HOL mechanised proofs supply mathematical certainty for the core properties; the COLIEE legal entailment evaluation supplies empirical evidence that the framework works on a real task. Together, these routes bridge theory and practice. The application domains—cybersecurity anomaly detection, financial risk assessment, and legal contract analysis—were chosen for their proximity to the technical core and their relevance to the EU AI Act.

Like classical MLNs, LIMEN-AI’s computational cost scales with domain size and knowledge-base complexity. I do not claim the framework is tractable for every conceivable problem; I characterise the complexity and pinpoint the regimes in which it is tractable. Lifted inference, lazy grounding, and tighter approximation algorithms are flagged as future work. On the regulatory side, the analysis targets the EU AI Act specifically; sector-specific regulations and other jurisdictions are acknowledged but not examined in depth, and the workflow patterns proposed are reference designs that will need adaptation to particular organisational contexts.

One final caveat deserves emphasis. Interpretability alone does not make an

AI system trustworthy. Trustworthiness also demands fairness, robustness under adversarial and distributional shifts, privacy protection, security against manipulation, and clear lines of accountability. I touch on these dimensions where they intersect with the work, but they are not the primary focus. LIMEN-AI’s explicit rule structure does make fairness auditing and pattern correction easier than they would be with an opaque model, yet full trustworthiness requires attention to all these dimensions simultaneously. The boundaries drawn here define the scope within which the contributions—mathematical, algorithmic, practical, and regulatory—stand on firm ground.

1.10 Summary

The argument of this chapter can be condensed as follows. The most powerful AI models tend to be the least transparent, and the domains where AI stands to do the most good—credit scoring, hiring, criminal justice, healthcare—are precisely those where transparency matters most. Opaque decisions erode the accountability on which public trust depends. The EU AI Act has made this concern legally binding for high-risk systems deployed in the European Union, and post-hoc explanation techniques may not satisfy the Act’s architectural transparency demands.

LIMEN-AI is designed for this regulatory reality. Weighted first-order rules from the Markov Logic tradition, evaluated under Łukasiewicz fuzzy semantics, yield a differentiable reasoning engine whose logical structure stays explicit and inspectable throughout. Piecewise linearity enables gradient-based learning; human-readable rules make transparency and audit natural rather than retrofitted. The framework sits at the boundary between symbolic and neural computation, borrowing the learning power of the latter without giving up the interpretability of the former.

Chapter 2 surveys the relevant literature, maps the research gaps, and sets the stage for the formal, algorithmic, practical, and regulatory contributions that occupy the remaining chapters.

2 Literature Review

Any substantial research contribution must be situated within the broader landscape of existing knowledge. This chapter reviews the literature relevant to LIMEN-AI, following the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) methodology (Page et al., 2021). It covers statistical relational learning and Markov Logic Networks, neural-symbolic integration and differentiable reasoning, fuzzy logic and Łukasiewicz semantics, explainable artificial intelligence, and the regulatory landscape governing AI deployment—with the aim of identifying the gaps LIMEN-AI addresses and fixing the vocabulary the remaining chapters take for granted.

Reviewing the literature for a project like LIMEN-AI is complicated by the fact that the relevant traditions developed largely in isolation. MLNs came from the statistical relational learning community, Łukasiewicz logic from mathematical logic, neural-symbolic integration from AI proper, and AI regulation from legal scholarship. These communities publish in different venues, use different terminology, and are often unaware of relevant work next door. Part of this review’s value lies in synthesising across those boundaries, surfacing connections that may not be apparent from within any single tradition.

The review has three intertwined purposes: to position LIMEN-AI fairly relative to existing work, to pinpoint the research gaps that motivated its design choices, and to fix the technical vocabulary the remaining chapters assume. I have tried to represent each area honestly, acknowledging achievements and limitations alike, so that the later treatment of novel contributions can proceed without repeated detours into background.

Figure 9 maps the terrain. The review begins with statistical relational learning and MLNs (Section 2.2), the representational backbone of LIMEN-AI, then turns to the computational bottleneck—MLN inference algorithms (Section 2.3)—whose limitations motivate the sampling approach developed later in this thesis. Section 2.4 examines the broader neural-symbolic landscape and the various ways researchers have tried to marry learning with symbolic reasoning. The mathematical underpinnings come next: Section 2.5 on fuzzy logic and Łukasiewicz semantics explains why LIMEN-AI adopts the particular continuous logic it does. Section 2.6 widens the lens to explainable AI, situating the framework within the transparency and accountability

Figure 9: The interdisciplinary foundations of LIMEN-AI. The framework synthesises contributions from six distinct research areas, each covered in a dedicated section of this chapter. Solid arrows indicate primary influences; dashed arrows indicate cross-connections between fields. Source: Author.

debate, while Section 2.7 narrows it again to the EU AI Act and the legal obligations it imposes. Section 2.8 surveys real-world uses of MLN-style reasoning, and Section 2.9 pulls the threads together, identifying the five research gaps that LIMEN-AI is designed to fill.

2.1 Systematic Review Methodology

The review follows the PRISMA 2020 guidelines for systematic reviews (Page et al., 2021). Although PRISMA was originally developed for healthcare, its core principles—explicit methodology, comprehensive search, transparent reporting—transfer directly to computer science research.

The search strategy, illustrated in Figure 10, targeted publications indexed in Scopus, focusing on articles published between 2014 and 2025 to capture recent advances while including foundational works that remain essential references. The search queries combined terms related to Markov Logic Networks (“Markov logic” OR “MLN” OR “statistical relational”), fuzzy logic (“fuzzy logic” OR “Łukasiewicz” OR “t-norm”), neural-symbolic integration (“neural-symbolic” OR “neuro-symbolic” OR “differentiable reasoning”), and explainable AI (“explainable AI” OR “XAI” OR “interpretable machine learning”).

The database search identified 1,240 records across the six thematic areas. In

Figure 10: PRISMA flow diagram showing the systematic literature search process, following PRISMA 2020 guidelines (Page et al., 2021). Database searching identified 1,240 records from Scopus; 16 additional foundational works were identified through citation tracking and expert recommendation. After screening, 145 studies were included in the final synthesis (129 recent studies plus 16 foundational works). Source: Author.

parallel, 16 additional foundational works that predate the search period but remain essential references—including Richardson and Domingos’s seminal paper on Markov Logic Networks (Richardson and Domingos, 2006) and Hájek’s treatise on the metamathematics of fuzzy logic (Hájek, 1998)—were identified through citation tracking and expert recommendation, yielding 1,256 records in total. After removing 340 duplicates, 916 unique records remained. Titles and abstracts were screened for relevance to the research questions, resulting in 266 records for full-text assessment. The full-text assessment applied inclusion criteria: the study must address at least one of the core topics (MLNs, fuzzy logic, neural-symbolic integration, XAI, or AI regulation), present original research or a substantial survey, and be published in a peer-reviewed venue. Following the exclusion of 121 papers that did not meet these criteria, 145 studies were included in the final synthesis—129 recent studies selected for their direct relevance to LIMEN-AI and 16 foundational works that have shaped the fields in which it operates. The inclusion of the foundational works reflects the judgment that a literature review should provide the context necessary for understanding the contribution, not merely enumerate recent publications.

Table 3: Distribution of included studies across thematic categories. Source: Author.

Thematic Category	Studies (2014–2025)	Foundational Works
Statistical Relational Learning & MLNs	35	3
MLN Inference Algorithms	25	2
Neural-Symbolic Integration	30	2
Fuzzy Logic & Łukasiewicz Semantics	15	2
Explainable AI	12	3
AI Regulation	12	4
Total	129	16

Table 3 distributes the 145 included studies—129 recent, 16 foundational—across the six thematic areas. Each was coded for its research problem, methodology, main findings, and bearing on LIMEN-AI; the synthesis looks for patterns of agreement and disagreement and positions LIMEN-AI against the resulting landscape.

A methodological note: the 145 studies included in the synthesis exceed the 139 entries in the bibliography because six reviewed works whose findings were entirely subsumed by a more comprehensive source already cited (typically a survey or a later paper by the same authors) are not individually referenced, while a small number of bibliography entries serve non-review purposes (the EU AI Act text, software documentation, foundational logic treatises predating the search window).

A caveat is in order. This review is systematic but not exhaustive. Each of the six areas could fill a survey paper of its own, and a handful inevitably were left aside. The selection criterion throughout has been relevance to LIMEN-AI: providing enough background to situate the contributions and enough evidence to confirm that the gaps addressed are genuine.

2.2 Statistical Relational Learning and Markov Logic Networks

Real-world intelligence is relational and uncertain at the same time: objects stand in structured relationships, and what we know about them is almost always incomplete. Statistical relational learning (SRL) grew up around this dual observation, and Markov Logic Networks—the representational backbone of LIMEN-AI—are its most influential product. The subsections below trace SRL’s foundations, define MLNs formally, and walk through the weight and structure learning challenges that later

chapters must address.

2.2.1 Foundations of Statistical Relational Learning

The premise behind SRL is disarmingly simple: first-order logic and probabilistic graphical models each do well what the other does badly (De Raedt et al., 2016). Logic gives you compositionality, relational structure, and the kind of systematic reasoning humans rely on—but it cracks under uncertainty. Probabilistic models handle noise and incomplete information gracefully—but they flatten relational structure into fixed-length feature vectors. Bolting the two together is the obvious next step; making the bolt principled is where the research gets interesting.

Traditional machine learning operates on flat feature vectors—each example encoded as a fixed-length list of attribute values, independent of every other example. This works for image classification, house-price prediction, or spam detection, but it struggles wherever the relevant structure involves relationships between entities. In a social network, predictions about one user depend on friends, friends of friends, and the user’s structural position in the graph. In molecular biology, a protein’s function depends on its interactions with other proteins, its pathway membership, and evolutionary relationships. Treating entities as independent vectors discards exactly the information that is most predictive.

Figure 11: A relational prediction problem. The prediction about entity D depends not only on D’s own attributes but also on the attributes of related entities (A, B, C) and the structure of relationships. Traditional feature-vector representations cannot capture this relational structure. Source: Author.

Figure 11 illustrates a simple relational prediction problem. Given that entity A smokes and given a rule that “friends of smokers tend to smoke,” we want to predict the probability that entity D smokes. This prediction depends on the path of friendship relations connecting A to D—a structural property that cannot be captured by representing D in isolation.

SRL pairs first-order logic’s representational power with the uncertainty-handling capacity of probabilistic models (De Raedt et al., 2016; Koller and Friedman, 2009).

First-order logic supplies predicates (e.g., `Friends(x,y)`, `Smokes(x)`), variables, quantifiers, and connectives for expressing relational structure; probabilistic models supply a framework for reasoning under noise, incomplete information, and data-driven learning (Li et al., 2025b). Together they allow a system to represent “friends of smokers tend to smoke” and learn how strongly the data support that claim.

De Raedt et al. synthesise the field in their influential SRL survey (De Raedt et al., 2016), identifying several paradigms, each combining logic and probability differently:

- **Probabilistic Relational Models (PRMs)** extend Bayesian networks with relational structures, defining conditional probability distributions in terms of the attributes of related objects.
- **Bayesian Logic Programs** combine logic programming with Bayesian networks, using logic clauses to define the structure of the probabilistic model.
- **Probabilistic Logic Programming** assigns probabilities to logical facts and uses the logic programming inference mechanism to compute the probabilities of queries.
- **Markov Logic Networks** attach weights to first-order formulas and define a probability distribution over possible worlds based on weighted satisfaction.

No single paradigm dominates across all criteria; the best choice depends on application requirements. For LIMEN-AI, MLNs provide the most natural foundation because they directly support the weighted rules central to the framework’s design.

Mathematically, SRL borrows its vocabulary from two traditions: predicates, atoms, formulas, and inference rules on the logic side; random variables, distributions, conditional independence, and Bayesian updating on the probabilistic side. The hard part is gluing them into a coherent semantics that assigns probabilities to logical formulas without violating the principles of either parent discipline. MLNs do this through log-linear models and template-based feature generation—an approach that has turned out to be both clean in theory and workable in practice.

2.2.2 Markov Logic Networks: Definition and Properties

Richardson and Domingos introduced Markov Logic Networks in a 2006 paper that has since become one of the most cited in all of SRL (Richardson and Domingos,

2006). The core idea is to take first-order formulas and make them soft: attach a real-valued weight to each formula, so that violating it incurs a penalty proportional to the weight rather than an outright contradiction. A formula with infinite weight behaves like a classical hard constraint; a formula with finite weight is a preference that the distribution can override when evidence pulls in the other direction.

The consequences are far-reaching. Classical logic is fragile: one violated rule makes the entire knowledge base unsatisfiable. MLNs are robust—a violated rule lowers a world’s probability but never zeros it out, so the system copes with contradictory evidence, noisy data, and graded preferences.

$$P(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{Z} \exp(1.5 \cdot n_1(\mathbf{x}) + 1.1 \cdot n_2(\mathbf{x}))$$

Figure 12: Structure of a Markov Logic Network. Weighted first-order formulas (left) are grounded with domain constants to produce ground atoms (right). Each possible world assigns truth values to all ground atoms, and its probability depends on how many groundings of each formula are satisfied. Source: Author.

Figure 12 illustrates the structure of an MLN in more detail. Formally, an MLN \mathcal{L} is a set of pairs $\{(\varphi_i, w_i)\}$ where each φ_i is a formula in first-order logic and $w_i \in \mathbb{R}$ is the associated weight. Given a finite set of constants \mathcal{C} , the MLN defines a probability distribution over possible worlds (Herbrand interpretations) as follows:

$$P(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{Z} \exp \left(\sum_i w_i n_i(\mathbf{x}) \right) \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{x} is an assignment of truth values to all ground atoms, $n_i(\mathbf{x})$ is the number of true groundings of formula φ_i in world \mathbf{x} , and $Z = \sum_{\mathbf{x}} \exp(\sum_i w_i n_i(\mathbf{x}))$ is the partition function that ensures the probabilities sum to one.

This definition makes MLNs a template for constructing Markov random fields. Given a set of constants, each formula is grounded by substituting constants for

variables in all possible ways. For example, the formula $\forall x : \text{Smokes}(x) \Rightarrow \text{Cancer}(x)$ with constants $\{\text{Alice}, \text{Bob}\}$ produces two ground formulas: $\text{Smokes}(\text{Alice}) \Rightarrow \text{Cancer}(\text{Alice})$ and $\text{Smokes}(\text{Bob}) \Rightarrow \text{Cancer}(\text{Bob})$. Each grounding defines a feature of the log-linear model, and the weight of the formula is the parameter associated with that feature.

The ground Markov network that results from this process encodes exactly the dependencies implied by the formulas: two ground atoms share an edge whenever they co-occur in at least one ground clause. Probabilistic dependencies thus mirror logical structure by construction.

Table 4: Key properties of Markov Logic Networks compared to classical logic and Bayesian networks. Source: Author.

Property	Classical Logic	Bayesian works	Net- MLNs
Uncertainty handling	None	Full	Full
Relational structure	First-order	Propositional	First-order
Constraint type	Hard only	Soft (probabilistic)	Hard and soft
Representation	Formulas	DAG + CPTs	Weighted formulas
Human readability	High	Medium	High
Learning from data	Limited	Full	Full

Table 4 contrasts MLNs with classical logic and Bayesian networks along several axes. What makes the framework appealing for knowledge representation is the combination: rules that experts can read and revise; weights that capture the strength of those rules numerically; a log-linear structure that plugs into the well-studied theory of exponential families, maximum entropy, and logistic regression; and a template mechanism through which a handful of weighted formulas can generate an arbitrarily large ground Markov network—compact representation of a complex domain.

Domingos later argued that first-order logic and probability are complementary rather than competing tools, positioning MLNs as a step towards unifying the major machine-learning paradigms (Domingos, 2015). The underlying thesis—that MLNs can reason with logical structure and statistical patterns simultaneously—has been influential in shaping subsequent SRL and neural-symbolic research.

2.2.3 Weight Learning in Markov Logic Networks

Once the formulas are fixed, the remaining question is how strongly each one should pull on the distribution. Weight learning starts from a given set of formulas and a dataset of ground atoms with known truth values, then searches for the real-valued weights that maximise the likelihood of the observed data. The problem is conceptually clean—optimise a concave objective—but computationally fierce, because the gradient involves an expectation over all possible worlds.

Figure 13: Weight learning in MLNs seeks to maximise the log-likelihood of the observed data. The gradient is the difference between observed and expected formula satisfaction counts. Gradient ascent moves toward weights where these counts match. Source: Author.

The log-likelihood of a dataset \mathcal{D} under an MLN, illustrated conceptually in Figure 13, is:

$$\log P(\mathcal{D}) = \sum_i w_i n_i(\mathcal{D}) - \log Z \quad (7)$$

where $n_i(\mathcal{D})$ is the number of true groundings of formula φ_i in the observed data. The first term rewards weights that are high for frequently satisfied formulas; the second (the log partition function) penalises high weights to maintain normalisation.

The gradient of the log-likelihood with respect to weight w_i is:

$$\frac{\partial \log P(\mathcal{D})}{\partial w_i} = n_i(\mathcal{D}) - \mathbb{E}_P[n_i] \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbb{E}_P[n_i]$ is the expected number of true groundings under the MLN distribution. The gradient has a clean reading: it is the difference between observed and expected counts. Formulas satisfied more often in the data than the model expects receive

a positive gradient, pushing their weight up; the reverse pushes weights down. At equilibrium the expected counts match the observed counts—a hallmark of maximum entropy models.

However, computing the gradient requires computing the expectation $\mathbb{E}_P[n_i]$, which involves summing over all possible worlds:

$$\mathbb{E}_P[n_i] = \sum_{\mathbf{x}} n_i(\mathbf{x})P(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{Z} \sum_{\mathbf{x}} n_i(\mathbf{x}) \exp \left(\sum_j w_j n_j(\mathbf{x}) \right) \quad (9)$$

For a domain with m ground atoms, this sum has 2^m terms — an intractable computation except for very small domains. This computational bottleneck has motivated the development of approximate learning algorithms.

Pseudo-likelihood maximisation replaces the full likelihood with a product of conditional likelihoods (Richardson and Domingos, 2006):

$$\log PL(\mathcal{D}) = \sum_a \log P(X_a = x_a | MB_a) \quad (10)$$

where the sum is over all ground atoms, and MB_a denotes the Markov blanket of atom a (its neighbours in the ground network). This decomposition avoids the need to compute the partition function Z because each conditional probability involves only local normalisation. Pseudo-likelihood provides consistent parameter estimates under certain conditions but may not match the true maximum likelihood estimates.

Contrastive divergence uses short Markov chain Monte Carlo runs to approximate the gradient. Rather than computing the exact expectation, contrastive divergence runs a few steps of Gibbs sampling from the current data and uses the resulting configuration to estimate the expected counts. This approximation can be computed efficiently, but it introduces bias that may affect the quality of the learned weights.

More recent work has explored **discriminative training**, where the focus is on predicting query atoms given evidence atoms rather than modelling the joint distribution. Discriminative approaches can be more effective when the goal is prediction rather than density estimation, as they focus on learning the relevant conditional distributions.

Khot et al. developed gradient-based boosting methods for MLN weight learning that are particularly effective when dealing with missing data (Khot et al., 2015).

Their approach uses functional gradient boosting to learn regression trees that capture the dependence of atom truth values on the structure of the knowledge base. The key insight is that the gradient of the likelihood can be approximated by learning a regression function that predicts the residuals between observed and expected values. This method avoids the need to compute expectations over missing values and has shown good performance on benchmark datasets with substantial missing data.

Bellodi et al. explored lifted discriminative learning for probabilistic logic programs, developing algorithms that exploit program structure to avoid redundant computation (Bellodi and Riguzzi, 2015). Although their work targets probabilistic logic programming rather than MLNs, the core insight—that many ground atoms share identical conditional distributions by symmetry, so learning can operate at the equivalence-class level—applies to both paradigms.

Weitkämper recently investigated the scaling properties of weight parameters in MLNs and related relational logistic regression models (Weitkämper, 2025). This work addresses the important question of how weights should be normalised as the domain size changes. When an MLN is applied to domains of different sizes, the number of groundings of each formula scales with the domain size, potentially leading to very different probability distributions. Weitkämper’s analysis provides guidance on weight scaling that ensures learned models generalise appropriately across domains of different sizes; however, it also reveals that for MLNs, the asymptotic behaviour is not always transparently controlled by the parameters. This finding presents a challenge to the claim that explicit rules and weights automatically ensure interpretability, as the collective behaviour of groundings in large domains can lead to unexpected emergent properties. LIMEN-AI addresses this concern by prioritising piecewise-linear semantics and L^1 regularisation to maintain sparse, manageable rule sets, but the scaling behaviour remains a critical area for ongoing research.

In LIMEN-AI, weight learning differs because fuzzy semantics replace Boolean counts with graded satisfaction degrees computed via Łukasiewicz operations. The gradient of the energy function still exists but involves derivatives of piecewise linear functions, enabling optimisation through standard automatic differentiation.

2.2.4 Structure Learning in Markov Logic Networks

Weight learning takes the formulas as given; structure learning tackles the harder upstream problem of discovering them. In the language of traditional machine learning, formulas are features, and finding good features matters at least as much as tuning their coefficients. The task: given a vocabulary of predicates and a dataset, identify logical formulas that capture the regularities worth modelling.

Figure 14: Structure learning in MLNs proceeds by heuristic search. Starting from an initial knowledge base, the algorithm proposes modifications (adding/removing literals, adding new formulas), evaluates the resulting KB against training data, and accepts modifications that improve the score. Source: Author.

Structure learning in MLNs typically proceeds by heuristic search through a space of candidate formulas, as illustrated in Figure 14. Starting from an initial set of formulas (which may be empty or may include domain knowledge provided by experts), the algorithm proposes modifications—adding literals to existing formulas, removing literals, generalising variables, and adding entirely new formulas—and evaluates the resulting MLN on the training data using a scoring function such as pseudo-log-likelihood or weighted pseudo-log-likelihood.

The search space is vast. With p predicates of arity up to a and v distinct variables, the number of possible literals grows as $O(p \cdot v^a)$, and a formula of length k has $O((p \cdot v^a)^k)$ possible forms—astronomically large even for modest parameter values.

This combinatorial explosion has motivated several approaches to constrain the search:

Bottom-up approaches start from specific observations in the data and generalise to produce candidate formulas. For example, if the data contains instances where

Friends(Alice, Bob) and Smokes(Alice) and Smokes(Bob) co-occur, the algorithm might propose the formula $\forall x, y : \text{Friends}(x, y) \wedge \text{Smokes}(x) \Rightarrow \text{Smokes}(y)$. This approach focuses the search on patterns that are actually present in the data.

Top-down approaches start from general patterns and specialise by adding constraints. For example, starting from the trivial formula $\text{True} \Rightarrow \text{Smokes}(x)$, the algorithm might add conditions until it finds a specific pattern that improves the score.

Relational pathfinding exploits the observation that many useful formulas correspond to paths in a relational schema. If predicates $P(x, y)$ and $Q(y, z)$ share a variable type at position y , formulas of the form $P(x, y) \wedge Q(y, z) \Rightarrow R(x, z)$ can be systematically generated.

Nguembang Fadja et al. developed methods for learning hierarchical probabilistic logic programs, where the structure of the program reflects a hierarchy of concepts (Nguembang Fadja et al., 2021). Their work demonstrates that structure learning can be guided by domain-specific structural constraints that reduce the search space while producing more interpretable models. By requiring that learned programs conform to a hierarchical structure, the search is constrained to programs that are both more tractable to learn and more comprehensible to human readers.

This difficulty motivates LIMEN-AI’s template-based approach to rule discovery. Instead of searching an unconstrained formula space, templates define structural patterns that candidate rules must match—for instance, a chain template $P(x, y) \wedge Q(y, z) \Rightarrow R(x, z)$ fixes the structure while leaving the predicates P, Q, R to be learned. The resulting search space is dramatically smaller.

Templates trade some expressiveness for tractability: they cannot discover patterns outside the specified structure. In many applications, however, domain knowledge characterises the space of useful rules well, and templates encode that knowledge while enhancing interpretability. LIMEN-AI extends the approach by pairing template-based instantiation with differentiable scoring under Łukasiewicz semantics, replacing discrete evaluation with gradient-based optimisation.

2.3 Advances in MLN Inference Algorithms

The representational elegance of MLNs counts for little if we cannot actually compute with them. Inference—answering queries given a model and evidence—is where the

framework’s theoretical appeal collides with computational reality, and the collision is brutal. Exact inference is intractable for all but toy domains, and the resulting scramble for good approximations has generated a large and varied algorithmic literature. This section traces the main threads: ground inference on fully instantiated networks, lifted inference that exploits symmetry to sidestep full instantiation, and specialised algorithms for particular problem structures. The design choices behind LIMEN-AI’s sampling approach will make more sense against this backdrop.

2.3.1 The Inference Challenge

The central computational task in an MLN is inference. In MLNs, inference involves computing quantities such as the probability of a query given evidence, the most probable explanation (MAP) for a set of observations, or the marginal probability of a ground atom. All of these tasks reduce to computations over the MLN distribution, which requires dealing with the partition function Z .

The partition function is a sum over all possible worlds:

$$Z = \sum_{\mathbf{x}} \exp \left(\sum_i w_i n_i(\mathbf{x}) \right) \quad (11)$$

For a domain with m binary ground atoms, this sum has 2^m terms. Even for modest domains—say, 100 ground atoms—this is approximately 10^{30} terms, far beyond what any computer could enumerate. This fundamental intractability is not a limitation of current algorithms but a mathematical fact: computing Z is #P-hard (Richardson and Domingos, 2006), meaning it is at least as hard as any problem in the class #P, which includes counting the number of satisfying assignments to a Boolean formula.

Figure 15 illustrates this exponential growth. The inference challenge in MLNs is related to, but distinct from, inference in propositional graphical models. The relational structure of MLNs means that the ground network has a highly regular structure, with many ground atoms playing symmetric roles. For example, before any evidence is observed, all individuals in a social network might have the identical probability of smoking because they are related to the model only through their structural position. This regularity can potentially be exploited to reduce computation, an insight that has driven the development of lifted inference algorithms.

An enormous amount of research has gone into taming this intractability. The subsections that follow trace three main lines of attack: ground inference that works

Figure 15: The exponential growth of the number of possible worlds with the number of ground atoms. Even moderate-sized domains have astronomically many possible worlds, making exact inference intractable. Source: Author.

on a fully instantiated network and applies standard graphical-model algorithms; lifted inference that exploits symmetries so the network never needs to be fully instantiated; and specialised algorithms tailored to particular problem structures.

2.3.2 Ground Inference Algorithms

The simplest approach to MLN inference is to first ground the MLN—substituting constants for variables to produce all ground formulas—and then apply standard inference algorithms for graphical models to the resulting ground network (Poon and Domingos, 2006; Shavlik and Natarajan, 2009). This approach, while conceptually straightforward, faces two significant challenges. The grounding step itself can produce an enormous number of ground formulas: a formula with k variables over a domain of n constants produces $O(n^k)$ groundings. Compounding this, the resulting ground network can be large and densely connected, with many atoms sharing clauses and thus influencing each other’s distributions (Ibrahim et al., 2017; Rincé and Kersting, 2017).

Figure 16 summarises the major ground inference approaches. **Gibbs sampling** starts from a random world and iteratively resamples each ground atom from its conditional distribution given the current values of all others. Because the conditional depends only on the atom’s Markov blanket, each update is cheap. Once the sampler reaches equilibrium, the resulting samples estimate marginal probabilities, expectations, and other quantities of interest.

The main limitation of Gibbs sampling is that it may “mix” slowly, meaning that many iterations are needed before the samples become representative of the true

Figure 16: Major ground inference algorithms for MLNs. Each has different strengths: Gibbs sampling is simple but may mix slowly; belief propagation is fast but approximate for loopy networks; MC-SAT handles hard clauses effectively. Source: Author.

distribution. This is particularly problematic when the distribution has multiple modes separated by low-probability regions: the sampler may become stuck in one mode for many iterations before transitioning to another. Various techniques have been developed to improve mixing, including parallel tempering, blocked sampling, and auxiliary variable methods.

Belief propagation passes messages between variables, iteratively updating beliefs based on messages from neighbours. For tree-structured models it is exact; for loopy models (the norm in MLNs) it provides an approximation whose accuracy depends on the loop structure. Loopy belief propagation often works well in practice and is considerably faster than sampling.

The **MC-SAT** algorithm represents an innovative combination of ideas from satisfiability testing with Markov chain Monte Carlo sampling (Poon and Domingos, 2006). The algorithm uses a slice sampling approach that first samples a set of active clauses based on the current world’s satisfaction levels and then samples a new world uniformly at random from those that satisfy all active clauses. The SAT component enables efficient exploration of satisfying assignments through local search techniques. MC-SAT has been shown to be sound (converging to the correct distribution) and particularly efficient for MLNs with hard clauses (infinite weight) that create deterministic dependencies.

Shavlik and Natarajan investigated scaling MLN inference (Shavlik and Natarajan, 2009), contributing lazy grounding (instantiating only query-relevant formulas), intermediate-result caching, and computation ordering to cut redundant work.

2.3.3 Lifted Inference

Lifted inference starts from an observation that is almost embarrassingly obvious once stated: if many ground atoms play identical roles in the model—same formulas, same evidence status—there is no point in processing them one by one. Group them into equivalence classes and reason about the classes instead. When n atoms collapse into $k \ll n$ classes, the computational savings can be dramatic. This simple idea has spawned a rich literature on detecting and exploiting symmetry in relational models.

Figure 17: The principle of lifted inference. Instead of processing each ground atom individually (left), lifted inference groups interchangeable atoms into equivalence classes and processes classes (right). When n atoms collapse into $k \ll n$ classes, this can provide dramatic speedups. Source: Author.

Figure 17 illustrates the principle. Before any evidence is observed, many ground atoms play symmetric roles—all users in a social-network model may share the same prior smoking probability because they occupy identical structural positions. Evidence breaks some of those symmetries (we learn that Alice smokes) while preserving others (Bob and Carol remain indistinguishable). Lifted algorithms detect and exploit whatever symmetry remains.

Riguzzi et al. provide a comprehensive survey of lifted inference approaches for probabilistic logic programming under distribution semantics (Riguzzi et al., 2017). The survey covers three main families of algorithms:

- **Knowledge compilation** approaches transform the logic program into a tractable representation (such as a binary decision diagram or arithmetic circuit) that supports efficient query answering.
- **Variable elimination** approaches adapt the classic variable elimination algorithm from Bayesian networks to exploit symmetry by eliminating groups of indistinguishable variables together.
- **Message passing** approaches adapt belief propagation to pass messages between groups of variables rather than individual variables.

The survey emphasises that lifting is most effective when the model has substantial symmetry that is not broken by the evidence. In the extreme case where each entity has unique evidence, lifting provides no benefit. In the opposite extreme, where no evidence is observed, lifting can reduce inference from exponential to polynomial in the domain size.

Sarkhel et al. developed efficient inference procedures for *untied* MLNs—models where different groundings of a formula can have different weights (Sarkhel et al., 2017). Standard lifted inference assumes that all groundings of a formula share the same weight, which is limiting for many applications. Sarkhel et al. show that even without this assumption, structural properties of the ground network can be exploited to avoid redundant computation. The key idea is to identify and exploit determinism (clauses that are certainly true or false) and context-specific independence (variables that become independent given the values of other variables) in the ground model.

Islam et al. explored integrating neural embeddings with lifted inference (Islam et al., 2019). Learned entity embeddings identify which entities are likely to be similar, enabling more aggressive grouping even when the logical structure alone does not guarantee equivalence—bridging neural and symbolic approaches to relational reasoning.

Wang et al. developed domain-lifted sampling for universal two-variable logic and extensions (Wang et al., 2022), providing provably efficient algorithms whose sample complexity grows polynomially (not exponentially) with domain size for fragments covering many common MLN structures.

Chen et al. developed lifted message passing for hybrid probabilistic models combining discrete and continuous variables (Chen et al., 2019). Although LIMEN-AI uses fuzzy truth values rather than hybrid models, the techniques for handling continuous variables in lifted settings are relevant to scaling LIMEN-AI to large domains.

2.3.4 Specialised Inference Algorithms

Beyond general-purpose inference algorithms, researchers have developed specialised algorithms for particular types of queries or specific structures of MLNs.

De Nijs et al. explored quadratisation and roof duality techniques for MLN inference (de Nijs et al., 2016). These techniques reformulate the inference problem

as a pseudo-Boolean optimisation problem and apply specialised algorithms from combinatorial optimisation. The approach is particularly effective when the MLN has a structure that admits efficient quadratisation.

Rincé et al. investigated the use of WalkSAT-based algorithms for MLN inference in realistic applications (Rincé and Kersting, 2017). WalkSAT is a local search algorithm for satisfiability that has been adapted for weighted satisfiability problems. The authors show that WalkSAT-based inference can be effective for large-scale MLNs where sampling-based approaches struggle.

Ibrahim et al. developed algorithms for improving probabilistic inference in graphical models with determinism and cycles (Ibrahim et al., 2017). Their techniques exploit deterministic constraints (hard clauses) to simplify the inference problem, which is relevant for MLNs that include both hard and soft constraints.

Venugopal and Gogate developed evidence-based clustering for scalable MLN inference (Venugopal et al., 2014), partitioning ground atoms into clusters and performing inference within each cluster before combining results.

2.4 Neural-Symbolic Integration and Differentiable Reasoning

This section surveys the landscape of neural-symbolic integration—currently one of the liveliest corners of AI research. The goal is to map how different frameworks negotiate the tension between the learning power of neural networks and the interpretability of symbolic reasoning, and to locate LIMEN-AI within that map.

2.4.1 The Neural-Symbolic Paradigm

AI’s history reads, in broad strokes, as an alternation between two camps. Symbolic AI held the stage for the first few decades: hand-crafted rules, logical inference, explicit representations. Connectionism took over in the late 1980s and then again, spectacularly, after 2012: learned representations, gradient descent, scale. Each camp has achieved things the other could not, and a growing community now contends that the most capable and trustworthy systems will have to draw on both (Garcez and Lamb, 2023).

Figure 18 sketches this trajectory. The rationale for integration is easy to state: neural networks handle perception, noise, and scale well but struggle with compositionality and transparency; symbolic systems reason compositionally and

Figure 18: The evolution of AI paradigms. Symbolic AI excels at reasoning but struggles with perception and learning. Neural AI excels at learning from data but struggles with reasoning and interpretability. Neural-symbolic integration seeks to combine the strengths of both approaches. Source: Author.

transparently but choke on raw data and uncertainty. Marrying the two should, in principle, deliver systems that inherit the best of each lineage and the worst of neither—though, as the rest of this section will show, the “in principle” qualifier does a lot of work.

Garcez et al. provide an influential overview of neural-symbolic computing in their survey on effective methodology for principled integration (Garcez and Lamb, 2023). The survey identifies several dimensions along which neural-symbolic systems can be characterised:

- **Level of integration:** Systems range from loose coupling (neural and symbolic components communicate through well-defined interfaces) to deep integration (symbolic structures are embedded within neural computation).
- **Direction of information flow:** Information may flow from neural to symbolic (e.g., neural perception feeding into symbolic reasoning), from symbolic to neural (e.g., logical constraints shaping neural learning), or bidirectionally.
- **Representation of knowledge:** Knowledge may be represented in distributed form (as in standard neural networks), localist form (with interpretable symbolic units), or hybrid form (combining both).

Several developments have accelerated work in this direction over the past few years (Marra et al., 2020; Xie et al., 2023). Deep learning’s spectacular successes

have also made its blind spots conspicuous: models that beat humans on narrow benchmarks yet stumble on reasoning tasks a child could handle (Shindo et al., 2023). Meanwhile, differentiable programming frameworks now let gradients flow through symbolic computation, removing what was once a hard engineering barrier (Chen et al., 2019). Regulatory and societal pressure for explainability has created genuine demand for systems that keep their structure visible (Barredo Arrieta et al., 2020; Doshi-Velez and Kim, 2017; Rudin, 2019), and the proliferation of large knowledge graphs has supplied rich relational data that neither pure neural nor pure symbolic approaches exploit fully (Li et al., 2024; Srinivasan et al., 2022).

Table 5: Taxonomy of existing neural-symbolic integration approaches and their key characteristics. Source: Author.

Approach	Key Mechanism	Strengths	Limitations
Logic Tensor Networks (Serafini and Garcez, 2016)	Neural predicates + fuzzy logic	Differentiable, expressive	Predicates opaque
DeepProbLog (Manhaeve et al., 2018)	Probabilistic logic + neural preds	Exact inference possible	Compilation overhead
Scallop (Li et al., 2024)	Datalog + provenance semirings	Compositional, efficient	Limited logic fragment
DPLogic (Li et al., 2025a)	MLN + relation embeddings	Scales to large KGs	Embedding-dependent
Differentiable ILP (Yang et al., 2017)	Rule learning via gradients	Learns structure	Search space limits
Probabilistic Soft Logic (Bach et al., 2017)	Hinge-loss MRFs	Convex optimisation	Non-standard logic

Table 5 provides a taxonomy of major neural-symbolic approaches from the literature, highlighting their mechanisms, strengths, and limitations. Recent advancements have further diversified the landscape. For instance, DPLogic (Li et al., 2025a) introduces relation-specific embeddings into the Markov Logic Network framework to facilitate end-to-end optimisation for knowledge graph completion, while Scallop (Li et al., 2024) leverages provenance semirings to enable differentiable reasoning over Datalog programs. Each of these approaches makes different trade-offs; the positioning of LIMEN-AI relative to this landscape is presented in Table 8 at the end of this chapter.

2.4.2 Logic Tensor Networks

Logic Tensor Networks (LTN) offer one of the clearest illustrations of how differentiability and logic can be woven together (Serafini and Garcez, 2016). The move that makes it work is deceptively simple: implement every predicate as a small neural network—entity embeddings go in, a truth value in $[0, 1]$ comes out. Because the network can learn arbitrary non-linear boundaries, predicates can capture relationships that would be extremely hard to write down as explicit rules.

Figure 19: Architecture of Logic Tensor Networks. Entities are represented as learnable embeddings. Predicates are implemented as neural networks that compute truth values from embeddings. Formulas combine predicate outputs using fuzzy connectives. Source: Author.

Figure 19 illustrates the architecture. Entities become learnable embedding vectors in \mathbb{R}^d ; predicates are neural networks mapping embeddings to truth values in $[0, 1]$; formulas combine these truth values through differentiable fuzzy connectives; quantifiers aggregate over entity embeddings.

Because predicates are neural networks, LTN can capture patterns that would be hard to specify manually—a “similar(x,y)” predicate can learn complex feature combinations without an explicit definition of similarity. Logical formula structure guides learning and enables compositional generalisation (correctly evaluating novel predicate combinations).

However, the LTN approach trades interpretability for expressiveness. Because predicates are implemented as neural networks, the relationships they capture are not directly inspectable. A predicate such as “similar(x,y)” in LTN is defined by the weights of a neural network rather than by explicit criteria that a domain expert can read and evaluate. We cannot ask, “what does this predicate mean?” and receive a human-readable answer. This opacity is problematic for applications where interpretability is a primary requirement, such as regulated domains subject to the

AI Act’s transparency requirements.

Marra et al. developed Relational Neural Machines, extending LTN with tensor factorisation for efficient relational pattern representation and logical constraints that guide learning (Marra et al., 2020). The approach achieves strong performance on relational benchmarks while preserving some logical structure.

LTN and LIMEN-AI share a reliance on fuzzy semantics for differentiability and on logical structure for compositionality, but they diverge on the central trade-off: LTN lets neural networks define predicates, buying expressiveness at the cost of inspectability; LIMEN-AI insists on explicit weighted rules, accepting narrower expressiveness in exchange for transparency that a regulator or domain expert can actually verify. Which choice is better depends entirely on whether the application rewards accuracy or auditability more.

2.4.3 Probabilistic Logic Programming with Neural Components

Probabilistic logic programming (PLP) provides an alternative approach to combining logic with uncertainty. Rather than attaching weights to formulas as in MLNs, PLP attaches probabilities to facts and derives the probabilities of queries through logical inference. The distribution semantics provides a principled foundation: each probabilistic fact independently chooses to be true or false according to its probability, and the probability of a query is the probability that it can be derived from the resulting (random) set of facts.

DeepProbLog extends probabilistic logic programming with neural predicates, enabling end-to-end differentiable learning of hybrid systems (Manhaeve et al., 2018). The key innovation is to treat the outputs of neural networks as probabilistic facts: a neural network classifying handwritten digits produces probabilities that each digit is a certain class, and these probabilities become probabilistic facts that feed into logical reasoning about arithmetic.

Figure 20 illustrates the DeepProbLog architecture. The system compiles probabilistic logic programs into arithmetic circuits that support efficient gradient computation. These circuits encode the structure of logical inference in a form that enables computing both the probability of queries and the gradients of those probabilities with respect to the neural network parameters.

DeepProbLog’s compilation can be more efficient than sampling for programs

Image input

Figure 20: DeepProbLog architecture. Neural networks produce probabilistic facts (e.g., digit classifications). A logic program expresses relationships. Compilation into arithmetic circuits enables efficient gradient computation. Source: Author.

with bounded recursion depth, but the compilation step itself is expensive, and circuits can grow exponentially for deep recursion or many probabilistic choices. The system uses distribution semantics—truth is still Boolean, but probabilities are computed across possible worlds—rather than the fuzzy semantics LIMEN-AI employs.

The **Scallop** language provides a more recent and highly developed framework for neurosymbolic programming (Li et al., 2024, 2023b). Scallop combines Datalog-style logic programming with differentiable provenance tracking, supporting a variety of provenance semirings that enable different forms of reasoning:

- **Probabilistic provenance** computes the probability that a fact can be derived.
- **Top- k provenance** tracks the k most likely derivations.
- **Weighted provenance** aggregates weights across derivations.

Provenance tracking enables gradient flow through logical inference, supporting end-to-end learning. Scallop has been applied to visual question answering, knowledge graph completion, and program synthesis.

The framework supports multiple execution modes, including exact inference for small problems and various approximations for larger ones. The design prioritises efficiency and scalability, making Scallop suitable for integration with deep learning pipelines that process large amounts of data.

DeepProbLog and Scallop together show that differentiable logic programming has moved well past proof-of-concept. Both operate within probabilistic semantics—truth is still Boolean; what varies is the probability of being true. LIMEN-AI works with fuzzy truth values under Łukasiewicz operations instead. The semantic difference

matters: fuzzy operations are piecewise linear, hence cheaper to differentiate, and graded truth values map naturally onto the “degrees of support” that auditors and domain experts find intuitive.

2.4.4 Differentiable Logic Programs for Visual Reasoning

Differentiable logic programming has been applied to visual reasoning tasks, demonstrating that logical structure can guide learning in domains where perception and reasoning must be tightly integrated.

Shindo et al. developed α ILP, a differentiable inductive logic programming system for visual scene understanding (Shindo et al., 2023). The system learns to parse visual scenes into symbolic representations and then reasons over those representations using differentiable implementations of logical inference. The approach combines the perception capabilities of neural networks with the compositional reasoning capabilities of logic programming.

Shindo et al. subsequently extended these ideas to abstract visual reasoning (Shindo et al., 2024), learning rules that identify abstract patterns in visual stimuli and generalise to novel stimuli sharing the same structure—a clear demonstration of compositional generalisation through logical representations.

Kamali et al. developed NeSyCoCo, a neuro-symbolic concept composer that combines neural perception with symbolic concept composition, enabling generalisation to novel concept combinations unseen during training (Kamali et al., 2025).

2.4.5 Knowledge Graph Reasoning

Knowledge graphs provide a natural application domain for neural-symbolic integration, as they combine relational structure with the need for learning and inference under uncertainty.

Nickel et al. review relational machine learning for knowledge graphs (Nickel et al., 2016), covering tensor factorisation, neural embeddings, and probabilistic graphical models. Knowledge graphs pose distinctive challenges: large scale, sparsity, and the need for both completion (predicting missing links) and inference (answering complex queries).

Yang et al. developed differentiable learning of logical rules for knowledge base reasoning (Yang et al., 2017). Their approach learns weighted rules that can be

used for both link prediction and interpretable explanations of predictions. The learned rules provide insight into the patterns that the model has discovered, thereby supporting interpretability.

Harsha Vardhan et al. developed probabilistic logic graph attention networks for reasoning (Harsha Vardhan et al., 2020). Their approach combines graph neural networks with probabilistic logic, using attention mechanisms to focus on relevant parts of the knowledge graph during inference.

Li et al. developed DPLogic, a differentiable probabilistic logic framework for scalable KG completion (Li et al., 2025a). DPLogic represents formula weights as relation-specific embeddings and introduces neural logical operators for end-to-end optimisation. The efficiency gains are significant, but the reliance on embedding-based approximations contrasts with LIMEN-AI’s emphasis on explicit, human-readable rules and weights.

Li et al. also developed an MLN-based inference framework for link prediction in heterogeneous networks (Li et al., 2025b), showing that MLN reasoning can be effective for knowledge graph tasks while providing interpretable explanations.

2.4.6 Temporal and Spatial Reasoning

Neural-symbolic approaches have also been applied to temporal and spatial reasoning, where the relational structures of time and space provide natural constraints for logical representation.

David et al. developed NeoMaPy for MAP inference on temporal knowledge graphs (David et al., 2023), extending MLN-based reasoning to temporal relations. Duckham et al. applied MLNs to qualitative spatial reasoning with uncertain evidence (Duckham and Worboys, 2023). Zhong et al. extended the MLN framework to continuous variables with Numerical Markov Logic Networks (Zhong et al., 2021)—relevant to LIMEN-AI’s use of continuous (fuzzy) truth values.

2.4.7 Comparative Analysis: Embedding-Based vs. Explicit-Semantic Approaches

Running through the systems surveyed above, one fault line stands out more sharply than any other: how much of the original logical semantics survives the journey into a differentiable computation graph? Two families of answers have crystallised, which

I will call *embedding-based approximations* and *explicit-semantic preservation*. The choice between them determines, to a large extent, what can be verified, explained, and audited in the resulting system—and is therefore central to positioning LIMEN-AI.

Embedding-based approximations achieve differentiability by encoding logical structure into learned neural representations. For example, DPLogic represents formula weights as relation-specific embeddings and implements logical operators through neural networks (Li et al., 2025a). This approach enables efficient end-to-end optimisation because the embedding space is continuous and smooth, allowing gradients to flow freely during backpropagation. Similarly, Jung et al.’s quantified neural Markov logic networks (QNMLN) extend the neural MLN framework with first-order quantifiers; however, they achieve this expressivity by representing logical operations through neural potentials rather than explicit semantics (Jung et al., 2024). The advantage of these approaches is computational: neural embeddings can capture complex patterns implicitly, and the learned representations can be updated efficiently through standard gradient descent.

This computational advantage comes at a cost to interpretability. DPLogic’s formula weights live in an embedding space whose dimensions do not correspond to human-interpretable concepts; inspecting them does not reveal why a formula is weighted as it is. The neural logical operators provide no direct correspondence between symbolic structure and numerical operations, precluding formal verification or audit—a genuine barrier to deployment in regulated domains governed by frameworks such as the EU AI Act.

In contrast, *explicit-semantic preservation* approaches maintain a direct, interpretable correspondence between logical structure and numerical computation throughout the reasoning process. LIMEN-AI achieves this through its use of Łukasiewicz fuzzy semantics, where each logical connective is implemented via a specific, piecewise-linear operation: the conjunction $a \wedge b$ is computed as $\max(0, a + b - 1)$, the disjunction as $\min(1, a + b)$, and negation as $1 - a$. These operations satisfy the algebraic properties expected of their logical counterparts (commutativity, associativity, de Morgan’s laws), and their piecewise linearity ensures almost-everywhere differentiability for gradient-based optimisation (Hájek, 1998). Crucially, the formula weights in LIMEN-AI are real-valued scalars whose magnitudes directly indicate the strength of belief in the corresponding rule—increasing a weight strengthens the

rule’s influence on the energy function in a transparent, algebraically predictable manner.

This explicit correspondence between logical semantics and implementation enables a level of formal verification that is unattainable with embedding-based approaches. LIMEN-AI’s implementation leverages PyTorch’s `torch.clamp` operation to realise the $\max(0, \cdot)$ component of the Łukasiewicz t-norm, ensuring that the exact same piecewise-linear function specified in the formal definition is executed during inference. The correctness of this correspondence has been mechanically verified using the Isabelle/HOL proof assistant (Appendix B), yielding 55 formally proven theorems that guarantee properties including well-formedness of truth degrees, algebraic laws (commutativity, associativity, De Morgan duality), formula-level semantic equivalences, and energy-function regularity (linearity, boundedness, non-negativity). Gradient properties and convergence results are established by conventional mathematical proofs in Chapter 3 and build on the verified algebraic substrate. To the best of our knowledge, LIMEN-AI is the first neural-symbolic system to provide this level of mechanised formal verification for its logical semantics.

The distinction reflects a fundamental choice about the role of logical structure. Embedding-based approaches treat logic as a scaffold for learning: formulas guide the construction of neural representations, but the learned embeddings may deviate from any interpretable logical semantics. Explicit-semantic approaches treat logic as the *language of reasoning*: formulas and their semantics remain directly accessible throughout, so the system’s inferences can always be explained in terms of the rules it implements.

To make this distinction concrete, consider the problem of understanding why a system assigned a high probability to a particular query. In DPLogic, answering this question requires analysing the contribution of embedding vectors to the neural logical operators—a process that involves interpreting high-dimensional vectors whose meaning is learned and implicit. The explanation is necessarily indirect, mediated through the embedding space. In LIMEN-AI, the same question can be answered by identifying which formulas in the knowledge base had high satisfaction degrees under the relevant interpretation and examining the weights associated with those formulas. The explanation is direct: "Formula ϕ_i (which states $\forall x, y : \text{Friend}(x, y) \wedge \text{Smokes}(x) \Rightarrow \text{Smokes}(y)$) was satisfied to degree 0.87, and it has weight 2.3, contributing $2.3 \times 0.87 = 2.0$ to the energy. This was the highest-weighted

satisfied formula, so the system’s conclusion follows primarily from this rule."

Recent work by Weitekämper on the scaling properties of MLN weights adds an important caveat to this interpretability claim (Weitekämper, 2025). Weitekämper demonstrates that as domain size increases, the number of groundings of each formula scales proportionally, and the collective behaviour of many groundings can lead to probability distributions whose characteristics are not transparently determined by the formula weights alone. This finding shows that even explicit-semantic approaches face interpretability challenges at scale, particularly when formulas produce large numbers of groundings. LIMEN-AI addresses this concern through two mechanisms: (1) the use of L^1 regularisation during weight learning encourages sparse rule sets, reducing the total number of formulas and thus limiting the combinatorial explosion of groundings; and (2) the piecewise linearity of Łukasiewicz operations ensures that the contribution of each grounding to the overall energy is additive and thus traceable, even when the number of groundings is large. Nevertheless, the scaling behaviour identified by Weitekämper represents an important area for ongoing research, and future extensions of LIMEN-AI may need to incorporate explicit constraints on grounding complexity or adopt lifted inference techniques (as discussed in §2.3) to maintain interpretability at very large scales.

Neither family is categorically better. For knowledge graph completion, where link prediction accuracy is paramount, DPLogic’s embedding pipeline may be the right tool. For regulated domains where every inference must be auditable—cybersecurity threat assessment, legal document analysis—LIMEN-AI’s explicit-semantic design offers an advantage no post-hoc probing can replicate: the reasoning trail leads to readable rules whose correspondence to the formal semantics has been mechanically verified.

The deeper point is that the performance–interpretability tradeoff is not a law of nature. By choosing piecewise-linear Łukasiewicz operations and backing the implementation with Isabelle/HOL, LIMEN-AI shows that differentiability, expressiveness, and transparency can coexist within a single framework.

2.5 Fuzzy Logic and Łukasiewicz Semantics

LIMEN-AI’s differentiability rests on Łukasiewicz fuzzy logic. The subsections below cover the general theory of fuzzy connectives (t-norms), the virtues of Łukasiewicz

operations for gradient-based optimisation, the relationship between fuzzy truth values and probability, and recent algebraic developments relevant to the framework.

2.5.1 Foundations of Fuzzy Logic

In classical logic, every proposition resolves to true or false—there is no room for “mostly” or “somewhat.” That binary view is perfectly adequate for pure mathematics, but it fits poorly with the vagueness that saturates natural language. Ask whether someone 180 cm tall counts as “tall” and classical logic insists on a crisp cutoff—say, 175 cm—that feels arbitrary and fails to capture the gradual nature of the concept.

Lotfi Zadeh’s 1965 introduction of fuzzy logic relaxed the binary constraint, letting truth values roam over the full interval $[0, 1]$ (Zadeh, 1965). A truth value of 0.7 can mean “fairly tall”—not fully true, but closer to true than to false. Vague concepts that resist sharp boundaries suddenly become representable.

Figure 21: Classical vs. fuzzy logic membership functions for the concept “tall.” Classical logic requires a sharp boundary; fuzzy logic allows a gradual transition, better capturing the vagueness inherent in natural language concepts. Source: Author.

Figure 21 contrasts classical and fuzzy approaches to representing the concept “tall.” The classical approach requires a sharp boundary that seems artificial; the fuzzy approach allows for a gradual transition that better matches human intuition.

The field owes much of its mathematical rigor to Hájek’s treatise on the metamathematics of fuzzy logic (Hájek, 1998). Hájek refused to treat fuzzy logic as an informal, ad hoc extension of classical logic; instead, he developed it as a fully fledged branch of mathematical logic, complete with syntax, semantics, and proof theory. His central insight was that the *t-norm*—the operation chosen for conjunction—determines the character of the entire logic, and he classified fuzzy logics accordingly.

A t-norm is a binary operation $T : [0, 1]^2 \rightarrow [0, 1]$ that generalises Boolean conjunction. It must satisfy four properties:

1. **Commutativity:** $T(a, b) = T(b, a)$
2. **Associativity:** $T(a, T(b, c)) = T(T(a, b), c)$
3. **Monotonicity:** If $a \leq a'$ and $b \leq b'$, then $T(a, b) \leq T(a', b')$
4. **Identity:** $T(a, 1) = a$

These properties ensure that the t-norm behaves like a generalised “and” operation: it is symmetric, can be applied to multiple arguments in any order, larger inputs produce larger outputs, and conjunction with “true” (1) returns the original value.

Figure 22: The three main t-norms defining fuzzy conjunction. Gödel (left) takes the minimum; Product (centre) multiplies; Łukasiewicz (right) is piecewise linear. Each leads to a different fuzzy logic with different properties. Source: Author.

The three main families of fuzzy logic, visualised in Figure 22, are distinguished by their choice of t-norm:

- **Gödel logic** uses the minimum t-norm: $T_G(a, b) = \min(a, b)$. This is the weakest continuous t-norm and produces the largest conjunction values.
- **Product logic** uses the product t-norm: $T_P(a, b) = a \cdot b$. This treats truth values like probabilities, with independent conjunction.
- **Łukasiewicz logic** uses the Łukasiewicz t-norm: $T_L(a, b) = \max(0, a + b - 1)$. This is the strongest continuous t-norm, producing the smallest non-zero conjunction values.

Each choice leads to different logical properties and distinct computational characteristics. The Łukasiewicz t-norm is particularly notable for being the only

continuous t-norm that is *piecewise linear*. This property, seemingly a technical detail, has profound implications for differentiability and integration with gradient-based optimisation—a key reason for its adoption in LIMEN-AI.

2.5.2 Łukasiewicz Logic: Properties and Applications

Łukasiewicz logic, named after the Polish logician Jan Łukasiewicz who first introduced three-valued logic in 1920 (Łukasiewicz, 1920), has several distinctive properties that make it particularly attractive for neural-symbolic integration and differentiable reasoning.

The logical operations in Łukasiewicz logic are defined as follows:

$$\text{Negation: } \neg_{\mathbb{L}} a = 1 - a \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Conjunction: } a \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} b = \max(0, a + b - 1) \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Disjunction: } a \vee_{\mathbb{L}} b = \min(1, a + b) \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Implication: } a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b = \min(1, 1 - a + b) \quad (15)$$

These operations possess several properties that are crucial for LIMEN-AI’s design:

Continuity: All Łukasiewicz operations are continuous functions. This ensures that small changes in truth values produce small changes in formula satisfaction degrees, which is important for numerical stability during optimisation. Discontinuous operations, by contrast, can cause optimisation algorithms to behave erratically.

Piecewise linearity: Each operation is composed of linear pieces joined at boundaries. The conjunction, for instance, has two pieces: $a + b - 1$ when $a + b > 1$, and 0 otherwise. This piecewise linear structure means that gradients are constant within each region and can be computed directly. At the boundaries, subgradients provide well-defined descent directions.

Figure 23 illustrates the piecewise linear structure. This structure is not merely a technical convenience; it is the key property that enables LIMEN-AI to integrate with gradient-based optimisation frameworks. Neural network training relies on computing gradients through complex compositions of operations. Łukasiewicz logic enables the same gradient flow through logical inference.

Differentiability almost everywhere. The operations are differentiable every-

Figure 23: Piecewise linear structure of Łukasiewicz operations. Each operation has constant gradient within each linear region, enabling efficient automatic differentiation. Boundaries define subgradients for optimisation. Source: Author.

where except at the boundaries between linear regions. These boundaries form a set of measure zero, meaning that during stochastic optimisation (where inputs have continuous distributions), the probability of landing exactly on a boundary is zero. In practice, subgradients at boundaries work well with standard optimisers like Adam or SGD.

Residuation. The Łukasiewicz implication is the *residuum* of the Łukasiewicz t-norm, meaning it satisfies the adjunction property:

$$a \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} c \leq b \quad \text{if and only if} \quad c \leq a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b$$

This property establishes a tight, principled connection between conjunction and implication. It ensures that the implication has the “right” relationship to conjunction from a logical perspective, not just from a numerical perspective.

De Morgan duality. Łukasiewicz logic satisfies the De Morgan laws: $\neg(a \wedge b) = \neg a \vee \neg b$ and $\neg(a \vee b) = \neg a \wedge \neg b$. This duality ensures that negation interacts properly with conjunction and disjunction, preserving the expected logical relationships. Recent research by Pusztaházi et al. has further explored advanced operators within this framework, specifically examining the behaviour of symmetric difference in nilpotent fuzzy systems (Pusztaházi et al., 2025). Their work introduces an aggregated symmetric difference operator that restores associativity while retaining symmetry and invariance under negation, providing a solid foundation for consistent multi-stage fuzzy computations that are particularly relevant to the deep reasoning chains in LIMEN-AI.

Esteva and Godo developed monoidal t-norm based logic (MTL), a general framework that includes Łukasiewicz logic as a special case (Esteva and Godo, 2001).

Their work provides a unified treatment of fuzzy logics based on different t-norms and establishes the logical properties that each t-norm induces. The framework enables a systematic study of how different t-norm choices affect logical reasoning and has been influential in the mathematical foundations of fuzzy logic.

Why Łukasiewicz and not, say, Gödel or Product? Because each alternative trades away something LIMEN-AI needs. Gödel’s min is flat almost everywhere, starving the gradient signal; Product’s multiplication vanishes towards zero faster than is helpful for saturated truth values. Łukasiewicz gives piecewise linearity (good gradients), continuity (stable optimisation), residuation (logical coherence), and arithmetic simplicity (fast computation). A different t-norm could be substituted, but not without giving up at least one of those properties.

2.5.3 Łukasiewicz Logic and Probability

Fuzzy truth values and probabilities both live in $[0, 1]$, which invites confusion—and has fuelled a long-running debate in the AI and logic communities. The two frameworks rest on different axioms and carry different interpretations, so conflating them leads to wrong conclusions about how conjunctions, disjunctions, and negations behave.

Key Difference:

Probability: Events partition possibilities
 Fuzzy: Degrees of partial truth/membership

Figure 24: Probability and fuzzy logic both operate on $[0, 1]$ but have different axioms and interpretations. Probability satisfies additivity; fuzzy logic satisfies t-norm axioms. The relationship between them has been extensively studied. Source: Author.

Figure 24 highlights the key distinction. Probability satisfies the axioms of probability theory, including additivity: $P(A \vee B) = P(A) + P(B) - P(A \wedge B)$ for any events A and B . This additivity reflects the interpretation that probabilities represent fractions of possible worlds or long-run frequencies. Fuzzy logic satisfies different axioms based on t-norms, which do not require additivity. In Łukasiewicz logic, $\mu(A \vee B) = \min(1, \mu(A) + \mu(B))$, which differs from the probabilistic formula.

Flaminio et al. provide a detailed mathematical analysis of the relationship between Łukasiewicz logic and probability (Flaminio et al., 2015). Their work shows that Łukasiewicz logic can be given a probabilistic interpretation under certain conditions, connecting the algebraic structure of Łukasiewicz logic to the structure of probability spaces. The key insight is that states on MV-algebras (the algebraic structures underlying Łukasiewicz logic) correspond to probability measures under appropriate conditions. This connection provides theoretical justification for using Łukasiewicz logic in settings where probabilistic reasoning is needed.

Dubois and Prade discuss probability-possibility transformations in the context of fuzzy set semantics (Dubois and Prade, 2023). Possibility theory provides an alternative uncertainty calculus that is closely related to fuzzy sets, and their work clarifies when and how fuzzy truth values can be interpreted probabilistically. The transformations they identify preserve relevant structural properties, enabling principled movement between fuzzy and probabilistic interpretations.

For LIMEN-AI, this bridge between Łukasiewicz logic and probability carries three practical consequences. The energy function, which aggregates weighted satisfaction degrees, yields a Boltzmann distribution over interpretations—giving the framework a bona fide probabilistic reading. That probabilistic reading, in turn, supports uncertainty quantification: expectations, marginals, and credible intervals become well-defined. And because the broader MLN community operates within probabilistic semantics, the connection lets LIMEN-AI be compared with, and potentially composed alongside, existing probabilistic reasoning systems.

2.5.4 Recent Developments in Fuzzy Logic

The mathematical foundations of fuzzy logic continue to be an active area of research. Recent work has explored algebraic structures, new operations, and connections to other logical systems.

Pusztaházi et al. provide a comprehensive study of symmetric difference operations in nilpotent fuzzy systems, which include Łukasiewicz logic (Pusztaházi et al., 2025). The symmetric difference operation, defined as $a \Delta b = (a \wedge \neg b) \vee (\neg a \wedge b)$ using fuzzy operations, generalises the Boolean XOR operation to fuzzy settings. Their work develops new characterisations and establishes algebraic properties that deepen the understanding of Łukasiewicz logic’s structure.

Gokila and Jansirani explore the algebraic structure of Łukasiewicz fuzzy BM-algebras (Gokila and Jansirani, 2024). BM-algebras provide an algebraic framework for bounded commutative residuated lattices, which include the algebraic structures underlying Łukasiewicz logic. Their work contributes to understanding the mathematical foundations of fuzzy reasoning systems.

Ongoing algebraic work of this kind confirms that fuzzy logic is not a closed chapter but an active research area. For LIMEN-AI, the implication is reassuring: the semantic foundation rests on mathematics that is still being strengthened, and future theoretical advances may translate directly into sharper reasoning guarantees.

2.6 Explainable AI and Interpretable Machine Learning

As AI systems take on decisions with real consequences—loan approvals, hiring, medical triage—the question of whether anyone can understand *why* a particular output was produced has moved from academic curiosity to practical necessity. This section reviews the explainability landscape, from post-hoc methods that probe opaque models after the fact to inherently interpretable architectures that build transparency in from the start. The coverage includes evaluation criteria for explanations and the long-running debate over whether post-hoc explanations are adequate for high-stakes settings. Situating LIMEN-AI in this landscape clarifies both its design philosophy and its alignment with regulatory expectations.

2.6.1 The Explainability Challenge

Deep learning has delivered a peculiar bargain. The models with the highest predictive power—networks with millions or billions of parameters—are also the hardest to understand. Their reasoning, if the word even applies, is smeared across cascades of matrix multiplications, nonlinear activations, and attention heads that no human can directly parse. When such a model approves a loan or flags a medical image, the basis for the decision lives in weight patterns that carry no interpretable meaning on their own.

The problem is not merely philosophical. A person denied a mortgage or turned down for a job has a legitimate interest in knowing why. “The algorithm said so” is not a satisfying answer—and, under an increasing number of legal frameworks, it may not be an acceptable one either. The field of Explainable Artificial Intelligence

(XAI) took shape around this gap, developing methods that attempt to make opaque systems understandable to the humans who deploy, oversee, and are affected by them (Barredo Arrieta et al., 2020).

Figure 25: The multiple purposes of explainability. XAI methods serve different stakeholders with different needs: users who must decide whether to trust the system, developers who must improve it, regulators who must ensure compliance, and affected individuals who may wish to contest decisions. Source: Author.

Figure 25 illustrates the multiple purposes that explanations serve. Different stakeholders have different needs: end users need to know whether to trust a particular prediction; developers need to identify when and why models fail; regulators need to verify compliance with legal requirements; affected individuals need to understand and potentially contest decisions; and researchers may seek insights into what the model has learned about the domain. No single explanation method serves all these purposes equally well.

Arrieta et al. provide a comprehensive survey of XAI concepts, taxonomies, opportunities, and challenges (Barredo Arrieta et al., 2020). The survey identifies multiple dimensions along which explanation methods can be characterised:

- **Scope:** Local explanations explain individual predictions; global explanations characterise overall model behaviour.
- **Audience:** Explanations may target domain experts who understand technical details or lay users who need intuitive summaries.
- **Format:** Explanations may take the form of feature attributions (which inputs matter), rules (if-then conditions), examples (similar cases), or visualisations.

- **Timing:** Intrinsic explanations arise from model structure; post-hoc explanations are generated after the fact.

The survey emphasises that there is no single best approach to explanation; the appropriate method depends on the context, the audience, and the purpose. A doctor evaluating a diagnostic recommendation has different needs than a patient trying to understand their diagnosis, and both have different needs than a regulator auditing the system for compliance.

Guidotti et al. provide a comprehensive survey of methods for explaining black box models (Guidotti et al., 2019). The survey organises explanation methods according to their approach: rule extraction attempts to approximate the model with interpretable rules; sensitivity analysis identifies input features that most influence output; and example-based explanation identifies training examples most relevant to a particular prediction (Costa et al., 2023). The survey evaluates methods according to criteria such as fidelity (how well the explanation reflects the model’s true behaviour), comprehensibility (how easy the explanation is to understand), and stability (how consistent explanations are across similar inputs) (Čolić et al., 2024).

2.6.2 Post-Hoc Explanation Methods

Post-hoc explanation methods generate explanations for models that are not inherently interpretable. The premise is pragmatic: we have deployed (or wish to deploy) a model that achieves good performance, and we need to understand its behaviour without changing the model itself. These methods treat the model as a black box and analyse its input-output behaviour to produce explanations.

LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations), illustrated in Figure 26, generates local explanations by fitting a simple, interpretable model to the predictions of the black box in the neighbourhood of a particular input (Ribeiro et al., 2016). The process works as follows:

1. Generate perturbed versions of the input by randomly modifying features.
2. Query the black box model on each perturbed input to obtain predictions.
3. Weight each perturbed sample by its distance from the original input.
4. Fit a simple model (typically a linear model or decision tree) to the weighted samples.

Figure 26: Post-hoc explanation with LIME. The black box model is queried on perturbed inputs in the neighbourhood of the input of interest. A simple interpretable model is fitted to these query results, and its parameters provide feature importance scores. Source: Author.

5. Use the parameters of the simple model as the explanation.

The resulting explanation describes which features pushed the prediction toward or away from the observed outcome. For an image classifier, LIME might highlight which regions of the image were important for classifying it as a “cat.” For a loan approval model, LIME might indicate that a high credit score increased the approval probability, while a low income decreased it.

SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) uses concepts from cooperative game theory to assign importance scores to features (Lundberg and Lee, 2017). The Shapley value, from game theory, assigns each player in a cooperative game a fair share of the total payoff based on their marginal contribution. SHAP adapts this concept to feature attribution: each feature is a “player,” the “payoff” is the model’s prediction, and the Shapley value of each feature is its average marginal contribution to the prediction across all possible subsets of features.

SHAP values satisfy several theoretically desirable properties:

- **Local accuracy:** The sum of SHAP values equals the model’s prediction minus a baseline.
- **Missingness:** Features that are not present (or are masked) receive zero attribution.
- **Consistency:** If a feature’s contribution increases in a modified model, its SHAP value should not decrease.

These theoretical properties have made SHAP popular in practice, particularly for applications requiring regulatory compliance, where having principled explanations is important.

While LIME and SHAP have been widely adopted, they have also been subject to significant criticism. Rudin argues forcefully that for high-stakes decisions, post-hoc explanations are fundamentally inadequate, and inherently interpretable models should be used instead (Rudin, 2019). Her argument rests on several observations:

- **Fidelity:** Post-hoc explanations may not be faithful to the model’s true reasoning. A linear approximation to a highly non-linear model is, by definition, an approximation that may miss important aspects of the model’s behaviour.
- **Manipulation:** Post-hoc explanations can potentially be manipulated to hide undesirable behaviour. A model that discriminates based on race could produce explanations that focus on correlated but legally permissible features.
- **Incompleteness:** They provide only a partial view of the model’s logic. Local explanations describe behaviour around a single point; they do not characterise global behaviour.
- **No guarantees:** They cannot guarantee that the model will behave consistently with the explanation on future inputs.

Doshi-Velez and Kim discuss the challenges of developing a rigorous science of interpretable machine learning (Doshi-Velez and Kim, 2017). They argue that interpretability is not a single, well-defined property but rather a family of properties that depend on context. A clinician evaluating a diagnostic recommendation has different interpretability needs than a data scientist debugging a model or a regulator auditing for compliance. Different applications may require different types of interpretability, and evaluation methods must be tailored to the specific requirements of each application.

2.6.3 Inherently Interpretable Models

Inherently interpretable models represent a fundamentally different approach to explainability. Rather than generating explanations for opaque models after the fact, they are designed to be transparent by construction. The reasoning process

can be directly inspected without approximation because the model’s structure *is* the explanation. Examples include linear models, decision trees, rule lists, scoring systems, and sparse linear combinations of interpretable features.

Table 6: Examples of inherently interpretable models and their interpretability mechanisms. Source: Author.

Model Type	Interpretability Mechanism	Typical Use Cases
Linear models	Coefficients directly indicate feature importance	Risk scoring, baseline models
Decision trees	Explicit if-then rules along root-to-leaf paths	Medical diagnosis, eligibility rules
Rule lists	Ordered list of condition-action pairs	Credit decisions, triage protocols
Scoring systems	Points assigned to features, summed for decision	Clinical risk assessment
Generalised Additive Models (GAMs)	Smooth functions of individual features	Scientific modelling
LIMEN-AI	Weighted first-order rules with fuzzy truth	Regulated AI, auditable reasoning

Table 6 summarises the major types of inherently interpretable models. Each provides transparency through different mechanisms suited to different application contexts.

Rudin advocates forcefully for the use of inherently interpretable models in high-stakes domains (Rudin, 2019). Her argument includes several components:

The accuracy myth: The alleged accuracy advantage of black box models over interpretable models is often illusory. When researchers claim that a complex model “significantly outperforms” simpler alternatives, they often compare a well-tuned complex model against a poorly-tuned simple one. When equal effort is invested in developing good interpretable models, they can often match or approach the accuracy of black boxes. The difference, if any, may not justify the loss of interpretability.

The importance of effort: Developing a good, interpretable model requires careful feature engineering, domain knowledge, and iterative refinement. This effort is often not invested because complex models promise good results “out of the box.” However, the effort required to make a black box model understandable through post-hoc techniques may exceed the effort required to build a good, interpretable

model in the first place.

The regulatory imperative: In domains where decisions must be justified and contested, model opacity is not merely inconvenient but may also be unlawful. If a model’s reasoning cannot be explained, it cannot be meaningfully reviewed by regulators, audited for compliance, or challenged by affected individuals. The EU AI Act’s transparency requirements make this particularly salient for European deployments.

The argument for inherently interpretable models is particularly compelling in domains where:

- Errors have serious consequences (healthcare, criminal justice, finance)
- Decisions must be explainable to affected individuals
- Regulatory compliance requires audits and documentation
- Domain experts need to validate and refine the model
- The model will be used by humans who need to understand it

LIMEN-AI belongs to the category of inherently interpretable models. Its knowledge base consists of explicit weighted rules that domain experts can directly inspect—rules like “if a user has multiple failed login attempts from different locations, they are likely compromised” with an associated weight indicating the strength of this inference. Its inference process produces traces that record which rules contributed to which conclusions, enabling auditors to understand exactly how a particular output was produced. Its fuzzy truth values provide nuanced information about degrees of support, moving beyond binary judgments while remaining interpretable in terms of domain concepts.

These properties ensure that LIMEN-AI’s reasoning is transparent by design rather than by approximation. The explanations it provides are not simplifications or approximations of its true behaviour; they *are* its behaviour, expressed in a form that humans can read and evaluate.

2.6.4 Evaluation of Explanations

Evaluating the quality of explanations is a challenging problem that has received increasing attention in the XAI literature. Unlike predictive accuracy, which can

be measured objectively against ground truth labels, explanation quality involves subjective judgments that depend on context, audience, and purpose. Nevertheless, several criteria have emerged as important for assessing explanations, and understanding these criteria helps clarify what makes LIMEN-AI’s approach distinctive.

Figure 27: Multiple criteria contribute to explanation quality. Different applications may weight these criteria differently depending on context and purpose. Source: Author.

Figure 27 illustrates the multidimensional nature of explanation quality. The key criteria include:

Fidelity is arguably the most fundamental: does the explanation accurately reflect how the model actually arrived at its output? An unfaithful explanation is worse than none at all, because it breeds false confidence. Post-hoc methods are inherently limited here—they approximate, and the gap between approximation and reality grows with model complexity. For a highly non-linear classifier, a local linear surrogate may capture only a sliver of the decision landscape.

Comprehensibility asks whether the intended audience can actually parse the explanation. A feature-attribution vector that satisfies a data scientist may mean nothing to a loan applicant, and vice versa. Format, vocabulary, and level of detail all matter; the most faithful explanation in the world is useless if nobody can read it.

Stability captures whether similar inputs produce similar explanations. When two nearly identical loan applications receive wildly different rationales for the same outcome, users reasonably suspect that the explanations reflect noise rather than genuine reasoning. LIME, in particular, has been shown to produce unstable explanations under small input perturbations.

Completeness concerns how much of the model’s reasoning an explanation covers. Omitting a factor that materially influenced the output can mislead; including every

factor can overwhelm. The right balance depends on context: contesting a decision demands more detail than a routine sanity check.

Actionability addresses a practical question: does the explanation tell affected individuals what they could change to obtain a different outcome? A loan denial explained in terms of credit score and debt-to-income ratio is actionable in a way that a denial explained by an opaque embedding vector is not. Counterfactual explanations—“if your income were \$5,000 higher, the model would approve”—target this criterion directly.

Trust calibration, finally, asks whether explanations help users develop an appropriate level of reliance—not blind trust, not reflexive distrust, but a calibrated sense of when the model is likely to be right and when its output should be questioned. This requires conveying not just what the model concluded but how firmly the evidence supports that conclusion and where the model’s blind spots lie.

For inherently interpretable models like LIMEN-AI, fidelity is guaranteed by construction: the explanation *is* the model’s reasoning, not an approximation of it. When LIMEN-AI reports that a conclusion follows from rules R1 and R3 with certain satisfaction degrees, that report accurately describes how the conclusion was reached. There is no approximation error because there is no approximation.

The other criteria depend on design choices regarding how LIMEN-AI presents explanations to users. Comprehensibility depends on whether the rules are expressed in terms that users understand; stability follows from the deterministic nature of the inference process; completeness depends on how much of the inference trace is exposed; and actionability depends on whether the rules identify factors that users can influence. These are design choices that can be tailored to application requirements, building on the foundation of the faithful explanations that LIMEN-AI provides.

2.7 The Regulatory Landscape: The EU AI Act

The interpretability debate is no longer purely academic—it now has legal teeth. The EU AI Act, which became law in August 2024, imposes binding technical requirements on high-risk AI systems, and non-compliance carries steep penalties. This section reviews the Act’s risk-based classification, the specific obligations it places on providers of high-risk systems, and the architectural implications of those obligations.

LIMEN-AI was designed with these constraints in mind, and understanding them is essential for understanding the framework’s priorities.

2.7.1 Overview of AI Regulation

The rapid deployment of AI systems in consequential domains has prompted regulatory responses around the world (Floridi et al., 2018; Jobin et al., 2019; Mittelstadt et al., 2016). Regulators face a difficult balancing act: they must protect citizens from harms that AI systems might cause—discrimination, manipulation, privacy violations, and safety risks—while not stifling the innovation that could bring substantial benefits (Hacker et al., 2023; Mökander et al., 2022; Novelli et al., 2024). Different jurisdictions have adopted various approaches, ranging from light-touch guidelines to comprehensive binding regulations (Balboni and Francis, 2025; Chu et al., 2025).

Figure 28: The spectrum of AI governance approaches, from non-binding ethics guidelines to comprehensive binding regulation. The EU AI Act represents the most far-reaching attempt at comprehensive AI regulation to date. Source: Author.

Figure 28 places these governance approaches on a spectrum. Voluntary ethics guidelines sit near the softest end—useful for signaling intent but toothless in enforcement. The EU AI Act sits near the hardest: binding obligations, conformity assessments, and penalties for non-compliance that can reach tens of millions of euros (European Parliament and Council, 2024).

The EU’s approach has global significance. European regulations have historically influenced standards elsewhere through what scholars call the “Brussels effect”—the tendency for EU regulations to become de facto global standards because companies find it easier to adopt a single standard than to maintain different products for different jurisdictions. The AI Act is likely to shape how AI systems are designed and deployed worldwide, making it essential for researchers and practitioners to understand its requirements.

Jobin et al. surveyed the global landscape of AI ethics guidelines, analysing 84 documents from governmental, private sector, and civil society organisations

(Jobin et al., 2019). The survey found convergence on high-level principles such as transparency, justice, non-maleficence, and responsibility, but significant divergence in how these principles should be interpreted and implemented. The gap between ethical aspirations and practical enforcement is a key challenge that the AI Act attempts to address through specific, enforceable requirements.

Mittelstadt et al. mapped the debate on the ethics of algorithms, organising concerns into five categories (Mittelstadt et al., 2016): inconclusive evidence (algorithms may draw unreliable conclusions from limited data), inscrutable evidence (the basis for conclusions may be opaque), misguided evidence (biased data may lead to biased conclusions), unfair outcomes (algorithms may discriminate against protected groups), and transformative effects (algorithms may reshape social practices in undesirable ways). These concerns inform the requirements that regulators have imposed on AI systems.

Floridi et al. developed the AI4People framework, which articulates ethical principles for AI and recommendations for their implementation (Floridi et al., 2018). The framework identifies five principles—beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy, justice, and explicability—and proposes twenty concrete recommendations for translating these principles into practice. The framework has been influential in shaping the EU’s approach to AI regulation, with many of its recommendations reflected in the AI Act’s requirements.

2.7.2 The EU AI Act: Structure and Requirements

The EU AI Act establishes the most comprehensive framework for AI regulation in the world. Understanding its structure and requirements is essential for researchers developing AI systems intended for European deployment—and increasingly for deployment elsewhere, given the Brussels effect. As illustrated in the risk-based framework introduced in Chapter 1 (see Figure 2), the Act classifies AI systems according to the level of risk they pose and imposes requirements proportionate to those risks. The Act establishes four risk categories:

Unacceptable risk: AI systems that pose unacceptable risks are entirely prohibited. This category includes systems that use subliminal techniques to materially distort behaviour in ways that cause harm, systems that exploit the vulnerabilities of specific groups (children, persons with disabilities) to distort behaviour, social

scoring by public authorities that leads to detrimental treatment, and real-time remote biometric identification in publicly accessible spaces for law enforcement (with narrow exceptions for specific serious crimes). These prohibitions reflect a judgment that certain uses of AI are fundamentally incompatible with European values.

High risk: AI systems used in specified High risk domains are subject to comprehensive requirements that span the entire system lifecycle. High-risk domains include critical infrastructure (transport, water, energy), educational and vocational training (determining access or assessing students), employment (recruitment, promotion, termination, task allocation), essential private and public services (credit scoring, insurance pricing, emergency services), law enforcement (risk assessment, evidence evaluation, polygraph systems), migration and border management (visa applications, asylum claims), and administration of justice (legal research, outcome prediction).

Limited risk: AI systems interacting with natural persons must disclose that they are AI systems. Deepfakes and other synthetic content must be labelled as artificially generated. Emotion recognition and biometric categorisation systems have specific disclosure requirements.

Minimal risk: Most AI systems fall into this category and are not subject to specific requirements beyond existing law, although voluntary codes of conduct are encouraged.

For high-risk AI systems, the Act imposes detailed requirements in seven areas. These requirements have direct implications for system design and are worth examining in detail:

Risk management (Article 9) requires providers to establish and maintain a lifecycle-long risk management system. The system must catalog foreseeable risks, evaluate risks arising under both intended use and reasonably foreseeable misuse, and adopt mitigation measures. Crucially, the obligation is ongoing: a deploy-and-forget posture is not permitted.

Data governance (Article 10) imposes quality criteria on training, validation, and test data—relevance, representativeness, error-freedom, and completeness relative to the intended purpose. Appropriate governance practices covering methodology, preparation, labelling, and cleaning are mandatory. The goal is to prevent biased or noisy data from propagating into system behaviour.

Article 11 (**technical documentation**) demands a pre-market description of

the system’s general architecture, development process, monitoring mechanisms, and—most telling—the *logic* involved in the AI system. For a black-box model with millions of parameters, documenting “the logic” is a non-trivial challenge; for a rule-based system like LIMEN-AI, the rules *are* the logic.

Record-keeping (Article 12) mandates automatic event logging throughout the system’s lifetime. Logs must be detailed enough to support traceability and post-market monitoring. In practice, this means the system must record not only its outputs but enough of the reasoning path to support after-the-fact audits.

Article 13 (**transparency**) is perhaps the most consequential for system design: the operation must be “sufficiently transparent to enable users to interpret the system’s output and use it appropriately.” Users must also receive clear information about capabilities, limitations, intended purpose, and accuracy. The phrasing “interpret the system’s output” stops short of requiring full explainability but clearly disfavours opaque architectures.

Human oversight (Article 14) obliges providers to build in measures that let assigned individuals understand the system’s strengths and weaknesses, monitor its operation, guard against automation bias, and override outputs when necessary. The system should support human judgment, not supplant it.

Accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity (Article 15): Systems must achieve appropriate levels of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity throughout their lifecycle. They must be resilient against errors, faults, and inconsistencies. Technical robustness is essential to prevent manipulation that could compromise safety or fundamental rights.

2.7.3 Implications for System Design

The requirements of the AI Act have profound implications for how AI systems must be designed. These implications go beyond mere compliance checkboxes; they affect fundamental architectural choices that must be made early in the development process.

Figure 29 traces the chain from regulatory mandate to design consequence.

Article 13’s transparency requirement—that users must be able to “interpret outputs”—could in principle be met by post-hoc explanations, but as Section 2.6 argued, those explanations carry inherent fidelity risks. Inherently interpretable

Figure 29: Flow from AI Act requirements to design implications to LIMEN-AI’s response. Each regulatory requirement implies specific architectural constraints that LIMEN-AI’s design satisfies. Source: Author.

architectures sidestep the problem by making the reasoning directly inspectable.

Article 11’s documentation mandate—“describe the logic involved”—is notoriously awkward for neural networks whose “logic” is smeared across millions of weights. For a rule-based system the mapping is trivial: document the rules, and you have documented the logic.

Article 12’s record-keeping obligation calls for automatic logging that “ensures traceability.” Logging inputs and outputs is the easy part; what matters is capturing enough of the reasoning path to reconstruct *how* the output was produced. LIMEN-AI’s inference traces—which record rule activations and their weighted contributions—meet this requirement by construction.

Article 14’s human oversight provision asks that assigned individuals be able to understand the system, interpret its outputs, and intervene when warranted. Black-box models can technically offer an override button, but making behaviour predictable enough that the button gets pressed at the right time demands a level of transparency that opaque architectures struggle to provide.

Novelli et al. decompose accountability into three components: *transparency* (being able to inspect behaviour), *answerability* (being able to explain decisions), and *liability* (having a clear assignment of responsibility) (Novelli et al., 2024). All three presuppose that some human can understand the system well enough to take ownership of what it does.

LIMEN-AI was built with exactly this kind of accountability in mind. Explicit weighted rules satisfy the transparency mandate by being directly readable; the same rules, exported from the knowledge base, serve as the “description of the logic” that

Article 11 requires; inference traces that log which rules fired and with what strength meet the record-keeping obligation of Article 12; and the ability to review, edit, and override rules supports the human oversight demanded by Article 14. None of this alignment is accidental—it reflects a decision, taken early in the design process, to treat regulatory compliance as a first-class engineering requirement rather than an afterthought.

2.8 Applications of MLN-Based Reasoning

Theory needs a reality check. This section surveys how MLN-style reasoning has been applied in practice—smart environments, natural language, biomedicine, e-commerce, security, and spatio-temporal domains—drawing attention both to the successes that confirm the framework’s practical value and to the bottlenecks that motivated LIMEN-AI’s design.

2.8.1 Activity Recognition and Smart Environments

Smart environments—homes, offices, hospitals, and other spaces equipped with sensors and actuators—generate streams of data about human activities. Inferring what people are doing from this data is a classic relational prediction problem: activities depend not only on immediate sensor readings but also on temporal patterns, spatial contexts, and relationships between different types of evidence. Markov Logic Networks provide a natural framework for combining logical domain knowledge (e.g., “if the stove is on, someone is likely cooking”) with statistical learning from sensor data.

Table 7 summarises key applications of MLN-based reasoning. A persistent challenge in smart-home activity recognition is that sensor data alone underspecifies what a person is doing; background knowledge about activity types and their sensory signatures must also be brought to bear. Chahuara et al. address this challenge by comparing sequential and non-sequential models—including MLN-based approaches—for recognising activities from audio and home automation sensors (Chahuara et al., 2016). Their MLN formulation integrates domain knowledge about activities with learning from sensor data, producing systems that are both data-driven and knowledge-guided.

The combination of ontological constraints with probabilistic inference extends

Table 7: Applications of MLN-based reasoning across domains. Source: Author.

Domain	Problem	MLN Contribution	Key Citation
Smart environments	Activity recognition	Fuse sensors + temporal patterns	Chahuara et al. (2016)
Smart homes	Probabilistic activity inference	Combine ontology + uncertainty	Civitarese et al. (2019)
NLP	Semantic reasoning	Logical + distributional models	Beltagy et al. (2016)
Molecular biology	Protein contact prediction	Structure-aware weights	Lippi (2016)
Knowledge graphs	Link prediction	Interpretable rules	Li et al. (2025b)
Spatial reasoning	Qualitative inference	Uncertain spatial evidence	Duckham and Worboys (2023)

this theme further. POLARIS (Civitarese et al., 2019) couples a formal ontology of activity types and their relationships with a probabilistic recognition layer, enabling robust classification even when sensor data is noisy or incomplete. The ontology fixes what activities can exist and how they relate; the probabilistic component quantifies confidence in the face of ambiguous evidence.

Probabilistic Soft Logic (PSL), a framework closely related to MLNs that substitutes continuous truth values in $[0, 1]$ for Boolean ones, offers a different angle on the same problem. Li’s PSL-based system for smart-home activity recognition (Li, 2023) exploits this continuous relaxation—similar in spirit to LIMEN-AI’s fuzzy approach—to obtain convex optimisation for inference, yielding tractable solutions even as the number of ground atoms grows.

Distinguishing activities that look alike at a low level of description but diverge in their temporal or contextual patterns demands richer representations still. Li et al. tackle this problem through temporal features and hierarchical structure (Li et al., 2023a), showing that structured representations pay off precisely where flat feature vectors fall short.

2.8.2 Natural Language Processing and Semantic Reasoning

Natural language exhibits a rich relational structure that makes it a natural domain for MLN-based reasoning. Words relate to other words through syntactic dependencies, semantic roles, and coreference chains. Sentences relate to world knowledge through entailment, contradiction, and presupposition. These relationships can be expressed as logical rules, and the uncertainty inherent in language understanding makes probabilistic weighting essential.

A central tension in computational semantics is that logical and distributional representations capture complementary aspects of meaning: the former excel at compositional structure and inference, while the latter (word embeddings) capture graded similarity and association. Beltagy et al. bridge this gap by using MLNs to combine both representation types (Beltagy et al., 2016), enabling inference that respects logical structure while leveraging distributional information.

For example, consider the inference from “a cat is on the mat” to “an animal is on the floor.” This requires knowing that cats are animals (taxonomic knowledge) and that mats are typically on floors (world knowledge). Distributional representations capture the similarity between “cat” and “animal,” while logical rules capture the inference pattern. The MLN framework enables the combination of these sources of information with appropriate weights.

Whether deductive databases can be made fully differentiable is a question that TensorLog answers affirmatively (Cohen et al., 2020). Though not strictly an MLN approach, it shares the goal of marrying logical structure with gradient-based learning: databases become sparse matrices, logical rules become sequences of matrix operations, and inference reduces to matrix multiplication. The resulting architecture supports efficient batch inference and gradient-based weight tuning.

The success of these approaches in NLP demonstrates that relational reasoning over language benefits from both logical structure and probabilistic uncertainty handling—precisely the combination that MLNs provide and that LIMEN-AI extends with fuzzy semantics.

2.8.3 Biomedical and Scientific Applications

Biomedical domains present some of the most compelling use cases for MLN-based reasoning. Biological systems exhibit a complex relational structure (genes interact

with proteins, proteins interact with other proteins, and pathways regulate processes), and scientific knowledge involves uncertainty that must be quantified. Moreover, the stakes are high: errors in biomedical reasoning can affect patient safety, making interpretability and accountability essential.

Predicting which amino acid residues in a protein are spatially close to each other in the folded structure—a crucial step toward understanding protein function—requires integrating sequence features with structural constraints. Lippi and Frasconi address this by employing MLN-based methods with grounding-specific weights that capture the complex, position-dependent dependencies between residues (Lippi, 2016). The MLN framework combines sequence information (what amino acids are present) with structural priors (residues close in sequence tend to be close in space; certain amino acid pairs are more likely to be in contact).

Beyond molecular biology, MLNs have been applied to clinical reasoning, drug-drug interaction prediction, and medical knowledge base completion. These applications share a common theme: the need to combine structured medical knowledge (ontologies, clinical guidelines) with uncertain evidence from patient data. The interpretability of MLN rules is particularly valuable in clinical settings, where physicians need to understand and validate the reasoning behind recommendations.

2.8.4 Commercial, Security, and Industrial Applications

The practical utility of MLN-based reasoning extends to commercial and industrial settings, where interpretability often serves business needs beyond regulatory compliance. Understanding why a recommendation was made helps customer service representatives explain decisions, aids product managers in identifying system behaviour, and supports compliance teams in auditing for fairness.

In e-commerce, recommendations must balance multiple objectives simultaneously: relevance to user preferences, profitability for the platform, and compliance with consumer protection regulations. Ala et al. show that MLN-based reasoning is well-suited to this balancing act (Ala et al., 2024), since the interpretable rule structure enables both debugging and systematic refinement of recommendation logic.

Bridging perception and reasoning is especially demanding in vision-language tasks, where a system must both recognise visual content and compose coherent descriptions. Shah et al. tackle this with a hybrid Markov Logic architecture (Shah

et al., 2024): neural networks handle object and relationship recognition, while MLN-based reasoning generates grammatically correct and semantically coherent captions. By separating perception from reasoning, the architecture makes it possible to explain why particular captions were generated.

Security applications represent another important domain. Anomaly detection, intrusion detection, and fraud detection all benefit from relational reasoning (attackers often leave patterns of related suspicious activities) and interpretability (security analysts need to understand why an alert was raised). The weighted rules of MLNs can encode expert knowledge about attack patterns while learning from data to refine detection thresholds.

2.8.5 Spatial and Temporal Reasoning

Reasoning about space and time involves a relational structure that is naturally expressed in first-order logic. Spatial relationships (e.g., A is north of B, B is adjacent to C) and temporal relationships (e.g., event X precedes event Y, interval I overlaps interval J) can be captured as predicates, and constraint propagation can derive implicit relationships. The uncertainty inherent in real-world spatial and temporal data makes a probabilistic treatment essential.

Temporal knowledge graphs introduce an extra dimension of complexity: events must be not only linked but also ordered, and inferences may depend on whether one event precedes, overlaps, or follows another. NeoMaPy (David et al., 2023) extends MLN-based reasoning to handle these temporal relations, with applications in timeline reconstruction, temporal question answering, and event prediction.

While most spatial reasoning systems operate on precise coordinates, qualitative approaches use symbolic representations—region A is inside region B, region B overlaps region C—that align more naturally with human spatial cognition. Duckham et al. demonstrate that MLNs can effectively combine such qualitative constraints with uncertain observations (Duckham and Worboys, 2023), enabling robust spatial inference even when the underlying data is noisy or incomplete.

A notable limitation of standard MLNs is their restriction to discrete variables, which excludes reasoning about numerical quantities such as temperatures, prices, or durations. Numerical Markov Logic Networks (Zhong et al., 2021) address this gap by extending the framework to handle continuous variables alongside discrete

ones—a development directly relevant to LIMEN-AI’s use of continuous fuzzy truth values, since the techniques for integrating continuous and discrete inference transfer naturally to the fuzzy setting.

2.8.6 Lessons from Applications

Four themes recur across these application domains and have directly shaped LIMEN-AI’s design.

Explicit structure pays off in practice, not just in principle. In every domain surveyed, the ability to read, question, and revise rules proved valuable—for debugging, for expert validation, and for explaining decisions to stakeholders. If interpretability were merely a theoretical nicety, practitioners would not lean on it so consistently.

Hand-crafted rules are a starting point, not an endpoint. Domain knowledge gets you a useful initial knowledge base, but learning from data—adjusting weights, discovering new rules—is what lifts performance to practical levels. LIMEN-AI’s differentiable framework supports both weight tuning and structural rule discovery.

No component works in isolation. The most effective deployments couple MLN-based reasoning with neural perception for raw-data processing, external knowledge bases for background facts, and domain-specific constraints contributed by experts. LIMEN-AI’s architecture is designed with exactly this kind of modular integration in mind.

Scale remains the elephant in the room. Large domains with many entities strain MLN inference to its limits. LIMEN-AI’s sampling-based approach and continuous relaxation offer a partial answer, and the COLIEE evaluation provides initial evidence that the approach scales to real tasks, but further algorithmic work—lifted inference, lazy grounding—will be needed for the largest domains.

2.9 Research Gaps and Positioning of LIMEN-AI

The six preceding sections have covered a great deal of ground. This final section pulls the threads together, identifying the specific research gaps that LIMEN-AI is designed to fill and positioning the framework relative to existing work.

2.9.1 Identified Research Gaps

A tension runs through the literature just reviewed. Neural-symbolic integration has made genuine progress—visual question answering, knowledge graph completion, differentiable theorem proving—yet the systems that post the strongest benchmark numbers tend to compromise the very interpretability that motivated the neural-symbolic agenda in the first place. Encode predicates as neural networks and you gain expressiveness but lose readable rules. Compile a logic program into an arithmetic circuit and inference speeds up, but the circuit no longer resembles the program it came from. Achieve state-of-the-art accuracy and you may still be unable to produce an explanation that would satisfy an EU AI Act auditor. In short, the field has successfully built hybrids—but hybrids that are simultaneously powerful, transparent, and demonstrably compliant remain scarce.

The literature review identifies five principal research gaps that collectively define the space LIMEN-AI occupies. These gaps are not mere oversights in the literature but represent genuine challenges that have resisted solutions despite significant research efforts. Each gap corresponds to a specific limitation in existing approaches that LIMEN-AI addresses through novel theoretical development, algorithmic design, or systematic analysis.

Figure 30: Research gaps identified in the literature and LIMEN-AI’s responses. Each gap represents a genuine limitation in existing approaches; each solution represents a specific contribution of this thesis. Source: Author.

Figure 30 summarises the gaps and LIMEN-AI’s responses. The gaps are elaborated below.

Gap 1: Differentiable MLN Semantics with Łukasiewicz Logic. While neural-symbolic systems have achieved differentiability through various means, the

specific combination of MLN-style weighted rules with Łukasiewicz fuzzy semantics has not been systematically developed and analysed. This gap is not trivial: it represents the absence of a principled bridge between two powerful paradigms. Classical MLNs use Boolean semantics, which creates discontinuities that prevent gradient-based learning—the very learning paradigm that has driven the deep learning revolution. Attempts to work around this limitation have led to three main strategies, each with fundamental drawbacks. Logic Tensor Networks and similar systems achieve differentiability by implementing predicates as neural networks, but this sacrifices the explicit rule structure that makes MLNs interpretable in the first place. An alternative path—Probabilistic Soft Logic—uses a different continuous relaxation based on squared hinge loss, yet this relaxation does not preserve the logical semantics of implication and does not satisfy the residuation property that characterises genuine fuzzy logics. A third line of work applies smooth approximations to Boolean operations (sigmoid functions, softmax), but these approximations are inherently arbitrary and lack the mathematical elegance and theoretical grounding of established fuzzy logics. The literature contains scattered uses of Łukasiewicz logic in various contexts, but no comprehensive framework has been developed that combines it with MLN-style weighted rules, proves the key mathematical properties (piecewise linearity, differentiability almost everywhere, convergence of gradient descent), develops the necessary inference and learning algorithms, and validates the approach through formal verification. This absence is particularly striking given that Łukasiewicz logic has been studied for over a century and MLNs for two decades; the synthesis of these two mature frameworks represents not an obvious next step but a genuine research challenge requiring careful mathematical development.

Gap 2: Interpretability as a Primary Design Goal. Many neural-symbolic systems sacrifice interpretability for computational efficiency or expressiveness, inadvertently replicating the opacity problem they ostensibly aim to solve. Neural implementations of predicates, while powerful, do not expose their learned relationships in explicit form. A predicate implemented as a neural network may capture complex patterns, but these patterns are encoded in weights that have no interpretable meaning—the system has merely shifted opacity from the inference process to the predicate definitions. This architectural choice fundamentally undermines the interpretability promise of neurosymbolic AI: users can see the logical structure of rules but cannot understand what the predicates themselves encode. For applications

where interpretability is not merely desirable but legally required—as mandated by Article 13 of the EU AI Act for high-risk systems—this trade-off is unacceptable. The literature contains frequent claims about interpretability but relatively few systems that maintain fully explicit, human-readable rule structures throughout the reasoning process, from knowledge representation through inference to explanation generation. The gap is not merely one of emphasis but of fundamental design philosophy: most existing systems treat interpretability as a feature to be added or approximated rather than as an architectural constraint that shapes every component of the framework.

Gap 3: Regulatory Alignment. The XAI literature has largely developed independently of regulatory requirements, creating a dangerous disconnect between technical capabilities and legal obligations. Explanation methods are typically evaluated based on criteria such as fidelity, comprehensibility, and stability—metrics that reflect researchers’ intuitions about what constitutes a good explanation—without a systematic analysis of whether they satisfy the specific legal requirements imposed by regulations such as the EU AI Act. Yet the Act imposes detailed, prescriptive requirements: transparency sufficient to enable users to interpret outputs and use them appropriately (Article 13); human oversight measures that enable assigned individuals to fully understand system capabilities and limitations (Article 14); technical documentation describing system logic and design choices (Article 11); and automatic logging of events during operation (Article 12). Meeting these requirements is not simply a matter of providing “some kind of explanation”; it requires specific technical capabilities that must be designed into the system architecture from the outset. A post-hoc explanation generated by LIME or SHAP may or may not satisfy Article 13’s transparency requirement—it depends on whether the explanation accurately represents the system’s actual reasoning, whether it is comprehensible to the intended users, and whether it provides sufficient detail to enable appropriate use. The literature contains almost no systematic analysis of how different XAI approaches align with these specific regulatory requirements, leaving practitioners and organisations in the uncomfortable position of deploying systems whose compliance status is uncertain. This gap is not merely academic; with the AI Act now in force and enforcement mechanisms being established, the lack of principled guidance on technical-regulatory alignment creates genuine legal and business risks.

Gap 4: Explanation Trace Generation. While inference algorithms for MLNs and related systems are well developed, the systematic generation of explanation

traces that record rule contributions has received less attention. Most inference algorithms focus on producing numerical outputs—probability estimates, MAP assignments—without tracking how different rules contributed to these outputs. However, for auditing, debugging, and regulatory compliance, it is often important to understand not just what the system concluded but how it reached that conclusion. The literature contains various approaches to generating explanations, but few produce structured traces as an integral part of the inference process.

Gap 5: Inductive Rule Discovery with Fuzzy Scoring. While structure learning in MLNs has been studied extensively, the integration of template-based rule discovery with differentiable scoring in a fuzzy setting represents a novel direction. Classical MLN structure learning uses discrete search over candidate formulas, evaluating each candidate’s contribution to likelihood. This approach does not naturally integrate with gradient-based learning or with fuzzy semantics. Template-based approaches constrain the search space but have not been combined with differentiable scoring functions that enable gradient-based optimisation of rule weights.

2.9.2 Positioning of LIMEN-AI

LIMEN-AI responds to all five gaps, not through incremental patches but through a design that weaves differentiability, explicit rules, trace generation, inductive learning, and regulatory analysis into a single coherent framework.

For Gap 1, Chapter 3 develops the full formal apparatus: syntax, Łukasiewicz semantics, energy functions, and proofs of the properties—piecewise linearity, a.e. differentiability, gradient-descent convergence—that make the combination mathematically sound rather than heuristically plausible.

For Gap 2, the design decision is architectural. LIMEN-AI’s knowledge base consists, at all times, of explicit weighted first-order formulas that a domain expert can read and edit. Truth assignments carry interpretable fuzzy values, not opaque neural activations. This comes at some cost in expressiveness—neural predicates can capture patterns that explicit rules cannot—but the trade is deliberate: for regulated deployments, transparency is non-negotiable.

Gap 3 is addressed in Chapter 7, which maps LIMEN-AI’s capabilities onto Articles 9–15 of the AI Act requirement by requirement and proposes reference deployment workflows for three illustrative domains. The analysis identifies where

the alignment is strong and where organisational measures must compensate for technical limitations.

For Gap 4, Chapter 4 instruments its sampling algorithms to emit structured explanation traces as a first-class output—not a bolt-on. Each trace records which rules fired, to what degree, and how their contributions combined, giving auditors a direct window into the reasoning behind every answer.

Gap 5 is the subject of Chapter 5. Template-based rule generation constrains the search space to domain-appropriate patterns; a differentiable scoring function grades candidates against labelled data via gradient descent; and a beam search expands the most promising templates while pruning the rest. The result is a knowledge base that can grow structurally without sacrificing the explicit logical form that makes the rest of the framework interpretable.

2.9.3 Comparative Analysis

Table 8 provides a detailed comparison of LIMEN-AI with the most closely related systems in the literature. The comparison highlights the distinctive combination of properties that LIMEN-AI achieves.

Table 8: Comparison of LIMEN-AI with related neural-symbolic systems. Source: Author.

System	Differentiable	Explicit Rules	Fuzzy	Traces	Regulatory
Classical MLN	No	Yes	No	Partial	No
Logic Tensor Networks	Yes	No	Yes	No	No
DeepProbLog	Yes	Yes	No	Partial	No
Scallop	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
PSL	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
LIMEN-AI	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Classical MLNs maintain explicit rules and can generate some form of explanation through the inspection of satisfied clauses, but they are not differentiable due to Boolean semantics. Logic Tensor Networks achieve differentiability and use fuzzy semantics but implement predicates as neural networks, sacrificing explicit rule structure. DeepProbLog maintains explicit rules and achieves differentiability but uses probabilistic rather than fuzzy semantics and does not systematically generate traces. Scallop provides provenance tracking that supports trace generation but does not use fuzzy semantics. Probabilistic Soft Logic uses continuous truth values and

explicit rules but employs a different semantic foundation and does not emphasise trace generation or regulatory alignment.

LIMEN-AI is unique in combining all five properties: differentiability through Łukasiewicz semantics, explicit weighted rules that remain inspectable, fuzzy truth values that support graded reasoning, systematic generation of explanation traces, and explicit analysis of regulatory alignment. This combination is not achieved by any existing system in the literature.

2.9.4 Detailed Comparison with Probabilistic Soft Logic

Among the systems surveyed, Probabilistic Soft Logic (PSL) is the closest relative of LIMEN-AI and therefore warrants a more thorough comparison than the summary table can provide. Both frameworks assign continuous truth values in $[0,1]$ to ground atoms, attach real-valued weights to first-order rules, and derive their continuous relaxations from the Łukasiewicz t-norm. An examiner encountering LIMEN-AI for the first time would rightly ask what separates the two. The differences, though subtle at the formula level, are architecturally consequential and manifest along four dimensions.

Semantic foundation. PSL replaces the exact Łukasiewicz t-norm $\max(0, a+b-1)$ with a squared hinge-loss surrogate: each rule’s potential is the square of the Łukasiewicz residual, clamped to be non-negative (Bach et al., 2017). The substitution is deliberate—it renders the resulting Markov random field energy *convex* in the atom truth values, guaranteeing a unique MAP solution. Convexity, however, comes at the cost of fidelity: the squared hinge loss is a *surrogate* for, not a realisation of, the Łukasiewicz semantics. In particular, the residuation property (Proposition 3.1, Property 7) no longer holds exactly, and the algebraic guarantees that Isabelle/HOL verifies for LIMEN-AI (Appendix B) do not transfer. LIMEN-AI preserves the exact Łukasiewicz operations and couples them with a proper Gibbs distribution $P(I; \mathbf{w}) \propto \exp(E(I; \mathbf{w}))$ (Definition 3.16), which assigns probabilities to *all* interpretations rather than collapsing to a single point estimate. The Gibbs formulation enables marginal inference and uncertainty quantification—capabilities that PSL’s MAP-only semantics cannot provide.

Inference strategy. Because the PSL energy is convex, inference reduces to a convex optimisation problem that Bach et al. solve with the Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM) (Bach et al., 2017). ADMM is efficient and scales well, but it returns a single optimal assignment—the MAP interpretation—without distributional information. LIMEN-AI’s piecewise-linear energy is *not* convex in the interpretation (the max and min operations break concavity), so the framework relies instead on Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling, including importance sampling and power-tempered chains (Chapter 4). Sampling is more expensive per query than ADMM but provides richer output: an approximate posterior over interpretations from which expected truth degrees, credible intervals, and calibrated confidences can be derived. For regulated deployments that require not only a decision but also a calibrated measure of confidence, distributional inference is essential.

Gradient properties. PSL’s squared hinge loss is convex and smooth almost everywhere, yielding well-behaved gradients that point toward the unique global optimum. LIMEN-AI’s energy is piecewise linear with sub-gradients at the region boundaries (Theorem 3.3, Corollary 3.1). Both frameworks support gradient-based weight learning, but through different mechanisms: PSL exploits the convexity of its surrogate to guarantee convergence to the global MAP solution; LIMEN-AI relies on the concavity of the log-likelihood in the weight space (Theorem 3.5) and on the fact that sub-gradient descent converges under Robbins–Monro conditions. The practical trade-off is speed versus semantic fidelity: PSL’s convex surrogate converges faster but approximates the underlying logic; LIMEN-AI’s exact operations preserve logical properties at the cost of a harder optimisation landscape in the interpretation space.

Explanation traces. PSL inference produces a single MAP assignment—a vector of atom truth values that jointly minimises the total hinge-loss penalty. The output does not decompose into per-rule contributions; one can inspect individual rule potentials after the fact, but the framework provides no systematic mechanism for recording which rules drove each atom’s value during optimisation. LIMEN-AI, by contrast, generates structured explanation traces as a first-class output of its inference algorithms (Chapter 4). Each trace records, for every query atom, the satisfaction degree of each rule grounding, the weight-scaled contribution to the energy, and the resulting influence on the atom’s posterior truth degree. This per-rule

decomposition is what enables the 100% explainability reported on the COLIEE benchmark (Chapter 6) and what supports the transparency requirements of the EU AI Act (Chapter 7).

Taken together, these four differences amount to a fundamental divergence in design philosophy. PSL optimises for computational efficiency by accepting a convex approximation of the underlying logic and returning point estimates. LIMEN-AI optimises for semantic fidelity and transparency by preserving exact Łukasiewicz operations, maintaining a proper probabilistic distribution, and instrumenting inference to produce auditable reasoning traces. Neither choice is unconditionally superior: PSL is the better tool when scalability to millions of groundings is the primary concern and distributional information is unnecessary; LIMEN-AI is the better tool when regulatory compliance, uncertainty quantification, and per-rule explainability are non-negotiable requirements.

2.10 Summary

This chapter has surveyed six research areas—statistical relational learning and MLNs, MLN inference, neural-symbolic integration, fuzzy logic, explainable AI, and AI regulation—through the PRISMA methodology, synthesising 145 studies to map the landscape in which LIMEN-AI operates. Across these areas, a consistent picture emerges. Boolean semantics block gradient-based MLN learning, and inference remains intractable at scale; neural-symbolic systems such as LTN, DeepProbLog, and Scallop demonstrate that differentiable logic works but each trades away explicit rule structure or adopts probabilistic rather than fuzzy semantics; Łukasiewicz logic offers piecewise linear connectives that are differentiable almost everywhere, residuated, and well suited to gradient-based optimisation; the XAI literature makes a strong case for inherent interpretability over post-hoc explanation in high-stakes settings; and the EU AI Act converts that case into a binding legal obligation. Five interconnected research gaps follow from this synthesis, already detailed in Section 2.9 and summarised in Table 9: (i) no prior framework combines MLN-style weighted rules with Łukasiewicz semantics and proves the resulting mathematical properties; (ii) most neural-symbolic pipelines sacrifice explicit rule structure; (iii) XAI methods are seldom evaluated against the specific articles of the AI Act; (iv) inference algorithms focus on numerical outputs rather than structured explanation traces;

and (v) MLN structure learning relies on discrete search rather than gradient-based fuzzy scoring. LIMEN-AI addresses all five within a single coherent design—formal NMLN framework, explicit weighted rules maintained throughout learning, systematic regulatory-alignment analysis, trace-generating inference algorithms, and differentiable template-based induction—positioning itself at the intersection of these research traditions. The following chapters develop this framework in full technical detail, beginning with the mathematical foundations in Chapter 3.

Table 9: Summary of research gaps and LIMEN-AI’s contributions addressing each gap. Source: Author.

Gap	Limitation of Existing Work	LIMEN-AI Contribution
Differentiable MLN semantics	Boolean MLNs not differentiable; fuzzy systems use different foundations	NMLN framework with Łukasiewicz semantics
Interpretability preservation	Neural-symbolic systems often sacrifice explicit structure	Explicit weighted rules maintained throughout
Regulatory alignment	XAI methods not analysed against AI Act	Systematic alignment analysis
Explanation trace generation	Inference focuses on outputs, not provenance	Trace-generating inference algorithms
Fuzzy inductive learning	Structure learning uses discrete search	Differentiable template-based induction

Table 9 distils these gaps and the corresponding LIMEN-AI contributions into a concise reference. The chapters that follow develop each contribution in full technical detail, beginning with the mathematical foundations in Chapter 3.

3 Mathematical Foundations

LIMEN-AI rests on Neuralized Markov Logic Networks (NMLNs), which pair weighted first-order rules with Łukasiewicz fuzzy semantics (Hájek, 1998). Fuzzy truth values in $[0, 1]$ make the resulting energy function differentiable, so weights can be learned by gradient descent while the logical structure stays explicit and inspectable.

Sections 3.1–3.2 fix the syntax and semantics: signatures, formulas, Łukasiewicz connectives, and their algebraic properties. Section 3.3 aggregates weighted formula satisfactions into a scalar energy, and Section 3.4 proves piecewise linearity—hence almost-everywhere differentiability. Sections 3.5 and 3.6 derive the Gibbs distribution and the convergence guarantee for weight learning. Section 3.7 gives complexity bounds, and Section 3.8 works through hand-calculable examples.

3.1 Syntax of Neuralized Markov Logic Networks

Evaluation and optimisation require a precise language for rules. I fix that language here: predicates, constants, formulas, and the grounding machinery that turns quantified statements into concrete propositions.

3.1.1 Signatures, Terms, and Atoms

NMLN syntax adapts standard first-order logic to the knowledge representation setting.

Definition 3.1 (Signature). *A signature $\Sigma = (\mathcal{P}, \mathcal{C})$ consists of:*

- 1. A finite set \mathcal{P} of predicate symbols, where each predicate $p \in \mathcal{P}$ has an associated arity $ar(p) \in \mathbb{N}$, denoting the number of arguments it takes.*
- 2. A finite set \mathcal{C} of constant symbols, representing the objects in the domain of discourse.*

Finite signatures are essential for computational tractability. Infinite signatures have theoretical interest, but every LIMEN-AI application operates over a finite domain.

Definition 3.2 (Terms). *Given a signature $\Sigma = (\mathcal{P}, \mathcal{C})$ and a countably infinite set \mathcal{V} of variable symbols (disjoint from \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{C}), a term is either:*

1. A constant $c \in \mathcal{C}$, or
2. A variable $x \in \mathcal{V}$.

A term is ground if it contains no variables; equivalently, a ground term is a constant.

Definition 3.3 (Atoms). An atom is an expression of the form $p(t_1, \dots, t_n)$ where:

1. $p \in \mathcal{P}$ is a predicate symbol with $ar(p) = n$, and
2. t_1, \dots, t_n are terms.

An atom is ground if all of its arguments are ground terms (constants). The set of all ground atoms over the signature Σ is denoted \mathcal{A}_Σ .

The set of ground atoms \mathcal{A}_Σ forms the basic vocabulary over which interpretations are defined. For a signature with predicates of maximum arity k and n constants, the number of ground atoms is bounded by $|\mathcal{P}| \cdot n^k$, which is polynomial in the domain size.

Example 3.1 (Cybersecurity Signature). Consider a cybersecurity domain with the following signature. The predicate set $\mathcal{P} = \{\text{failedLogin}/2, \text{accessedResource}/2, \text{suspicious}/1, \text{raiseAlert}/2\}$ captures relationships between users, resources, and security events, while the constant set $\mathcal{C} = \{\text{alice}, \text{bob}, \text{srv1}, \text{srv2}, \text{db1}\}$ represents specific users and servers in the domain. Ground atoms constructed from this signature include $\text{failedLogin}(\text{alice}, \text{srv1})$, $\text{suspicious}(\text{bob})$, and $\text{raiseAlert}(\text{alice}, \text{srv2})$.

3.1.2 Formulas

Formulas are built from atoms using logical connectives and quantifiers.

Definition 3.4 (Formulas). The set of formulas over signature Σ is defined inductively as follows:

1. Every atom over Σ is a formula.
2. If φ is a formula, then $\neg\varphi$ (negation) is a formula.
3. If φ and ψ are formulas, then:
 - $\varphi \wedge \psi$ (conjunction) is a formula,

- $\varphi \vee \psi$ (*disjunction*) is a formula, and
- $\varphi \rightarrow \psi$ (*implication*) is a formula.

4. If φ is a formula and $x \in \mathcal{V}$ is a variable, then:

- $\forall x. \varphi$ (*universal quantification*) is a formula, and
- $\exists x. \varphi$ (*existential quantification*) is a formula.

A variable x is *free* in a formula if it occurs outside the scope of any quantifier binding x . A formula is *closed* (or a *sentence*) if it has no free variables. A formula is *ground* if it contains no variables.

Definition 3.5 (Substitution). A substitution is a mapping $\theta : \mathcal{V} \rightarrow \mathcal{C} \cup \mathcal{V}$ from variables to terms. For a formula φ , the result of applying substitution θ to φ , written $\varphi\theta$, is the formula obtained by simultaneously replacing each free occurrence of variable x in φ with $\theta(x)$.

A grounding substitution maps all variables to constants. For a formula φ with free variables x_1, \dots, x_k , a grounding of φ is a ground formula $\varphi[x_1/c_1, \dots, x_k/c_k]$ obtained by substituting constants c_1, \dots, c_k for the free variables.

Definition 3.6 (Groundings). For a formula φ with free variables $\{x_1, \dots, x_k\}$ over signature Σ , the set of groundings of φ is:

$$\text{Gr}(\varphi) = \{\varphi[x_1/c_1, \dots, x_k/c_k] : c_1, \dots, c_k \in \mathcal{C}\}$$

The number of groundings is $|\text{Gr}(\varphi)| = |\mathcal{C}|^k$, which is exponential in the number of free variables.

3.1.3 Knowledge Bases

A Neuralized Markov Logic Network knowledge base consists of weighted formulas that express domain knowledge.

Definition 3.7 (Weighted Formula). A weighted formula is a pair (φ, w) where φ is a formula and $w \in \mathbb{R}$ is a real-valued weight.

Definition 3.8 (NMLN Knowledge Base). A Neuralized Markov Logic Network knowledge base \mathcal{K} over signature Σ is a tuple $(\Sigma, \mathcal{F}, \mathbf{w})$ where:

1. $\Sigma = (\mathcal{P}, \mathcal{C})$ is a signature.
2. $\mathcal{F} = \{\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_m\}$ is a finite set of formulas over Σ .
3. $\mathbf{w} = (w_1, \dots, w_m) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is a vector of weights, where w_i is the weight associated with the formula φ_i .

The weight w_i associated with formula φ_i indicates the strength or importance of the constraint expressed by that formula. A positive weight indicates that the formula should be satisfied; a negative weight indicates that the formula should be violated. The magnitude of the weight indicates the relative importance of the constraint.

Remark 3.1 (Hard and Soft Constraints). In classical MLNs, a formula with infinite weight is a *hard constraint* that must be satisfied in all possible worlds, while a formula with finite weight is a *soft constraint* that can be violated with a penalty. In LIMEN-AI, all weights are finite, and all constraints are soft. Hard constraints can be approximated by using very large weights.

3.2 Semantics Under Łukasiewicz Interpretation

Classical logic assigns Boolean truth values; LIMEN-AI assigns values in $[0, 1]$ using Łukasiewicz fuzzy operations. Piecewise linearity feeds directly into gradient-based optimisation, and the semantics still preserves commutativity, De Morgan laws, and residuation—making it a genuine logic rather than an ad hoc continuous relaxation.

3.2.1 Fuzzy Interpretations

In classical logic, an interpretation assigns a Boolean truth value (true or false) to each ground atom. In Łukasiewicz fuzzy logic, truth values range over the unit interval $[0, 1]$, enabling the representation of partial or graded truth.

Definition 3.9 (Fuzzy Interpretation). A fuzzy interpretation I over signature Σ is a function $I : \mathcal{A}_\Sigma \rightarrow [0, 1]$ that assigns a truth degree $I(A) \in [0, 1]$ to each ground atom $A \in \mathcal{A}_\Sigma$.

The set of all fuzzy interpretations over Σ is denoted \mathcal{I}_Σ . This set can be identified with the hypercube $[0, 1]^{|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma|}$.

The truth degree $I(A)$ represents the extent to which the atom A holds under interpretation I . A truth degree of 1 indicates full truth; a truth degree of 0 indicates full falsity; intermediate values indicate partial truth.

3.2.2 Łukasiewicz Connectives

Truth assignments extend from ground atoms to complex formulas through Łukasiewicz operations.

Definition 3.10 (Łukasiewicz Operations). *For truth degrees $a, b \in [0, 1]$, the Łukasiewicz operations are defined as follows:*

$$\text{Negation: } \neg_{\mathcal{L}} a = 1 - a \tag{16}$$

$$\text{Conjunction: } a \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} b = T_{\mathcal{L}}(a, b) = \max(0, a + b - 1) \tag{17}$$

$$\text{Disjunction: } a \vee_{\mathcal{L}} b = S_{\mathcal{L}}(a, b) = \min(1, a + b) \tag{18}$$

$$\text{Implication: } a \rightarrow_{\mathcal{L}} b = \min(1, 1 - a + b) \tag{19}$$

The conjunction $T_{\mathcal{L}}$ is called the Łukasiewicz t-norm, and the disjunction $S_{\mathcal{L}}$ is called the Łukasiewicz t-conorm (or s-norm).

3.2.3 From Fuzzy Logic to Differentiable Computation

Łukasiewicz operations are piecewise linear—exactly the class of functions that automatic differentiation frameworks handle best. This subsection spells out the connection and shows how each operation maps to a PyTorch primitive.

Piecewise Linearity and Gradient Flow. Each Łukasiewicz operation can be expressed as a composition of affine functions and the operations \max and \min . Consider the conjunction $a \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} b = \max(0, a + b - 1)$. This formulation reveals two critical properties:

The unit square $[0, 1]^2$ splits along the line $a + b = 1$ into two regions: one where the output is 0 and one where it equals $a + b - 1$. Within each region the gradient is constant. All four Łukasiewicz connectives share this two-region structure (negation is globally affine). Modern AD engines handle such piecewise linear functions efficiently. In LIMEN-AI, the conjunction is implemented as:

```
1 torch.clamp(a + b - 1.0, min=0.0, max=1.0)
```

The `torch.clamp` function applies the transformation $x \mapsto \max(\min_val, \min(\max_val, x))$, which is precisely the piecewise linear clamping operation. PyTorch’s automatic differentiation engine computes gradients through `clamp` using the sub-gradient at the boundaries: when x is strictly inside the interval $[\min_val, \max_val]$, the gradient is 1; when x is outside, the gradient is 0. At the exact boundary points, the sub-gradient is not uniquely defined, but PyTorch conventionally uses the right-continuous value (gradient 1 at the lower boundary, gradient 0 at the upper boundary).

Formally verified in Isabelle/HOL (see Appendix B, theorems `luk_and_monotonic_left` and `luk_and_valid`), the Łukasiewicz conjunction satisfies the monotonicity and well-formedness properties that ensure the operations remain within $[0, 1]$ throughout optimisation.

Correctness-by-Construction: From Definition to Implementation.

LIMEN-AI achieves *correctness-by-construction* for its algebraic substrate: the Łukasiewicz connective definitions (Definition 3.10) are exactly realised in the executable code, and the algebraic properties of those connectives are formally verified through mechanised proof. Embedding-based approaches such as DPLogic (Li et al., 2025a) approximate logical operations through learned neural networks, and other neural-symbolic systems validate their semantics–implementation link only empirically. LIMEN-AI closes that gap for the core algebraic layer, while the higher-level properties—differentiability, gradient correctness, and convergence—rest on conventional paper proofs rather than machine-checked formalisation.

Three mutually reinforcing arguments support the algebraic guarantee; their scope and limitations are stated explicitly.

Semantic precision. Definition 3.10 pins down the Łukasiewicz conjunction as the real-analytic function $T_L(a, b) = \max(0, a + b - 1)$ for $a, b \in [0, 1]$ —a specification, not a guiding metaphor.

Implementation fidelity. The LIMEN-AI codebase realises this function via `torch.clamp(a + b - 1.0, min=0.0, max=1.0)` (Chapter 6). Since `clamp` computes $\max(\min, \min(\max, x))$ and for $a, b \in [0, 1]$ we have $a + b - 1 \leq 1$, the expression simplifies to

$$\text{torch.clamp}(a + b - 1, 0, 1) = \max(0, a + b - 1) = T_L(a, b).$$

The implementation computes the mathematical function exactly, not an approximation of it.

Mechanised verification (scope and limits). The informal algebraic argument above is backed by 55 machine-checked theorems in Isabelle/HOL (Appendix B). These cover well-formedness (`luk_and_valid`: outputs stay in $[0, 1]$), the t-norm axioms—commutativity, associativity, monotonicity (Hájek, 1998)—De Morgan duality (`luk_demorgan_and`, `luk_demorgan_or`), energy-level properties (linearity in weights, boundedness), and the piecewise linearity of each Łukasiewicz connective (`luk_and_piecewise`, `luk_or_piecewise`, `luk_not_piecewise`, `luk_implies_piecewise`). It is important to delineate what the Isabelle formalisation does and does not cover. The 55 theorems verify the *algebraic substrate and piecewise-linear structure* of the individual connectives: connective identities, range invariants, structural properties of the energy function, and the two-region decomposition of each operation (Theorem 3.2). They do *not* cover the inductive extension of piecewise linearity to arbitrary formula depth (Theorem 3.3), sub-gradient correctness, or the convergence of weight learning (Theorem 3.5). Those results are established by conventional mathematical proofs in Sections 3.4 and 3.6 and have not been machine-checked. The correctness-by-construction claim therefore applies fully to the algebraic and piecewise-linear layer and partially to the system as a whole: the verified substrate provides a sound foundation on which the paper proofs build, but extending the mechanised formalisation to formula-level differentiability and convergence remains future work (Appendix B).

The Isabelle formalisation spans approximately 650 lines across four theory files, mechanically checked by the Isabelle kernel. The proofs are constructive—they provide explicit derivations that can be inspected and audited.

Contrast with embedding-based approaches. DPLogic encodes formula weights as relation-specific embeddings and implements logical operations through neural networks (Li et al., 2025a). The result can be accurate on knowledge graph tasks, but nothing formally ties the learned operators to any logical semantics—inspecting the embedding vectors reveals no interpretable structure. Jung et al.’s quantified neural MLNs trade the same way: neural potentials gain flexibility but lose the direct formula-to-number correspondence that LIMEN-AI preserves (Jung et al., 2024).

Regulatory implications. Because every step from specification to imple-

mentation is auditable—with the algebraic core backed by the mechanised proofs in Appendix B and the differentiability and convergence properties established by the paper proofs in this chapter—the correctness-by-construction property directly supports the transparency requirements of AI regulation (Chapter 7).

A remaining question: what happens to differentiability at the boundaries between linear regions?

Measure-Zero Singularities and Sub-Gradient Methods. The boundaries between affine pieces form a measure-zero set in $[0, 1]^{|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma|}$. At these points the left and right derivatives differ, so classical differentiability fails. The non-differentiability is benign for reasons detailed below and elaborated in Section 3.4.

Non-differentiable points form a Lebesgue-measure-zero set, so any stochastic gradient procedure hits them with probability zero. Floating-point arithmetic reinforces this: exact equality on a hyperplane requires a specific bit pattern, exponentially unlikely under random perturbation.

At a boundary point the sub-gradient—the set of all limiting gradients—remains well-defined and bounded. The standard update

$$\mathbf{w}_{t+1} = \mathbf{w}_t + \eta_t \cdot \mathbf{g}_t, \quad \mathbf{g}_t \in \partial E(\mathbf{w}_t),$$

converges under the same Robbins–Monro conditions as smooth gradient descent.

The discontinuous gradient switch at a boundary is informative, not pathological. Within each linear region the gradient points toward the region’s optimum; crossing a boundary replaces it with one reflecting the new geometry, letting the optimiser traverse the piecewise landscape efficiently.

Comparison with Alternative Fuzzy Semantics. Why not use Gödel logic, where conjunction is $\min(a, b)$, or product logic, where conjunction is $a \cdot b$? Both alternatives have their own mathematical elegance, but they pose challenges for gradient-based learning.

Gödel’s $\min(a, b)$ yields sparse gradients—only one input contributes at any point. The product t-norm $a \cdot b$ suffers from vanishing gradients when truth degrees are small. The Łukasiewicz t-norm avoids both problems: it maintains unit gradients within its linear regions (Chapter 2). Figure 31 visualises the differences.

Figure 31: Comparison of three fuzzy t-norms (conjunction operations). **Left:** Łukasiewicz t-norm is piecewise linear with two regions separated by the plane $a + b = 1$. Gradients are unit-valued within the active region ($a + b > 1$), providing strong learning signals. **Centre:** Gödel t-norm is piecewise linear but has sparse gradients (only one input contributes at any point). **Right:** Product t-norm is smooth but suffers from vanishing gradients when truth degrees are small. LIMEN-AI uses Łukasiewicz operations for optimal gradient flow. Source: Author.

Operation	Mathematical Definition	PyTorch Implementation
Negation	$1 - a$	<code>1.0 - a</code>
Conjunction	$\max(0, a + b - 1)$	<code>clamp(a + b - 1, min=0, max=1)</code>
Disjunction	$\min(1, a + b)$	<code>clamp(a + b, min=0, max=1)</code>
Implication	$\min(1, 1 - a + b)$	<code>clamp(1 - a + b, min=0, max=1)</code>

Table 10: Mapping between Łukasiewicz operations (mathematical formulation) and their implementation in PyTorch. The `clamp` operation ensures values remain in $[0, 1]$ while enabling automatic differentiation through sub-gradients. Source: Author.

Implementation Correspondence. Table 10 maps each mathematical definition to its PyTorch realization; Chapter 6 gives full implementation details.

Because the mapping is exact, the properties verified in Isabelle/HOL—commutativity, associativity, De Morgan laws, residuation (Appendix B, theorems `luk_and_commutative` through `luk_demorgan_or`)—hold in the implementation without approximation. Every formula evaluation in the Python code corresponds to a composable sequence of these primitive operations, and the computed gradients are guaranteed to be correct sub-gradients of the energy function. This property is essential for the re-ranking architecture evaluated in Chapter 6, where the COLIEE benchmark results (Precision: 11.67%, a 46% relative improvement over BM25) depend critically on the correctness of the gradient flow through thousands of formula evaluations.

Figure 32 summarises the complete pipeline from knowledge base definition to gradient computation, showing how the compositional semantics enable end-to-end

differentiation.

Figure 32: Compositional semantics pipeline in LIMEN-AI. The knowledge base defines formulas and weights (structure). A fuzzy interpretation assigns truth degrees to atoms (variables). Formula evaluation uses Łukasiewicz operations (piecewise linear, differentiable a.e.). Ground satisfaction averages over formula groundings. The energy function aggregates weighted satisfactions into a scalar objective. Automatic differentiation computes gradients for optimisation. This end-to-end differentiable architecture enables neurosymbolic learning. Source: Author.

Symbolic specification sits at the top, numerical optimisation at the bottom, and every intermediate step is differentiable. The algebraic properties that hold this pipeline together are stated next.

Proposition 3.1 (Properties of Łukasiewicz Operations). *The Łukasiewicz operations satisfy the following properties:*

1. **Commutativity:** $a \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} b = b \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} a$ and $a \vee_{\mathcal{L}} b = b \vee_{\mathcal{L}} a$.

2. **Associativity:** $(a \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} b) \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} c = a \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} (b \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} c)$ and $(a \vee_{\mathcal{L}} b) \vee_{\mathcal{L}} c = a \vee_{\mathcal{L}} (b \vee_{\mathcal{L}} c)$.
3. **Identity:** $a \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} 1 = a$ and $a \vee_{\mathcal{L}} 0 = a$.
4. **Annihilator:** $a \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} 0 = 0$ and $a \vee_{\mathcal{L}} 1 = 1$.
5. **De Morgan laws:** $\neg_{\mathcal{L}}(a \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} b) = (\neg_{\mathcal{L}} a) \vee_{\mathcal{L}} (\neg_{\mathcal{L}} b)$ and $\neg_{\mathcal{L}}(a \vee_{\mathcal{L}} b) = (\neg_{\mathcal{L}} a) \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} (\neg_{\mathcal{L}} b)$.
6. **Double negation:** $\neg_{\mathcal{L}}(\neg_{\mathcal{L}} a) = a$.
7. **Residuation:** $a \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} c \leq b$ if and only if $c \leq a \rightarrow_{\mathcal{L}} b$.

Proof. Properties (1)–(6) follow directly from the definitions by algebraic manipulation. Property (7), the residuation property, characterises the Łukasiewicz implication as the residuum of the t-norm and can be verified by case analysis:

- If $a + c - 1 \leq 0$, then $a \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} c = 0 \leq b$, and we need $c \leq 1 - a + b$. Since $c \leq 1 - a + 1 = 2 - a$ and $1 - a + b \geq 1 - a$, this holds when $c \leq 1 - a$.
- If $a + c - 1 > 0$, then $a \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} c = a + c - 1 \leq b$ iff $c \leq 1 - a + b$, which is exactly $c \leq a \rightarrow_{\mathcal{L}} b$ when $1 - a + b \leq 1$.

□

Significance of the Residuation Property. Residuation ties conjunction and implication together: $a \rightarrow_{\mathcal{L}} b$ is the greatest c such that $a \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} c \leq b$. When $a \rightarrow_{\mathcal{L}} b = 1$ and $a = 1$, the bound forces $b = 1$ —the fuzzy analogue of modus ponens. More generally, the inferrable degree $a \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} (a \rightarrow_{\mathcal{L}} b)$ is at most b , so partial antecedents yield partial conclusions.

Proof-theoretically, residuation means the implication operator internalises the entailment relation $(a \vdash b)$ as a truth-functional connective $(a \rightarrow b)$, not a syntactic shorthand.

Computationally, residuation guarantees well-behaved gradient flow through implications. The optimiser can adjust the consequent truth degree b to compensate for the antecedent a while respecting logical consistency.

Advanced Algebraic Properties: Symmetric Difference in Nilpotent Systems. Łukasiewicz logic also supports derived operators relevant to multi-stage reasoning. The *symmetric difference* has been recently revisited for its role in comparing and reconciling intermediate conclusions along competing inference paths.

The Łukasiewicz symmetric difference can be defined as:

$$a \triangle_{\mathbb{L}} b = (a \vee_{\mathbb{L}} b) \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} \neg_{\mathbb{L}}(a \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} b)$$

Intuitively, $a \triangle_{\mathbb{L}} b$ measures the degree to which a and b differ: it is 1 when they are maximally different (one is 0, the other is 1), and 0 when they are identical. In classical Boolean logic, the symmetric difference corresponds to the exclusive-or (XOR) operation, but in fuzzy logic, it captures a graded notion of dissimilarity.

Recent work by Puzstaházi et al. has investigated the behaviour of the *aggregated symmetric difference operator* in nilpotent fuzzy systems, demonstrating that it satisfies the associativity property (Puzstaházi et al., 2025). A fuzzy t-norm T is *nilpotent* if there exist values $a, b > 0$ such that $T(a, b) = 0$. The Łukasiewicz t-norm is nilpotent; for instance, $T_{\mathbb{L}}(0.4, 0.4) = \max(0, 0.8 - 1) = 0$. This contrasts with the product t-norm (which is never zero unless one input is zero) and the Gödel t-norm (which equals the minimum of its inputs).

Nilpotency matters for multi-hop knowledge graph reasoning and deep logic program evaluation. When LIMEN-AI evaluates a chain of implications $\phi_1 \Rightarrow \phi_2 \Rightarrow \dots \Rightarrow \phi_n$, truth degrees propagate through successive applications of $T_{\mathbb{L}}$. If intermediate truth degrees drop low enough, the conjunction annihilates to zero, cutting off further propagation. This natural filtering prevents weak evidence from accumulating through long inference chains.

Puzstaházi et al.’s associativity result for the aggregated symmetric difference operator means that the order of pairwise comparisons does not affect the final dissimilarity measure—important when LIMEN-AI decides between alternative legal interpretations or threat hypotheses. Formally, if a_1, a_2, a_3 are the truth degrees of three competing hypotheses:

$$(a_1 \triangle_{\mathbb{L}} a_2) \triangle_{\mathbb{L}} a_3 = a_1 \triangle_{\mathbb{L}} (a_2 \triangle_{\mathbb{L}} a_3)$$

This property depends on the algebraic structure of the underlying t-norm and t-conorm. Its validity for Łukasiewicz operations means that complex reasoning patterns—hypothesis comparison, refinement—can be decomposed and evaluated in a compositionally consistent manner.

Application to LIMEN-AI. In LIMEN-AI’s inductive rule discovery mechanism

(Chapter 5), candidate rules are evaluated by comparing their satisfaction degrees on positive and negative training examples. The symmetric difference $\bar{I}_{\text{pos}}(\phi) \Delta_{\mathbb{L}} \bar{I}_{\text{neg}}(\phi)$ quantifies the discriminative power of rule ϕ : a high symmetric difference indicates that ϕ is satisfied by positive examples and falsified by negative examples, making it a strong candidate. The associativity property ensures that when multiple candidate rules are being compared simultaneously—as in beam search over rule templates—the comparison metric behaves consistently, regardless of the evaluation order.

Gokila and Jansirani provide complementary support through a formal algebraic framework for Łukasiewicz fuzzy BM-algebras (Gokila and Jansirani, 2024). They show that Łukasiewicz operations embed within BM-algebras—algebraic systems generalising Boolean algebras to fuzzy truth degrees. The embedding confirms that LIMEN-AI’s Łukasiewicz semantics rests on established algebraic foundations, not on computational convenience alone.

Verifying De Morgan Laws. The De Morgan laws (Property 5)—verified as `luk_demorgan_and` and `luk_demorgan_or` in Appendix B—reveal the algebraic duality between conjunction and disjunction under negation.

For the first law, $\neg_{\mathbb{L}}(a \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} b) = (\neg_{\mathbb{L}} a) \vee_{\mathbb{L}} (\neg_{\mathbb{L}} b)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LHS} &= \neg_{\mathbb{L}}(\max(0, a + b - 1)) = 1 - \max(0, a + b - 1) \\ &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a + b \leq 1 \\ 1 - (a + b - 1) = 2 - a - b & \text{if } a + b > 1 \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{RHS} = (1 - a) \vee_{\mathbb{L}} (1 - b) = \min(1, (1 - a) + (1 - b)) = \min(1, 2 - a - b)$$

When $a + b \leq 1$, we have $2 - a - b \geq 1$, so $\text{RHS} = 1 = \text{LHS}$. When $a + b > 1$, we have $2 - a - b < 1$, so $\text{RHS} = 2 - a - b = \text{LHS}$. Thus the law holds in all cases.

The second De Morgan law follows by symmetry (see Appendix B, §B.4.3). Both laws are essential for formula normalisation: pushing negations inward converts any formula to negation normal form, reducing the structural cases the implementation must handle and simplifying gradient computation.

Figure 33: Truth value propagation through a formula tree for $(A \wedge B) \rightarrow C$ under interpretation $I(A) = 0.7, I(B) = 0.6, I(C) = 0.8$. Leaves (blue) are ground atoms assigned truth degrees by I . Internal nodes (orange) compute Łukasiewicz operations bottom-up. The conjunction $A \wedge B$ yields $\max(0, 0.7 + 0.6 - 1) = 0.3$. The implication $(A \wedge B) \rightarrow C$ yields $\min(1, 1 - 0.3 + 0.8) = 0.85$. This compositional structure enables efficient gradient computation via automatic differentiation. Source: Author.

3.2.4 Formula Evaluation

Truth degrees of compound formulas are computed recursively.

Definition 3.11 (Formula Evaluation). *For a fuzzy interpretation I and a ground formula φ , the truth degree $I(\varphi) \in [0, 1]$ is defined inductively:*

$$I(A) = I(A) \quad \text{for ground atom } A \quad (20)$$

$$I(\neg\psi) = 1 - I(\psi) \quad (21)$$

$$I(\psi_1 \wedge \psi_2) = \max(0, I(\psi_1) + I(\psi_2) - 1) \quad (22)$$

$$I(\psi_1 \vee \psi_2) = \min(1, I(\psi_1) + I(\psi_2)) \quad (23)$$

$$I(\psi_1 \rightarrow \psi_2) = \min(1, 1 - I(\psi_1) + I(\psi_2)) \quad (24)$$

For formulas with free variables, evaluation requires grounding.

Compositional Semantics and Formula Trees. Evaluation proceeds bottom-up through the formula’s syntax tree: leaves carry atom truth degrees, each internal node applies a Łukasiewicz operation, and the root yields the formula’s satisfaction degree.

Figure 33 illustrates this for $(A \wedge B) \rightarrow C$ under a specific interpretation.

Because evaluation is compositional, gradients follow by backpropagation: each node contributes a local gradient that combines with those from parent nodes (Figure 33). The evaluation semantics extend to quantified formulas as follows.

Definition 3.12 (Quantifier Evaluation — Hybrid Łukasiewicz-Gödel Semantics).

For a formula $\varphi(x)$ with a free variable x and a finite domain \mathcal{C} :

$$I(\forall x. \varphi(x)) = \min_{c \in \mathcal{C}} I(\varphi[x/c]) \quad (25)$$

$$I(\exists x. \varphi(x)) = \max_{c \in \mathcal{C}} I(\varphi[x/c]) \quad (26)$$

Universal quantification is interpreted as the minimum truth degree across all groundings; existential quantification is interpreted as the maximum. Note that these quantifier operations use the Gödel min/max rather than the Łukasiewicz t-norm and t-conorm employed for binary connectives (Definition 3.10). LIMEN-AI therefore operates under hybrid Łukasiewicz-Gödel semantics: Łukasiewicz operations govern propositional connectives within formulas, while Gödel operations govern quantification over the domain.

Justification of the Hybrid Quantifier Semantics. Using min for \forall and max for \exists —that is, adopting the Gödel t-norm and t-conorm for quantifiers while retaining the Łukasiewicz t-norm for binary connectives—is a deliberate design choice rather than an oversight. Quantifiers should extend conjunction and disjunction to collections of arbitrary size, but the Łukasiewicz t-norm does not scale to this role gracefully.

In classical logic, $\forall x. \varphi(x)$ holds iff every grounding $\varphi[x/c]$ holds, equivalent to $\bigwedge_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \varphi[x/c]$. Dually, $\exists x. \varphi(x)$ holds iff at least one grounding holds, equivalent to $\bigvee_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \varphi[x/c]$.

Under Łukasiewicz logic the n -ary conjunction is:

$$a_1 \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} a_2 \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} \cdots \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} a_n = \max(0, a_1 + a_2 + \cdots + a_n - (n - 1))$$

This formula depends on n , so it cannot represent quantifiers over variable-sized domains: adding a single constant to \mathcal{C} would change the semantics of every existing universal sentence. A domain-independent semantics uses the Gödel t-norm $\min(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ for quantifiers, keeping the Łukasiewicz t-norm for binary conjunctions within formulas. The resulting hybrid Łukasiewicz-Gödel semantics is standard in fuzzy first-order logic (Hájek, 1998) and stays stable under domain expansion. Throughout the remainder of this thesis, references to “Łukasiewicz semantics” should

be understood as referring to this hybrid scheme unless explicitly stated otherwise.

The rationale: \min gives a "bottleneck" semantics—the universal is only as true as its least satisfied grounding. If even one grounding has a low truth degree, the universal reflects that weakness. Dually, \max gives a "best-case" semantics: $\exists x. \varphi(x)$ is as true as its most satisfied grounding, regardless of how other groundings fare.

Computationally, \min and \max also simplify gradient computation. The gradient of $\min(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ with respect to a_i is 1 if a_i is the (possibly tied) minimum, and 0 otherwise. This sparse structure focuses the learning signal on the critical groundings that currently determine the quantified formula's truth degree. The iterated Łukasiewicz t-norm would spread the gradient across all groundings, diluting the signal.

Over finite domains the truth degree is well-defined and computable: the universal quantifier behaves as an iterated conjunction, the existential as an iterated disjunction.

Example 3.2 (Formula Evaluation). Consider a knowledge base with the rule $\text{failedLogin}(u, h) \rightarrow \text{suspicious}(u)$ and an interpretation where $I(\text{failedLogin}(\text{alice}, \text{srv1})) = 0.9$ and $I(\text{suspicious}(\text{alice})) = 0.75$. The truth degree of the grounded implication is:

$$I(\text{failedLogin}(\text{alice}, \text{srv1}) \rightarrow \text{suspicious}(\text{alice})) = \min(1, 1 - 0.9 + 0.75) = \min(1, 0.85) = 0.85$$

The implication is satisfied to a degree of 0.85, indicating that the rule is mostly satisfied for this grounding.

3.3 Energy Functions and Knowledge Bases

The *energy function* aggregates all satisfaction degrees—weighted by importance—into a single number that measures how well an interpretation fits the knowledge base. It doubles as the sufficient statistic of an exponential-family distribution over interpretations (Section 3.5).

3.3.1 Motivation: From Constraints to Energy

In classical SAT, an interpretation either satisfies a formula or it does not. Once truth admits degrees, different formulas may be satisfied to different extents, and some constraints matter more than others. Aggregation requires both a combination

rule and a weighting scheme.

Each formula φ_i carries a weight $w_i \in \mathbb{R}$. A large positive weight marks a constraint as highly desirable; a large negative weight favours its violation; zero makes it irrelevant.

The total energy is a weighted sum of satisfaction degrees. Four useful properties follow immediately. For fixed I the energy is linear in \mathbf{w} , so the parameterised family forms a vector space. High energy means the interpretation aligns with the knowledge base; low energy means it does not. The same energy serves as the sufficient statistic of an exponential-family distribution (Section 3.5), linking logic to probabilistic inference. And almost-everywhere differentiability (Section 3.4) makes the energy a legitimate objective for gradient-based optimisation.

3.3.2 Ground Satisfaction

Before aggregating, I define ground satisfaction.

Definition 3.13 (Ground Satisfaction Degree). *For a formula φ with free variables $\{x_1, \dots, x_k\}$ and an interpretation I , the ground satisfaction degree (or average satisfaction degree) is:*

$$\bar{I}(\varphi) = \frac{1}{|\text{Gr}(\varphi)|} \sum_{\gamma \in \text{Gr}(\varphi)} I(\varphi^\gamma)$$

where $\text{Gr}(\varphi)$ is the set of groundings of φ and φ^γ denotes the result of applying grounding substitution γ to φ .

For a closed formula (no free variables), $\bar{I}(\varphi) = I(\varphi)$.

Averaging over groundings prevents formulas with more instances from dominating the energy merely because of their count.

Example 3.3 (Ground Satisfaction). Consider the formula $\varphi(u) = \text{suspicious}(u)$ over the domain $\mathcal{C} = \{\text{alice}, \text{bob}\}$. The groundings are $\text{suspicious}(\text{alice})$ and $\text{suspicious}(\text{bob})$. If $I(\text{suspicious}(\text{alice})) = 0.8$ and $I(\text{suspicious}(\text{bob})) = 0.2$, then:

$$\bar{I}(\varphi) = \frac{1}{2}(0.8 + 0.2) = 0.5$$

3.3.3 Energy Function

The energy function combines weighted satisfaction degrees across all formulas.

Definition 3.14 (Energy Function). For a knowledge base $\mathcal{K} = (\Sigma, \mathcal{F}, \mathbf{w})$ with formulas $\mathcal{F} = \{\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_m\}$ and weights $\mathbf{w} = (w_1, \dots, w_m)$, the energy function is:

$$E(I; \mathbf{w}) = \sum_{i=1}^m w_i \cdot \bar{I}(\varphi_i)$$

The energy function maps an interpretation I and a weight vector \mathbf{w} to a real number.

In plain terms, high energy means the interpretation fits the knowledge base well; low energy means it does not. Positive weights reward satisfaction; negative weights penalise it; and magnitudes encode relative importance.

Theorem 3.1 (Energy Function Properties). The energy function $E(I; \mathbf{w})$ satisfies:

1. **Linearity in weights:** For fixed I , $E(I; \mathbf{w})$ is a linear function of \mathbf{w} .
2. **Boundedness:** For weights \mathbf{w} with $\|\mathbf{w}\|_1 = W$, we have $|E(I; \mathbf{w})| \leq W$.
3. **Continuity in I :** For fixed \mathbf{w} , $E(I; \mathbf{w})$ is a continuous function of I .

Proof. (1) The energy is a sum of terms $w_i \cdot \bar{I}(\varphi_i)$, each linear in w_i .

(2) Since $0 \leq \bar{I}(\varphi_i) \leq 1$ for all i :

$$|E(I; \mathbf{w})| = \left| \sum_i w_i \bar{I}(\varphi_i) \right| \leq \sum_i |w_i| \cdot \bar{I}(\varphi_i) \leq \sum_i |w_i| = W$$

(3) Each $\bar{I}(\varphi_i)$ is continuous in I because it is a finite sum of compositions of continuous functions (the Łukasiewicz operations are continuous). The sum of continuous functions is continuous. \square

3.4 Differentiability Properties

The energy function is piecewise linear and therefore differentiable almost everywhere—all that gradient-based optimisers need. The proofs follow.

3.4.1 Piecewise Linear Functions

Piecewise linear functions characterise the geometry of formula evaluations and underpin the differentiability results below.

Definition 3.15 (Piecewise Linear Function). *A function $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is piecewise linear if there exists a finite partition of \mathbb{R}^n into polyhedral regions $\{R_1, \dots, R_k\}$ such that f is affine (linear plus constant) on each region R_j .*

Lemma 3.1 (Closure Properties of Piecewise Linear Functions). *The class of piecewise linear functions is closed under:*

1. *Affine transformations: If f is piecewise linear, so is $af + b$ for $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$.*
2. *Sums: If f and g are piecewise linear, so is $f + g$.*
3. *Maximum and minimum: If f and g are piecewise linear, so are $\max(f, g)$ and $\min(f, g)$.*
4. *Composition with affine functions: If $f : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is piecewise linear and $g : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ is affine, then $f \circ g$ is piecewise linear.*

Proof. Properties (1), (2), and (4) follow from the fact that affine combinations of affine functions are affine. Property (3) follows because the pointwise maximum (or minimum) of finitely many affine functions on a polyhedral region is piecewise linear, with the boundaries determined by where the functions are equal. \square

3.4.2 Piecewise Linearity of Formula Evaluation

Piecewise linearity of Łukasiewicz operations—and of the entire formula evaluation pipeline—now follows directly.

Theorem 3.2 (Piecewise Linearity of Łukasiewicz Operations). *The Łukasiewicz operations are piecewise linear functions of their arguments:*

1. *Negation $\neg_{\mathcal{L}} a = 1 - a$ is affine (and hence piecewise linear).*
2. *Conjunction $a \wedge_{\mathcal{L}} b = \max(0, a + b - 1)$ is piecewise linear with two regions.*
3. *Disjunction $a \vee_{\mathcal{L}} b = \min(1, a + b)$ is piecewise linear with two regions.*
4. *Implication $a \rightarrow_{\mathcal{L}} b = \min(1, 1 - a + b)$ is piecewise linear with two regions.*

Proof. (1) The function $1 - a$ is affine; hence, it is piecewise linear with one region.

(2) The function $\max(0, a + b - 1)$ equals 0 when $a + b \leq 1$ and equals $a + b - 1$ when $a + b > 1$. Both pieces are affine, and the boundary is the hyperplane $a + b = 1$.

(3) and (4) are similar, with boundaries at $a + b = 1$ and $1 - a + b = 1$ (i.e., $a = b$) respectively. \square

Theorem 3.3 (Piecewise Linearity of Formula Evaluation). *For any formula φ over the signature Σ , the function $I \mapsto I(\varphi)$ from interpretations to truth degrees is piecewise linear in the truth degrees of the ground atoms.*

Proof. The proof proceeds by structural induction on formulas.

Base case: For a ground atom A , $I(A)$ is a coordinate projection, which is affine (and hence piecewise linear).

Inductive case (negation): If $I(\psi)$ is piecewise linear in the atomic truth degrees, then $I(\neg\psi) = 1 - I(\psi)$ is an affine transformation of a piecewise linear function, hence piecewise linear by Lemma 3.1(1).

Inductive case (conjunction): If $I(\psi_1)$ and $I(\psi_2)$ are piecewise linear, then:

$$I(\psi_1 \wedge \psi_2) = \max(0, I(\psi_1) + I(\psi_2) - 1)$$

The sum $I(\psi_1) + I(\psi_2) - 1$ is piecewise linear by Lemma 3.1(1,2). Taking the maximum with the constant function 0 (which is piecewise linear) preserves piecewise linearity by Lemma 3.1(3).

Inductive case (disjunction and implication): Similar arguments using closure under min and affine transformation.

Inductive case (universal quantification): For $\forall x. \psi(x)$ over finite domain \mathcal{C} :

$$I(\forall x. \psi(x)) = \min_{c \in \mathcal{C}} I(\psi[x/c])$$

By the inductive hypothesis, each $I(\psi[x/c])$ is piecewise linear. The minimum of finitely many piecewise linear functions is piecewise linear by repeated application of Lemma 3.1(3).

Inductive case (existential quantification): Similar, using max. □

Counting Polyhedral Regions. Theorem 3.3 does not bound the number of polyhedral regions. That count matters for implementation: each boundary requires a conditional check in the gradient computation, and excessive fragmentation slows automatic differentiation.

With k binary connectives the worst-case region count is $O(2^k)$, but two factors keep the effective count low in practice.

On the structural side, formula topology constrains boundary interactions. A

chain of implications $A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow A_n$ has only $O(n)$ regions because boundaries align along the propagation direction—far below $O(2^n)$.

On the algorithmic side, the optimisation trajectory typically stays inside a single region for many steps, crossing a boundary only when the gradient pushes a constraint from active to inactive (or vice versa).

Empirically, in the COLIEE experiments (Chapter 6), formulas with 5-10 connectives exhibit effective region counts of $O(10)$ – $O(100)$, far below the theoretical worst case, and gradient computation remains efficient on GPU hardware.

3.4.3 Geometry of the Interpretation Space

The interpretation space $\mathcal{I}_\Sigma = [0, 1]^{|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma|}$ has geometric structure that shapes optimisation dynamics, convergence, and the logic–probability interface.

Hypercube Structure. Each dimension of the unit hypercube corresponds to a ground atom; each point is a complete fuzzy truth-degree assignment. Vertices ($\{0, 1\}^{|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma|}$) are classical Boolean interpretations. Interior and boundary points carry intermediate truth degrees.

Several properties follow from this geometry:

Compactness guarantees that every continuous function—including the energy—attains its maximum, so $I^* = \arg \max_I E(I; \mathbf{w})$ always exists. The domain is convex, but the energy is generally *not* concave in I (the max and min operations break concavity), so MAP inference may have multiple local maxima.

Dimensionality is the other concern. For p predicates of arity a over n constants, the atom count scales as $O(p \cdot n^a)$. In COLIEE ($n \approx 2000$, binary predicates) the space has roughly 4×10^6 dimensions—far beyond grid search. Gradient-based optimisation follows local geometry instead (Boyd and Vandenberghe, 2004).

Energy Landscape and Critical Points. $E(I; \mathbf{w})$ defines a scalar field over the interpretation space. The gradient $\nabla_I E$ points in the direction of steepest energy ascent; MAP inference seeks the global maximum.

Piecewise linearity makes the landscape flat polyhedral facets separated by sharp boundaries. Within each facet the gradient is constant, so energy varies linearly in any direction. The global maximum typically sits at a vertex where multiple constraints are simultaneously active.

Critical points include global maxima (targets of MAP inference), local maxima (reachable under poor initialisation), and boundary points (the measure-zero gradient-discontinuity set, negligible in practice). Saddle points are rarer than in smooth landscapes because piecewise linearity produces sharp ridges, not smooth saddles.

LIMEN-AI mitigates local maxima through warm-start initialisation (e.g., seeding from a neural retrieval model in the COLIEE re-ranker) and through knowledge base design that keeps formulas cooperative rather than competing.

Probabilistic Mass Concentration. The Gibbs distribution $P(I; \mathbf{w}) \propto \exp(E(I; \mathbf{w}))$ converts the energy landscape into a probability distribution. The exponential concentrates mass around high-energy regions, with concentration strength set by the weight magnitudes.

Small weights (≈ 0) yield a nearly uniform distribution; large weights concentrate mass on the energy-maximising interpretation(s). In the limit of infinite weights the distribution collapses to a point mass at the MAP interpretation—deterministic logical inference.

This concentration is analogous to the temperature in simulated annealing (Kirkpatrick et al., 1983). Writing $E(I; \mathbf{w}) = \beta \cdot E(I; \mathbf{w}')$ with $\beta = \|\mathbf{w}\|$ and $\mathbf{w}' = \mathbf{w}/\|\mathbf{w}\|$, high β (low temperature) concentrates; low β (high temperature) diffuses.

The power tempering sampler (Chapter 4) exploits this geometric intuition by maintaining a ladder of distributions at different temperatures, allowing the sampler to explore the space more efficiently by occasionally "heating up" to escape local maxima.

Corollary 3.1 (Differentiability Almost Everywhere). *For any formula φ , the function $I \mapsto I(\varphi)$ is:*

1. *Continuous on $[0, 1]^{|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma|}$.*
2. *Differentiable at all points except for a set of measure zero (the boundaries between linear regions).*

Proof. Piecewise linear functions are continuous. They are differentiable within each polyhedral region and may fail to be differentiable only at the boundaries, which form a finite union of lower-dimensional polyhedra—a set of Lebesgue measure zero. \square

Implications for Automatic Differentiation. The “almost everywhere” qualifier matters for integration with deep learning frameworks. Non-differentiable points sit on boundaries between linear regions—for instance, where $a+b = 1$ in $\max(0, a+b-1)$.

These boundaries have Lebesgue measure zero. During stochastic gradient descent the probability of landing exactly on one is zero; random initialisation and noisy gradient estimates keep the trajectory away with probability one. Floating-point arithmetic reinforces this: the bit pattern for exact equality (e.g., $a + b = 1.0$) is exponentially unlikely under perturbation.

If the optimiser does reach a boundary, PyTorch returns a valid sub-gradient (an element of the Clarke generalised gradient), and sub-gradient descent converges under the same conditions as smooth gradient descent.

The piecewise linear landscape is, in fact, advantageous: within each region the gradient is constant and points directly toward the region’s optimum, so every step makes maximally efficient progress. Crossing a boundary switches the gradient to reflect the new geometry—an accurate response to the objective’s shape, not a failure.

3.4.4 Differentiability of the Energy Function

The following result formally establishes that the aggregated satisfaction of weighted logical rules is differentiable almost everywhere.

Corollary 3.2 (Energy Function Differentiability). *The energy function $E(I; \mathbf{w})$ is:*

1. *Piecewise linear and continuous in both I and \mathbf{w} .*
2. *Differentiable almost everywhere in both arguments.*

Proof. The energy function is a weighted sum of ground satisfaction degrees:

$$E(I; \mathbf{w}) = \sum_i w_i \cdot \bar{I}(\varphi_i) = \sum_i w_i \cdot \frac{1}{|\text{Gr}(\varphi_i)|} \sum_\gamma I(\varphi_i^\gamma)$$

Each $I(\varphi_i^\gamma)$ is piecewise linear in I by Theorem 3.3. The average $\bar{I}(\varphi_i)$ is a finite sum of piecewise linear functions; hence, it is piecewise linear. The weighted sum is piecewise linear in both I (for fixed \mathbf{w}) and \mathbf{w} (for fixed I).

Continuity and almost-everywhere differentiability follow as in Corollary 3.1. \square

The energy can therefore be optimised by standard gradient descent, with gradients computed efficiently via PyTorch’s automatic differentiation.

3.4.5 Gradient Computation

The analytical gradients below drive weight learning and truth-degree optimisation.

Theorem 3.4 (Gradients of the Energy Function). *At points where the energy function is differentiable:*

1. *The gradient with respect to the weights is:*

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial w_i}(I; \mathbf{w}) = \bar{I}(\varphi_i)$$

2. *The gradient with respect to atomic truth degrees can be computed via backpropagation through the formula evaluation.*

Proof. (1) Since $E(I; \mathbf{w}) = \sum_i w_i \bar{I}(\varphi_i)$ and $\bar{I}(\varphi_i)$ depends only on I (not on \mathbf{w}), we have $\frac{\partial E}{\partial w_i} = \bar{I}(\varphi_i)$.

(2) The gradient with respect to $I(A)$ for a ground atom A requires applying the chain rule through the formula evaluation. Within each linear region of the piecewise linear function, the gradient is constant and equals the coefficient of $I(A)$ in the affine expression. \square

The weight gradient $\frac{\partial E}{\partial w_i} = \bar{I}(\varphi_i)$ is intuitive: raising a formula’s weight raises energy in proportion to its current satisfaction. A fully satisfied formula ($\bar{I} = 1$) benefits maximally; a completely unsatisfied one ($\bar{I} = 0$) gains nothing.

Backpropagation Through Formula Trees. The interpretation gradient $\nabla_I E$ is more revealing: it shows which atoms the optimiser would adjust—and in which direction—to improve energy.

Consider a formula $\varphi = (A \wedge B) \rightarrow C$ with weight $w = 2.0$ and interpretation $I(A) = 0.7, I(B) = 0.6, I(C) = 0.5$. The formula tree (as in Figure 33) computes:

$$I(A \wedge B) = \max(0, 0.7 + 0.6 - 1) = 0.3$$

$$I(\varphi) = \min(1, 1 - 0.3 + 0.5) = \min(1, 1.2) = 1.0$$

The implication is fully satisfied, so the energy contribution is $w \cdot I(\varphi) = 2.0$.

To compute $\frac{\partial E}{\partial I(A)}$, we apply the chain rule:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial I(A)} = w \cdot \frac{\partial I(\varphi)}{\partial I(A)} = w \cdot \frac{\partial I(\varphi)}{\partial I(A \wedge B)} \cdot \frac{\partial I(A \wedge B)}{\partial I(A)}$$

For the outer term, since $1 - I(A \wedge B) + I(C) = 1.2 > 1$, we are in the saturated region of the min operation; therefore, $\frac{\partial I(\varphi)}{\partial I(A \wedge B)} = 0$. Consequently, $\frac{\partial E}{\partial I(A)} = 0$.

This zero gradient is not a defect—it correctly reflects that the formula is already fully satisfied, so marginal changes to $I(A)$ do not improve energy. The interpretation is in a "safe" region for this formula.

Now suppose $I(C) = 0.2$ instead; thus,

$$I(\varphi) = \min(1, 1 - 0.3 + 0.2) = 0.9$$

$$E_{\text{contribution}} = 2.0 \cdot 0.9 = 1.8$$

Now the implication is not saturated, so:

$$\frac{\partial I(\varphi)}{\partial I(A \wedge B)} = \frac{\partial}{\partial I(A \wedge B)}(1 - I(A \wedge B) + 0.2) = -1$$

Since $I(A) + I(B) = 1.3 > 1$, the conjunction is in its active region:

$$\frac{\partial I(A \wedge B)}{\partial I(A)} = 1$$

Thus:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial I(A)} = 2.0 \cdot (-1) \cdot 1 = -2.0$$

The negative gradient indicates that *increasing* $I(A)$ would *decrease* energy because it makes the antecedent of the implication stronger, thereby making the implication harder to satisfy. To increase energy, the optimiser should either decrease $I(A)$ or increase $I(C)$.

This per-atom blame signal is what drives the neurosymbolic induction loop (Chapter 5): by iterating over gradient updates, the system tightens consistency between the knowledge base and observed data.

3.5 Probabilistic Interpretation

Exponentiating the energy yields a probability distribution—the Gibbs (Boltzmann) distribution over fuzzy interpretations. The derivation below also explains the partition function and grounds the inference algorithms of Chapter 4.

3.5.1 From Energy to Probability: The Gibbs Distribution

The link is forced, not chosen. The least informative distribution whose expected formula satisfactions match observed values is, by the maximum-entropy principle, an exponential family:

$$P(I; \mathbf{w}) = \frac{1}{Z(\mathbf{w})} \exp\left(\sum_i w_i \bar{I}(\varphi_i)\right) = \frac{1}{Z(\mathbf{w})} \exp(E(I; \mathbf{w}))$$

This is the Gibbs distribution (from statistical mechanics). The weights act as Lagrange multipliers dual to the satisfaction constraints, and $Z(\mathbf{w})$ normalises the distribution.

Energy Landscape and Probability. The exponential map converts energy differences into probability ratios, with two notable effects.

The exponential amplifies energy differences sharply. Two interpretations with $E = 5$ vs. $E = 3$ have a probability ratio of $e^2 \approx 7.4$ —the higher-energy one is over seven times as probable despite only 40% more energy. Mass concentrates on interpretations that satisfy the knowledge base well.

The exponential also converts the additive decomposition into a product in probability space:

$$P(I; \mathbf{w}) \propto \prod_i \exp(w_i \bar{I}(\varphi_i)).$$

Each formula contributes $\exp(w_i)$ when fully satisfied and 1 when unsatisfied—the product structure of exponential families and Markov random fields.

Figure 34 illustrates this for a toy knowledge base with two ground atoms and one implication rule. High-energy regions correspond to interpretations satisfying the rule; the Gibbs distribution makes them exponentially more probable than inconsistent alternatives.

The implication $A \rightarrow B$ creates a gradient toward regions where the consequent holds whenever the antecedent does.

3.5.2 Distribution Over Interpretations

The Boltzmann (Gibbs) distribution over fuzzy interpretations is defined as follows.

Definition 3.16 (Gibbs Distribution). *The energy function induces a probability*

Figure 34: Energy landscape for a knowledge base with one formula: $(A \rightarrow B, w = 2.0)$. The surface shows $E(I; w) = w \cdot \min(1, 1 - I(A) + I(B))$ over the interpretation space $[0, 1]^2$. High-energy regions (red, upper-right) correspond to interpretations where $I(B)$ is high relative to $I(A)$, satisfying the implication. The Gibbs distribution $P(I; w) \propto \exp(E(I; w))$ concentrates probability mass on these high-energy regions, making logically consistent interpretations exponentially more probable. Source: Author.

distribution over interpretations:

$$P(I; \mathbf{w}) = \frac{1}{Z(\mathbf{w})} \exp(E(I; \mathbf{w}))$$

where the partition function is:

$$Z(\mathbf{w}) = \int_{\mathcal{I}_\Sigma} \exp(E(I; \mathbf{w})) dI$$

and the integral is over all fuzzy interpretations (the hypercube $[0, 1]^{|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma|}$).

The Partition Function: Normalisation and Intractability. $Z(\mathbf{w})$ serves two roles: it normalises the density ($\int P dI = 1$) and is the central quantity for inference tasks such as marginals and expected values.

For continuous interpretation spaces, $Z(\mathbf{w})$ is a high-dimensional integral over $[0, 1]^{|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma|}$. In COLIEE ($|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma| \approx 10^4$) the integral is over a 10^4 -dimensional space—

clearly intractable exactly.

Three standard remedies apply. Monte Carlo methods draw samples $I^{(1)}, \dots, I^{(N)} \sim P$ and average; Chapter 4 develops Gibbs, Metropolis–Hastings, and power-tempering samplers for the NMLN landscape. Variational inference replaces P with a tractable surrogate $Q(I; \theta)$ and minimises $\text{KL}(Q\|P)$. MAP approximation side-steps $Z(\mathbf{w})$ entirely by collapsing to a point mass at $I^* = \arg \max_I E(I; \mathbf{w})$, trading uncertainty quantification for speed.

The LIMEN-AI re-ranker (Chapter 6) uses the MAP approximation for inference efficiency, sacrificing probabilistic uncertainty for computational tractability while retaining full explainability through the formula-based energy decomposition.

Higher energy means higher probability: interpretations that better satisfy the weighted constraints are exponentially favoured.

Remark 3.2 (Comparison with Classical MLNs). In classical MLNs with Boolean interpretations, the partition function is a sum over finitely many (but exponentially many) possible worlds. In LIMEN-AI with fuzzy interpretations, the partition function is an integral over a continuous space. This integral is generally intractable but can be approximated using sampling methods.

3.5.3 Inference Quantities

Several inference quantities arise naturally.

Definition 3.17 (Expected Truth Degree). *For a query formula Q , the expected truth degree under the distribution is:*

$$\mathbb{E}_P[I(Q)] = \int_{\mathcal{I}_\Sigma} I(Q) \cdot P(I; \mathbf{w}) dI$$

This represents the average truth degree of Q across interpretations, weighted by their probability.

Definition 3.18 (Most Probable Interpretation). *The most probable interpretation (or MAP interpretation) is:*

$$I^* = \arg \max_{I \in \mathcal{I}_\Sigma} P(I; \mathbf{w}) = \arg \max_{I \in \mathcal{I}_\Sigma} E(I; \mathbf{w})$$

Since the exponential function is monotonic, maximising probability is equivalent to maximising energy.

The expected truth degree integrates over uncertainty; the MAP interpretation gives a single “best” state maximising consistency with the knowledge base.

Query Answering: Expected vs. MAP Semantics. Given a query formula Q (e.g., "Is document d relevant to case c ?"), there are two natural ways to produce an answer.

Under *expected semantics*, one computes $\mathbb{E}_P[I(Q)]$ —the average truth degree of Q weighted across all interpretations. Under *MAP semantics*, one first finds $I^* = \arg \max_I E(I; \mathbf{w})$ and then evaluates $I^*(Q)$, producing a point estimate from the single most probable interpretation.

The two can disagree. Suppose two equiprobable modes have $I_1(Q) = 1$ and $I_2(Q) = 0$. Expected semantics gives $\mathbb{E}_P[I(Q)] = 0.5$. MAP semantics returns whichever mode has marginally higher energy—1 or 0—ignoring the other entirely.

LIMEN-AI typically uses MAP semantics for two reasons:

1. **Computational efficiency:** Finding I^* is an optimisation problem that can be solved using gradient ascent on $E(I; \mathbf{w})$, exploiting the differentiability established in Section 3.4. Computing the expected truth degree, in contrast, requires integration over the high-dimensional interpretation space, which is intractable without sampling.
2. **Explainability:** The MAP interpretation I^* is a complete assignment of truth degrees to all ground atoms, and it satisfies the knowledge base constraints "as well as possible" (in the sense of maximising energy). This provides a concrete, interpretable state that can be inspected and validated by domain experts. The expected truth degree, being an integral, does not correspond to any single coherent interpretation and is harder to explain in terms of specific atom truth degrees.

In the COLIEE re-ranker (Chapter 6), MAP inference enables 100% explainability: for every retrieved document the system can cite the specific formulas and truth degrees that drove its high energy. Expected semantics would average over many interpretations, obscuring the reasoning path.

3.6 Convergence of Gradient-Based Learning

Weight learning maximises the log-likelihood under the Gibbs distribution. Gradient ascent converges to the global optimum under standard regularity conditions, as shown below.

3.6.1 Weight Learning Objective

Given a dataset \mathcal{D} of observed truth degrees for some ground atoms, the log-likelihood is:

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{w}) = \log P(\mathcal{D}; \mathbf{w}) = E(I_{\mathcal{D}}; \mathbf{w}) - \log Z(\mathbf{w})$$

where $I_{\mathcal{D}}$ denotes the interpretation consistent with the observed data.

The gradient of the log-likelihood with respect to weight w_i is:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial w_i} = \bar{I}_{\mathcal{D}}(\varphi_i) - \mathbb{E}_P[\bar{I}(\varphi_i)]$$

This is the difference between the observed satisfaction degree and the expected satisfaction degree under the model.

3.6.2 Convergence Results

Convergence holds under standard stochastic-optimisation conditions, formalised below.

Theorem 3.5 (Convergence of Gradient Ascent). *Under the following conditions:*

1. *The learning rate sequence $\{\eta_t\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$ satisfies the Robbins-Monro conditions: $\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \eta_t = \infty$ and $\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \eta_t^2 < \infty$.*
2. *The gradients are computed exactly or estimated with bounded variance.*
3. *The weight space is bounded (e.g., $\|\mathbf{w}\|_2 \leq W$ for some W).*

Gradient ascent on the log-likelihood converges to a stationary point.

Proof. The log-likelihood of the NMLN model belongs to the exponential family and can be written as

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{w}) = \mathbf{w}^{\top} \mathbb{E}_{\text{data}}[\bar{I}(\boldsymbol{\varphi})] - \log Z(\mathbf{w}),$$

where $\log Z(\mathbf{w}) = \log \int \exp(\mathbf{w}^\top \bar{I}(\boldsymbol{\varphi})) dI$ is the log-partition function. The log-partition function of any exponential family is convex, since its Hessian equals the covariance matrix of the sufficient statistics, which is positive semi-definite (Boyd and Vandenberghe, 2004). Because \mathcal{L} is a linear function of \mathbf{w} minus a convex function, it is concave; every stationary point is therefore a global maximum.

The gradient is $\nabla_{\mathbf{w}} \mathcal{L} = \mathbb{E}_{\text{data}}[\bar{I}(\boldsymbol{\varphi})] - \mathbb{E}_{P(\cdot; \mathbf{w})}[\bar{I}(\boldsymbol{\varphi})]$, which is bounded whenever the weight space is bounded (condition 3). Under the Robbins–Monro conditions on the step size ($\sum_t \eta_t = \infty$, $\sum_t \eta_t^2 < \infty$), convergence of stochastic gradient ascent on a concave objective with bounded gradients to the global optimum is guaranteed by classical stochastic approximation theory (Robbins and Monro, 1951). When gradients are estimated with bounded variance (condition 2), the same conclusion holds by the extension due to Blum (Blum, 1954). \square

Learning Rate Scheduling and Practical Considerations. The learning rate η_t controls the step size:

$$\mathbf{w}_{t+1} = \mathbf{w}_t + \eta_t \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{w}} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{w}_t)$$

The Robbins–Monro conditions make η_t decrease slowly enough for convergence but fast enough to escape poor initial configurations. A common schedule is $\eta_t = \eta_0 / (1 + t/T)$.

In practice, LIMEN-AI uses the Adam optimiser (Chapter 6), which adapts per-parameter learning rates from first- and second-moment estimates of the gradients. Adam typically converges faster than vanilla gradient ascent while retaining theoretical guarantees under mild extra assumptions.

Computing $\mathbb{E}_P[\bar{I}(\boldsymbol{\varphi}_i)]$ exactly requires the intractable partition function; the sampling-based inference algorithms of Chapter 4 approximate it instead.

3.7 Complexity Analysis

Tight bounds on formula evaluation, ground satisfaction, and energy computation drive the engineering decisions in Chapter 6.

3.7.1 Formula Evaluation Complexity

Evaluating a single ground formula requires one bottom-up pass through its syntax tree.

Theorem 3.6 (Formula Evaluation Complexity). *For a ground formula φ with $|\varphi|$ nodes (connectives and atoms) and an interpretation I :*

1. *The time complexity of computing $I(\varphi)$ is $O(|\varphi|)$.*
2. *The space complexity is $O(|\varphi|)$ (for the recursive evaluation stack or the formula tree).*

Proof. Formula evaluation traverses the formula tree once, performing constant-time operations (Łukasiewicz operations) at each node. The time is proportional to the number of nodes. Space is proportional to the depth of recursion or the tree size. \square

Theorem 3.7 (Ground Satisfaction Complexity). *For a formula φ with k free variables over a domain of size n :*

1. *The number of groundings is $|\text{Gr}(\varphi)| = n^k$.*
2. *The time complexity of computing $\bar{I}(\varphi)$ is $O(n^k \cdot |\varphi|)$.*

Proof. Computing $\bar{I}(\varphi)$ requires evaluating $I(\varphi^\gamma)$ for each of the n^k groundings, with each evaluation taking $O(|\varphi|)$ time. \square

3.7.2 Energy Computation Complexity

Aggregating across all formulas gives the full energy computation cost.

Corollary 3.3 (Energy Computation Complexity). *For a knowledge base with m formulas, maximum formula size $|\varphi|_{\max}$, maximum number of free variables k_{\max} , and domain size n :*

$$\text{Time complexity of } E(I; \mathbf{w}) = O(m \cdot n^{k_{\max}} \cdot |\varphi|_{\max})$$

The exponential dependence on k_{\max} makes formulas with many free variables expensive. Knowledge bases are therefore designed with a bounded variable count.

3.7.3 Space Complexity

Memory can also dominate: storing truth degrees for every ground atom is expensive.

Theorem 3.8 (Interpretation Space Complexity). *Storing a fuzzy interpretation over a signature with predicates of maximum arity a_{\max} and n constants requires $O(|\mathcal{P}| \cdot n^{a_{\max}})$ space.*

For signatures with high-arity predicates or large domains, the interpretation can become the dominant memory cost. Sparse representations can reduce this cost when most atoms have a truth degree of 0 or 1.

3.7.4 Implications for Implementation

These bounds dictate four engineering decisions. The $O(n^{k_{\max}})$ grounding cost restricts formulas to at most 2–3 free variables; the induction module (Chapter 5) prunes wider candidates before weight optimisation begins. For large domains (hundreds of legal cases in COLIEE), dense tensors in $\mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{A}_{\Sigma}|}$ are prohibitive, so the implementation stores only non-zero truth degrees in sparse dictionaries. Satisfaction degrees are computed lazily, with intermediate results cached in the PyTorch graph to avoid redundancy when formulas share substructure. Grounding-level evaluation is embarrassingly parallel, so the system batches groundings into tensors for vectorised GPU execution.

These choices let LIMEN-AI scale to hundreds of formulas and thousands of constants, as the COLIEE benchmark demonstrates (11.67% precision on 2,159 candidate documents).

3.8 Pedagogical Examples

The calculations below can be verified by hand and show how Łukasiewicz semantics, energy aggregation, and gradient computation play out on concrete formulas.

3.8.1 Illustrative Example: Simple Implication

Consider a knowledge base with a single implication rule and two atomic propositions.

Signature: $\mathcal{P} = \{A/0, B/0\}$, $\mathcal{C} = \emptyset$ (no constants, so both A and B are already ground atoms).

Knowledge base: $\mathcal{K} = \{(A \rightarrow B, w)\}$ with weight $w = 2.0$.

Interpretation: $I(A) = 0.7, I(B) = 0.6$.

Formula evaluation:

$$I(A \rightarrow B) = \min(1, 1 - 0.7 + 0.6) = \min(1, 0.9) = 0.9$$

Energy:

$$E(I; w) = w \cdot I(A \rightarrow B) = 2.0 \cdot 0.9 = 1.8$$

Gradient with respect to w :

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial w} = I(A \rightarrow B) = 0.9$$

Gradient with respect to $I(A)$: The implication $I(A \rightarrow B) = \min(1, 1 - I(A) + I(B))$ is in the region where $1 - I(A) + I(B) < 1$ (since $0.9 < 1$), so $I(A \rightarrow B) = 1 - I(A) + I(B)$. Therefore:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial I(A)} = w \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial I(A)}(1 - I(A) + I(B)) = w \cdot (-1) = -2.0$$

Gradient with respect to $I(B)$:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial I(B)} = w \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial I(B)}(1 - I(A) + I(B)) = w \cdot 1 = 2.0$$

Interpretation: The negative gradient with respect to $I(A)$ indicates that increasing $I(A)$ would decrease the energy (make the implication harder to satisfy). The positive gradient with respect to $I(B)$ indicates that increasing $I(B)$ would increase the energy (make the implication easier to satisfy). This aligns with the intuition that an implication is better satisfied when the antecedent is weaker or the consequent is stronger.

3.8.2 Illustrative Example: Conjunction and Disjunction

Consider formulas $A \wedge B$ and $A \vee B$ with $I(A) = 0.6$ and $I(B) = 0.7$.

Conjunction:

$$I(A \wedge B) = \max(0, 0.6 + 0.7 - 1) = \max(0, 0.3) = 0.3$$

Disjunction:

$$I(A \vee B) = \min(1, 0.6 + 0.7) = \min(1, 1.3) = 1.0$$

Note that the Łukasiewicz conjunction is more demanding than the minimum (Gödel t-norm would give $\min(0.6, 0.7) = 0.6$), and the disjunction quickly saturates to 1.

3.8.3 Illustrative Example: Quantified Formula

Consider the formula $\varphi(u) = \text{suspicious}(u) \rightarrow \text{alert}(u)$ over the domain $\mathcal{C} = \{\text{alice}, \text{bob}\}$.

Interpretation:

- $I(\text{suspicious}(\text{alice})) = 0.8, I(\text{alert}(\text{alice})) = 0.9$
- $I(\text{suspicious}(\text{bob})) = 0.3, I(\text{alert}(\text{bob})) = 0.1$

Grounding evaluations:

$$I(\varphi[\text{alice}]) = \min(1, 1 - 0.8 + 0.9) = \min(1, 1.1) = 1.0 \quad (27)$$

$$I(\varphi[\text{bob}]) = \min(1, 1 - 0.3 + 0.1) = \min(1, 0.8) = 0.8 \quad (28)$$

Ground satisfaction:

$$\bar{I}(\varphi) = \frac{1}{2}(1.0 + 0.8) = 0.9$$

The formula is well satisfied on average: Alice fully satisfies the rule (high suspicion and high alert), while Bob partially violates it (low suspicion but even lower alert).

3.8.4 Illustrative Example: End-to-End Gradient Computation

A comprehensive example integrating knowledge base definition, formula evaluation, energy computation, and gradient-based optimisation follows.

Setup: Consider a miniature legal reasoning scenario with the following signature:

- Predicates: $\mathcal{P} = \{\text{cites}/2, \text{relevant}/1, \text{similar}/2\}$

- Constants: $\mathcal{C} = \{\text{case1, case2, query}\}$

The knowledge base contains three weighted formulas representing domain knowledge:

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi_1(x) &: \text{cites}(x, \text{query}) \rightarrow \text{relevant}(x) \quad [w_1 = 3.0] \\ \varphi_2(x, y) &: (\text{similar}(x, y) \wedge \text{relevant}(y)) \rightarrow \text{relevant}(x) \quad [w_2 = 2.0] \\ \varphi_3(x) &: \neg \text{relevant}(x) \quad [w_3 = -1.0]\end{aligned}$$

The first formula encodes that cases citing the query are relevant. The second encodes transitive relevance: if x is similar to a relevant case y , then x is also relevant. The third formula represents a weak prior against relevance (in the absence of other evidence, cases are assumed to be irrelevant).

Initial interpretation: Consider the interpretation I_0 defined by:

$$\begin{aligned}I_0(\text{cites}(\text{case1}, \text{query})) &= 0.8 & I_0(\text{relevant}(\text{case1})) &= 0.5 \\ I_0(\text{cites}(\text{case2}, \text{query})) &= 0.2 & I_0(\text{relevant}(\text{case2})) &= 0.3 \\ I_0(\text{similar}(\text{case1}, \text{case2})) &= 0.7\end{aligned}$$

All other ground atoms have a truth degree 0.

Step 1: Formula evaluation for φ_1 . The formula $\varphi_1(x) = \text{cites}(x, \text{query}) \rightarrow \text{relevant}(x)$ has two groundings:

Grounding 1 ($x = \text{case1}$):

$$I_0(\varphi_1[\text{case1}]) = \min(1, 1 - 0.8 + 0.5) = \min(1, 0.7) = 0.7$$

Grounding 2 ($x = \text{case2}$):

$$I_0(\varphi_1[\text{case2}]) = \min(1, 1 - 0.2 + 0.3) = \min(1, 1.1) = 1.0$$

Ground satisfaction:

$$\bar{I}_0(\varphi_1) = \frac{1}{2}(0.7 + 1.0) = 0.85$$

Step 2: Formula evaluation for φ_2 . The formula $\varphi_2(x, y) = (\text{similar}(x, y) \wedge \text{relevant}(y)) \rightarrow \text{relevant}(x)$ has $3 \times 3 = 9$ groundings (all pairs of cases). Most

groundings involve atoms with a truth degree 0. The only non-trivial grounding is $x = \text{case2}, y = \text{case1}$:

$$I_0(\text{similar}(\text{case2}, \text{case1})) = 0 \quad (\text{not defined; assume } 0)$$

$$I_0(\text{similar}(\text{case1}, \text{case2}) \wedge \text{relevant}(\text{case2})) = \max(0, 0.7 + 0.3 - 1) = 0$$

$$I_0(\varphi_2[\text{case1}, \text{case2}]) = \min(1, 1 - 0 + 0.5) = 1.0$$

All other groundings yield 1.0 (implications with false antecedents). Thus:

$$\bar{I}_0(\varphi_2) = \frac{1}{9}(9 \times 1.0) = 1.0$$

Step 3: Formula evaluation for φ_3 . The formula $\varphi_3(x) = \neg \text{relevant}(x)$ has three groundings:

$$I_0(\varphi_3[\text{case1}]) = 1 - 0.5 = 0.5$$

$$I_0(\varphi_3[\text{case2}]) = 1 - 0.3 = 0.7$$

$$I_0(\varphi_3[\text{query}]) = 1 - 0 = 1.0$$

Ground satisfaction:

$$\bar{I}_0(\varphi_3) = \frac{1}{3}(0.5 + 0.7 + 1.0) = 0.733$$

Step 4: Energy computation.

$$E(I_0; \mathbf{w}) = w_1 \bar{I}_0(\varphi_1) + w_2 \bar{I}_0(\varphi_2) + w_3 \bar{I}_0(\varphi_3)$$

$$= 3.0 \cdot 0.85 + 2.0 \cdot 1.0 + (-1.0) \cdot 0.733 = 2.55 + 2.0 - 0.733 = 3.817$$

Step 5: Gradient with respect to weights. From Theorem 3.4:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial w_1} = \bar{I}_0(\varphi_1) = 0.85$$

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial w_2} = \bar{I}_0(\varphi_2) = 1.0$$

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial w_3} = \bar{I}_0(\varphi_3) = 0.733$$

These gradients indicate that if we were to learn weights from data (Chapter 5), increasing w_2 would have the largest impact on energy (since φ_2 is fully satisfied), while increasing w_1 would have a moderate impact (since φ_1 is only 85% satisfied on average).

Step 6: Gradient with respect to interpretation. To compute $\frac{\partial E}{\partial I(\text{relevant}(\text{case1}))}$, we trace through all formulas that depend on this atom:

From $\varphi_1[\text{case1}]$: The formula $\text{cites}(\text{case1}, \text{query}) \rightarrow \text{relevant}(\text{case1})$ evaluates to $0.7 < 1$, so we are in the unsaturated region. The gradient is:

$$\frac{\partial I_0(\varphi_1[\text{case1}])}{\partial I(\text{relevant}(\text{case1}))} = 1$$

Contribution to the energy gradient: $\frac{w_1}{2} \cdot 1 = 1.5$.

From $\varphi_3[\text{case1}]$: The formula $\neg \text{relevant}(\text{case1})$ has gradient:

$$\frac{\partial I_0(\varphi_3[\text{case1}])}{\partial I(\text{relevant}(\text{case1}))} = -1$$

Contribution to energy gradient: $\frac{w_3}{3} \cdot (-1) = \frac{-1.0}{3} \cdot (-1) = 0.333$.

Total gradient:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial I(\text{relevant}(\text{case1}))} = 1.5 + 0.333 = 1.833$$

The positive gradient indicates that increasing $I(\text{relevant}(\text{case1}))$ would increase the energy. This makes sense: case 1 cites the query strongly (0.8), so marking it as more relevant aligns with formula φ_1 (weight 3.0), and the penalty from φ_3 (weight -1.0) is weaker.

Step 7: Optimisation step. Using gradient ascent with a learning rate $\eta = 0.1$:

$$\begin{aligned} I_1(\text{relevant}(\text{case1})) &= I_0(\text{relevant}(\text{case1})) + \eta \cdot \frac{\partial E}{\partial I(\text{relevant}(\text{case1}))} \\ &= 0.5 + 0.1 \cdot 1.833 = 0.5 + 0.1833 = 0.6833 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we could compute gradients for all other atoms and update the entire interpretation. After multiple iterations, the interpretation would converge to a local maximum of the energy function, corresponding to a MAP interpretation that best satisfies the weighted knowledge base.

Every stage of the pipeline appears above: knowledge base definition, compositional formula evaluation, ground satisfaction averaging, energy aggregation, and gradient computation. Piecewise linearity ensures every gradient in the chain is well-defined (except on a measure-zero boundary set), so standard deep-learning optimisers drive the interpretation toward a MAP solution without custom differentiation code.

3.9 Summary

The key results are worth recapping briefly.

Sections 3.1–3.2 fixed the NMLN framework: signatures, formulas, Łukasiewicz operations ($\max(0, a + b - 1)$, $\min(1, a + b)$, $\min(1, 1 - a + b)$), and quantifier semantics (min for \forall , max for \exists). All 55 algebraic properties are mechanically verified in Isabelle/HOL (Appendix B).

The energy function $E(I; \mathbf{w}) = \sum_i w_i \bar{I}(\varphi_i)$ is linear in \mathbf{w} , bounded, and continuous in I . Piecewise linearity of formula evaluation (Theorem 3.3) yields almost-everywhere differentiability (Corollary 3.1), which is exactly what PyTorch’s sub-gradient semantics require. The weight gradient takes the clean form $\partial E / \partial w_i = \bar{I}(\varphi_i)$ (Theorem 3.4); interpretation gradients follow by backpropagation through formula trees.

The direct mapping to PyTorch primitives (`torch.clamp`; Table 10) ensures that every theoretical property holds in the executable code—a correctness-by-construction guarantee absent from embedding-based approaches.

Exponentiating the energy gives the Gibbs distribution $P(I; \mathbf{w}) \propto \exp(E(I; \mathbf{w}))$ (Section 3.5), grounded in maximum-entropy statistics. The intractable partition function is approximated via MCMC (Chapter 4) or sidestepped with MAP inference ($I^* = \arg \max E$). Theorem 3.5 guarantees convergence of gradient ascent under Robbins–Monro conditions, putting weight learning (Chapter 5) on firm footing. Complexity bounds— $O(|\varphi|)$ per ground formula, $O(n^k |\varphi|)$ for ground satisfaction, $O(m n^{k_{\max}} |\varphi|_{\max})$ for full energy—drive the engineering strategy: variable restriction to ≤ 3 , sparse storage, lazy evaluation, and GPU batching.

This rigour serves three practical purposes. The exact Definition 3.10–PyTorch correspondence eliminates implementation ambiguity: every computed gradient is a valid sub-gradient, ruling out a class of subtle bugs. At the application level, formal semantics underpin the 100% explainability on COLIEE (Chapter 6), where every

prediction traces to formula evaluations with explicit truth degrees—a prerequisite for EU AI Act compliance (Chapter 7, Articles 13 and 14). More broadly, piecewise linearity (Theorem 3.3) clarifies *why* Łukasiewicz logic fits neurosymbolic integration: it is interpretable, differentiable almost everywhere, and logically coherent (residuation holds). Gödel and product logics each violate at least one of these criteria.

Subsequent chapters build directly on these results. Chapter 4 exploits differentiability and the Gibbs distribution for sampling-based inference. Chapter 5 relies on gradient flow and the convergence guarantee. Chapter 6 translates the complexity bounds into sparse-storage, lazy-evaluation, and GPU-batching strategies. The 55 machine-checked Isabelle/HOL theorems (Appendix B) provide the verified algebraic substrate underneath.

4 Inference Algorithms

Exact inference in NMLNs—computing expectations, marginals, or most probable interpretations—is intractable for all but the smallest domains (de Nijs et al., 2016; Jaeger, 2015; Wang et al., 2022). The continuous fuzzy truth space aggravates the problem: classical MLNs sum over exponentially many Boolean interpretations, but NMLNs integrate over a continuous hypercube (Kimmig et al., 2015; Riguzzi et al., 2017; Srinivasan et al., 2022). Sampling-based algorithms offer a practical way forward, and developing them for the Łukasiewicz setting of Chapter 3 is the purpose of what follows.

The chapter makes three contributions. It begins by formalising the inference tasks that arise in LIMEN-AI and relating them to standard problems in probabilistic graphical models (Romanov et al., 2020). Building on that foundation, importance sampling and power sampling schemes are developed for the Łukasiewicz setting, together with bias, variance, and sample-complexity analyses (Gerlach and Bocklisch, 2021; Rodríguez-Cándido et al., 2021). The sampling process is then instrumented to produce explanation traces that record each rule’s contribution to the result, meeting the transparency demands of regulated applications.

4.1 Inference Tasks in LIMEN-AI

LIMEN-AI must compute expected truth degrees, conditional expectations, and MAP interpretations. Each has a counterpart in classical probabilistic graphical models, and each is hard for different reasons. Pinning down their definitions gives the sampling algorithms developed later a precise specification to target.

4.1.1 Queries and Quantities of Interest

Each quantity below adapts a familiar concept from classical probabilistic graphical models to the continuous truth-degree setting.

Definition 4.1 (Query Formula). *A query is a formula Q whose truth degree under the distribution $P(I; \mathbf{w})$ is of interest. The query may be a single ground atom, a complex formula involving multiple atoms and connectives, or a formula with free variables (interpreted as the average over groundings).*

Definition 4.2 (Expected Truth Degree). *The expected truth degree of a query Q is:*

$$\mu_Q = \mathbb{E}_P[I(Q)] = \int_{\mathcal{I}_\Sigma} I(Q) \cdot P(I; \mathbf{w}) dI$$

This quantity represents the average truth degree of Q across all interpretations, weighted by their probability under the energy-based distribution.

The expected truth degree is analogous to the marginal probability in classical MLNs. If Q is a ground atom, μ_Q indicates how strongly that atom is supported by the knowledge base. If Q is a complex formula, μ_Q indicates the degree to which that constraint is typically satisfied.

Definition 4.3 (Conditional Expected Truth Degree). *Given evidence E (a partial assignment of truth degrees to some atoms), the conditional expected truth degree is:*

$$\mu_{Q|E} = \mathbb{E}_{P(\cdot|E)}[I(Q)] = \frac{\int_{\mathcal{I}_\Sigma \cap E} I(Q) \cdot P(I; \mathbf{w}) dI}{\int_{\mathcal{I}_\Sigma \cap E} P(I; \mathbf{w}) dI}$$

where $\mathcal{I}_\Sigma \cap E$ denotes the set of interpretations consistent with evidence E .

Definition 4.4 (Most Probable Interpretation). *The most probable interpretation (MAP interpretation) is:*

$$I^* = \arg \max_{I \in \mathcal{I}_\Sigma} P(I; \mathbf{w}) = \arg \max_{I \in \mathcal{I}_\Sigma} E(I; \mathbf{w})$$

This interpretation maximises consistency with the knowledge base.

Definition 4.5 (ϵ -Optimal Interpretations). *For tolerance $\epsilon > 0$, the set of ϵ -optimal interpretations is:*

$$\mathcal{I}_\epsilon = \{I \in \mathcal{I}_\Sigma \mid E(I; \mathbf{w}) \geq E^* - \epsilon\}$$

where $E^ = \max_I E(I; \mathbf{w})$ is the maximum energy.*

The ϵ -optimal set provides a soft version of MAP inference, identifying all interpretations that are nearly as good as the best one. This is useful when the MAP interpretation is not unique or when small deviations from optimality are acceptable.

4.1.2 Inference in Decision Support

In decision support, each inference quantity serves a concrete purpose. Query answering computes expected truth degrees—“to what degree is this transaction

suspicious?” Ranking orders competing conclusions by knowledge-base support, driving alert triage and risk assessment. Threshold detection fires when a truth degree exceeds a preset cutoff, triggering an action or flagging a case for human review. Explanation generation identifies which rules and groundings drove the result, letting users evaluate the system’s reasoning.

4.2 Complexity of Exact Inference

Can any of these quantities be computed exactly? For all but toy-sized knowledge bases, no. The continuous fuzzy truth space turns the discrete sum of classical MLNs into a high-dimensional integral, and even discretization does not rescue tractability. The hardness results below motivate the sampling-based approximations of later sections.

4.2.1 The Partition Function

The partition function $Z(\mathbf{w}) = \int_{\mathcal{I}_\Sigma} \exp(E(I; \mathbf{w})) dI$ is the normalising constant for the probability distribution. Computing Z exactly requires integrating the exponential of the energy function over the entire interpretation space.

Theorem 4.1 (Intractability of Exact Inference). *Computing the partition function $Z(\mathbf{w})$ exactly is intractable for general NMLNs, even for knowledge bases with only unary predicates.*

Proof. The proof proceeds by reduction from classical MLN inference. When every truth value is restricted to $\{0, 1\}$, the Łukasiewicz connectives collapse to their Boolean counterparts ($\max(0, a + b - 1) = a \wedge b$, $\min(1, 1 - a + b) = a \rightarrow b$, etc.), the integral over $[0, 1]^n$ reduces to a sum over $\{0, 1\}^n$, and the NMLN partition function coincides with the classical MLN partition function. Computing marginal probabilities in classical MLNs is #P-hard (Richardson and Domingos, 2006). Since the Boolean case is a special case of the general NMLN problem, any algorithm that computes $Z(\mathbf{w})$ exactly for general NMLNs would, in particular, solve the #P-hard Boolean instance. Therefore, exact NMLN inference is at least #P-hard.

The continuous truth-value space only compounds the difficulty. For m formulas involving the Łukasiewicz conjunction $\max(0, a + b - 1)$, each formula introduces a hyperplane boundary (e.g., $a + b = 1$) that partitions $[0, 1]^n$ into a region where the

max is active and one where it is clamped to zero. The number of combinatorially distinct regions grows exponentially in m , so exact analytic integration is infeasible even when each region’s contribution is individually tractable. \square

4.2.2 Discretization Approaches

A natural approximation strategy is to discretize the truth-value space, replacing the integral with a finite sum.

Definition 4.6 (Discretized Interpretation Space). *For discretization level k , the discretized interpretation space is:*

$$\mathcal{I}_\Sigma^{(k)} = \left\{ 0, \frac{1}{k}, \frac{2}{k}, \dots, 1 \right\}^{|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma|}$$

This space contains $(k + 1)^{|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma|}$ interpretations.

The discretized partition function $Z^{(k)} = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}_\Sigma^{(k)}} \exp(E(I; \mathbf{w}))$ can be computed by enumeration, but the number of terms is doubly exponential in the number of atoms for reasonable k . Even with coarse discretization ($k = 1$, Boolean semantics), the sum is exponential.

Proposition 4.1 (Discretization Error). *For a Lipschitz-continuous energy function with constant L (boundedness formally verified by `energy_bounded` in Appendix B), the discretization error satisfies:*

$$|Z - Z^{(k)}| \cdot k^{-|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma|} = O\left(\frac{L}{k}\right)$$

where the factor $k^{-|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma|}$ accounts for the volume of each discretization cell.

Finer discretization reduces approximation error, but computational cost grows exponentially with the number of atoms. Discretization is feasible only for very small problems.

4.2.3 Lifted Inference and Scalability Comparison

The sampling-based approach developed here relies on grounding the Markov Logic Network before inference. Grounding transforms the relational model into a propositional one at a cost that grows exponentially with predicate arity and domain

size. Beyond roughly 10^3 ground atoms, this creates bottlenecks that sampling alone cannot overcome.

Lifted inference avoids full grounding by exploiting symmetries at the first-order level. Recent work has broadened its reach considerably. Malhotra et al. (2025) proved that the two-variable fragment with counting quantifiers (C^2) is domain-liftable— inference runs in polynomial time in the domain size (Malhotra et al., 2025). Their results extend to graph constraints such as acyclicity and connectivity, properties common in real-world data that usually render inference intractable. Baader and Claußnitzer (2025) showed that maximum entropy reasoning with domain-lifted model counting is feasible for description logics with counting quantifiers (Baader and Claußnitzer, 2025).

The efficiency gains can be substantial. Nguembang Fadja and Riguzzi (2019) reported speedups of up to $15\times$ for lifted discriminative learning of probabilistic logic programs, with no loss in solution quality (Nguembang Fadja and Riguzzi, 2019). Neural embeddings (e.g., Obj2Vec) have also been used to discover symmetries that are hard to specify manually, enabling lifted inference in more complex domains (Islam et al., 2019).

LIMEN-AI’s current implementation preserves rule structure explicitly and uses continuous Łukasiewicz semantics—both of which create challenges for lifting techniques designed for discrete domains. Weitekämper (2025) stresses that weight parameters must be scaled correctly across domain sizes to ensure generalisation, and that the asymptotic behaviour of unlifted models can be opaque (Weitekämper, 2025). The absence of lifted inference restricts applicability to domains whose grounding size remains manageable. A rigorous complexity analysis, a defence of grounding for regulated domains, and a roadmap for future scalability improvements follow.

Formal Complexity Comparison: LIMEN-AI vs. Domain-Lifted Inference

A formal complexity comparison between LIMEN-AI and state-of-the-art lifted inference clarifies the cost of grounding. The comparison centres on the recent results of Baader and Claußnitzer (2025) for description logics with counting quantifiers (Baader and Claußnitzer, 2025).

Baader’s ALCSCC: Domain-Lifted Model Counting. The description logic ALCSCC extends the base logic ALC with *successive counting constraints*, enabling expressions such as "at least n entities satisfy property P " without explicitly

enumerating those entities. Baader and Claußnitzer prove that maximum entropy reasoning in ALCSCC admits *domain-lifted inference*, meaning that probabilistic inference can be performed in time polynomial in the domain size $|D|$ rather than exponential in the number of ground atoms (Baader and Claußnitzer, 2025).

Formally, for a knowledge base \mathcal{K} with maximum predicate arity k over a domain of size $|D|$, Baader’s lifted model counting algorithm achieves complexity:

$$\mathcal{O}(|D|^k \cdot \text{poly}(|\mathcal{K}|))$$

where $\text{poly}(|\mathcal{K}|)$ denotes a polynomial factor in the size of the knowledge base (number of formulas, maximum formula length, etc.). Crucially, the exponent on $|D|$ is determined by the arity k , not by the total number of groundings—a dramatic improvement over grounding-based approaches.

LIMEN-AI: Grounding-Based Complexity. In contrast, LIMEN-AI’s current implementation follows a two-phase process:

Phase 1: Grounding. For each formula φ_i with free variables of types $\tau_1, \dots, \tau_{a_i}$, generate all groundings by substituting constants from the domain. The number of groundings is $|\text{Gr}(\varphi_i)| = |D_{\tau_1}| \times \dots \times |D_{\tau_{a_i}}|$. For a binary predicate over a domain of size $|D|$, this yields $|D|^2$ groundings; for a ternary predicate, $|D|^3$ groundings. The total number of ground atoms is:

$$N = \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{K}|} |\text{Gr}(\varphi_i)| = \mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{K}| \cdot |D|^{k_{\max}})$$

where k_{\max} is the maximum arity in the knowledge base.

Phase 2: Sampling. Given the grounded MLN with N ground atoms, power sampling (Section 4.4) performs T MCMC iterations, where each iteration evaluates the energy function:

$$E(I; \mathbf{w}) = \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{K}|} w_i \cdot \bar{I}(\varphi_i) = \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{K}|} w_i \cdot \frac{1}{|\text{Gr}(\varphi_i)|} \sum_{\gamma \in \text{Gr}(\varphi_i)} I(\varphi_i^\gamma)$$

Computing $\bar{I}(\varphi_i)$ requires iterating over all $|\text{Gr}(\varphi_i)|$ groundings of formula φ_i , applying the Łukasiewicz operations to compute $I(\varphi_i^\gamma)$, and averaging. For a knowledge

Table 11: Complexity comparison between domain-lifted inference (Baader ALCSCC) and grounding-based inference (LIMEN-AI) for a knowledge base of size $|\mathcal{K}|$ over a domain of size $|D|$ with maximum predicate arity k . Source: Author.

Approach	Complexity	Dependence on $ D $
Baader ALCSCC (Lifted)	$\mathcal{O}(D ^k \cdot \text{poly}(\mathcal{K}))$	Polynomial
LIMEN-AI (Grounding)	$\mathcal{O}(T \cdot \mathcal{K} \cdot D ^k)$	Polynomial \times sampling

base with m formulas, this costs:

$$\mathcal{O}\left(\sum_{i=1}^m |\text{Gr}(\varphi_i)|\right) = \mathcal{O}(N)$$

per energy evaluation. Over T samples, the total cost is:

$$\mathcal{O}(T \cdot N) = \mathcal{O}(T \cdot |\mathcal{K}| \cdot |D|^{k_{\max}})$$

Complexity Gap. Table 11 compares the two approaches:

Both scale as $\mathcal{O}(|D|^k)$, so the asymptotic order looks comparable. The gap lies elsewhere. Baader’s $\text{poly}(|\mathcal{K}|)$ factor is typically modest ($|\mathcal{K}|^2$ or $|\mathcal{K}|^3$), whereas LIMEN-AI’s sampling factor T must be large enough for mixing—usually $T \geq 10^4$ for non-trivial models. Memory is a sharper constraint: Baader’s algorithm works on the lifted representation ($\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{K}|)$ memory); LIMEN-AI stores the full grounding ($\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{K}| \cdot |D|^k)$). At $|D| = 10,000$ with binary predicates, that amounts to $\sim 10^8$ ground atoms—*infeasible* on standard hardware. Lifted inference can also exploit symmetries to reduce effective arity, a benefit unavailable to grounding.

Concrete Numerical Example. Consider a legal document analysis task with:

- Domain: $|D| = 5,000$ documents
- Predicates: Cites(x,y) (arity 2), Relevant(x) (arity 1), SameTopic(x,y) (arity 2)
- Knowledge base: $|\mathcal{K}| = 100$ weighted formulas
- Sampling: $T = 10,000$ iterations for convergence

Baader ALCSCC (assuming $\text{poly}(|\mathcal{K}|) = |\mathcal{K}|^2$):

$$\mathcal{O}(|D|^2 \cdot |\mathcal{K}|^2) = \mathcal{O}(5000^2 \cdot 100^2) = \mathcal{O}(2.5 \times 10^{13}) \text{ operations}$$

LIMEN-AI:

$$N = 2 \times 5000^2 + 1 \times 5000 = 5 \times 10^7 \text{ ground atoms}$$

$$\mathcal{O}(T \cdot N) = \mathcal{O}(10^4 \cdot 5 \times 10^7) = \mathcal{O}(5 \times 10^{11}) \text{ operations}$$

Gap: Baader’s approach requires $\sim 50\times$ more operations in this scenario, but crucially, it requires only $\mathcal{O}(100)$ memory for the lifted KB, whereas LIMEN-AI requires $\mathcal{O}(5 \times 10^7)$ memory for ground atoms—a difference that determines feasibility on standard hardware.

The Intractability Horizon: Defining LIMEN-AI’s Scalability Limit

LIMEN-AI’s cost grows as $\mathcal{O}(|D|^k \cdot T)$, but this asymptotic bound leaves a practical question open: *at what domain size does the system become unusable?* The *intractability horizon* formalises the answer.

Definition 4.7 (Intractability Horizon). *The intractability horizon N_{\max} is the number of ground atoms beyond which LIMEN-AI inference fails to complete within acceptable resource constraints. We define three failure modes:*

1. **Memory exhaustion:** *The grounded MLN exceeds available RAM (> 64 GB on a typical workstation).*
2. **Sampling timeout:** *Power sampling fails to achieve mixing within a reasonable time budget (< 24 hours of wall-clock time).*
3. **Gradient overflow:** *The automatic differentiation computation graph exceeds PyTorch’s memory limits during weight learning.*

When any of these conditions is triggered, we declare the domain intractable for current LIMEN-AI.

Empirical Calibration. Drawing on the experiments reported in Chapter 4 (power sampling benchmarks) and Chapter 5 (rule learning experiments), we empirically estimate N_{\max} by measuring wall-clock time and memory consumption across domains of varying sizes.

Table 12 reveals a clear threshold: $N_{\max} \approx 10^7$ ground atoms. Beyond this point, sampling either fails to mix within 24 hours or exhausts available memory. For

Table 12: Empirical scalability of LIMEN-AI grounding and sampling across domain sizes. Experiments conducted on a workstation with 64 GB RAM, 16-core CPU, NVIDIA RTX 4090 GPU. “Mixing” indicates whether 10,000 power sampling iterations achieved Gelman-Rubin $\hat{R} < 1.1$ convergence diagnostic. Source: Author.

Domain	$ D $	Predicates	Ground Atoms N	Sampling Time	Status
Toy (Friends/Smokes)	10	5	$\sim 5 \times 10^2$	< 1 s	Tractable
Small (Citations)	100	10	$\sim 1 \times 10^5$	~ 10 s	Tractable
Medium (Legal Docs)	1,000	20	$\sim 2 \times 10^7$	~ 30 min	Borderline
Large (Enterprise KB)	10,000	50	$\sim 5 \times 10^9$	> 24 h	Intractable

$|D| = 10,000$, the system is infeasible—this represents the intractability horizon for current LIMEN-AI.

Real-World Implications. Three enterprise scenarios illustrate the stakes. In *cybersecurity threat detection*, a network with 100,000 hosts and 30 predicates (Connects(x,y), HasVulnerability(x), SuspiciousTraffic(x,y)) produces roughly $N \approx 3 \times 10^{11}$ ground atoms—clearly infeasible. *Legal contract analysis* over 10,000 contracts with 50 predicates (Clause(c,x), Conflict(c1,c2), Regulates(c,d)) yields $N \approx 5 \times 10^9$, also beyond reach. *Supply chain reasoning* with 5,000 suppliers and 20 predicates (Supplies(s,p), Certifies(s,c), Risk(s)) reaches $N \approx 5 \times 10^8$ —marginally feasible with domain partitioning.

Many enterprise-scale applications therefore lie beyond LIMEN-AI’s current reach. The implication is not that the framework is useless, but that the deployment model shifts from batch ingestion of massive corpora to incremental construction of curated knowledge bases, as argued in the next subsection.

Why Grounding Is Not a Bug: The Case for Epistemic Transparency

LIMEN-AI’s grounding-based approach is expensive compared to lifted inference. One might treat this as a defect to be fixed by adopting lifting. We argue instead that grounding is a deliberate architectural choice, aligned with the regulatory and epistemic requirements of high-stakes AI deployment. The positive case for explicit grounding rests on the role of transparency in trustworthy AI.

The Transparency-Efficiency Trade-off. Lifted inference achieves polynomial

complexity by abstracting away specific variable instantiations, reasoning instead about equivalence classes of groundings with identical probabilistic behaviour. The abstraction is mathematically elegant and computationally powerful. Its cost is that the intermediate representations—par-factor graphs, weighted model counts—do not directly correspond to human-interpretable statements about specific entities.

Baader’s domain-lifted model counting for ALCSCC (Baader and Claußnitzer, 2025) illustrates the trade-off. The algorithm computes a weighted model count by exploiting symmetries, never enumerating individual groundings. It produces a number—a partition function or probability—but the derivation involves combinatorial identities, symmetry reductions, and lifted operations opaque to domain experts. If the system concludes that “Document d_{1337} is relevant to Case c_{42} with probability 0.87,” a compliance officer cannot inspect the lifted trace to see *which specific rules and documents* contributed, because the algorithm never materialised those groundings.

In contrast, LIMEN-AI’s grounding-based approach maintains a one-to-one correspondence between logical formulas and their instantiations. When inference concludes that $\text{Relevant}(d_{1337}, c_{42})$ has a truth degree of 0.87, the explanation trace (Section 4.6) can point to specific ground formulas:

- $\text{Cites}(d_{1337}, d_{89}) \wedge \text{Relevant}(d_{89}, c_{42}) \Rightarrow \text{Relevant}(d_{1337}, c_{42})$: satisfied to degree 0.92, weight 3.1
- $\text{SameTopic}(d_{1337}, d_{512}) \wedge \text{Relevant}(d_{512}, c_{42}) \Rightarrow \text{Relevant}(d_{1337}, c_{42})$: satisfied to degree 0.85, weight 2.7

A human auditor can read these ground rules, verify their semantic correctness, and trace the inference path. Lifted inference, by contrast, exploits symmetries without recording which specific entities participated in which rules, making this level of granularity unattainable.

Regulatory Alignment: EU AI Act Articles 13 & 14. The European Union AI Act (Regulation 2024/1689) imposes strict transparency and oversight requirements on "high-risk" AI systems, including those used in law enforcement, credit scoring, employment decisions, and access to essential services (European Parliament and Council, 2024). Article 13 mandates that such systems be "designed and developed in such a way as to ensure that their operation is sufficiently transparent to enable users to interpret the system’s output and use it appropriately." Article 14

requires "human oversight measures" that enable humans to "fully understand the capacities and limitations of the AI system and to duly monitor its operation."

Black-box models (neural networks) and even lifted inference—whose algorithmic traces involve abstract combinatorial operations—struggle to meet these requirements. Grounding-based inference produces *human-interpretable explanations* referencing specific logical rules and specific entities, precisely what Article 13 demands. When an AI system denies a loan application, the applicant has the right (under Article 14) to contest the decision and receive a meaningful explanation. LIMEN-AI can provide: "Your application was flagged because formula φ_{23} ($\text{HighDebtRatio}(x) \wedge \text{RecentDefault}(x) \Rightarrow \text{HighRisk}(x)$) was satisfied to a degree of 0.93, and this formula has a weight of 4.2." A lifted inference system cannot provide this level of detail without re-grounding the model post-hoc—at which point the computational advantage of lifting is lost.

Incremental Knowledge Construction: A Defence Against Scale.

Grounding supports transparency, yet the scalability challenge remains: what happens when the domain exceeds $N_{\max} = 10^7$ atoms? The answer is that LIMEN-AI targets *incremental construction of curated knowledge bases*, not *batch ingestion of massive corpora*.

We emphasised in the directive, "our knowledge is never lost and the idea is to build it time by time providing a human verification and not generating 'all' the knowledge at once ingesting millions of documents." This philosophy aligns with the reality of high-stakes decision-making: expert knowledge bases (e.g., legal precedents, clinical guidelines, regulatory compliance rules) are not generated by scraping the internet—they are carefully curated, validated, and maintained over time by domain experts. A legal AI system does not need to reason simultaneously over 100,000 case documents; it needs to reason over the 50–500 most relevant precedents identified by a lawyer through retrieval and filtering.

Under this paradigm, the grounding bottleneck acts as a natural constraint enforcing disciplined knowledge engineering. The system operates on knowledge bases of manageable size ($|\mathcal{K}| \sim 100$ formulas, $|D| \sim 1000$ entities), so every rule can be inspected, every grounding traced, and every inference explained. New data (e.g., a new court ruling) is reviewed by a human expert, formalised as new rules or facts, and integrated into the existing KB—the incremental, human-in-the-loop process that the EU AI Act's "human oversight" requirement envisions.

Lifted Inference as Complementary. Nothing above amounts to a rejection of lifted inference. It is better understood as a *complementary* technique for sub-tasks where transparency can be relaxed:

- **Pre-processing:** Use lifted inference to identify candidate entities for grounding (e.g., "Which 100 documents are most likely to be relevant?" can be answered approximately via lifted approximations).
- **Verification:** After LIMEN-AI produces a grounded explanation, use lifted inference to verify consistency across the broader domain ("If this rule holds for these 10 documents, would it generalise to the other 9,990?").
- **Low-stakes queries:** For exploratory queries where transparency is not legally required, employ lifted approximations for speed.

Not all inference tasks carry the same transparency requirements. LIMEN-AI’s design prioritises the subset where epistemic transparency is non-negotiable, and for those tasks grounding is a feature, not a limitation.

Future Roadmap: Tiled Grounding via Hierarchical Parallelisation

Grounding may be principled for regulated AI, yet scalability improvements are still needed. A promising direction for extending LIMEN-AI to larger domains without sacrificing explainability is *tiled grounding*, inspired by hierarchical parallelisation techniques for transformer attention mechanisms (Yang et al., 2025).

Inspiration: UltraAttn’s Hierarchical Context-Tiling. Yang et al. (2025) developed UltraAttn, a method for efficiently parallelising the attention mechanism in large language models through hierarchical context-tiling (Yang et al., 2025). The standard attention operation has complexity $\mathcal{O}(L^2)$ for sequence length L , becoming prohibitive for long contexts ($L > 10^5$ tokens). UltraAttn partitions the sequence into K tiles of size L/K , computes local attention within each tile ($\mathcal{O}((L/K)^2)$ per tile), and aggregates through a hierarchy of cross-tile attention operations. The total complexity becomes $\mathcal{O}(K \cdot (L/K)^2 + K^2) = \mathcal{O}(L^2/K + K^2)$, optimised at $K = \sqrt{L}$ to yield $\mathcal{O}(L^{3/2})$ —a significant improvement over $\mathcal{O}(L^2)$.

The key insight is that long-range dependencies (between distant tokens) are *sparse*: most tokens attend primarily to nearby context. By tiling the sequence and limiting full attention to local regions, UltraAttn reduces computation while maintaining expressivity.

Analogous Challenge in LIMEN-AI. The grounding bottleneck in LIMEN-AI arises from the $\mathcal{O}(|D|^k)$ groundings of k -ary predicates over the domain D . However, in many real-world domains, *relational structure is sparse*: not all pairs of entities are related. For example, in a legal citation network, each document cites only ~ 10 – 20 others, not all $|D| - 1$ documents. The naive grounding approach generates $|D|^2$ groundings for $\text{Cites}(x,y)$, but only $\sim 10|D|$ of these are non-zero in the data.

Proposed Algorithm: Tiled LIMEN-AI (T-LIMEN). We propose a partitioned grounding scheme that mirrors UltraAttn’s hierarchical tiling:

Step 1: Domain Partitioning. Partition the domain D into K overlapping tiles D_1, D_2, \dots, D_K such that:

- $D = \bigcup_{i=1}^K D_i$ (every entity appears in at least one tile)
- $|D_i| = |D|/K + \delta$ where δ is a small overlap ($\delta \approx 0.1 \cdot |D|/K$)
- Tiles are constructed via graph clustering (e.g., Louvain algorithm) to minimise cross-tile edges in the relational structure

Step 2: Local Grounding. For each tile D_i , ground the knowledge base \mathcal{K} over D_i to produce a local ground MLN \mathcal{G}_i with $N_i = \mathcal{O}((|D|/K)^k)$ ground atoms.

Step 3: Local Inference. Run power sampling independently on each \mathcal{G}_i to obtain local marginal distributions $P_i(I_i)$ over ground atoms in tile D_i .

Step 4: Message Passing. For entities $e \in D_i \cap D_j$ (appearing in multiple tiles), enforce consistency via message passing:

$$P_i(e) \leftarrow \alpha \cdot P_i(e) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot P_j(e)$$

where α is a damping factor. Iterate until $\max_{i,j} \|P_i(e) - P_j(e)\|_2 < \epsilon$.

Step 5: Global Aggregation. Merge the consistent local distributions into a global distribution over D .

Complexity Analysis. Each tile has $N_i = \mathcal{O}((|D|/K)^k)$ ground atoms. Sampling each tile costs $\mathcal{O}(T \cdot N_i) = \mathcal{O}(T \cdot (|D|/K)^k)$. For K tiles in parallel:

$$\text{Parallel cost} = \mathcal{O}(T \cdot (|D|/K)^k)$$

Sequential cost (for comparison): $\mathcal{O}(T \cdot |D|^k)$

$$\text{Speedup: } \frac{|D|^k}{(|D|/K)^k} = K^k$$

For $K = 10$ partitions and binary predicates ($k = 2$), this yields a $10^2 = 100\times$ speedup. Memory usage per tile is $\mathcal{O}((|D|/K)^k)$, allowing domains 10–100 \times larger to fit in RAM.

Approximation Error. Tiled grounding introduces approximation error because local inference ignores long-range dependencies between tiles. However, the overlap and message-passing steps bound this error. Chen et al. (2019) proved convergence guarantees for lifted message passing in hybrid MLNs (Chen et al., 2019), and similar results apply to tiled grounding. The key requirement is that the relational graph has a *community structure* (strong intra-tile connections, weak inter-tile connections), which holds for many real-world domains (citation networks, social networks, supply chains).

Implementation Roadmap. Tiled LIMEN-AI can be implemented as an extension to the current PyTorch codebase:

1. **Graph clustering:** Use NetworkX’s Louvain algorithm to partition the relational graph induced by the knowledge base.
2. **Distributed sampling:** Use PyTorch’s `torch.distributed` module to run power sampling on each tile in parallel across multiple GPUs.
3. **Message passing:** Implement belief propagation-style updates for overlap entities, iterating until convergence.

Analytically, tiled grounding with K partitions reduces per-tile complexity from $O(|D|^k)$ to $O((|D|/K)^k)$, suggesting that $K = 10$ partitions could extend LIMEN-AI’s practical scalability from $|D| \sim 1,000$ to $|D| \sim 10,000$. Empirical validation of this projection is planned for future work.

Broader Implications. Tiled grounding occupies a middle ground between pure grounding (transparent but slow) and pure lifting (fast but opaque). Domain partitioning with local grounding preserves the interpretability of ground-level inference while unlocking parallelisation gains—scalability improvements achieved by respecting transparency requirements rather than circumventing them.

4.3 Importance Sampling for NMLN Inference

Exact inference being intractable, we turn to approximations with quantifiable error. Importance sampling draws samples from a tractable proposal distribution

R , reweights them to correct for the mismatch with the target P , and estimates expectations as weighted averages. The framework is developed from the basic identity through self-normalised estimators that eliminate the intractable partition function.

4.3.1 Basic Importance Sampling

The target distribution $P(I; \mathbf{w}) = \frac{1}{Z} \exp(E(I; \mathbf{w}))$ cannot be sampled directly because it requires the partition function Z . Importance sampling sidesteps this by sampling from a tractable proposal $R(I)$ and correcting via importance weights.

The Importance Sampling Identity

Definition 4.8 (Importance Sampling Setup). *Let $P(I) = \frac{1}{Z} \exp(E(I; \mathbf{w}))$ be the target distribution and $R(I)$ be a proposal distribution that is easy to sample from and has support wherever P is positive. The importance weight for an interpretation I is:*

$$W(I) = \frac{P(I)}{R(I)} = \frac{\exp(E(I; \mathbf{w}))}{Z \cdot R(I)}$$

When $W(I) > 1$, interpretation I is underrepresented by the proposal and its contribution is upweighted; when $W(I) < 1$, it is overrepresented and downweighted. The support condition— $R(I) > 0$ wherever $P(I) > 0$ —is essential so that no region of positive target mass is invisible to the sampler; in practice, proposals with full support on $[0, 1]^{|A_\Sigma|}$ (e.g., uniform or product-Beta) satisfy this automatically.

Theorem 4.2 (Importance Sampling Identity). *For any function $f : \mathcal{I}_\Sigma \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with $\mathbb{E}_P[|f|] < \infty$:*

$$\mathbb{E}_P[f(I)] = \mathbb{E}_R[f(I) \cdot W(I)]$$

Proof.

$$\mathbb{E}_R[f(I) \cdot W(I)] = \int f(I) \cdot W(I) \cdot R(I) dI \tag{29}$$

$$= \int f(I) \cdot \frac{P(I)}{R(I)} \cdot R(I) dI \tag{30}$$

$$= \int f(I) \cdot P(I) dI = \mathbb{E}_P[f(I)] \tag{31}$$

□

The identity is elementary—a change of measure—yet it converts an intractable integral under P into a tractable one under R . For LIMEN-AI queries, $f(I) = I(Q) \in [0, 1]$, so the integrability condition $\mathbb{E}_P[|f|] < \infty$ holds automatically.

Monte Carlo Estimation To turn the identity into a computation, draw N independent samples $I^{(1)}, \dots, I^{(N)} \sim R$ and form the Monte Carlo estimator:

$$\hat{\mu}_N^{\text{MC}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N f(I^{(k)}) \cdot W(I^{(k)})$$

By the law of large numbers this converges to $\mathbb{E}_P[f]$, and by linearity of expectation it is unbiased. Setting $f(I) = I(Q)$ gives the expected truth degree μ_Q : sample from R , evaluate both $I(Q)$ and $W(I)$ for each draw, and average the products.

The Partition Function Obstacle A catch remains: computing $W(I) = \exp(E(I; \mathbf{w})) / (Z \cdot R(I))$ requires the intractable partition function Z . But Z cancels in weight *ratios*. For any two interpretations I and I' :

$$\frac{W(I)}{W(I')} = \frac{\exp(E(I)) / (Z \cdot R(I))}{\exp(E(I')) / (Z \cdot R(I'))} = \frac{\exp(E(I)) / R(I)}{\exp(E(I')) / R(I')}$$

Z drops out of the ratio. Working with unnormalised weights and dividing by their sum—self-normalising—eliminates the need for Z entirely. This leads to the self-normalised importance sampling estimator.

4.3.2 Self-Normalised Importance Sampling

Self-normalised importance sampling exploits the cancellation of Z by working with unnormalised weights and dividing by their sum. The price is a small bias— $O(1/N)$ —that vanishes faster than the $O(1/\sqrt{N})$ standard error and is negligible for moderate sample sizes.

Unnormalised Weights and the Self-Normalised Estimator

Definition 4.9 (Unnormalised Weights). *The unnormalised importance weight is:*

$$\tilde{W}(I) = \frac{\exp(E(I; \mathbf{w}))}{R(I)}$$

Note that $W(I) = \tilde{W}(I)/Z$.

Both ingredients of $\tilde{W}(I)$ —the energy $E(I; \mathbf{w})$ and the proposal density $R(I)$ —are computable; the intractable Z is absent. We estimate numerator and denominator separately and take their ratio:

$$S_N = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N I^{(k)}(Q) \cdot \tilde{W}(I^{(k)}), \quad W_N = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \tilde{W}(I^{(k)})$$

By the law of large numbers, S_N converges to $\mathbb{E}_R[I(Q) \cdot \tilde{W}(I)] = Z \cdot \mu_Q$ and W_N converges to $\mathbb{E}_R[\tilde{W}(I)] = Z$. Therefore, the ratio $\hat{\mu}_N = S_N/W_N$ converges to μ_Q , and crucially, the partition function Z cancels in the ratio.

Proposition 4.2 (Self-Normalised Estimator). *For samples $I^{(1)}, \dots, I^{(N)} \sim R$, the self-normalised importance sampling estimator is:*

$$\hat{\mu}_N = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N I^{(k)}(Q) \cdot \tilde{W}(I^{(k)})}{\sum_{k=1}^N \tilde{W}(I^{(k)})}$$

This estimator is biased but consistent: $\hat{\mu}_N \xrightarrow{P} \mu_Q$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof. Let $\bar{W}_N = \frac{1}{N} \sum_k \tilde{W}(I^{(k)})$ and $\bar{S}_N = \frac{1}{N} \sum_k I^{(k)}(Q) \cdot \tilde{W}(I^{(k)})$. By the law of large numbers:

$$\bar{W}_N \xrightarrow{P} \mathbb{E}_R[\tilde{W}(I)] = \int \frac{\exp(E(I))}{R(I)} \cdot R(I) dI = \int \exp(E(I)) dI = Z \quad (32)$$

$$\bar{S}_N \xrightarrow{P} \mathbb{E}_R[I(Q) \cdot \tilde{W}(I)] = Z \cdot \mathbb{E}_P[I(Q)] = Z \cdot \mu_Q \quad (33)$$

By Slutsky's theorem, $\hat{\mu}_N = \bar{S}_N/\bar{W}_N \xrightarrow{P} (Z \cdot \mu_Q)/Z = \mu_Q$. \square

The estimator is consistent but biased for finite N : the expectation of a ratio is not the ratio of expectations. The bias is $O(1/N)$ and vanishes faster than the $O(1/\sqrt{N})$ standard error, so in practice it is negligible.

Bias of the Self-Normalised Estimator To understand the bias more precisely, we can expand the ratio estimator using a Taylor series. Let $\bar{W}_N = Z + \delta_W$ and $\bar{S}_N = Z\mu_Q + \delta_S$, where δ_W and δ_S are zero-mean random fluctuations of order $O(1/\sqrt{N})$ by the central limit theorem. Then:

$$\hat{\mu}_N = \frac{\bar{S}_N}{\bar{W}_N} = \frac{Z\mu_Q + \delta_S}{Z + \delta_W} = \frac{Z\mu_Q}{Z} \cdot \frac{1 + \delta_S/(Z\mu_Q)}{1 + \delta_W/Z}$$

Algorithm 1 Self-Normalised Importance Sampling for NMLN Inference. Source: Author.

Require: Knowledge base \mathcal{K}

- 1: Query Q
- 2: Proposal distribution R
- 3: Number of samples N

Ensure: Estimated expected truth degree $\hat{\mu}_N$

- 4: Initialize $S \leftarrow 0, W \leftarrow 0$
 - 5: **for** $k = 1$ to N **do**
 - 6: Sample interpretation $I^{(k)} \sim R$
 - 7: Compute energy $E^{(k)} \leftarrow E(I^{(k)}; \mathbf{w})$
 - 8: Compute unnormalised weight $\tilde{W}^{(k)} \leftarrow \exp(E^{(k)})/R(I^{(k)})$
 - 9: Evaluate query $q^{(k)} \leftarrow I^{(k)}(Q)$
 - 10: Update $S \leftarrow S + q^{(k)} \cdot \tilde{W}^{(k)}$
 - 11: Update $W \leftarrow W + \tilde{W}^{(k)}$
 - 12: Compute estimate $\hat{\mu}_N \leftarrow S/W$ **return** $\hat{\mu}_N$
-

Using the approximation $(1+x)^{-1} \approx 1-x+x^2$ for small x :

$$\hat{\mu}_N \approx \mu_Q \left(1 + \frac{\delta_S}{Z\mu_Q}\right) \left(1 - \frac{\delta_W}{Z} + \frac{\delta_W^2}{Z^2}\right)$$

Expanding and taking expectations, the first-order cross-term $\mathbb{E}[\delta_S\delta_W]$ contributes to the bias. If δ_S and δ_W are negatively correlated (which occurs when large weights correspond to large query values), the bias is negative; if positively correlated, the bias is positive. In either case, the bias is $O(1/N)$ and vanishes faster than the standard error $O(1/\sqrt{N})$, so for moderate sample sizes the bias is negligible compared to the statistical uncertainty.

In practice, self-normalised importance sampling delivers reliable estimates despite the bias. Enough samples are needed for \bar{W}_N and \bar{S}_N to stabilise near their expectations—typically $N \geq 100$ with a reasonable proposal. The effective sample size (Section 4.5) provides a diagnostic for adequacy.

4.3.3 Choice of Proposal Distribution

Efficiency hinges on how well the proposal R approximates the target P . A close match keeps weight variance low, but the proposal must also be cheap to sample from.

The Uniform Proposal: Simplicity vs. Efficiency

Definition 4.10 (Uniform Proposal). *The simplest proposal is the uniform distribu-*

tion over the interpretation space:

$$R_{\text{uniform}}(I) = 1 \quad \text{for all } I \in [0, 1]^{|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma|}$$

Sampling from R_{uniform} is trivial: independently sample each atomic truth degree from $\text{Uniform}(0, 1)$.

The uniform proposal is maximally simple: one random number per atom, constant density $R_{\text{uniform}}(I) = 1$, and weights that reduce to $\tilde{W}(I) = \exp(E(I; \mathbf{w}))$. Its weakness appears when the target concentrates in a small corner of the hypercube. Most uniform samples then land in low-energy regions with negligible weight; the rare samples that hit high-energy regions carry enormous weight and dominate the estimate. The resulting variance, proportional to $\chi^2(P\|R)$ (Theorem 4.4), can be exponentially large in the dimension of the interpretation space.

Tempered Proposals: Bridging the Gap

Definition 4.11 (Tempered Proposal). *A tempered proposal uses a flattened version of the target distribution:*

$$R_\alpha(I) \propto \exp(\alpha \cdot E(I; \mathbf{w}))$$

for temperature parameter $\alpha \in (0, 1)$. When $\alpha = 0$, this reduces to the uniform distribution; when $\alpha = 1$, it equals the target.

The tempered proposal places more mass on high-energy interpretations than the uniform distribution, but less than the target distribution. This can reduce variance when the target is highly concentrated. The temperature parameter α controls the degree of flattening: small α gives a proposal close to uniform (easy to sample from but potentially high variance), while large α gives a proposal close to the target (low variance but hard to sample from).

The difficulty is that tempered proposals are themselves complex distributions requiring normalisation. Sampling from R_α demands either its partition function $Z_\alpha = \int \exp(\alpha \cdot E(I)) dI$ —as intractable as the original Z —or MCMC targeting R_α , which introduces autocorrelation and requires careful tuning.

This circularity motivates the power sampling framework of the next section. Instead of sampling from a single clever proposal, power sampling traverses a sequence

of intermediate distributions, moving gradually from the uniform to the target and applying importance sampling at each step with only a small distributional change.

4.4 Power Sampling for NMLN Inference

Uniform proposals break down when the target distribution is sharply peaked or multimodal, as is common for NMLN knowledge bases with strong constraints. Power sampling (annealed importance sampling) breaks the problem into manageable steps. A tempering ladder of intermediate distributions bridges from the uniform to the target, and resampling with MCMC moves keeps the particle population diverse at each rung.

4.4.1 Tempered Distributions and Annealing

The idea originates in simulated annealing. At high temperature a system explores its state space freely; as temperature drops, it concentrates on high-energy states. Cooling slowly—splitting one large distributional shift into many small ones—keeps weight variation modest at each step.

The Temperature Ladder: Discretizing the Annealing Path

Definition 4.12 (Tempering Ladder). *A tempering ladder is a sequence of temperatures $0 = \alpha_0 < \alpha_1 < \dots < \alpha_L = 1$ defining a sequence of distributions:*

$$P_\ell(I) \propto \exp(\alpha_\ell \cdot E(I; \mathbf{w})), \quad \ell = 0, 1, \dots, L$$

Note that P_0 is the uniform distribution (since $\exp(0) = 1$) and $P_L = P$ is the target.

The idea is to gradually “heat up” the distribution from uniform to target, with each step involving a small change in temperature. This avoids the large importance weights that arise when sampling directly from a distribution very different from the target.

Temperature schedule $\{\alpha_\ell\}$ is critical. If rungs are too coarse (large $\Delta\alpha_\ell = \alpha_\ell - \alpha_{\ell-1}$), each importance-sampling step has high variance, defeating the purpose of intermediate distributions. If they are too fine (small $\Delta\alpha_\ell$), computational cost becomes prohibitive because each step evaluates the energy function and runs MCMC transitions.

Figure 35: Temperature ladder in power sampling. The sequence of intermediate distributions P_ℓ transitions from uniform ($\alpha = 0$) to the target ($\alpha = 1$), with non-uniform spacing that concentrates more steps near the target where distributional changes are steepest. Source: Author.

A common heuristic is to space temperatures such that the expected squared weight variation $\mathbb{E}[(w_\ell - 1)^2]$ is approximately constant across levels, where $w_\ell = \exp(\Delta\alpha_\ell \cdot E)$ is the incremental weight. This can be implemented adaptively by monitoring the effective sample size at each level and inserting additional temperatures when ESS drops below a threshold. For LIMEN-AI, the implementation in `src/limen/inference.py` (v0.3.0) uses a geometric spacing $\alpha_\ell = (\ell/L)^2$, which concentrates more temperatures near $\alpha = 1$ where the distribution changes most rapidly, with the exponent 2 determined empirically to balance variance and computational cost for typical knowledge bases. Figure 35 illustrates the resulting temperature ladder and the corresponding intermediate distributions.

The temperature ladder encapsulates a fundamental trade-off between exploration and exploitation: too few levels force each importance-sampling step to bridge a large distributional gap, inflating variance, while too many levels waste computation on nearly identical distributions. Non-uniform spacing—concentrating levels near the target where the density changes most steeply—achieves a favourable balance, keeping incremental weights close to unity throughout the schedule. This design principle guides the sequential importance sampling procedure that follows.

4.4.2 Sequential Importance Sampling

Sequential importance sampling propagates samples along the tempering ladder, applying importance sampling at each step. A population of “particles”—weighted interpretations—evolves through the temperature sequence, reusing information rather than discarding it by drawing fresh samples at every level.

Incremental Reweighting

Definition 4.13 (Incremental Weight). *For the transition from temperature $\alpha_{\ell-1}$ to α_ℓ , the incremental weight is:*

$$w_\ell(I) = \frac{P_\ell(I)}{P_{\ell-1}(I)} = \frac{\exp(\alpha_\ell E(I))}{\exp(\alpha_{\ell-1} E(I))} = \exp((\alpha_\ell - \alpha_{\ell-1}) \cdot E(I))$$

The incremental weight depends only on the energy $E(I)$ and the temperature step $\alpha_\ell - \alpha_{\ell-1}$. For small temperature steps, the incremental weights are close to 1 for most interpretations.

Crucially, the incremental weight ratio $w_\ell(I)$ does not involve any partition functions—both Z_ℓ and $Z_{\ell-1}$ cancel. This means we can compute $w_\ell(I)$ exactly given the energy $E(I)$ and the temperature schedule, without any intractable integrals. The total weight accumulated by a particle that starts at temperature $\alpha_0 = 0$ and transitions through all levels to $\alpha_L = 1$ is:

$$W(I) = \prod_{\ell=1}^L w_\ell(I) = \exp\left(\sum_{\ell=1}^L (\alpha_\ell - \alpha_{\ell-1}) E(I)\right) = \exp(E(I))$$

since the telescoping sum $\sum_{\ell=1}^L (\alpha_\ell - \alpha_{\ell-1}) = \alpha_L - \alpha_0 = 1 - 0 = 1$. This confirms that the cumulative weight equals the unnormalised target weight, as required for correctness.

The power of sequential importance sampling lies in computing this product incrementally. At each level ℓ , we multiply each particle’s weight by $w_\ell(I^{(k)})$, a number typically close to 1, rather than attempting to compute $\exp(E(I))$ directly, which might be a huge number if $E(I)$ is large. This numerical stability is particularly important for knowledge bases with many highly satisfied rules, where direct evaluation of $\exp(E(I))$ could overflow.

Algorithm 2 Sequential Importance Sampling with Resampling. Source: Author.

Require: Knowledge base \mathcal{K}

- 1: Query Q
- 2: Tempering ladder $\{\alpha_\ell\}_{\ell=0}^L$
- 3: Number of particles N

Ensure: Estimated expected truth degree $\hat{\mu}_N$

- 4: Initialize particles $\{I^{(k)}\}_{k=1}^N \sim \text{Unif}([0, 1]^{|A_\Sigma|})$
- 5: Initialize weights $W^{(k)} \leftarrow 1$ for all k
- 6: **for** $\ell = 1$ to L **do**

▷ Reweight

- 7: **for** $k = 1$ to N **do**
- 8: $w_\ell^{(k)} \leftarrow \exp((\alpha_\ell - \alpha_{\ell-1}) \cdot E(I^{(k)}; \mathbf{w}))$
- 9: $W^{(k)} \leftarrow W^{(k)} \cdot w_\ell^{(k)}$

▷ Resample (optional)

- 10: Normalise weights: $\bar{W}^{(k)} \leftarrow W^{(k)} / \sum_j W^{(j)}$

- 11: Compute ESS: $\text{ESS} \leftarrow (\sum_k (\bar{W}^{(k)})^2)^{-1}$

- 12: **if** $\text{ESS} < N/2$ **then**

- 13: Resample particles $\{I^{(k)}\}$ according to $\{\bar{W}^{(k)}\}$

- 14: Reset weights: $W^{(k)} \leftarrow 1$ for all k

▷ Move (MCMC targeting P_ℓ)

- 15: **for** $k = 1$ to N **do**

- 16: Apply MCMC kernel K_ℓ to $I^{(k)}$

- 17: Compute estimate

$$\hat{\mu}_N \leftarrow \frac{\sum_k I^{(k)}(Q) W^{(k)}}{\sum_k W^{(k)}}$$

return $\hat{\mu}_N$

4.4.3 Resampling and MCMC Moves

Pure sequential importance sampling suffers from weight degeneracy: as steps accumulate, weight variance grows until a single particle dominates. Two techniques address this, and together they make power sampling practical for complex knowledge bases.

Weight Degeneracy and the Curse of Dimensionality As particles traverse the temperature ladder, their weights diverge: those in steeply rising energy regions accumulate large weights; the rest dwindle. After L steps, a handful of “lucky” particles may carry nearly all the weight, leaving the effective sample size as low as 1. In high-dimensional interpretation spaces the problem is acute—the probability that any given particle falls in the target’s high-probability region shrinks exponentially with dimension.

Resampling: Pruning and Duplication Resampling: When the *effective sample size* (ESS) falls below a threshold, resample particles according to their weights and reset all weights to 1. This eliminates low-weight particles and duplicates high-weight particles.

Definition 4.14 (Effective Sample Size). *The effective sample size is:*

$$ESS = \frac{(\sum_k W^{(k)})^2}{\sum_k (W^{(k)})^2}$$

ESS ranges from 1 (one particle dominates) to N (all weights equal).

The effective sample size provides a scalar diagnostic for weight degeneracy. When weights are perfectly uniform, $ESS = N$, indicating that all N particles contribute equally. When a single weight dominates, ESS approaches 1, indicating that only one particle matters. A common resampling trigger is $ESS < N/2$: when fewer than half the particles are effectively contributing, we resample.

Resampling is implemented by drawing N new particles from the current particle set with probabilities proportional to normalised weights $\bar{W}^{(k)} = W^{(k)} / \sum_j W^{(j)}$. Multinomial resampling draws each of the N new particles independently, while stratified or systematic resampling uses deterministic schemes that reduce the variance of the resampling step itself. After resampling, all particles have equal weight, so we reset $W^{(k)} \leftarrow 1$ for all k .

The critical property of resampling is that it preserves the distribution: the empirical distribution of the particle set (treating particles as point masses with weights) remains an approximation to P_ℓ before and after resampling. What changes is the support of the approximation—low-weight particles are eliminated, high-weight particles are duplicated—which concentrates computational effort on regions where the target distribution places significant mass.

MCMC Moves: Diversification and Exploration MCMC Moves: After resampling, apply Markov chain Monte Carlo transitions that leave the current distribution P_ℓ invariant. This diversifies the particle population without changing the target distribution.

Definition 4.15 (Metropolis-Hastings Move). *A single-site Metropolis-Hastings move for atom A proposes a new truth degree $I'(A) \sim \text{Uniform}(0, 1)$ and accepts with*

probability:

$$\min \left(1, \frac{\exp(\alpha_\ell E(I'; \mathbf{w}))}{\exp(\alpha_\ell E(I; \mathbf{w}))} \right) = \min (1, \exp(\alpha_\ell (E(I') - E(I))))$$

where I' agrees with I except at atom A .

Resampling and MCMC moves work in tandem: resampling concentrates effort on high-probability regions, while MCMC restores diversity among the resulting duplicates. After resampling, many particles share the same high-weight ancestor. MCMC transitions “jitter” each one to a nearby interpretation, preserving P_ℓ while eliminating redundancy. The Metropolis–Hastings kernel proposes a random change to one atom’s truth degree and accepts with probability $\min(1, \exp(\alpha_\ell \Delta E))$ —energy-increasing moves are always accepted; energy-decreasing moves incur a penalty enforcing detailed balance.

The current implementation performs $M = 2|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma|$ single-site updates per particle per level with uniform $[0, 1]$ proposals (symmetric, simplifying the acceptance ratio). Gaussian or gradient-guided proposals could improve mixing at the cost of step-size tuning.

4.4.4 Properties of Power Sampling

Theorem 4.3 (Consistency of Power Sampling). *The power sampling estimator $\hat{\mu}_N$ is consistent: $\hat{\mu}_N \xrightarrow{P} \mu_Q$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$, provided:*

1. *The MCMC kernels K_ℓ are ergodic with respect to P_ℓ .*
2. *The temperature steps are finite: $L < \infty$.*
3. *The resampling is unbiased (e.g., multinomial or systematic).*

Proof sketch. Under these conditions, sequential Monte Carlo theory establishes that the particle approximation to P_ℓ converges to the true distribution as $N \rightarrow \infty$ for each ℓ . Since $P_L = P$, the estimator converges to the true expectation. \square

Variance of the power sampling estimator depends on the temperature schedule and MCMC quality. Finer schedules reduce variance at higher computational cost; the best schedule depends on the energy function’s structure and is usually set empirically.

Convergence Diagnostics and Adaptive Scheduling Theorem 4.3 guarantees asymptotic convergence, but practical inference must diagnose convergence for finite samples and adapt parameters when convergence is slow. LIMEN-AI provides several diagnostic tools:

The ESS trajectory is the primary diagnostic: if ESS drops below $N/10$ at any level, more particles or finer temperature spacing is needed. The weight coefficient of variation at each level should stay below 1 (values above 3 indicate excessive variance). MCMC acceptance rates should sit in the range $[0.2, 0.5]$; rates outside this range signal that proposals are either too aggressive or too conservative. The most reliable diagnostic, however, is running power sampling R times with different seeds and checking inter-run agreement: a coefficient of variation below 0.1 across runs is strong evidence of convergence.

For LIMEN-AI applications requiring certified accuracy—such as safety-critical systems subject to regulatory audit—we recommend using the multiple-run diagnostic with $R = 10$ independent runs and reporting both the mean estimate $\bar{\mu} = \frac{1}{R} \sum_r \hat{\mu}_N^{(r)}$ and the inter-run standard error $\text{SE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{R(R-1)} \sum_r (\hat{\mu}_N^{(r)} - \bar{\mu})^2}$. This provides a robust assessment of inferential uncertainty that accounts for both Monte Carlo variance and potential convergence failures.

4.5 Variance Analysis

Convergence in the limit is guaranteed; the practical question is how fast. Estimator variance governs sample complexity—the number of draws needed for a target accuracy—and depends on proposal–target match. The variance formulas derived below translate into concrete guidance on proposal selection, temperature scheduling, and sample budgets.

4.5.1 Variance of Importance Sampling

Variance Decomposition and the Role of Proposal Quality Because the self-normalised estimator is a ratio of two averages, its variance has a complex structure. A precise formula requires second-order delta method expansions; an approximation suffices for understanding the key dependencies.

Theorem 4.4 (Variance of Self-Normalised Estimator). *For the self-normalised*

importance sampling estimator with N samples:

$$\text{Var}[\hat{\mu}_N] \approx \frac{1}{N} (\sigma_Q^2 + \mu_Q^2 \cdot \chi^2(P\|R))$$

where $\sigma_Q^2 = \text{Var}_P[I(Q)]$ is the variance of the query under the target, and $\chi^2(P\|R) = \int \frac{(P(I)-R(I))^2}{R(I)} dI$ is the chi-squared divergence between P and R .

Proof sketch. The result follows from a delta method expansion of the ratio estimator. The first term σ_Q^2/N is the variance that would remain even with perfect importance sampling (when $P = R$). The second term reflects the additional variance due to the mismatch between P and R . \square

Two sources of uncertainty are separated. The term σ_Q^2/N is irreducible—even direct sampling from P would need $O(\sigma_Q^2/\epsilon^2)$ draws for additive error ϵ . The term $\mu_Q^2\chi^2(P\|R)/N$ penalises proposal mismatch. When P and R are close, χ^2 is small. When P concentrates mass where R is thin, χ^2 can be exponentially large, rare samples receive enormous weights, and variance explodes.

Corollary 4.1 (Optimal Proposal). *The variance is minimised when $R(I) \propto |I(Q) - \mu_Q| \cdot P(I)$, which concentrates sampling on interpretations where the query deviates most from its mean.*

The optimal proposal is unavailable in practice because it depends on μ_Q —the quantity being estimated. Proposals that approximate the target (such as tempered proposals) nonetheless outperform the uniform distribution.

4.5.2 Sample Complexity

Definition 4.16 (Sample Complexity). *The sample complexity for estimating μ_Q to relative error ϵ with probability $1 - \delta$ is the minimum N such that:*

$$P(|\hat{\mu}_N - \mu_Q| > \epsilon\mu_Q) < \delta$$

Sample complexity gives concrete guidance where asymptotic guarantees do not: for a given error tolerance and confidence level, how many draws are enough?

Figure 36: Estimator standard deviation as a function of sample size for different proposal distributions. The standard deviation decays as $1/\sqrt{N}$ (characteristic of Monte Carlo methods), but the coefficient depends on the chi-squared divergence between target and proposal. Good proposals (low χ^2) require fewer samples to achieve a given accuracy than poor proposals (high χ^2). Source: Author.

Theorem 4.5 (Sample Complexity Bound). *For the self-normalised importance sampling estimator:*

$$N = O\left(\frac{\sigma_Q^2 + \mu_Q^2 \chi^2(P\|R)}{\epsilon^2 \mu_Q^2} \cdot \log(1/\delta)\right)$$

samples suffice to achieve relative error ϵ with probability $1 - \delta$.

Sample complexity depends critically on $\chi^2(P\|R)$: large divergence demands many samples; small divergence allows fewer. The logarithmic dependence on δ is standard for concentration inequalities—each additional “nine” of confidence (99% to 99.9%) costs only a constant factor. The quadratic dependence on $1/\epsilon$ is inherent to Monte Carlo: halving the error quadruples the sample budget.

For LIMEN-AI applications, typical parameter values are $\epsilon = 0.1$ (10% relative error) and $\delta = 0.05$ (95% confidence). If $\chi^2(P\|R_{\text{uniform}}) = O(e^C)$ for some constant C related to the knowledge base structure, then the required sample size scales as $N = O(e^C/\epsilon^2) = O(100e^C)$. This exponential dependence on knowledge base complexity motivates the use of power sampling with carefully chosen temperature schedules to keep χ^2 under control at each step. Figure 36 visualises how the estimator standard deviation decays with sample size for proposals of varying quality.

The $1/\sqrt{N}$ decay visible in Figure 36 confirms that Monte Carlo variance can always be reduced by drawing more samples, yet the multiplicative constant—governed

by the chi-squared divergence—determines whether hundreds or millions of samples are needed for a given accuracy. In practice, a well-chosen proposal distribution can shrink the required sample budget by orders of magnitude, making the difference between a feasible real-time query and an intractable computation.

4.5.3 Effective Sample Size as a Diagnostic

The effective sample size offers a practical diagnostic for importance sampling quality.

Proposition 4.3 (ESS and Variance). *The effective sample size satisfies:*

$$ESS \approx \frac{N}{1 + \chi^2(P\|R)}$$

High ESS (close to N) indicates that the proposal is well-matched to the target; low ESS indicates poor matching.

A rule of thumb: ESS should reach at least $N/2$ for reliable estimates; below that threshold, either more samples or a better proposal is needed. ESS measures how many truly independent samples the weighted set is worth— N when all weights are equal, as few as 1 when one weight dominates. Because it is observable directly from the weights, requiring no knowledge of P , R , or χ^2 , it serves as a real-time diagnostic. When ESS drops below $N/2$, the system can increase the sample count, refine the proposal, or (in power sampling) insert additional temperature levels.

For LIMEN-AI inference using uniform proposal on a knowledge base with m formulas and average weight magnitude \bar{w} , empirical studies suggest that $ESS \approx N \exp(-\bar{w}m/4)$, indicating exponential decay with knowledge base size and strength. Power sampling with $L \approx 2\bar{w}m$ temperature levels maintains $ESS > N/2$ at each step, keeping the algorithm efficient.

4.6 Explanation Trace Generation

Regulated applications require more than a numerical prediction: auditors, domain experts, and affected individuals need to know *why* the system reached its conclusion. Because the energy function decomposes additively into per-rule contributions, the sampling process can be instrumented—at negligible extra cost—to record each rule’s role in the result.

4.6.1 Traces from Samples

The additive structure of the energy function makes rule-level attribution a natural byproduct of sampling rather than a post-hoc approximation.

The Energy Gradient Perspective To understand how traces arise, recall that the energy function is a weighted sum:

$$E(I; \mathbf{w}) = \sum_{i=1}^m w_i \cdot \sigma(\varphi_i, I)$$

where m is the number of formulas, w_i is the weight of formula φ_i , and $\sigma(\varphi_i, I) \in [0, 1]$ is its satisfaction degree under interpretation I (via the Łukasiewicz semantics of Chapter 3). Linearity in the satisfaction degrees lets us attribute responsibility for the total energy to individual formulas: formula i contributes exactly $w_i \sigma(\varphi_i, I)$.

Consider the gradient of the expected truth degree $\mu_Q = \mathbb{E}_P[I(Q)]$ with respect to a rule weight w_i . By the chain rule:

$$\frac{\partial \mu_Q}{\partial w_i} = \mathbb{E}_P \left[I(Q) \cdot \frac{\partial \log P(I)}{\partial w_i} \right] = \mathbb{E}_P [I(Q) \cdot \sigma(\varphi_i, I)]$$

A positive gradient means that formulas with high satisfaction are correlated with high query values—rule φ_i “supports” the query. A negative gradient means the rule works against it. Magnitude indicates relationship strength.

Importance sampling provides an empirical estimate of this gradient:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\mu}_N}{\partial w_i} = \frac{\sum_k I^{(k)}(Q) \cdot \sigma(\varphi_i, I^{(k)}) \cdot W^{(k)}}{\sum_k W^{(k)}}$$

This weighted average of formula φ_i ’s satisfaction, weighted by query value and importance weight, is recorded in the explanation trace for every formula, giving a complete decomposition of the estimated truth degree.

Definition 4.17 (Explanation Trace). *An explanation trace for a sample $I^{(k)}$ is a tuple:*

$$\tau^{(k)} = \left\{ (i, \varphi_i, w_i, s_i^{(k)}, c_i^{(k)}) : i = 1, \dots, m \right\}$$

where:

- i is the formula index

- φ_i is the formula
- w_i is the weight
- $s_i^{(k)} = \bar{I}^{(k)}(\varphi_i)$ is the satisfaction degree under sample $I^{(k)}$
- $c_i^{(k)} = w_i \cdot s_i^{(k)}$ is the contribution to the energy

Each trace records, for a single sampled interpretation, how much each rule was satisfied and how much that satisfaction contributed to the total energy. Large positive contributions $c_i^{(k)}$ make the interpretation more probable; small or negative contributions (possible only when $w_i < 0$, i.e., soft penalties) make it less probable.

A per-sample trace is a snapshot for one interpretation. An aggregate summary across all samples, reflecting the overall inference result, is obtained by weighted averaging.

Definition 4.18 (Aggregate Trace). *The aggregate trace across all samples is:*

$$\bar{\tau} = \{(i, \varphi_i, w_i, \bar{s}_i, \bar{c}_i) : i = 1, \dots, m\}$$

where $\bar{s}_i = \sum_k W^{(k)} s_i^{(k)} / \sum_k W^{(k)}$ is the weighted average satisfaction degree and $\bar{c}_i = w_i \cdot \bar{s}_i$ is the weighted average contribution.

Rules with large positive \bar{c}_i support interpretations where the query has high truth degree; rules with large negative \bar{c}_i work against them. The aggregate trace is LIMEN-AI’s primary explanation artefact. When a user asks “Why is this transaction suspicious with truth degree 0.78?”, the system returns the trace sorted by $|\bar{c}_i|$, showing the top- K rules ($K = 5$ – 10 for readability). Each rule is annotated with its average satisfaction \bar{s}_i , letting the user see both which rules matter (weight w_i) and how strongly they fired in the sampled interpretations (\bar{s}_i).

From Satisfaction Degrees to Groundings For first-order rules with free variables, $\sigma(\varphi_i, I)$ aggregates (typically averages or maximises) over all groundings. Maximally informative explanations require drilling down from the aggregate to identify the most active groundings.

Let $\varphi_i(\mathbf{x})$ be a formula with free variables \mathbf{x} , and let $G_i = \{g_1, \dots, g_{n_i}\}$ be its set

of groundings. The satisfaction degree is:

$$\sigma(\varphi_i, I) = \frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{g \in G_i} \sigma(g, I)$$

(assuming average aggregation; maximum aggregation would use $\max_{g \in G_i}$ instead). For each grounding g , we can compute its contribution to the overall formula satisfaction. Groundings with high $\sigma(g, I)$ are the "evidence instances" that support the formula.

In the LIMEN-AI trace structure (implemented in `src/limen/inference.py`, v0.3.0), the aggregate trace optionally includes a `top_groundings` field for each formula, listing the K groundings with highest average weighted satisfaction. This allows explanations like: "Rule 3 (weight 2.0): `failedLogin(u,h) → suspicious(u)` was satisfied with degree 0.85 on average. Top groundings: `failedLogin(alice, srv1)` (0.92), `failedLogin(bob, srv2)` (0.81)." Such grounding-level detail is critical for cybersecurity, legal, and financial applications where auditors need to trace decisions back to specific entities and events.

4.6.2 Representative Samples

Identifying representative samples that illustrate the reasoning strengthens explanations.

Definition 4.19 (Representative Sample). *A sample $I^{(k)}$ is representative if its weighted contribution $I^{(k)}(Q) \cdot W^{(k)}$ to the estimator exceeds a threshold. Formally, define the contribution:*

$$C^{(k)} = I^{(k)}(Q) \cdot W^{(k)} / \sum_j W^{(j)}$$

and select samples with $C^{(k)} > \theta/N$ for some threshold factor θ .

These are the interpretations that contribute most to the expected truth degree; examining their traces reveals which rules drive the inference.

Algorithm 3 Inference with Explanation Trace Generation. Source: Author.

Require: Knowledge base \mathcal{K}

- 1: Query Q
- 2: Proposal distribution R
- 3: Number of samples N
- 4: Selection threshold θ

Ensure: Estimated truth degree $\hat{\mu}_N$

- 5: Aggregate explanation trace $\bar{\tau}$
- 6: Representative samples set \mathcal{R}
- 7: Initialize accumulators: $S \leftarrow 0, W \leftarrow 0$
- 8: Initialize trace sums: $\bar{s}_i \leftarrow 0$ for all formulas φ_i
- 9: Initialize representative set: $\mathcal{R} \leftarrow \emptyset$
- 10: **for** $k = 1$ to N **do**
- 11: Sample interpretation $I^{(k)} \sim R$
- 12: Compute energy and weight: $E^{(k)} \leftarrow E(I^{(k)}; \mathbf{w}), \tilde{W}^{(k)} \leftarrow \exp(E^{(k)})/R(I^{(k)})$
- 13: Evaluate query: $q^{(k)} \leftarrow I^{(k)}(Q)$

▷ Accumulate for estimator
- 14: $S \leftarrow S + q^{(k)} \cdot \tilde{W}^{(k)}$
- 15: $W \leftarrow W + \tilde{W}^{(k)}$

▷ Accumulate explanation trace
- 16: **for** each formula φ_i **do**
- 17: $s_i^{(k)} \leftarrow I^{(k)}(\varphi_i)$
- 18: $\bar{s}_i \leftarrow \bar{s}_i + \tilde{W}^{(k)} \cdot s_i^{(k)}$

▷ Representative sample selection
- 19: **if** $q^{(k)} \cdot \tilde{W}^{(k)} > \theta \cdot W/k$ **then**
- 20: Add tuple $(I^{(k)}, q^{(k)}, \{s_i^{(k)}\})$ to \mathcal{R}
- 21: Compute estimate: $\hat{\mu}_N \leftarrow S/W$
- 22: Normalise explanation traces:

$$\bar{s}_i \leftarrow \bar{s}_i/W, \quad \bar{c}_i \leftarrow w_i \cdot \bar{s}_i$$
- 23: Construct aggregate trace:

$$\bar{\tau} \leftarrow \{(i, \varphi_i, w_i, \bar{s}_i, \bar{c}_i)\}$$

return $\hat{\mu}_N, \bar{\tau}, \mathcal{R}$

4.6.3 From Traces to Explanations

Traces from Algorithm 3 become human-readable explanations in three steps: select the rules with largest $|\bar{c}_i|$; for first-order rules, drill down to the most active groundings; assemble a natural-language narrative—e.g., “The high truth degree for Q is driven by rule φ_3 (weight 2.5, satisfaction 0.85), strongly satisfied because atoms A_1 and A_2 have truth degrees 0.9 and 0.8.” Predicate names and rule descriptions in the knowledge base supply the domain-specific vocabulary. Figure 37 depicts the full human-in-the-loop workflow, from inference through explanation review to decision

Figure 37: Human-in-the-loop inference workflow with decision contestation. The explanation trace $\bar{\tau}$ enables meaningful human oversight by exposing the rules and groundings that drove the inference. Users can accept the decision or reject it, with rejections logged for audit and fed back to improve the knowledge base (via weight updates or rule revision). Source: Author.

contestation and audit logging.

The workflow depicted in Figure 37 directly operationalises the human oversight provisions of Article 14 of the EU AI Act: explanation traces give reviewers the information they need to form an independent judgement, the contestation path ensures that automated decisions can be overridden, and the audit log preserves a complete record of every override for subsequent regulatory inspection. Together, these mechanisms embed meaningful human agency into the inference pipeline rather than relegating oversight to a superficial approval stamp.

4.7 Pedagogical Examples

The examples below are small enough to compute by hand yet large enough to exhibit the essential mechanics: importance weights correcting for proposal mismatch, self-normalisation removing dependence on Z , and explanation traces decomposing a prediction into per-rule contributions.

4.7.1 Illustrative Example: Two-Atom System

Consider a simple system with two atoms A and B and a single implication rule.

Knowledge base: $\mathcal{K} = \{(A \rightarrow B, w = 2.0)\}$

Query: $Q = B$

Energy function: $E(a, b) = 2.0 \cdot \min(1, 1 - a + b)$ where $a = I(A)$ and $b = I(B)$.

Discretized analysis: For pedagogical clarity, consider a coarse discretization with $a, b \in \{0, 0.5, 1\}$. The energy values are:

$E(a, b)$	$b = 0$	$b = 0.5$	$b = 1$
$a = 0$	2.0	2.0	2.0
$a = 0.5$	1.0	2.0	2.0
$a = 1$	0.0	1.0	2.0

The energy is highest (2.0) when the implication is fully satisfied, which occurs when $a \leq b$ or when $1 - a + b \geq 1$, i.e., $b \geq a$.

Unnormalised probabilities: $\tilde{P}(a, b) = \exp(E(a, b))$:

$\tilde{P}(a, b)$	$b = 0$	$b = 0.5$	$b = 1$
$a = 0$	$e^2 \approx 7.39$	$e^2 \approx 7.39$	$e^2 \approx 7.39$
$a = 0.5$	$e^1 \approx 2.72$	$e^2 \approx 7.39$	$e^2 \approx 7.39$
$a = 1$	$e^0 = 1.00$	$e^1 \approx 2.72$	$e^2 \approx 7.39$

Partition function: $Z = \sum_{a,b} \tilde{P}(a, b) \approx 7.39 \cdot 6 + 2.72 \cdot 2 + 1.00 \approx 50.8$

Expected truth degree of B :

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_B &= \frac{\sum_{a,b} b \cdot \tilde{P}(a, b)}{Z} = \frac{0 \cdot (7.39 + 2.72 + 1.00) + 0.5 \cdot (7.39 + 7.39 + 2.72)}{50.8} \\ &\quad + \frac{1 \cdot (7.39 + 7.39 + 7.39)}{50.8} \\ &= \frac{0 + 8.75 + 22.17}{50.8} \approx \frac{30.92}{50.8} \approx 0.61 \end{aligned}$$

The expected truth degree of B is approximately 0.61, reflecting that the distribution favours interpretations where B is high (which satisfies the implication more easily).

Importance sampling estimate: With uniform proposal $R(a, b) = 1/9$ over the 9 grid points:

a	b	$q = b$	\tilde{P}	$\tilde{W} = 9\tilde{P}$	$q \cdot \tilde{W}$
0	0	0	7.39	66.5	0
0	0.5	0.5	7.39	66.5	33.2
0	1	1	7.39	66.5	66.5
0.5	0	0	2.72	24.5	0
0.5	0.5	0.5	7.39	66.5	33.2
0.5	1	1	7.39	66.5	66.5
1	0	0	1.00	9.0	0
1	0.5	0.5	2.72	24.5	12.2
1	1	1	7.39	66.5	66.5

$$\sum \tilde{W} = 457.0, \sum q \cdot \tilde{W} = 278.1, \hat{\mu} = 278.1/457.0 \approx 0.61.$$

The importance sampling estimate matches the exact calculation.

The uniform proposal assigns equal probability to all nine grid points, but importance weights automatically upweight interpretations satisfying the implication. Self-normalisation handles the unknown Z without separate computation. The expected truth degree $\mu_B \approx 0.61$, above the uniform average of 0.5, reflects the knowledge base's preference for high- B interpretations. Continuous inference samples from $[0, 1]^2$ rather than a discrete grid, but the procedure is identical: evaluate energy, compute weight, accumulate, normalise.

4.7.2 Illustrative Example: Cybersecurity Scenario

Consider a cybersecurity knowledge base with the following rules:

1. ($w_1 = 2.0$): $\text{failedLogin}(u, h) \rightarrow \text{suspicious}(u)$
2. ($w_2 = 1.5$): $\text{suspicious}(u) \wedge \text{accessedResource}(u, r) \rightarrow \text{raiseAlert}(u, h)$
3. ($w_3 = -0.5$): $\text{suspicious}(u)$ (soft prior against suspicion)

Evidence: $I(\text{failedLogin}(\text{alice}, \text{srv1})) = 0.9$, $I(\text{accessedResource}(\text{alice}, \text{db1})) = 0.8$

Query: $Q = \text{raiseAlert}(\text{alice}, \text{srv1})$

For a single sample with $I(\text{suspicious}(\text{alice})) = 0.75$ and $I(\text{raiseAlert}(\text{alice}, \text{srv1})) = 0.6$:

Rule 1 satisfaction:

$$I(\text{failedLogin}(\text{alice}, \text{srv1}) \rightarrow \text{suspicious}(\text{alice})) = \min(1, 1 - 0.9 + 0.75) = 0.85$$

Rule 2 satisfaction:

$$I(\text{suspicious}(\text{alice}) \wedge \text{accessedResource}(\text{alice}, \text{db1})) = \max(0, 0.75 + 0.8 - 1) = 0.55$$

$$I(\text{rule 2 grounding}) = \min(1, 1 - 0.55 + 0.6) = 1.0$$

Rule 3 satisfaction: $I(\text{suspicious}(\text{alice})) = 0.75$ **Energy:**

$$E = 2.0 \cdot 0.85 + 1.5 \cdot 1.0 + (-0.5) \cdot 0.75 = 1.7 + 1.5 - 0.375 = 2.825$$

Explanation trace:

- Rule 1 contributes $c_1 = 2.0 \cdot 0.85 = 1.7$ (positive: supports high energy)
- Rule 2 contributes $c_2 = 1.5 \cdot 1.0 = 1.5$ (positive: supports high energy)
- Rule 3 contributes $c_3 = -0.5 \cdot 0.75 = -0.375$ (negative: penalises suspicion)

The trace shows that rules 1 and 2 support raising an alert for Alice, while rule 3 provides a mild counterweight reflecting the prior that most users are not suspicious.

Multi-Sample Inference and Trace Aggregation To illustrate how importance sampling aggregates evidence across multiple samples, consider running the inference with $N = 3$ samples drawn from a uniform proposal:

Sample k	$I(\text{sus.})$	$I(\text{alert})$	$E^{(k)}$	$\tilde{W}^{(k)}$	$q^{(k)} \cdot \tilde{W}^{(k)}$
1	0.75	0.60	2.825	16.89	10.13
2	0.40	0.30	0.575	1.78	0.53
3	0.90	0.85	3.600	36.60	31.11
				$\sum = 55.27$	$\sum = 41.77$

The self-normalised estimator gives:

$$\hat{\mu}_{\text{alert}} = \frac{41.77}{55.27} \approx 0.76$$

Sample 3, with high satisfaction of both evidence atoms and the query, receives the largest weight ($\tilde{W}^{(3)} = 36.60$) and dominates. Sample 2, where suspicion and alert values are low, carries the smallest weight ($\tilde{W}^{(2)} = 1.78$) and contributes minimally. Importance sampling thus focuses automatically on interpretations consistent with the knowledge base.

The aggregate trace across these three samples would be:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{s}_1 &= \frac{0.85 \cdot 16.89 + 0.65 \cdot 1.78 + 0.95 \cdot 36.60}{55.27} \approx 0.90 \\ \bar{c}_1 &= 2.0 \cdot 0.90 = 1.80 \\ \bar{s}_2 &= \frac{1.0 \cdot 16.89 + 0.85 \cdot 1.78 + 1.0 \cdot 36.60}{55.27} \approx 0.99 \\ \bar{c}_2 &= 1.5 \cdot 0.99 = 1.49 \\ \bar{s}_3 &= \frac{0.75 \cdot 16.89 + 0.40 \cdot 1.78 + 0.90 \cdot 36.60}{55.27} \approx 0.83 \\ \bar{c}_3 &= -0.5 \cdot 0.83 = -0.42\end{aligned}$$

A generated explanation might read: “The system recommends raising an alert for Alice with confidence 0.76. Rule 1 (contribution 1.80) infers suspicion from failed logins; Rule 2 (contribution 1.49) links suspicious behaviour and resource access to alerts. Rule 3 provides a weak countervailing prior (−0.42), but the evidence strongly supports the alert.” Such explanations are mathematically grounded—derived directly from the sampling process—and semantically meaningful, phrased in the domain-specific vocabulary, satisfying the dual requirements of statistical correctness and regulatory transparency.

Computational Complexity and Scalability Importance sampling inference costs $O(N \cdot m \cdot |\mathcal{G}|)$, where N is the sample count, m the number of formulas, and $|\mathcal{G}|$ the average number of groundings per formula. Power sampling multiplies this by the number of temperature levels L and MCMC steps per level M , yielding $O(N \cdot L \cdot M \cdot m \cdot |\mathcal{G}|)$. With $N = 1000$, $L = 20$, $M = 2|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma|$, and GPU-accelerated energy computation, inference completes in seconds for knowledge bases of 10–100 formulas and hundreds of ground atoms—fast enough for interactive decision support.

4.7.3 Empirical Validation of Sampling Algorithms

The four inference algorithms developed in this chapter—simple Monte Carlo, importance sampling, power sampling, and Langevin MCMC—are implemented in the LIMEN-AI library and validated against a synthetic knowledge base benchmark. The benchmark executes each sampler five times under identical conditions, recording expectation estimates, standard deviations across runs, and effective sample size percentages. The empirical results confirm the theoretical predictions of the preceding sections: importance sampling achieves substantially lower variance than simple Monte Carlo, consistent with the $\chi^2(P\|R)$ analysis of Theorem 4.4, while power sampling attains the highest effective sample size, corroborating the tempering analysis of Section 4.4. Langevin MCMC, which exploits gradient information for proposal generation within the $[0, 1]$ box, offers complementary exploration characteristics that prove advantageous in multimodal energy landscapes. Full benchmark details, including the sampler configurations and reproducible scripts, are available in the LIMEN-AI codebase.

4.8 Summary

The inference machinery now in place turns LIMEN-AI’s mathematical framework into a computational tool. Expected truth degrees, conditional expectations, MAP interpretations, and ϵ -optimal sets define the inference targets; exact computation is intractable beyond toy sizes. Self-normalised importance sampling yields consistent estimators without the partition function, and power sampling with tempering ladders, resampling, and MCMC moves extends them to the sharply peaked distributions of real knowledge bases. Variance analysis characterises sample complexity via $\chi^2(P\|R)$, giving concrete guidance on sample budgets. Explanation traces decompose each prediction into per-rule contributions at negligible extra cost, meeting regulatory transparency requirements.

The next chapter addresses the complementary problem: learning the knowledge base itself through inductive rule discovery.

Implementation and Practical Considerations The algorithms are implemented in `src/limen/inference.py` (v0.3.0), using PyTorch for energy evaluation and automatic differentiation. The default configuration uses a geometric temperature

schedule $\alpha_\ell = (\ell/L)^2$ with $L = 20$ levels, resamples when $\text{ESS} < N/2$ (typically 3–5 times per run), performs $M = 2|\mathcal{A}_\Sigma|$ single-site Metropolis–Hastings updates per particle per level, and starts with $N = 1000$ particles (scalable to 5000 for larger domains). Diagnostic outputs—ESS trajectory, MCMC acceptance rate, weight coefficient of variation—let users detect ESS collapse or poor mixing and adjust parameters accordingly.

Connection to Formal Verification Three properties from Chapter 3, all mechanically verified in Isabelle/HOL, underpin the algorithms. Energy boundedness (`energy_bounded`, Appendix B) keeps MCMC transitions stable and importance weights well-behaved. Satisfaction monotonicity (`luk_and_monotonic_left` and related lemmas, Appendix B) ensures smooth weight variation along MCMC trajectories, ruling out pathological oscillations. Almost-everywhere differentiability enables gradient-based diagnostics and opens the door to gradient-informed proposals (the current implementation uses gradient-free Metropolis–Hastings). These verified properties give LIMEN-AI inference robustness guarantees that heuristic samplers lack.

Bridge to Chapter 5 All of the above assumes a given knowledge base. Manually writing weighted rules is laborious and error-prone. Inductive rule discovery, the subject of Chapter 5, learns weighted formulas from data by combining LLM-proposed candidates with the inference and gradient machinery developed here, completing the LIMEN-AI pipeline from data to prediction to explanation.

5 Inductive Rule Discovery

Chapters 3 and 4 gave LIMEN-AI its mathematical foundations and inference machinery. A complementary question remains: how can new weighted rules be discovered from data without sacrificing the explicit logical structure that supports interpretability (Abdur Rahman et al., 2023; Muda et al., 2023; Schulte and Khosravi, 2012)?

Conventional machine learning encodes patterns in opaque numerical parameters (Bryda and Baker, 2024; Villamil et al., 2023). LIMEN-AI instead learns explicit logical formulas with associated weights—formulas that domain experts can read, critique, and revise (Gonçalves et al., 2025). Because the learned rules enter the knowledge base directly, they stay open to inspection and modification, a property central to the regulatory compliance goals of the framework.

Three contributions anchor the work that follows: template-based rule generation to constrain the search space, a differentiable scoring function under Łukasiewicz semantics that turns weight optimisation into a convex problem (exploiting the piecewise linearity verified in Appendix B), and a proof that the resulting learning algorithm converges to the global optimum.

5.1 The Induction Problem

Neurosymbolic induction produces first-order formulas that remain readable after training, rather than opaque weight matrices. The setup is supervised: given a knowledge base, a target predicate, and sets of positive and negative groundings, the goal is to find weighted rules that generalise from those examples.

5.1.1 Learning from Labelled Examples

Given a knowledge base with existing predicates and facts, the task is to discover new rules that explain observed patterns in the data.

Definition 5.1 (Label Set). *A label set $\mathcal{L} = (\mathcal{L}^+, \mathcal{L}^-)$ for a target predicate p of arity k consists of positive examples $\mathcal{L}^+ \subseteq \mathcal{C}^k$, which are tuples for which p should have a high truth degree, and negative examples $\mathcal{L}^- \subseteq \mathcal{C}^k$, which are tuples for which p should have a low truth degree.*

Definition 5.2 (Induction Task). *Given a knowledge base \mathcal{K} , a target predicate p , and a label set \mathcal{L} , the induction task is to find weighted formulas $\{(\varphi_j, w_j)\}$ such that each φ_j has p as its head (consequent), and adding these formulas to \mathcal{K} increases the truth degree of positive examples while decreasing the truth degree of negative examples.*

Put differently, induction looks for rules that separate positive from negative groundings by exploiting relational structure already in the knowledge base.

5.1.2 Challenges of Rule Discovery

Rule discovery faces three intertwined obstacles. The **search space** is combinatorially large: candidate formulas grow exponentially with the predicate count and allowed formula depth, so exhaustive enumeration is out of the question. Even within that vast space, only a fraction of syntactically valid formulas are **semantically coherent**—rules should encode genuine domain patterns, not arbitrary predicate combinations. Compounding both difficulties, finding the optimal **weight** for a promising formula is nontrivial because rules interact through the energy function; a rule helpful on its own may turn redundant or harmful alongside others. LIMEN-AI responds with template-based generation (to constrain the search space) and differentiable scoring (to enable efficient weight optimisation).

5.2 Template-Based Rule Generation

The candidate space grows as $O(|\mathcal{P}|^n)$ for chain templates of length n , making unconstrained search impractical even for modest vocabularies. Templates tame this explosion by encoding structural patterns—chains, stars, cyclic motifs—as schemas with placeholder predicates and arity constraints. The hypothesis space shrinks by orders of magnitude, yet the relational structures most likely to carry genuine domain regularities survive.

5.2.1 Rule Templates

A rule template fixes a structural pattern that every candidate rule must match, bounding the search space without forfeiting expressiveness.

Definition 5.3 (Rule Template). *A rule template T is a formula schema with placeholder predicate symbols P_1, \dots, P_r . Each placeholder has an associated arity*

constraint. The template may also specify constraints on variable sharing across placeholders.

Definition 5.4 (Template Instantiation). *Given a template T with placeholders P_1, \dots, P_r and a knowledge base \mathcal{K} with predicates \mathcal{P} , an instantiation of T is a formula obtained by:*

1. *Substituting predicates from \mathcal{P} for each placeholder, respecting arity constraints.*
2. *Instantiating the target predicate position with the target predicate p .*

The set of all instantiations is denoted $T[\mathcal{P}, p]$.

5.2.2 Common Template Types

Three template families cover the most common relational patterns.

Definition 5.5 (Single-Body Template). *A single-body template generates rules of the form:*

$$P_1(x_1, \dots, x_k) \rightarrow p(y_1, \dots, y_m)$$

where the variables in the head are a subset of the variables in the body. This template captures direct relationships between predicates.

Definition 5.6 (Chain Template). *A chain template of length n generates rules of the form:*

$$P_1(x_0, x_1) \wedge P_2(x_1, x_2) \wedge \dots \wedge P_{n-1}(x_{n-2}, x_{n-1}) \rightarrow p(x_0, x_{n-1})$$

This template captures transitive and path-based relationships, where the head relates the endpoints of a chain defined by the body predicates.

Definition 5.7 (Star Template). *A star template generates rules of the form:*

$$P_1(x, y_1) \wedge P_2(x, y_2) \wedge \dots \wedge P_k(x, y_k) \rightarrow p(x)$$

This template captures patterns where multiple properties of a central entity combine to determine a conclusion about that entity.

Example 5.1 (Chain Template for Reachability). For a knowledge base with predicate $\text{connectsTo}(h_1, h_2)$ and target predicate $\text{canReach}(h_1, h_2)$, a chain template of length 2 generates candidate rules including:

$$\text{connectsTo}(x, y) \wedge \text{connectsTo}(y, z) \rightarrow \text{canReach}(x, z)$$

This rule captures two-hop reachability.

5.2.3 Template Selection

Templates fall into three categories: *domain-generic* (transitivity, symmetry, composition), *domain-specific* (structural constraints particular to an application), and *user-specified* (contributed by experts who know which patterns to explore). The trade-off is expressiveness for tractability: exotic formulas may be excluded, but every learned rule keeps a recognisable, inspectable structure.

5.3 Neurosymbolic Hybrid Induction

Even with templates, a “curse of predicates” persists: a vocabulary of $|\mathcal{P}|$ predicates and chain templates of length n yield $O(|\mathcal{P}|^n)$ candidates. At 460 predicates and length 3, that is $460^3 \approx 97$ million rules—far too many for interactive use.

Most of those candidates, though, are semantically meaningless. *Neurosymbolic Hybrid Induction* exploits this fact: an LLM proposes a small set (typically 3–10) of plausible rules based on predicate names and domain context; data-driven validation and differentiable optimisation then refine and filter the proposals. Search complexity drops from $O(|\mathcal{P}|^k)$ to $O(r \cdot M)$, where r is the number of proposals and M the number of gradient steps—a speedup of several orders of magnitude (approximately 3×10^5 in the 460-predicate case; see the complexity analysis below).

5.3.1 The Three-Step Pipeline

Figure 38 outlines the three phases.

Phase 1: Semantic Proposal (LLM). An LLM receives the schema (predicate signatures and arities) together with optional domain context (e.g., “cybersecurity” or “legal reasoning”) and returns a small set $\mathcal{R}_{\text{prop}}$ of r plausible rule templates. Typically $r \in [3, 10]$, balancing diversity against redundancy. Rules are requested

in a structured format (e.g., JSON) specifying antecedent predicates, consequent predicate, and variable bindings.

Because the LLM absorbed statistical associations between predicate names during pretraining, it can propose semantically plausible—though not logically guaranteed—rule bodies. For `isSecure(System)`, typical suggestions involve `hasMitigation`, `hasVulnerability`, and `riskLevel`. Hallucinations are possible, but the heuristic eliminates the bulk of implausible predicate combinations.

Phase 2: Data-Driven Validation. Each proposal is checked against the facts in the knowledge base. Rules whose body predicates never co-occur with shared constants (and therefore have no grounding) are pruned, along with rules referencing predicates absent from the schema or violating arity constraints. Both LLM hallucinations and syntactically valid but unsupported candidates are filtered out.

Formally, for a candidate rule φ with body predicates $\{P_1, \dots, P_m\}$ and a knowledge base \mathcal{K} with fact base \mathcal{F} , we compute a support count:

$$\text{support}(\varphi, \mathcal{F}) = \left| \left\{ (c_1, \dots, c_k) \in \mathcal{C}^k : \exists I \in \text{Interp}(\mathcal{K}). I(P_i(c_{j_1}, \dots)) > 0 \text{ for all } i \in [1..m] \right\} \right|$$

A rule is accepted when $\text{support}(\varphi, \mathcal{F}) \geq s$ for a minimum support threshold s (typically $s = 2$), guaranteeing that at least s distinct groundings of the rule body rest on non-zero-valued facts.

Phase 3: Differentiable Optimisation. Each validated rule φ_j starts at weight $w_j = 0$. Gradient descent on the differentiable scoring function (Section 5.4) adjusts weights to maximise agreement with the labelled examples. Low dimensionality ($r \sim 5\text{--}10$ weights), convexity of the loss (Theorem 5.2), and piecewise linearity of Łukasiewicz semantics (Appendix B) jointly guarantee rapid, globally optimal convergence.

Complexity Reduction. Search complexity falls from $O(|\mathcal{P}|^k)$ to $O(r \cdot M)$, where M is the number of optimisation steps. Concretely, in the 460-predicate cybersecurity domain with chain rules of length 3, traditional template-based ILP must evaluate $460^3 = 97,336,000$ candidates. At $M = 20$ gradient steps per candidate, that totals 1,946,720,000 operations. The neurosymbolic approach proposes $r = 5$ rules, validates them in $O(5 \cdot |\mathcal{F}|)$ time (where $|\mathcal{F}| = 500$ facts), and optimises in

Figure 38: The three-phase neurosymbolic hybrid induction pipeline. Phase 1 leverages an LLM to propose a small set of semantically plausible rules, reducing the search space from $O(|\mathcal{P}|^k)$ to $O(r)$ where $r \ll |\mathcal{P}|^k$. Phase 2 validates rules against the knowledge base to filter hallucinations. Phase 3 optimises weights using gradient descent on a differentiable loss function. The total complexity is $O(r \cdot M)$, achieving speedups of approximately 3×10^5 compared to exhaustive template instantiation (the exact factor depends on domain size and LLM overhead). Source: Author.

$O(5 \cdot 100)$ steps (more steps per rule, since fewer rules exist). Total complexity:

$$O_{\text{neuro}} = O(r) + O(r \cdot |\mathcal{F}|) + O(r \cdot M) = O(5) + O(2,500) + O(500) \approx 3,000 \text{ operations}$$

compared to:

$$O_{\text{trad}} = O(|\mathcal{P}|^k \cdot M) = O(97,336,000 \cdot 20) \approx 1,946,720,000 \text{ operations}$$

Under this simplified operation count the speedup factor is $\frac{1,946,720,000}{3,000} \approx 650,000$. The more detailed runtime analysis below (Proposition 5.2 and the empirical case study), which accounts for per-fact evaluation costs and LLM latency, yields a speedup of approximately 3×10^5 —the exact factor depends on domain size, rule length, and LLM overhead, but the reduction consistently spans five to six orders of magnitude.

The three phases illustrated in Figure 38 are designed to complement one another: the LLM contributes broad semantic knowledge that would be impractical to encode by hand, the consistency filter eliminates hallucinations that inevitably accompany

neural generation, and the gradient-based weight learner grounds the surviving rules in the statistical evidence of the fact base. By chaining creativity, verification, and optimisation in this order, the pipeline preserves the strengths of each paradigm while compensating for its weaknesses.

5.3.2 Dual-Heuristic Schema Pruning

With large schemas (100+ predicates), feeding the full vocabulary to the LLM degrades output quality—the model may hallucinate predicates or lose focus. *Dual-Heuristic Schema Pruning* retains only the top- k most relevant predicates (typically $k = 30$) before the LLM sees them (Figure 39). Two heuristics drive the pruning:

Heuristic 1: Linguistic Similarity. Fuzzy string matching (e.g., normalised Levenshtein distance) identifies predicates whose names are semantically related to the target predicate. For example, if the target predicate is `isSecure(System)`, predicates such as `hasSecurityControl`, `securityProtocol`, and `vulnerabilityAssessment` receive high similarity scores due to the shared substring “`secur`”. Formally, for a target predicate p and candidate predicate q , the linguistic similarity score is:

$$\text{sim}_{\text{ling}}(p, q) = 1 - \frac{\text{LevenshteinDistance}(\text{name}(p), \text{name}(q))}{\max(|\text{name}(p)|, |\text{name}(q)|)}$$

where $\text{name}(\cdot)$ extracts the predicate name as a string. Predicates with $\text{sim}_{\text{ling}}(p, q) > \tau_{\text{sim}}$ (typically $\tau_{\text{sim}} = 0.3$) are considered linguistically relevant.

Heuristic 2: Frequency Analysis. Predicates appearing often in the fact base represent “dense” regions where learning has the most data support. A predicate backed by hundreds of facts enables robust weight learning; one backed by only one or two facts offers little signal. The frequency score for predicate q is:

$$\text{freq}(q) = \frac{|\{a \in \text{atoms}(\mathcal{F}) : \text{pred}(a) = q\}|}{|\text{atoms}(\mathcal{F})|}$$

where $\text{atoms}(\mathcal{F})$ is the set of all ground atoms in the fact base \mathcal{F} , and $\text{pred}(a)$ extracts the predicate symbol of atom a .

Combined Ranking. The two scores are combined via a weighted sum:

$$\text{relevance}(p, q) = \alpha \cdot \text{sim}_{\text{ling}}(p, q) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \text{freq}(q)$$

Figure 39: Semantic pruning of the rule search space. The full search space (red) contains all possible combinations of predicates, totaling $P^3 = 97,336,000$ candidate rules for a 460-predicate schema with chain templates of length 3. Dual-heuristic schema pruning (linguistic similarity + frequency analysis) reduces this to approximately 27,000 candidates using only the top-30 relevant predicates (orange). The LLM then leverages semantic heuristics to propose just 5 plausible rules (green), achieving a cumulative reduction factor exceeding 10^7 . This two-stage filtering enables tractable induction in large-scale knowledge bases while preserving high-quality rule candidates. Source: Author.

where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ (typically 0.6, favouring semantic relatedness) controls the trade-off. The top- k predicates form the pruned schema Σ_{rel} presented to the LLM, shrinking the prompt from tens of thousands of tokens to roughly 2,000–3,000.

The cumulative reduction factor exceeding 10^7 shown in Figure 39 underscores the practical necessity of pruning: without it, even moderately sized schemas render exhaustive enumeration infeasible. By cascading linguistic similarity and frequency analysis before the LLM stage, the pipeline confines neural generation to a manageable candidate pool, thereby controlling both computational cost and the risk of hallucinated predicates.

5.3.3 Arity Auto-Correction

LLMs occasionally produce argument lists whose length does not match a predicate’s declared arity, yielding unparseable formulas. Instead of re-prompting, LIMEN-AI applies *Arity Auto-Correction* during parsing:

Case 1: Excess Arguments ($m > k$). When a proposed rule supplies m arguments for a predicate of arity $k < m$, the list is truncated to its first k entries. LLMs tend to place the most important arguments first (a side effect of left-to-right generation), so truncation usually preserves intent. For instance, if `connectsTo(host1, host2)` has arity 2 but the LLM emits `connectsTo(x, y, z)`, the

corrected atom is connectsTo(x, y).

Case 2: Insufficient Arguments ($m < k$). If the proposed rule provides m arguments for a predicate requiring $k > m$ arguments, the argument list is padded with unique “dummy” variables of the form UNK_ i where i is an index ensuring uniqueness across all corrections in the same rule. For example, if the LLM generates hasProperty(x) but the schema defines hasProperty(entity, property, value) with arity 3, the correction yields hasProperty(x , UNK_1, UNK_2).

Empirical Efficacy. Ablation studies on 200 LLM-generated rules across five domains (cybersecurity, legal reasoning, supply chain, healthcare compliance, financial risk) show that arity auto-correction lifts rule recovery from 42% to 87%, as summarised in Table 13. The remaining 13% of failures stem from hallucinated predicate names (caught by Phase 2 validation) or malformed logical connectives.

Table 13: Ablation of arity auto-correction on 200 LLM-generated candidate rules across five domains. Rule recovery denotes the fraction of candidates that parse into well-formed first-order formulas. Source: Author.

Configuration	Rule Recovery (%)
Without arity correction	42
With arity correction	87
Improvement	+45 pp

Dummy variables rarely survive the pipeline. Rules whose padded variables cannot unify with any constant receive zero support in Phase 2 or converge to negligible weights in Phase 3. The few that persist usually correspond to genuinely existential patterns where the extra variables are legitimately unconstrained.

5.4 Differentiable Scoring

Once the candidate set is fixed, rules must be scored by how well they separate positive from negative examples. A differentiable loss function rooted in logistic regression turns this into continuous optimisation. Łukasiewicz operations are piecewise linear and almost-everywhere differentiable (Appendix B, luk_and_piecewise_luk_implies_piecewise), so satisfaction degrees $\sigma(\varphi, I)$ inherit these properties. Composing them with a sigmoid activation produces a convex, gradient-stable loss landscape where optimal weights emerge in seconds.

5.4.1 The Induction Loss Function

Weights should push positive examples toward high truth degrees, push negatives toward low truth degrees, and favour sparsity—simpler knowledge bases that use fewer rules.

Definition 5.8 (Candidate Rule Evaluation). *For a candidate rule φ with body B and head $p(\mathbf{x})$, and an example $e = (c_1, \dots, c_k) \in \mathcal{C}^k$, define:*

$$\sigma_\varphi(e) = \max_{\mathbf{y}} I(B[\mathbf{x}/e, \mathbf{y}])$$

where the maximum is over all instantiations \mathbf{y} of the body variables not appearing in the head. This quantity measures how strongly the rule body supports the head for example e .

Intuitively, $\sigma_\varphi(e)$ asks: is there *any* binding of the body-only variables that makes the body highly satisfied? A single good binding suffices to support the head. For example, consider the rule:

$$\varphi : \text{connectsTo}(x, y) \wedge \text{connectsTo}(y, z) \rightarrow \text{canReach}(x, z)$$

and an example $e = (a, c)$. The evaluation $\sigma_\varphi(a, c)$ computes:

$$\sigma_\varphi(a, c) = \max_{y \in \mathcal{C}} [I(\text{connectsTo}(a, y)) \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} I(\text{connectsTo}(y, c))]$$

If the knowledge base contains $\text{connectsTo}(a, b) = 0.9$ and $\text{connectsTo}(b, c) = 0.8$, then:

$$\sigma_\varphi(a, c) = \max(0, 0.9 + 0.8 - 1) = 0.7$$

reflecting that there is a two-hop path from a to c through intermediate node b with joint satisfaction degree 0.7.

Definition 5.9 (Induction Loss). *For a candidate rule φ with weight w and a label set $\mathcal{L} = (\mathcal{L}^+, \mathcal{L}^-)$, the induction loss is:*

$$L(w; \varphi, \mathcal{L}) = - \sum_{e \in \mathcal{L}^+} \log(\sigma(w \cdot \sigma_\varphi(e))) \tag{34}$$

$$- \sum_{e \in \mathcal{L}^-} \log(1 - \sigma(w \cdot \sigma_\varphi(e))) + \lambda|w| \tag{35}$$

where $\sigma(z) = 1/(1 + e^{-z})$ is the sigmoid function and $\lambda > 0$ is a regularisation parameter.

Loss Function Structure. The loss is a regularised logistic regression with “features” equal to truth degrees $\sigma_\varphi(e) \in [0, 1]$. Equation 34 rewards high predicted probabilities for positives; Equation 35 penalises high predictions on negatives. The L^1 term $\lambda|w|$ promotes sparsity: rules whose weights shrink to near zero can be pruned, yielding smaller, more interpretable knowledge bases.

Connection to Probabilistic Semantics. The logistic form is not ad hoc—it arises from maximum likelihood estimation under a probabilistic reading. Model the probability that an example e is positive as:

$$P(e \in \mathcal{L}^+ \mid \varphi, w) = \sigma(w \cdot \sigma_\varphi(e))$$

Then $L(w; \varphi, \mathcal{L})$ without regularisation is exactly the negative log-likelihood of the observed labels \mathcal{L} . Minimising it recovers the maximum likelihood estimate of w .

5.4.2 Gradient Computation

Each satisfaction degree $\sigma_\varphi(e)$ depends on the interpretation I but not on w , so the loss gradient has a closed-form expression—no numerical approximation is needed.

Proposition 5.1 (Loss Gradient).

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial w} = - \sum_{e \in \mathcal{L}^+} (1 - \hat{p}_e) \cdot \sigma_\varphi(e) + \sum_{e \in \mathcal{L}^-} \hat{p}_e \cdot \sigma_\varphi(e) + \lambda \cdot \text{sign}(w)$$

where $\hat{p}_e = \sigma(w \cdot \sigma_\varphi(e))$ is the predicted probability for example e , and $\text{sign}(w) \in \{-1, 0, 1\}$ is the sign of w .

Proof. We compute the gradient term-by-term. For a positive example $e \in \mathcal{L}^+$, the contribution to the loss is $-\log(\sigma(w \cdot s))$ where $s = \sigma_\varphi(e)$ is constant with respect

to w . Using the chain rule and the derivative identity $\frac{d}{dz} \log(\sigma(z)) = 1 - \sigma(z)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial w} [-\log(\sigma(w \cdot s))] &= -\frac{1}{\sigma(w \cdot s)} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial w} \sigma(w \cdot s) \\ &= -\frac{1}{\sigma(w \cdot s)} \cdot \sigma(w \cdot s) \cdot (1 - \sigma(w \cdot s)) \cdot s \\ &= -(1 - \sigma(w \cdot s)) \cdot s \\ &= -(1 - \hat{p}_e) \cdot s \end{aligned}$$

For a negative example $e \in \mathcal{L}^-$, the contribution is $-\log(1 - \sigma(w \cdot s))$. Using $\frac{d}{dz} \log(1 - \sigma(z)) = -\sigma(z)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial w} [-\log(1 - \sigma(w \cdot s))] &= -\frac{1}{1 - \sigma(w \cdot s)} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial w} (1 - \sigma(w \cdot s)) \\ &= \frac{1}{1 - \sigma(w \cdot s)} \cdot \sigma(w \cdot s) \cdot (1 - \sigma(w \cdot s)) \cdot s \\ &= \sigma(w \cdot s) \cdot s \\ &= \hat{p}_e \cdot s \end{aligned}$$

The regularisation term $\lambda|w|$ has subgradient $\lambda \cdot \text{sign}(w)$ (technically, at $w = 0$ the subgradient is the interval $[-\lambda, \lambda]$, but in practice we use 0 at this point). Summing over all examples yields the stated gradient formula. \square

Gradient Interpretation. Missed positives (low \hat{p}_e) drive a large negative gradient that pushes w up, strengthening the rule. False positives on negatives create a positive gradient that suppresses it. The regularisation term $\lambda \cdot \text{sign}(w)$ pulls steadily toward zero—a form of Occam’s razor: a rule survives only when its explanatory power outweighs the complexity penalty.

5.4.3 Piecewise Linearity and Gradient Stability

Efficient gradient-based optimisation relies on the piecewise linearity of Łukasiewicz semantics, formally verified in Appendix B. Satisfaction degrees $\sigma_\varphi(e)$ are piecewise linear in the truth assignments I , so gradients are well-defined and Lipschitz-continuous almost everywhere.

Theorem 5.1 (Gradient Lipschitz Continuity). *The gradient $\frac{\partial L}{\partial w}$ is Lipschitz con-*

tinuous with constant:

$$L_{grad} = \sum_{e \in \mathcal{L}} \sigma_{\varphi}(e)^2 + \lambda$$

where $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}^+ \cup \mathcal{L}^-$.

Proof sketch. The Lipschitz constant of $\frac{\partial}{\partial w} \log(\sigma(w \cdot s))$ with respect to w is bounded by s^2 (this follows from the second derivative of the logistic loss). Summing over all examples and adding the regularisation contribution λ yields the stated bound. The full proof follows from standard results on the smoothness of logistic regression (Boyd and Vandenberghe, 2004). \square

This Lipschitz constant dictates the learning rate: convergence requires $\eta < 2/L_{grad}$. For typical label sets ($|\mathcal{L}| \sim 10\text{--}100$ examples, $\sigma_{\varphi}(e) \in [0, 1]$), $L_{grad} = O(|\mathcal{L}|)$, placing practical learning rates in the range $\eta \in [0.01, 0.1]$.

Link to Chapter 3. The Łukasiewicz t-norm $T_{\mathbb{L}}(a, b) = \max(0, a + b - 1)$, t-conorm $S_{\mathbb{L}}(a, b) = \min(1, a + b)$, and implication $\phi \rightarrow \psi := \min(1, 1 - \phi + \psi)$ are each piecewise linear. Appendix B proves (in Isabelle/HOL) that every composite formula inherits this property, with at most $O(2^n)$ linear pieces for n connectives. The “kinks” between pieces form a measure-zero set, so almost-everywhere differentiability suffices for gradient descent convergence.

5.5 The Neurosymbolic Induction Algorithm

Algorithm 4 combines the three phases into one procedure.

Algorithm 4 Neurosymbolic Hybrid Induction. Source: Author.

Require: Knowledge base \mathcal{K}

- 1: Target predicate p
- 2: LLM client \mathcal{M}
- 3: Predicate schema Σ
- 4: Learning rate η
- 5: Number of optimisation steps M
- 6: Minimum support threshold s
- 7: Acceptance threshold τ

Ensure: Set of induced weighted rules \mathcal{R}^*

```

8:  $\Sigma_{\text{rel}} \leftarrow \text{SELECTRELEVANTPREDICATES}(\Sigma, p, \mathcal{K})$ 
9:  $\mathcal{R}_{\text{prop}} \leftarrow \mathcal{M}.\text{PROPOSERULES}(p, \Sigma_{\text{rel}})$ 
▷ Phase 1: Semantic proposal via LLM

10:  $\mathcal{R}_{\text{val}} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
11: for each candidate rule  $\varphi \in \mathcal{R}_{\text{prop}}$  do
12:    $\varphi_{\text{fixed}} \leftarrow \text{AUTOCORRECTARITY}(\varphi, \Sigma)$ 
13:   if  $\text{SUPPORTCOUNT}(\varphi_{\text{fixed}}, \mathcal{K}) \geq s$  then
14:      $\mathcal{R}_{\text{val}} \leftarrow \mathcal{R}_{\text{val}} \cup \{\varphi_{\text{fixed}}\}$ 
▷ Phase 2: Data-driven validation

▷ Phase 3: Differentiable weight optimisation
15: for each validated rule  $\varphi \in \mathcal{R}_{\text{val}}$  do
16:   Initialize weight:  $w_\varphi \leftarrow 0$ 
▷ Neutral prior:  $\sigma(0) = 0.5$ 
17:   for  $m = 1$  to  $M$  do
18:     Compute gradient  $g \leftarrow \partial L / \partial w_\varphi$ 
19:     Update weight:  $w_\varphi \leftarrow w_\varphi - \eta \cdot g$ 
20:  $\mathcal{R}^* \leftarrow \{(\varphi, \sigma(w_\varphi)) \mid \varphi \in \mathcal{R}_{\text{val}}, \sigma(w_\varphi) > \tau\}$ 
   return  $\mathcal{R}^*$ 

```

5.5.1 Complexity Analysis and Scaling

The following proposition quantifies the speedup from semantic proposal over exhaustive template instantiation.

Proposition 5.2 (Complexity Comparison). *Let $P = |\mathcal{P}|$ be the number of predicates, k be the maximum rule length (number of predicates in the body), $|\mathcal{F}|$ be the number of facts in the knowledge base, and M be the number of optimisation steps per candidate rule.*

1. **Traditional ILP:** Exhaustive search over templates of length k requires evaluating $O(P^k)$ candidate rules. For each candidate, weight optimisation requires M gradient steps, and each gradient step requires evaluating the satisfaction degree over the knowledge base in $O(|\mathcal{F}|)$ time. The total complexity is:

$$O_{\text{trad}} = O(P^k \cdot M \cdot |\mathcal{F}|)$$

2. **Neurosymbolic Induction:** By leveraging LLM heuristics, the search space is pruned to a constant number of proposals $r \ll P^k$ (typically $r \in [3, 10]$). Phase 2 validation requires $O(r \cdot |\mathcal{F}|)$ time to check rule support. Phase 3 optimisation requires $O(r \cdot M \cdot |\mathcal{F}|)$ time. The LLM call in Phase 1 requires $O(1)$ time (constant with respect to P and $|\mathcal{F}|$, though dependent on LLM latency). The total complexity is:

$$O_{neuro} = O(1) + O(r \cdot |\mathcal{F}|) + O(r \cdot M \cdot |\mathcal{F}|) = O(r \cdot M \cdot |\mathcal{F}|)$$

The speedup factor is therefore:

$$Speedup = \frac{O_{trad}}{O_{neuro}} = \frac{P^k \cdot M \cdot |\mathcal{F}|}{r \cdot M \cdot |\mathcal{F}|} = \frac{P^k}{r}$$

Empirical Case Study: Cybersecurity Domain. Consider a cybersecurity knowledge base drawn from network logs and vulnerability databases:

- Number of predicates: $P = 460$ (representing entities such as hosts, vulnerabilities, exploits, mitigations, network connections, authentication events, etc.)
- Maximum rule length: $k = 3$ (chain rules capturing transitive properties like “vulnerability leads to exploit leads to compromise”)
- Number of facts: $|\mathcal{F}| = 500$ (ground atoms extracted from security logs)
- Optimisation steps per rule: $M = 20$ for traditional ILP (few steps per rule due to large candidate set), $M = 100$ for neurosymbolic ILP (more steps per rule since fewer candidates)
- Number of LLM proposals: $r = 5$

For traditional template-based ILP:

$$\text{Candidate rules} = P^k = 460^3 = 97,336,000$$

$$\text{Total operations} = 97,336,000 \times 20 \times 500 = 973,360,000,000 \approx 10^{12}$$

Assuming 1 microsecond per operation (optimistic, given the need to evaluate Łukasiewicz satisfaction degrees over a distributed fact base), the estimated runtime

is:

$$\text{Runtime}_{\text{trad}} = \frac{10^{12} \text{ ops}}{10^6 \text{ ops/sec}} = 10^6 \text{ sec} \approx 11.6 \text{ days}$$

For neurosymbolic hybrid ILP:

$$\text{Proposed rules} = r = 5$$

$$\text{Validation operations} = 5 \times 500 = 2,500$$

$$\text{Optimisation operations} = 5 \times 100 \times 500 = 250,000$$

$$\text{Total operations} = 2,500 + 250,000 \approx 252,500$$

With the same per-operation cost:

$$\text{Runtime}_{\text{neuro}} = \frac{252,500 \text{ ops}}{10^6 \text{ ops/sec}} \approx 0.25 \text{ sec}$$

Adding LLM latency (typically 2–5 seconds for a single completion request):

$$\text{Runtime}_{\text{neuro, total}} \approx 0.25 + 3 = 3.25 \text{ sec}$$

The speedup factor is:

$$\text{Speedup} = \frac{10^6 \text{ sec}}{3.25 \text{ sec}} \approx 307,692 \approx 3 \times 10^5$$

This represents a reduction from 11.6 days to 3.25 seconds, making interactive knowledge base construction feasible.

Scalability Beyond 460 Predicates. At $P = 1000$ (typical of enterprise-scale regulatory KBs), traditional ILP confronts 10^9 candidates and years of computation; the neurosymbolic pipeline still proposes $r \sim 5$ rules and finishes in seconds. Figure 40 plots the divergence: the $O(P^3)$ curve (red) separates sharply from the constant $O(r)$ line (blue) once P exceeds 100.

5.5.2 Comparative Analysis with State-of-the-Art ILP

Classical ILP systems (Aleph, Prolog, SLIPCOVER) search discrete hypothesis spaces, while pure neural rule learners (Neural Logic Machines, differentiable Prolog) embed rules in latent parameters. LIMEN-AI occupies the gap between them, using LLM semantic guidance to constrain the search and Łukasiewicz energy functions to

Figure 40: Complexity comparison between traditional template-based ILP (red curve) and neurosymbolic hybrid ILP (blue line). The vertical axis shows the number of candidate rules on a logarithmic scale; the horizontal axis shows the number of predicates P . Traditional ILP grows as $O(P^3)$ for chain templates of length 3, reaching 97 million candidates at $P = 460$. Neurosymbolic ILP uses semantic proposal to constrain candidates to a constant $r = 5$ regardless of P , achieving a speedup factor of approximately 3×10^5 in large-scale domains (derived from the complexity reduction analysis above). The shaded region at $P = 460$ illustrates the magnitude of this reduction. Source: Author.

refine the result.

The Expressivity-Graded Challenge: Why Pure LLM Induction Fails. De Souza et al. (2025) benchmark LLMs (GPT-4, LLaMA-2-70B) against classical ILP on induction tasks graded by dependency-chain complexity (de Souza et al., 2025). On simple theories—single-clause rules with shallow chains—LLMs match Aleph, but performance drops sharply as chain length grows.

Specifically, de Souza et al. identify **predicate relationship chain length** as the critical bottleneck: “tracking long predicate relationship chains is a more difficult obstacle than theory complexity for LLMs.” Consider the following induction task:

Background Knowledge:

Parent(x, y), Sibling(x, y), WorksAt(x, c), Manages(x, y)
 Employs(c, x), Salary(x, s)

Target Predicate: InfluenceRisk(x) (person x has potential conflicts of interest)

Ground Truth Rule:

$$\forall x, y, z, c : \text{Parent}(x, y) \wedge \text{WorksAt}(y, c) \wedge \text{Manages}(x, z) \wedge \text{WorksAt}(z, c) \Rightarrow \text{InfluenceRisk}(x)$$

This rule expresses: “If x is a parent of y , both y and someone x manages work at the same company, then x has influence risk.” The predicate chain has length 4: $\text{Parent} \rightarrow \text{WorksAt} \rightarrow \text{Manages} \rightarrow \text{WorksAt}$.

LLM Performance (from de Souza et al.’s experiments):

- **Chain length 1–2:** Accuracy $\sim 85\%$ (competitive with Aleph)
- **Chain length 3–4:** Accuracy drops to $\sim 45\%$
- **Chain length ≥ 5 :** Accuracy $\sim 20\%$ (random baseline is $\sim 10\%$)

Root Cause: Autoregressive generation makes it hard for the model to track variable roles across many predicates. Common failure modes include swapping x and y in later clauses, reversing argument order in predicate calls, and omitting intermediate predicates. LIMEN-AI’s hybrid architecture is designed to mitigate exactly this weakness.

LIMEN-AI’s Hybrid Mechanism: LLM for Hypothesis Generation + Łukasiewicz for Refinement. The hybrid architecture addresses this through two stages:

Stage 1: LLM-Based Hypothesis Generation (Semantic Guidance). The LLM (GPT-4, Claude, or domain-specific fine-tuned model) is prompted to generate candidate rule *templates*, not complete rules. The prompt provides:

- Background schema (predicate signatures)
- Positive/negative examples
- Request for short rule templates (chain length ≤ 3)

Example Prompt:

```
1 Given predicates: Parent(x,y), WorksAt(x,c), Manages(x,y),  
   Salary(x,s)  
2 Positive examples: InfluenceRisk(Alice), InfluenceRisk(Bob)  
3 Negative examples: ~InfluenceRisk(Carol), ~InfluenceRisk(Dave)
```

```

4
5 Generate 5 candidate rule templates for InfluenceRisk(x),
   using at most 3 body predicates.
6 Format: [P1(?x, ?y), P2(?y, ?z), ...] => InfluenceRisk(?x)

```

LLM Output (5 candidates):

1. [Parent(x, y), WorksAt(y, c)]
2. [Manages(x, y), WorksAt(y, c)]
3. [Parent(x, y), Salary(y, s)]
4. [WorksAt(x, c), Manages(x, y)]
5. [Sibling(x, y), WorksAt(y, c)]

Key Constraint: Capping chain length at ≤ 3 keeps proposals in the LLM’s competent range (85% accuracy per de Souza’s results). The LLM contributes *semantic guidance*—plausible predicate combinations drawn from its training on natural-language descriptions of relational patterns—without being asked for end-to-end logical correctness.

Stage 2: Łukasiewicz Optimisation (Formal Refinement). Each LLM-generated template is instantiated as a first-order formula and assigned an initial weight $w_i = 0$. The differentiable induction loss (Section 5.4) is then optimised via gradient descent:

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_{e \in \mathcal{L}^+} -\log \hat{p}_e + \sum_{e \in \mathcal{L}^-} -\log(1 - \hat{p}_e) + \lambda \|\mathbf{w}\|_1$$

where $\hat{p}_e = \sigma(\sum_i w_i \bar{I}(\varphi_i[e]))$ is the predicted probability for example e , computed via sampling over the energy function.

Gradient Update:

$$w_i \leftarrow w_i - \eta \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial w_i}$$

The gradient $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial w_i}$ is computed via automatic differentiation through the Łukasiewicz operations, leveraging the piecewise linearity verified in Appendix B.

Outcome: After 100–200 gradient steps, weights converge. Rules with $|w_i| > \tau$ (e.g., $\tau = 0.5$) are accepted; others are discarded. For the InfluenceRisk example, the

Table 14: Positioning LIMEN-AI’s hybrid ILP in the design space of inductive learners, comparing symbolic explicitness, search efficiency, and key properties. Source: Author.

Approach	Symbolic	Search Effi- ciency	Chain Track- ing	Regulatory
Classical ILP (Aleph)	1.0	$O(P^k)$	✓ Exact	✓ Auditable
Pure Neural (NLM)	0.2	$O(1)$	× Latent	× Opaque
Pure LLM (de Souza)	0.8	$O(r)$	× Fails at >3	! Unverified
LIMEN-AI Hybrid	1.0	$O(r)$	✓ LLM+Opt	✓ Explicit+Diff

optimisation might yield:

$$w_1 = 2.3 \quad (\text{Parent} + \text{WorksAt: strong positive signal})$$

$$w_2 = 1.8 \quad (\text{Manages} + \text{WorksAt: moderate positive})$$

$$w_3 = 0.1 \quad (\text{Parent} + \text{Salary: weak, discarded})$$

$$w_4 = -0.3 \quad (\text{WorksAt} + \text{Manages: weak negative, discarded})$$

$$w_5 = 0.6 \quad (\text{Sibling} + \text{WorksAt: moderate positive})$$

Key Insight: The LLM need not have guessed the correct rule. Weight learning acts as a continuous relaxation of discrete search, retaining whichever proposals the data actually supports.

Positioning as a Bridge: Pure Neural ↔ Pure Symbolic. Two axes organise the design space: *symbolic explicitness* (are learned rules readable first-order formulas?) and *search efficiency* (how many candidates must be evaluated?). Pure neural learners score $\sim 0.1\text{--}0.3$ on explicitness but $O(1)$ on search; classical ILP scores 1.0 on explicitness but $O(P^k)$ on search. LIMEN-AI reaches 1.0 explicitness *and* $O(r)$ search, with $r \sim 5\text{--}10$.

Table 14 summarises these positions. LIMEN-AI matches classical ILP on explicitness and neural/LLM approaches on search efficiency, tracks predicate chains through short-chain proposal plus weight refinement, and keeps the explicit rule structure that EU AI Act compliance requires. The trade-off is *expressivity*: only rules within the LLM’s proposal space can be discovered. For high-stakes applications where auditability outweighs maximal expressive range, this concession is acceptable.

Acknowledging LLM Limitations: Predicate-Chain Hallucinations and Differentiable Filtering. The hybrid architecture carries risks. LLM proposals may reverse argument order, chain predicates with incompatible types, hallucinate predicates absent from the schema, or be overly generic. These **predicate-chain hallucinations** originate in the autoregressive process, which has no formal grounding in the schema’s type system.

Differentiable Filtering. Two filters catch invalid proposals:

Filter 1: Schema Validation (Pre-Optimisation). Before entering the optimisation loop, each LLM-generated template is validated against the schema:

```

1 def validate_template(template, schema):
2     for predicate in template.body:
3         if predicate.name not in schema.predicates:
4             return False # Hallucinated predicate
5         if not schema.type_check(predicate.args):
6             return False # Type mismatch
7     return True

```

Invalid templates are rejected before entering weight learning.

Filter 2: Data-Driven Selection (Post-Optimisation). A schematically valid template may still be semantically irrelevant. The optimisation stage doubles as a data-driven filter: templates uncorrelated with positive/negative examples converge to $w_i \approx 0$ and are discarded by the $|w_i| > \tau$ threshold.

Example: If the LLM proposes $\text{Sibling}(x, y) \wedge \text{Salary}(y, s) \Rightarrow \text{InfluenceRisk}(x)$, which is schematically valid but semantically irrelevant, the optimisation will find that this template has near-zero correlation with the training labels, yielding $w \approx 0.05 < \tau = 0.5$, and the rule will be discarded.

Empirical Validation (Chapter 8): roughly 15% of LLM proposals fail schema validation. Of the remainder, about 40% converge to $|w| < \tau$ and are pruned. The net acceptance rate is $\sim 50\%$, so only schematically valid and data-supported rules enter the knowledge base.

The Stochastic Search Problem: Why Differentiability Matters. Classical ILP systems like Aleph rely on stochastic search (random restarts, beam search, genetic algorithms), which introduces non-determinism—different seeds can yield different theories—and plateau sensitivity, where discrete scores supply no gradient

signal. Casting induction as continuous weight optimisation over a fixed template set gives LIMEN-AI deterministic, reproducible results (same data and templates produce the same weights up to numerical precision), smooth gradients that bypass plateaus, and formal convergence guarantees under convexity and Lipschitz assumptions. The price is expressivity: only rules within the LLM’s proposal space can be found. In regulated domains, where reproducibility (EU AI Act Article 12) outweighs maximal expressive range, this trade-off is well justified.

Synergies with Broader ML+KRR Research. The hybrid architecture fits a wider trend toward integrating machine learning with knowledge representation & reasoning (KRR). Baaj et al. (2024) survey seven intersection areas—including statistical relational learning and neurosymbolic AI—and argue that successful integration requires assigning each paradigm the task it handles best (Baaj et al., 2024). LIMEN-AI applies this principle: pattern recognition (which predicates plausibly co-occur?) goes to the LLM; logical refinement (which proposals survive the data?) goes to the differentiable optimiser. The LLM also addresses the “cold start” problem of large vocabularies ($P > 100$) by acting as a learned prior over rule structures, much like pretrained feature extractors in transfer learning. Youssef & Hassan (2024) combine ILP with LLMs for multimodal fault explanation (Youssef and Hassan, 2024), illustrating the broader applicability of such hybrid designs.

5.5.3 Weight Initialization and Optimisation

All weights start at zero, giving an initial prediction of $\hat{p}_e = \sigma(0) = 0.5$ for every example—maximum uncertainty.

Proposition 5.3 (Initial Neutrality). *With $w = 0$, the predicted probability $\hat{p}_e = \sigma(0) = 0.5$ for all examples.*

Plain gradient descent with a fixed learning rate suffices for this low-dimensional problem (one weight per rule). More sophisticated optimisers (Adam, L-BFGS) could accelerate convergence if needed.

5.5.4 Rule Selection

After optimisation, rules are selected by weight magnitude. Rules with $|w| > \tau$ are kept as meaningful; rules with $|w| \leq \tau$ are discarded.

Definition 5.10 (Acceptance Criterion). *A candidate rule (φ, w) is accepted if $|w| > \tau$ for threshold $\tau > 0$. The sign of w indicates the direction of the relationship:*

- $w > \tau$: *The rule body positively supports the head.*
- $w < -\tau$: *The rule body negatively supports the head (i.e., the body being true suggests the head is false).*

The threshold τ governs the precision–recall trade-off: higher τ yields fewer but more confident rules; lower τ admits more rules, some with weaker support.

5.6 Convergence Analysis

Convergence guarantees pin down how many gradient steps are needed and rule out entrapment in suboptimal solutions. The induction loss inherits convexity from the logistic structure and the piecewise linearity of Łukasiewicz satisfaction degrees, so gradient descent reaches the global optimum from any initialisation. The formal statements and rates follow.

5.6.1 Convergence of Weight Learning

For each candidate rule, the induction loss is convex in w , so gradient descent converges to the global optimum.

Theorem 5.2 (Convexity of Induction Loss). *For fixed φ and \mathcal{L} , the induction loss $L(w; \varphi, \mathcal{L})$ is convex in w .*

Proof. The negative log-likelihood terms are convex because the logistic loss is convex. The regularisation term $\lambda|w|$ is convex (though not strictly convex at $w = 0$). The sum of convex functions is convex. □

Corollary 5.1 (Global Convergence). *Gradient descent on the induction loss converges to the global minimum from any initialisation, provided the learning rate is sufficiently small.*

Proposition 5.4 (Convergence Rate). *For learning rate $\eta < 2/L$ where L is the Lipschitz constant of the gradient (formally bounded in Appendix B), gradient descent achieves $L(w_m) - L(w^*) \leq O(1/m)$ after m iterations.*

The Lipschitz constant depends on the scores $\sigma_\varphi(e)$ and the regularisation parameter λ . In practice, $\eta = 0.1$ or 0.01 usually suffices.

5.6.2 Statistical Consistency

Statistical consistency complements optimisation convergence: as the number of examples grows, the learned weights approach the true weights (if such exist).

Proposition 5.5 (Consistency of Rule Weight Estimation). *Suppose the label set \mathcal{L} is generated i.i.d. from a true model with ground-truth weights w^* , and that the following regularity conditions hold:*

1. Identifiability: *The true weight vector w^* is the unique minimiser of the expected loss $\mathbb{E}[\ell(w)]$.*
2. Feature regularity: *The satisfaction scores $\sigma_\varphi(e)$ are bounded in $[0, 1]$ (which holds by construction for Łukasiewicz semantics) and the resulting design matrix has full column rank almost surely.*
3. Compactness: *The weight space is contained in a compact subset of \mathbb{R}^r (ensured by the ℓ_2 regulariser).*

Then the learned weights \hat{w} satisfy:

$$|\hat{w} - w^*| = O_P \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{|\mathcal{L}|}} \right)$$

where O_P denotes convergence in probability.

Proof sketch. Under these conditions, the induction loss reduces to a regularised logistic regression whose negative log-likelihood is strictly convex and twice continuously differentiable on the compact weight space. The \sqrt{n} -consistency then follows from standard M-estimator theory (van der Vaart, 1998). Condition (2) deserves attention: although satisfaction scores depend on the knowledge base interpretation, they are deterministic given the input example and the fixed rule set, so the feature vector for each example is a measurable function of the observed data. The ℓ_2 regularisation (Condition 3) ensures the estimator remains well-defined even when the sample size is small relative to the number of rules. \square

5.7 Integration with Knowledge Bases

Learned rules must be folded back into the knowledge base, where they interact with existing formulas and may introduce redundancy or conflict. The subsections

below cover the update operation, consistency checks, incremental learning, and human-in-the-loop validation.

5.7.1 Adding Induced Rules

Accepted rules enter the knowledge base through a formal update that extends the formula set and weight vector while preserving existing structure.

Definition 5.11 (Knowledge Base Update). *For a knowledge base $\mathcal{K} = (\Sigma, \mathcal{F}, \mathbf{w})$ and a set of induced rules $\mathcal{R}^* = \{(\varphi_j, w_j)\}_{j=1}^r$, the updated knowledge base is:*

$$\mathcal{K}' = (\Sigma, \mathcal{F} \cup \{\varphi_j\}_{j=1}^r, (\mathbf{w}, w_1, \dots, w_r))$$

where $\mathcal{F} \cup \{\varphi_j\}$ denotes the formula set extended with the new rules, and $(\mathbf{w}, w_1, \dots, w_r)$ is the concatenated weight vector.

The update is *non-destructive*: existing formulas and weights stay unchanged, and new rules simply augment the knowledge base. An unhelpful rule can later be removed or its weight zeroed without side effects.

5.7.2 Consistency Validation

Two checks guard against knowledge-base degradation before a learned rule is committed:

Redundancy Detection. A learned rule φ_{new} is redundant when it is logically equivalent to, or subsumed by, an existing rule φ_{old} . Exact logical equivalence is undecidable in first-order logic, but syntactic equivalence up to variable renaming can be checked efficiently. If φ_{new} matches any formula in \mathcal{F} after variable normalisation, the rule is either discarded or merged with the existing rule by averaging weights:

$$w_{\text{merged}} = \frac{w_{\text{old}} + w_{\text{new}}}{2}$$

Averaging reflects increased confidence when independent induction runs converge to the same rule.

Conflict Detection. A learned rule φ_{new} conflicts with existing knowledge if adding it significantly decreases the satisfaction degrees of high-confidence existing formulas. Formally, let $E(\mathcal{K})$ be the total energy of the knowledge base under the

current interpretation I :

$$E(\mathcal{K}) = \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{F}|} w_i \cdot \sigma(\varphi_i, I)$$

After adding the new rule, the energy becomes:

$$E(\mathcal{K}') = E(\mathcal{K}) + w_{\text{new}} \cdot \sigma(\varphi_{\text{new}}, I)$$

If $w_{\text{new}} < 0$ (a negatively weighted rule) and $\sigma(\varphi_{\text{new}}, I)$ is high under interpretations that also satisfy existing positive-weight rules, this indicates a potential conflict. LIMEN-AI flags such cases and prompts the user to review the conflicting rules before integration.

5.7.3 Incremental Induction

LIMEN-AI supports incremental induction: new rules are learned as additional labelled examples arrive. Dynamic domains—security logs, financial transactions, legal precedents—demand exactly this capability.

Definition 5.12 (Incremental Induction). *Given an existing knowledge base \mathcal{K} (possibly containing previously induced rules) and a new label set \mathcal{L}_{new} , incremental induction:*

1. *Generates candidate rules from templates or LLM proposals, using predicates from both the original schema and any predicates introduced by previously induced rules.*
2. *Optimises weights using the new labels \mathcal{L}_{new} , keeping existing weights fixed to preserve previously learned knowledge.*
3. *Adds newly selected rules to the knowledge base via the update operation.*

To prevent *catastrophic forgetting*, existing weights are frozen during incremental updates; only new candidates are optimised. Joint re-optimisation on $\mathcal{L}_{\text{old}} \cup \mathcal{L}_{\text{new}}$ is possible but risks destabilizing well-tuned rules and costs more.

5.7.4 Human-in-the-Loop Validation

Every learned rule is an explicit first-order formula, so it can be shown to a domain expert in readable form:

Learned Rule 1 (weight = 1.8):

IF connectsTo(X, Y) AND connectsTo(Y, Z) THEN canReach(X,
Z)

The expert may *accept* the rule, *reject* it (e.g., if it encodes a spurious pattern), or *edit* its structure or weight. Per-rule auditability of this kind—impossible with opaque neural parameters—is central to regulatory compliance in healthcare, finance, and legal domains (EU AI Act Article 13; Chapter 7).

5.7.5 Example: Incremental Learning in Cybersecurity

Consider a cybersecurity knowledge base monitoring network traffic, initially containing rules for known attack patterns. After disclosure of a new vulnerability (CVE-2024-12345), the security team labels affected systems as $\mathcal{L}^+ = \{\text{compromised}(\text{srv01}), \text{compromised}(\text{srv07})\}$. Incremental induction with target predicate $\text{compromised}(s)$ yields:

$$\text{hasVulnerability}(s, \text{CVE-2024-12345}) \wedge \text{exposed}(s, \text{internet}) \rightarrow \text{compromised}(s)$$

with weight $w = 2.3$. A security analyst confirms that the rule accurately reflects the attack vector—internet-exposed systems with the vulnerability are indeed being compromised—and approves integration. Once added, the rule immediately contributes to real-time inference, flagging other matching systems for urgent patching.

5.8 Pedagogical Example

A small network-security example, computable by hand, walks through the full induction pipeline.

5.8.1 Learning Reachability Rules

Consider a network domain with the following setup:

Knowledge base predicates: $\text{connectsTo}(h_1, h_2)$ (direct network connection)

Target predicate: $\text{canReach}(h_1, h_2)$ (reachability)

Domain: $\mathcal{C} = \{a, b, c, d\}$ (four hosts)

Facts:

$$\text{connectsTo}(a, b) = 0.9$$

$$\text{connectsTo}(b, c) = 0.8$$

$$\text{connectsTo}(c, d) = 0.85$$

Labels:

• $\mathcal{L}^+ = \{(a, c), (b, d)\}$ (two-hop reachable pairs)

• $\mathcal{L}^- = \{(a, d), (d, a)\}$ (not two-hop reachable pairs)

Template: Chain template of length 2

Candidate rule:

$$\varphi : \text{connectsTo}(x, y) \wedge \text{connectsTo}(y, z) \rightarrow \text{canReach}(x, z)$$

5.8.2 Step 1: Score Computation

For each labelled example, we compute $\sigma_\varphi(e)$, the maximum satisfaction degree of the rule body.

Positive example (a, c) :

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_\varphi(a, c) &= \max_{y \in \mathcal{C}} I(\text{connectsTo}(a, y) \wedge \text{connectsTo}(y, c)) \\ &= \max_{y \in \{a, b, c, d\}} [I(\text{connectsTo}(a, y)) \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} I(\text{connectsTo}(y, c))] \end{aligned}$$

We evaluate each candidate intermediate node y :

$$y = a : \max(0, I(\text{connectsTo}(a, a)) + I(\text{connectsTo}(a, c)) - 1) = \max(0, 0 + 0 - 1) = 0$$

$$y = b : \max(0, I(\text{connectsTo}(a, b)) + I(\text{connectsTo}(b, c)) - 1) = \max(0, 0.9 + 0.8 - 1) = 0.7$$

$$y = c : \max(0, I(\text{connectsTo}(a, c)) + I(\text{connectsTo}(c, c)) - 1) = \max(0, 0 + 0 - 1) = 0$$

$$y = d : \max(0, I(\text{connectsTo}(a, d)) + I(\text{connectsTo}(d, c)) - 1) = \max(0, 0 + 0 - 1) = 0$$

Therefore $\sigma_\varphi(a, c) = \max(0, 0.7, 0, 0) = 0.7$.

Positive example (b, d) :

$$\sigma_\varphi(b, d) = \max_{y \in \mathcal{C}} [I(\text{connectsTo}(b, y)) \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} I(\text{connectsTo}(y, d))]$$

Evaluating:

$$y = c : \max(0, I(\text{connectsTo}(b, c)) + I(\text{connectsTo}(c, d)) - 1) = \max(0, 0.8 + 0.85 - 1) = 0.65$$

All other values of y yield 0, so $\sigma_\varphi(b, d) = 0.65$.

Negative example (a, d) :

$$\sigma_\varphi(a, d) = \max_{y \in \mathcal{C}} [I(\text{connectsTo}(a, y)) \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} I(\text{connectsTo}(y, d))]$$

Since there is no two-hop path from a to d (the actual path requires three hops: $a \rightarrow b \rightarrow c \rightarrow d$), the maximum is 0. Specifically:

$$y = b : \max(0, 0.9 + 0 - 1) = 0 \quad (\text{no edge } b \rightarrow d)$$

$$y = c : \max(0, 0 + 0.85 - 1) = 0 \quad (\text{no edge } a \rightarrow c)$$

Thus $\sigma_\varphi(a, d) = 0$.

Negative example (d, a) :

Similarly, there is no path from d to a in the directed graph, so $\sigma_\varphi(d, a) = 0$.

5.8.3 Step 2: Weight Initialization

We initialise the weight to $w = 0$. At this initialisation, the predicted probabilities are:

$$\hat{p}_e = \sigma(w \cdot \sigma_\varphi(e)) = \sigma(0) = \frac{1}{1 + e^0} = 0.5$$

for all examples, reflecting maximum uncertainty.

5.8.4 Step 3: Gradient Descent Iteration

We compute the gradient using Proposition 5.1. For simplicity, assume $\lambda = 0.1$ and learning rate $\eta = 0.1$.

Initial gradient at $w = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial L}{\partial w} &= - \sum_{e \in \mathcal{L}^+} (1 - \hat{p}_e) \cdot \sigma_\varphi(e) + \sum_{e \in \mathcal{L}^-} \hat{p}_e \cdot \sigma_\varphi(e) + \lambda \cdot \text{sign}(w) \\
&= -(1 - 0.5) \cdot 0.7 - (1 - 0.5) \cdot 0.65 + 0.5 \cdot 0 + 0.5 \cdot 0 + 0.1 \cdot 0 \\
&= -0.5 \cdot 0.7 - 0.5 \cdot 0.65 \\
&= -0.35 - 0.325 = -0.675
\end{aligned}$$

Weight update:

$$w \leftarrow w - \eta \cdot \frac{\partial L}{\partial w} = 0 - 0.1 \cdot (-0.675) = 0.0675$$

After iteration 1: The weight has increased to $w = 0.0675$, reflecting that the rule provides positive evidence (the positive examples have higher scores than the negative examples).

We continue this process for multiple iterations. After convergence (typically 50–100 steps), suppose the final weight is $w^* = 1.8$.

5.8.5 Step 4: Rule Acceptance

Given the acceptance threshold $\tau = 0.5$, we check:

$$|w^*| = 1.8 > \tau = 0.5 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \text{Rule is accepted}$$

The learned rule is added to the knowledge base:

$$(\text{connectsTo}(x, y) \wedge \text{connectsTo}(y, z) \rightarrow \text{canReach}(x, z), w = 1.8)$$

5.8.6 Interpretation

The learned rule encodes two-hop transitivity with moderate confidence ($w = 1.8$, not absolute). Once integrated, it raises the satisfaction degree of $\text{canReach}(a, c)$ and $\text{canReach}(b, d)$ under the Gibbs distribution, consistent with the positive labels. The example underscores three hallmarks of the approach: the formula is readable, optimisation converges in tens of iterations, and the result slots directly into the energy function alongside existing rules.

5.9 Summary

Template-based rule generation keeps the search space tractable; a convex differentiable loss under Łukasiewicz semantics enables efficient weight optimisation; and the resulting algorithm provably converges to the global optimum with statistically consistent weights as the label set grows. A neurosymbolic hybrid architecture built on LLM semantic proposals shrinks the candidate space by over six orders of magnitude in large-vocabulary domains. Learned rules integrate non-destructively into the knowledge base and remain explicit first-order formulas—readable, editable, and auditable by domain experts—preserving the transparency that regulated applications demand.

6 Implementation

LIMEN-AI is released as an open-source Python library.¹ Turning the mathematical abstractions into working software forced decisions about data representation, algorithmic trade-offs, and error handling that have no counterpart in the theoretical formulation (Islam et al., 2019; Li et al., 2023b). Many of these decisions emerged through iterative development rather than upfront planning (Chahuara et al., 2016; Civitarese et al., 2019). The sections below cover architecture and design rationale, the core modules (knowledge representation, energy computation, inference, induction, orchestration) with references to Appendix A, and testing, validation, and deployment practices.

Figure 41: High-level architecture of the LIMEN-AI library. The core module provides foundational data structures used by all other modules. Energy computation supports both scalar evaluation and PyTorch-based automatic differentiation. The inference module generates explanation traces alongside estimates. The orchestrator integrates with external LLM clients for natural language interaction. Source: Author.

Figure 41 shows the high-level architecture. Each module has a single responsibility and communicates through narrow interfaces, so modules can be developed, tested, or replaced independently.

6.1 Design Principles and Philosophy

Four principles shaped the implementation. Each emerged from concrete mistakes or bottlenecks during development.

¹Repository: <https://github.com/enricozanardo/limen-ai>

6.1.1 Guiding Principles

Interpretability first. Every data structure exposes its contents. String representations are human-readable, knowledge bases offer natural-language summaries, inference traces record full reasoning chains, and internal indices are accessible via public methods. Where efficiency and transparency conflict, transparency wins unless the performance cost is prohibitive.

Differentiability throughout. All energy-related computations use PyTorch tensors so that automatic differentiation propagates through every learnable path. Łukasiewicz operations rely on `torch.clamp` and related differentiable primitives; a dual implementation pattern (scalar + tensor) lets developers verify mathematical correctness before confirming gradient flow.

Modularity and composability. Modules are loosely coupled: the core depends only on standard Python and PyTorch; inference depends on core and energy but knows nothing about orchestration; orchestration treats LLM clients as pluggable components. Users can adopt any subset of the library or swap individual modules without ripple effects.

Extensibility through composition. New truth functions, proposal distributions, and LLM clients can be added by implementing abstract base classes; factory methods and dependency injection let users substitute custom implementations without modifying library code.

6.1.2 Technology Choices

The stack is **Python** (readability, ML ecosystem, type hints for static checking via `mypy`), **PyTorch** (eager execution suits dynamic formula graphs; automatic differentiation is a core requirement), and **frozen dataclasses** for immutable, hashable data structures with auto-generated `__init__`/`__repr__`/`__eq__`/`__hash__`.

6.1.3 Error Handling Philosophy

The library follows a *fail-fast* philosophy: public API boundaries validate inputs immediately with descriptive error messages. Core mathematical operations never silently absorb errors, but the orchestration pipeline degrades gracefully—logging warnings and proceeding with partial results when LLM responses are malformed, since partial extractions are often still useful.

6.2 Library Architecture

The architecture is layered. Lower modules know nothing about higher ones, and each layer exposes narrow interfaces upward.

6.2.1 Module Organisation

Six modules (directory structure in Listing 1, Appendix A) divide the work: `core.py` (predicates, atoms, formulas, truth assignments, knowledge bases), `energy.py` (scalar and tensor energy computation), `inference.py` (sampling with explanation traces), `deduction.py` (forward-chaining rule application), `induction.py` (neurosymbolic hybrid ILP with approximately $3 \times 10^5 \times$ speedup over exhaustive template enumeration), and `orchestrator.py` (LLM integration for natural language interaction).

6.2.2 Data Flow

Figure 42: Typical data flow through the LIMEN-AI library. Users construct a knowledge base, initialise truth assignments, compute energy for inference or learning, and optionally discover new rules that feed back into the knowledge base. Source: Author.

Figure 42 traces the typical data flow from knowledge base construction through truth assignment initialisation, energy computation, inference with trace generation, and optional rule learning. Discovered rules feed back into the knowledge base, and users can iterate between steps as their domain understanding evolves.

6.3 Core Data Structures

The core data structures balance three demands: expressiveness for NMLN reasoning, efficient lookup and computation, and clarity under inspection.

6.3.1 Predicates, Constants, and Atoms

Predicates and constants (Listings 2 and 3, Appendix A) are frozen dataclasses—immutable and hashable, safe for use as dictionary keys. `Predicate` implements `__call__` so that `connected("a","b")` creates the corresponding atom directly, with arity validation at construction time. `Atom` validates argument counts in `__post_init__` and provides a `substitute` method for grounding variables to constants.

6.3.2 Formula Nodes

Formulas are abstract syntax trees (Listing 4, Appendix A), chosen over string parsing or bytecode compilation so that logical structure stays directly inspectable. Each node supports two evaluation modes: scalar (Python floats, handy for debugging) and tensor (PyTorch, for differentiable computation). `torch.clamp` enforces the $[0, 1]$ range in tensor mode against floating-point drift. The same dual pattern appears throughout the library—scalar for readability, tensor for GPU-accelerated gradients.

6.3.3 Truth Assignments and Knowledge Bases

`TruthAssignment` (Listing 5, Appendix A) implements the Mapping protocol with $[0, 1]$ validation and a closed-world default of zero for unassigned atoms. `KnowledgeBase` (Listing 6, Appendix A) aggregates vocabulary, weighted formulas, and the current truth assignment. Its `set_truth` method auto-registers predicates and constants, cutting boilerplate. Frequently used mappings (e.g., the atom-to-tensor index) are cached and invalidated automatically on change.

6.4 Energy Computation

Energy computation—the weighted sum of satisfaction degrees over all formulas—needs to be efficient and differentiable at the same time.

6.4.1 Scalar and Tensor Implementations

The scalar path (Listing 7, Appendix A) iterates over formulas in standard Python. A `compute_energy_breakdown` helper lists each formula’s contribution, which proves invaluable for debugging and audit logging. The tensor path (Listing 8, Appendix A)

wraps truth values in a PyTorch tensor. The atom-to-index mapping is cached and auto-invalidated to ensure gradients flow to the correct parameters.

6.4.2 Ground Satisfaction Averaging

Universally quantified formulas are evaluated as the average satisfaction degree over all groundings. Because k free variables over n constants produce n^k groundings (Theorem 3.7), this step dominates cost for broad formulas; careful formula design (limiting free variables) keeps it tractable, while lifted inference is planned for future versions.

Figure 43: Computation graph for tensor-based energy computation. Truth values flow through atom indexing, Łukasiewicz operations, weight multiplication, and summation to produce the energy. Gradients flow backward (dashed arrow) through the same graph via automatic differentiation. Source: Author.

Figure 43 shows the tensor computation graph; PyTorch traverses it backward to compute gradients for all learning algorithms.

6.5 Inference Module

Every inference produces both a numerical estimate and a structured explanation trace recording each rule’s contribution, so results are auditable by default.

6.5.1 Importance Sampling

`ImportanceSampler` (Listing 9, Appendix A) implements the algorithm from Section 4 in log space to avoid overflow and underflow, relying on the importance sampling identity (Theorem 4.2) and using the self-normalised estimator (Proposition 4.2) to bypass the intractable partition function. The proposal distribution is pluggable (default: uniform); custom distributions subclass `ProposalDistribution`. Traces are built inline during sampling, capturing per-rule, per-sample contributions without a separate post-processing pass.

6.5.2 Explanation Traces

`ExplanationTrace` (Listing 10, Appendix A) offers three views: `rule_importance` ranks rules by importance-weighted contribution across samples; `effective_sample_size` quantifies estimate quality using the relationship between ESS and proposal–target divergence established in Proposition 4.3; and `summary` produces a human-readable overview—top samples, dominant rules, diagnostics—suitable for audit logs.

6.6 Orchestration Pipeline

Orchestration bridges natural language and formal logic so that domain experts can interact with the knowledge base without writing code.

6.6.1 Pipeline Architecture

`LimemPipeline` (Listing 11, Appendix A) acts as a Facade: it coordinates document ingestion, query translation, and response generation behind a small set of high-level methods, with callback hooks for monitoring. State persistence (`save_state/load_state`) serialises the schema and truth assignments to JSON, so a knowledge base can be built incrementally across sessions.

6.6.2 Document Ingestion

Document ingestion (Listing 12, Appendix A) first chunks text (default: 1 000 words, 100-word overlap), then prompts the LLM for JSON-structured fact extraction constrained by the schema registry (Listing 13, Appendix A). Each extracted fact is validated—predicate name, arity, argument types—before entering the knowledge base. Malformed or hallucinated outputs are logged for review but never committed.

6.7 Testing and Validation

Testing operates at three levels. **Unit tests** (Listing 14, Appendix A) check individual functions against edge cases and mathematical properties such as negation involution, conjunction identity, and implication tautology. **Integration tests** exercise the full pipeline—knowledge base construction through inference and state persistence—to catch interface mismatches and state-management bugs. **Property-based tests**

randomly generate inputs and verify invariants: all Łukasiewicz outputs lie in $[0, 1]$, importance sampling converges as sample count grows, and so on. These often surface edge cases that hand-crafted tests miss.

6.7.1 Continuous Integration

GitHub Actions (Listing 15, Appendix A) runs mypy (strict), flake8, and pytest on every push, across Python 3.9–3.11. Coverage reports go to Codecov (target: $\geq 90\%$ for core modules). Version tags trigger automatic PyPI publication.

6.8 Performance Considerations

6.8.1 Computational Complexity

Energy computation is $O(|F|)$ per formula (Theorem 3.6), plus $O(n^k)$ groundings for k free variables over n constants, yielding an aggregate cost of $O(m \cdot n^{k_{\max}} \cdot |\varphi|_{\max})$ per energy evaluation (Corollary 3.3). Importance sampling adds a factor of S samples, giving $O(S \cdot |F|)$. GPU acceleration via PyTorch yields significant speedups for batch tensor operations. The implementation exhibits near-linear scaling with respect to the number of formulas for fixed domain sizes, while scaling polynomially with domain size for fixed formula counts. For small knowledge bases, tensor overhead may exceed scalar cost; beyond roughly 200 formulas the GPU path dominates. Detailed benchmarking across hardware configurations remains future work.

6.8.2 Caching Strategies

Three caches mitigate repeated work: the *atom index* (atom-to-tensor mapping, invalidated on change), *formula memoization* (keyed by assignment identity, avoiding costly equality checks), and *ground formula caching* (storing grounded instantiations for formulas evaluated many times during sampling). All caches are bounded with LRU eviction.

6.9 Deployment and Distribution

The library is distributed on PyPI as `limen-ai` under AGPLv3 (Listing 16, Appendix A). Installation via `pip` pulls PyTorch as the main dependency; a basic usage example is in Listing 18 (Appendix A).

6.9.1 Advanced Usage Patterns

Three usage patterns recur. *Incremental construction* (Listing 19, Appendix A) adds predicates and facts as they arrive, fitting continuous-monitoring workflows. *Neurosymbolic rule learning* (Listings 20–22, Appendix A) replaces exhaustive $O(P^3)$ template enumeration with LLM semantic proposal, data-driven validation, and differentiable weight optimisation, cutting computation from hours to seconds ($\sim 3 \times 10^5 \times$ speedup). *Decision support* (Listing 23, Appendix A) wraps inference in a function that emits structured explanations suitable for audit and regulatory compliance.

6.10 Limitations and Future Development

6.10.1 Current Limitations

Scalability. The implementation handles hundreds to thousands of atoms well; million-atom knowledge bases would need distributed computing or lifted inference. Storing the full fuzzy interpretation alone requires $O(|\mathcal{P}| \cdot n^{a_{\max}})$ space (Theorem 3.8), and the bottleneck is grounding: k free variables over n constants yield n^k ground formulas, and four variables over 100 constants already produce 10^8 groundings. Users can mitigate this by decomposing formulas, adding type constraints, and avoiding unnecessary universal quantification.

LLM dependence. The orchestration pipeline relies on external LLM services, introducing latency, cost, and availability risks. Local model support (via Hugging Face Transformers) is planned for air-gapped and cost-sensitive deployments.

6.10.2 Planned Enhancements

Four enhancements are planned: *lazy grounding*, which defers ground-formula generation until query time; *parallel GPU sampling*, batching importance samples for higher throughput; *local LLM support*, plugging Hugging Face models into the existing `LLMClient` interface; and *interactive visualization* with knowledge-base graphs, trace exploration, and rule-importance dashboards.

Contributions follow the fork–branch–test–PR workflow shown in Figure 44.

Figure 44: Contribution workflow for LIMEN-AI. Contributors fork the repository, develop features on branches, ensure tests pass, then submit pull requests for code review before merging. Source: Author.

6.11 Experimental Validation on Legal Case Retrieval

We evaluate LIMEN-AI on the COLIEE benchmark (COLIEE, 2025), Task 1 (case law retrieval). The neurosymbolic re-ranking architecture achieves substantially higher *precision* than BM25—at the cost of some recall—and produces fully explainable rankings, something no purely statistical baseline offers.

6.11.1 The COLIEE Case Law Retrieval Task

COLIEE Task 1 provides 2,159 Canadian court decisions and 400 queries; systems must retrieve relevant precedents as judged by legal professionals. Legal relevance depends on analogous principles and reasoning structures, not just keyword overlap—a contract-breach query may be highly relevant to a warranty-obligations precedent even when the terminology differs entirely. Cases range from concise summary judgments to lengthy appellate opinions, stressing extraction robustness across varying document complexity.

6.11.2 The Neurosymbolic Re-ranking Architecture

The architecture operates in three stages.

Stage 1: Candidate retrieval with BM25. BM25 (Robertson and Zaragoza, 2009) retrieves the top-5 candidates per query in milliseconds, narrowing the 2,159-document corpus to a tractable set. Five candidates balance recall against LLM extraction cost (~ 10 – 12 seconds per document with Llama 3.1, 8B parameters); larger pools would linearly increase latency.

Stage 2: Logic extraction via LLM prompting. The LLM extracts *facts* (ground atoms) from query cases and *rules* (weighted implications) from candidates, much as a legal researcher maps a new factual scenario against established principles.

A fixed schema (party, claim, fact, ruling, etc.), iteratively refined for reliability, constrains the output to JSON-structured extractions.

Stage 3: Entailment scoring and re-ranking. For each query–candidate pair, a temporary knowledge base is built: candidate rules become weighted formulas and query facts initialise the truth assignment. The entailment score—the average Łukasiewicz satisfaction degree of the candidate’s rules under the query’s facts—quantifies logical alignment. Re-ranking by this score can override BM25’s keyword-based ordering, promoting cases with strong principled overlap even when lexical similarity is modest.

Figure 45: The three-stage neurosymbolic re-ranking pipeline. BM25 provides efficient candidate retrieval, LLM extraction produces structured logic, and entailment scoring quantifies logical relevance while generating explainable rankings. Source: Author.

Figure 45 shows the pipeline. Each stage is independently replaceable: a different retriever, LLM, or scoring mechanism can be swapped in without touching the other stages.

6.11.3 Experimental Setup and Evaluation Protocol

We report precision, recall, and F1 at rank 3 (legal researchers typically examine only the top few hits). Three baselines span different retrieval paradigms: **BM25** (keyword statistics), **BERT-Legal**² (BERT base fine-tuned on legal text), and **Ollama-COLIEE** (COLIEE-LLaMA, 1B, prompt-based retrieval). A 20-query development phase tuned hyperparameters; the full evaluation covered all 400 COLIEE test queries. Per-query processing time for LIMEN-AI was ~ 30 s (1 s BM25, 25–28 s LLM extraction, 1–2 s entailment scoring), acceptable for batch legal research.

Hardware: NVIDIA RTX 4080 (16 GB), AMD Ryzen 9 7950X, 64 GB RAM; Python 3.11, LIMEN-AI v0.3.0; Llama 3.1 (8B) via Ollama for local, reproducible LLM inference. All traces and evaluation scripts are in the project repository.

²BERT-Legal denotes a standard BERT-base model (Devlin et al., 2019) fine-tuned by the author on the COLIEE legal corpus for baseline comparison; it is not a separately published system.

6.11.4 Quantitative Results

Table 15 presents the results. LIMEN-AI achieves 11.67% precision—a 46% relative gain over BM25’s 8.00%—meaning that among three retrieved cases a practitioner reviews, more will actually be relevant.

Table 15: Experimental results on COLIEE Task 1 case law retrieval (400 queries, 2159 documents in corpus). Metrics computed for top-3 retrieved results. Explainability percentage indicates proportion of results with structured logical justifications. Source: Author.

Method	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Explainability
BM25	8.00%	31.00%	12.18%	0%
BERT-Legal	2.00%	5.40%	2.90%	0%
Ollama-COLIEE	(skipped—context window limitation)			
LIMEN-AI Re-ranker	11.67%	16.67%	12.30%	100%

Recall drops (16.67% vs. BM25’s 31.00%) because only the top-5 BM25 candidates enter re-ranking; documents BM25 misses are unrecoverable. The F1 scores are nearly identical (12.30% vs. 12.18%), indicating that the precision gain compensates for the recall loss in the harmonic mean. With 400 queries, the standard error of the mean precision estimate is approximately $\sqrt{p(1-p)/n} \approx 1.6$ percentage points, yielding a 95% confidence interval of roughly [8.5%, 14.8%] for LIMEN-AI and [5.3%, 10.7%] for BM25; the intervals overlap only marginally, supporting the reliability of the observed difference. LIMEN-AI additionally provides fully structured explanations for every result.

BERT-Legal performed poorly (2.00% precision, 2.90% F1). Its general-purpose dense embeddings missed the specific factual and doctrinal parallels that define legal relevance, consistent with findings that domain-specific term weighting often outperforms generic semantic embeddings in professional domains (Zhong et al., 2020). Ollama-COLIEE could not be evaluated at all: its 2048-token context window cannot accommodate both a query and corpus-scale retrieval, underscoring the advantage of separating retrieval from reasoning.

6.11.5 Qualitative Analysis: Explainability

The explainability column in Table 15 stands out: 100% for LIMEN-AI, 0% for every baseline. Each ranked result carries a trace that decomposes the relevance score into individual rule satisfactions. BM25 and BERT, by contrast, produce only opaque

numerical scores.

Figure 46 shows a representative trace. The query concerned breach of a construction contract (delay, replacement costs); the top precedent (entailment score 0.62) dealt with analogous incomplete contractual performance in a commercial lease. Four of the candidate’s five extracted rules were satisfied:

Query 067520: Breach of construction contract (delay + replacement costs)
Top Result: Case 049739 (Logic Score: 0.62)

Extracted Query Facts (11 atoms):
claim(plaintiff, damages), fact(breach_of_contract),
fact(delay_in_performance), party(plaintiff, homeowner),
party(defendant, contractor), statute(Civil_Code_Art_415), ...

Extracted Candidate Rules (5 implications):
Rule 1: fact(breach) \wedge claim(X, damages) \rightarrow ruling(damages_awarded)
 \rightsquigarrow Satisfaction degree: **0.85** (antecedent strongly satisfied)
Rule 2: statute(Art_415) \rightarrow applies_to(breach_cases)
 \rightsquigarrow Satisfaction degree: **0.90** (statute mentioned in query)
Rule 3: claim(X, damages) \rightarrow requires(proof_of_loss)
 \rightsquigarrow Satisfaction degree: **0.75** (claim present, loss documented)
Rule 4: fact(delay) \rightarrow entitles(consequential_damages)
 \rightsquigarrow Satisfaction degree: **0.60** (delay fact present)
Rule 5: statute(Art_709) \rightarrow applies_to(tort_cases)
 \rightsquigarrow Satisfaction degree: **0.00** (statute not applicable here)

Entailment Score: $(0.85 + 0.90 + 0.75 + 0.60 + 0.00) / 5 = \mathbf{0.62}$

Explanation: This precedent establishes the principle that breach of contractual obligations (Rule 1), particularly when statutory provisions for contractual damages apply (Rule 2), creates entitlement to compensatory damages (Rule 3) and, in cases involving delay, consequential damages for additional costs (Rule 4). The analogous factual pattern (breach, delay, damages claim) justifies high relevance.

Figure 46: Example explanation trace for a query-candidate pair with high entailment score. The trace decomposes the relevance judgment into specific rule satisfactions, enabling validation by legal experts. Source: Author.

- Rule 1 (breach \rightarrow damages) is strongly satisfied (0.85) because both the breach fact and the damages claim appear in the query with high confidence.
- Rule 2 (statute Art_415 applies to breach) is satisfied (0.90) because the query explicitly cites this provision governing contractual remedies.
- Rule 3 (damages require proof of loss) is satisfied (0.75) based on the query’s documentation of replacement costs.

- Rule 4 (delay entitles consequential damages) is moderately satisfied (0.60) based on the delay fact.
- Rule 5 (tort statute applicability) is not satisfied (0.00) because the query involves contract law, not tort law.

A legal expert reviewing this trace can judge whether each rule’s application is sound and, where it is not, refine the knowledge base. Unlike post-hoc methods such as SHAP or LIME—which flag important terms but cannot show how those terms combine into a coherent legal argument—the trace exposes the full reasoning chain. The distinction matters for EU AI Act Article 13 compliance (European Parliament and Council, 2024).

Across the 400 queries, high-scoring pairs typically had 3–5 rules with satisfaction above 0.5. Low-scoring pairs either yielded few extracted rules or rules whose antecedents found no support in the query facts. In roughly 15% of cases, re-ranking corrected a BM25 error, demoting keyword-similar but logically irrelevant cases and promoting principled matches.

6.11.6 Discussion and Implications

For legal research, where practitioners examine a handful of cases in depth, top-result quality (precision) matters more than broad coverage (recall). The comparable F1 scores show that BM25 and LIMEN-AI sit at different but equally reasonable points on the precision–recall curve; LIMEN-AI adds full explainability on top.

The precision gain over BM25 supports the claim that even approximate logical structure—extracted via LLM prompting—improves relevance estimation in domains where reasoning patterns are explicit, as in judicial opinions. Query latency of roughly 30 seconds, dominated by LLM extraction, is acceptable for batch research. Interactive use would benefit from caching extracted logic or pre-computing representations offline.

Several limitations remain. The candidate-selection bottleneck means broader first-stage retrieval could recover missed documents. Extraction robustness depends on prompt engineering and hallucination reduction. The fixed `party/claim/fact/ruling` vocabulary may be too coarse for multi-theory cases. Despite these gaps, competitive quantitative performance paired with complete

explainability makes LIMEN-AI a viable tool for legal AI under the transparency mandates of the EU AI Act.

6.11.7 Complementary Evaluation: Statute Retrieval

The case law evaluation reported in Table 15 demonstrates LIMEN-AI’s behaviour on one category of legal retrieval. To probe how well the engine adapts to a structurally different task, I conducted a complementary evaluation on COLIEE Task 1 statute law retrieval, which requires identifying relevant legislative provisions for a given legal query. The experiment used LIMEN-AI v0.2.5 with Llama 3.1 8B across ten sample cases drawn from the COLIEE statute corpus. Note that this is a *pilot illustration* of the pipeline’s adaptability; the sample size ($n = 10$) is too small for statistical inference, and the results should be interpreted as indicative rather than conclusive. Table 16 summarises the results.

Table 16: Statute law retrieval results on COLIEE Task 1 (10 sample cases, LIMEN-AI v0.2.5 with Llama 3.1 8B). Source: Author.

Method	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Explainability
LIMEN-AI	76.7%	95.0%	83.7%	100%

The contrast with the full-corpus case law task is striking: precision rises from 11.67% to 76.7%, and F1 from 12.30% to 83.7%. This gap reflects the fundamentally different nature of the two corpora rather than a change in the engine itself. Statute retrieval involves a small set of well-structured legislative provisions whose language follows predictable drafting conventions, making LLM-based rule extraction considerably more reliable. Case law retrieval, by contrast, spans 2,159 diverse judicial opinions whose reasoning structures vary widely—extraction must contend with discursive argumentation, implicit legal principles, and inconsistent terminology across decades of jurisprudence.

What remains invariant across both tasks is explainability coverage: every result returned by LIMEN-AI, whether a statute or a case, carries a complete explanation trace linking the relevance judgment to specific rule satisfactions. The statute task confirms that LIMEN-AI can achieve competitive precision when the target domain is well-structured and extraction is dependable, while the case law task exposes the challenges that LLM-based extraction faces on unstructured judicial text. Together, the two evaluations delineate a clear direction for future work: improving extraction

robustness on free-form legal prose is the primary bottleneck separating the engine’s current case law performance from the levels it already attains on statutory material.

6.11.8 Cross-Domain Pipeline Validation

While the formal evaluation above focused on legal case retrieval, the orchestration pipeline was designed to be domain-agnostic. To verify this claim, I validated the full thirteen-step pipeline on three additional document types drawn from distinct professional domains. Table 17 summarises the results.

Table 17: Cross-domain extraction results. Each document was processed through the complete thirteen-step pipeline without domain-specific configuration.

Source: Author.

Domain	Document Type	Predicates	Vocabulary Character
Contractual	Service agreement	6	Transactional (e.g. <code>payment</code> , <code>obligation</code>)
Regulatory	GDPR privacy policy	6	Regulatory (e.g. <code>dataSubject</code> , <code>consent</code>)
Cybersecurity	ISO 27001 Annex A	10–15	Hierarchical taxonomy of controls

The most telling observation is that schema overlap between the contractual and regulatory extractions was zero per cent: the LLM-driven extraction layer invented entirely different predicate vocabularies for each domain rather than forcing documents into a pre-defined ontology. This adaptive behaviour supports the thesis that the pipeline’s logic layer operates on structure, not on domain-specific lexical cues.

From a scalability standpoint, the ISO 27001 Annex A document—exceeding 2 500 words—was processed in under ten seconds, yielding a throughput above 200 words per second on commodity hardware. These figures suggest that enterprise-length policy documents remain well within the pipeline’s practical operating range.

I note that these cross-domain runs constitute functional validation: they confirm that the pipeline executes correctly and produces coherent knowledge bases across domains, but they do not include ground-truth annotations against which precision or recall could be measured. Systematic cross-domain evaluation with annotated corpora is identified as future work in Chapter 9.

6.12 Summary

LIMEN-AI’s mathematical framework maps onto a modular, open-source Python library. The dual scalar/tensor pattern lets developers inspect algorithms in plain

Python and train with GPU-accelerated PyTorch using the same formula structures. Explanation traces are built into inference from the start—every conclusion carries an auditable reasoning record. The orchestration pipeline bridges natural language and formal logic, making the library usable by domain experts who do not write code.

On COLIEE Task 1 case law retrieval, LIMEN-AI achieved a 46% relative precision improvement over BM25 with comparable F1 and 100% explainable rankings. A complementary statute retrieval evaluation demonstrated 76.7% precision and 83.7% F1, confirming that the engine achieves strong performance when extraction reliability is high. Cross-domain validation on service agreements, GDPR privacy policies, and ISO 27001 controls showed that the pipeline adapts its extraction vocabulary to each domain without manual configuration. Grounding scalability and LLM dependence remain engineering challenges, addressed by planned lazy grounding, parallel sampling, and local model support. Complete code listings appear in Appendix A.

7 Regulatory Compliance

Regulated environments increasingly require AI systems to be transparent, accountable, and subject to human oversight (Floridi et al., 2018; Jobin et al., 2019; Mittelstadt et al., 2016). LIMEN-AI was designed with these constraints in mind. Its explicit knowledge representation, traceable inference, and controllable complexity speak directly to the obligations imposed by the European Union Artificial Intelligence Act (EU AI Act) (Hacker et al., 2023; Novelli et al., 2024).

The analysis below covers three areas: the transparency, oversight, and documentation obligations the EU AI Act places on high-risk systems; evidence that LIMEN-AI satisfies them structurally rather than through post-hoc additions; and deployment workflow patterns that put these capabilities into practice.

7.1 The EU AI Act: Requirements for High-Risk Systems

Three clusters of obligations bear on LIMEN-AI: Articles 13 (transparency), 14 (human oversight), and 11–12 (documentation).

7.1.1 Overview and Scope

The EU AI Act, which entered into force in August 2024, establishes a risk-based regulatory framework for artificial intelligence systems deployed or affecting persons within the European Union (European Parliament and Council, 2024). Systems are categorised by risk level, with “high-risk” systems subject to the most stringent requirements. High-risk categories include AI systems used in critical infrastructure, education, employment, essential services, law enforcement, migration, and the administration of justice.

Organisations deploying high-risk AI systems must demonstrate compliance with a comprehensive set of requirements before placing systems on the market or putting them into service. Non-compliance can result in significant penalties, including fines of up to €35 million or 7% of global annual turnover.

7.1.2 Transparency Requirements

Article 13 requires that high-risk systems be transparent enough for users to interpret outputs appropriately. Outputs must be *intelligible*—users should understand their

meaning in context. The system’s intended purpose, accuracy, and limitations must be *documented*. *Input dependencies* must be clear, showing how changes propagate to outputs. And *uncertainty* must be communicated when confidence varies. Users should be able to form a mental model of the system’s reasoning, not just receive a score.

7.1.3 Human Oversight Requirements

Article 14 mandates effective human oversight of high-risk systems. Overseers must understand the system’s capacities and limitations, guard against automation bias, correctly interpret outputs using available tools, override or disregard any particular output, and interrupt the system at will. Opaque systems make these obligations hard to meet (Goddard et al., 2012): an overseer who cannot understand why an output was produced cannot exercise meaningful oversight (Baniecki and Biecek, 2025).

7.1.4 Documentation Requirements

Articles 11 and 12 require comprehensive *technical documentation* (specifications, design choices, test results), *automatic logging* of risk-relevant events accessible for audit, and sufficient *traceability* to reconstruct the reasoning behind any specific decision. The system must generate auditable records of *how* it reasons, not just *what* it outputs.

7.2 LIMEN-AI’s Compliance Architecture

LIMEN-AI achieves compliance *by design*: transparency and interpretability are foundational constraints, not afterthoughts bolted onto a black-box core. Explicit knowledge representation, traceable inference, and human-readable explanations—the architectural pillars developed earlier—map directly onto the obligations outlined above.

7.2.1 Transparency by Design

Four architectural properties jointly produce transparency. The knowledge base consists of *explicit weighted first-order rules* readable by domain experts. Truth values in $[0, 1]$ carry clear semantics as degrees of belief. The Łukasiewicz operations that

combine them are mathematically simple—corresponding to intuitive conjunction, disjunction, and implication—so users can trace how conclusions follow from premises. Finally, the energy function provides a global measure of how well an interpretation satisfies the knowledge base, offering an intuitive frame for explaining behaviour.

Since the reasoning *is* the explanation—no hidden computation needs post-hoc reconstruction—LIMEN-AI is natively compatible with automated compliance checkers. The CO2 framework of Prathyush Turaga et al. (2025), which builds knowledge graphs from legal documents for AI compliance auditing (Prathyush Turaga et al., 2025), could validate LIMEN-AI’s logic traces directly against regulator-defined ontologies.

7.2.2 Traceable Inference

Inference produces structured explanation traces at two granularities. At the *sample level*, each importance sample records its contribution to the final estimate, letting users inspect which scenarios mattered most. At the *rule level*, satisfaction degrees connect numerical results to specific domain knowledge. Differentiability of the energy function makes counterfactual “what-if” queries straightforward, and aggregated summaries identify the most influential rules overall. These traces provide the complete, auditable reasoning records that Articles 11–12 demand.

7.2.3 Controllable Complexity

Complexity is kept within human comprehension through template-based induction (constraining learned rules to interpretable patterns), L^1 weight regularisation (promoting sparse, simpler knowledge bases), adjustable sampling budgets (trading precision against response time), and query scoping (focusing inference on relevant predicates rather than the full knowledge base).

7.3 Mapping Requirements to Capabilities

The tables below align specific EU AI Act articles with the LIMEN-AI mechanisms that fulfill them.

7.3.1 Transparency Mapping

Table 18 summarises how LIMEN-AI’s technical capabilities address the transparency requirements of Article 13.

Table 18: Mapping of EU AI Act transparency requirements to LIMEN-AI capabilities. Source: Author.

Requirement	LIMEN-AI Capability	Mechanism
Intelligible outputs	Explicit truth degrees with semantic content	$[0, 1]$ interval semantics
Capability information	Knowledge base is directly inspectable	Weighted first-order rules
Input dependencies	Differentiable energy function	Gradient computation
Uncertainty communication	Probabilistic semantics over interpretations	Gibbs distribution

Having established how LIMEN-AI satisfies the transparency obligations of Article 13, the next subsection examines how these same technical capabilities support the human oversight requirements of Article 14.

7.3.2 Human Oversight Mapping

Table 19 covers the human oversight requirements under Article 14.

Table 19: Mapping of EU AI Act human oversight requirements to LIMEN-AI capabilities. Source: Author.

Requirement	LIMEN-AI Capability	Mechanism
Effective oversight	Transparent knowledge representation	Readable rules and facts
Automation bias mitigation	Explanation traces with attribution	Rule importance scores
Interpretation capability	Structured reasoning traces	Sample and rule attribution
Override capability	Modifiable knowledge base	Weight adjustment, fact modification
Interruption capability	Query-based inference	Stateless computation

The oversight mechanisms catalogued in Table 19 rely, in turn, on robust documentation and logging infrastructure to remain auditable over time. The following subsection maps these documentation obligations.

7.3.3 Documentation Mapping

Table 20 addresses the documentation requirements under Articles 11 and 12.

Table 20: Mapping of EU AI Act documentation requirements to LIMEN-AI capabilities. Source: Author.

Requirement	LIMEN-AI Capability	Mechanism
Technical documentation	Serialisable knowledge bases	JSON/database export
Automatic logging	Inference trace recording	Structured trace objects
Traceability	Complete reasoning records	Sample-level attribution

Taken together, the three mapping tables above demonstrate that LIMEN-AI’s architecture addresses the transparency, oversight, and documentation pillars of the EU AI Act through complementary mechanisms rather than ad-hoc patches. The next subsection builds on this foundation by specifying the concrete audit protocol through which third parties can verify conformity.

7.4 Technical Documentation for Regulatory Auditing

Compliance also requires *demonstrable conformity*—documentation and audit trails that third parties can verify (Articles 43–44). Fernsel et al. (2024) and Mökander et al. (2022) identify four essential audit capabilities for high-risk systems (Fernsel et al., 2024; Mökander et al., 2022). LIMEN-AI satisfies each of them, and the analysis below extends into a multi-layered audit protocol.

7.4.1 Conformity Assessment Requirements

Fernsel et al. (2024) developed a plugin for auditing Moodle’s Learning Analytics component under the EU AI Act’s conformity assessment requirements (Fernsel et al., 2024). Their work identifies four fundamental capabilities that AI systems must provide for effective auditing—a framework well suited to evaluating LIMEN-AI’s audit readiness.

Capability 1: Audit Data Upload and Selection. Auditors must be able to upload test datasets or select subsets of operational data for evaluation. This enables

both pre-market testing (verifying performance on standardised benchmarks) and post-market monitoring (analysing performance on real-world cases that triggered concerns).

LIMEN-AI Implementation: Knowledge bases are stored as human-readable files in JSON or YAML format (‘.limen’ extension), containing formulas, weights, and metadata. Training and test data are provided in standard formats (CSV, Pandas DataFrames, SQL databases). The system provides programmatic APIs for data loading:

```
1 # Auditor loads specific cases for review
2 import limen
3 audit_cases = pd.read_csv("suspicious_decisions.csv")
4 kb = limen.load_kb("production_model_v3.2.limen")
5 results = kb.infer_batch(audit_cases, return_traces=True)
```

Auditors can thus verify data quality through direct inspection, satisfying Article 10(3)’s requirement that training data be “relevant, representative, free of errors and complete.”

Capability 2: Model Configuration vs. Trained Models. Auditors must clearly differentiate the system’s *configuration* (hyperparameters, architectural choices, formula templates) from the *trained model* (learned weights, rule instantiations, calibration parameters). Without this distinction, it is impossible to tell whether observed behaviour stems from design choices or from patterns learned from data.

LIMEN-AI Implementation: Knowledge base metadata records all configuration parameters:

```
1 kb.metadata = {
2     "version": "3.2.1",
3     "training_date": "2024-11-15",
4     "training_data_hash": "sha256:a3f2...",
5     "inference_algorithm": "power_sampling",
6     "temperature_schedule": [1.0, 0.5, 0.1],
7     "num_samples": 10000,
8     "learning_rate": 0.01,
9     "l1_regularisation": 0.001
```

10 }

Trained models are serialised using PyTorch’s state dictionary mechanism, preserving exact numerical weights. Configuration lives in metadata; learned parameters live in the state dict. Auditors can therefore distinguish design decisions from emergent learned behaviour.

Capability 3: Persistence for Future Inspections. Models, configurations, and training data must be retained for post-market monitoring and incident investigation. The EU AI Act’s Article 12(1) mandates that high-risk systems “be designed and developed with capabilities enabling the automatic recording of events (logs) while the high-risk AI systems are operating.”

LIMEN-AI Implementation: Each deployment creates an immutable snapshot with timestamp and version identifier. Knowledge bases are version-controlled using Git, providing a complete audit trail of all changes:

```
1 git log production_model.limen
2 commit a3f2e1b 2024-11-15 "Update rule weights after
   validation"
3 commit 7c8d9a2 2024-11-10 "Add new rule for edge case
   handling"
4 commit 2b4f6e3 2024-11-01 "Initial production deployment"
```

Data lineage is recorded in metadata, linking each trained model to the specific dataset used for training (identified by cryptographic hash). The exact conditions under which the model was developed can therefore be reconstructed, satisfying Article 11(1)’s requirement for “comprehensive technical documentation.”

Capability 4: Raw Predictions for Further Analysis. Auditors need access to individual predictions—not just aggregated metrics—for fairness audits, bias detection, and error analysis. Aggregate scores like accuracy or F1 can mask systematic biases against specific subpopulations.

LIMEN-AI Implementation: Inference traces record complete reasoning information for each query:

```
1 trace = kb.infer("Relevant(doc_1337, case_42)",
2                 evidence=evidence,
```

```

3         return_trace=True)
4
5 # Trace contains:
6 trace.query # "Relevant(doc_1337, case_42)"
7 trace.evidence # Dictionary of observed truth degrees
8 trace.samples # List of sampled interpretations
9 trace.formula_contributions # Per-formula energy
   contributions
10 trace.final_prediction # Expected truth degree with CI

```

Traces are serialisable to JSON for integration with external analysis tools (SHAP, LIME, custom auditing software). This satisfies Article 14(4)(a)’s requirement that systems provide “the ability to correctly interpret the system’s outputs.”

Table 21: Mapping of Fernsel et al.’s conformity assessment capabilities to LIMEN-AI’s technical implementation and corresponding EU AI Act articles. Source: Author.

Capability	LIMEN-AI Implementation	Mechanism	AI Act Article
Audit data upload	<code>limen.load_kb()</code> , <code>set_evidence()</code>	JSON/CSV APIs	Article 10(3)
Configuration model	vs. Metadata + PyTorch state dict	Separate serialisation	Article 11(1)
Persistence	Git-versioned <code>.limen</code> files	Immutable snapshots	Article 12(1)
Raw predictions	Inference traces with satisfaction degrees	JSON export	Article 14(4)(a)

Table 21 aligns Fernsel’s framework with LIMEN-AI’s implementation and the relevant EU AI Act articles. Each audit capability required by the regulation is realised through an explicit technical mechanism in LIMEN-AI’s architecture.

7.4.2 Article 14(4) Compliance: Interpreting System Outputs

Article 14(4)(a) merits close attention:

“High-risk AI systems shall be designed and developed in such a way that natural persons to whom human oversight is assigned are enabled [...] to correctly interpret the system’s outputs, taking into account in

particular the characteristics of the system and the interpretation tools and methods available.”

Three obligations follow: *correct interpretation* of outputs, understanding of the *system characteristics* that produced them, and provision of *interpretation tools*.

Correct Interpretation: Semantic Clarity. A neural network that outputs 0.87 for a binary classification provides no inherent semantic content. Is this a probability? If so, of what event? Under what distributional assumptions? How should a human overseer interpret this number when making a decision?

LIMEN-AI’s outputs are *expected fuzzy truth degrees* of logical formulas:

$$\mu_Q = \mathbb{E}_P[I(Q)] = 0.87 \quad \text{where} \quad Q = \text{Relevant}(\text{doc}_{1337}, \text{case}_{42})$$

The reading is unambiguous: “Given the knowledge base and observed evidence, formula Q is satisfied to degree 0.87 on average across the probability distribution over interpretations induced by the energy function.” This is a *logical satisfaction degree* computed from explicit rules, not a frequency-based probability derived from training data statistics. The overseer therefore knows exactly what quantity is being reported and can judge its relevance to the decision at hand.

System Characteristics: Causal Explanation. Knowing *what* the output means is not enough; Article 14(4) also requires understanding *how* the system arrived at it. Neural networks apply high-dimensional nonlinear transformations layer by layer, making causal tracing infeasible for humans.

LIMEN-AI’s explanation traces decompose μ_Q into contributions from individual rules:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_Q &= 0.87 \\ &= \text{Contribution from } \varphi_{23} (\text{Cites}(x, y) \wedge \text{Relevant}(y, c) \Rightarrow \text{Relevant}(x, c)) : 0.43 \\ &\quad + \text{Contribution from } \varphi_{17} (\text{SameTopic}(x, y) \wedge \text{Relevant}(y, c) \Rightarrow \text{Relevant}(x, c)) : 0.31 \\ &\quad + \text{Contribution from } \varphi_{05} (\text{KeywordMatch}(x, c) \Rightarrow \text{Relevant}(x, c)) : 0.13 \quad (36) \end{aligned}$$

The overseer can identify which rules drive the prediction, verify their semantic

correctness (“Does it make sense that documents citing relevant documents are themselves relevant?”), and assess whether relative contributions align with domain expectations—satisfying the “characteristics of the system” requirement.

Interpretation Tools: Technical Infrastructure. Article 14(4) explicitly requires “interpretation tools and methods” to be provided. LIMEN-AI offers:

1. **Built-in Trace Viewer:** Command-line tool `limen explain -query Q -evidence E` generates human-readable explanations.
2. **Export API:** `trace.export_json()` enables integration with external analysis tools (Jupyter notebooks, BI dashboards, custom auditing software).
3. **Visualization:** Rule activation heatmaps, satisfaction degree histograms, contribution bar charts.
4. **Counterfactual Analysis:** “What if we removed rule φ_{23} ? How would μ_Q change?” Implemented via ablation studies.

These tools turn the abstract capability of interpretability into concrete operational support for overseers, satisfying the “methods available” clause.

7.4.3 Multi-Layered Audit Protocol

A robust audit should not depend on a single evidence source. The *multi-layered audit protocol* proposed here uses intrinsic explanations as primary evidence and post-hoc methods (SHAP, LIME) as secondary validation, providing defence-in-depth per Article 15.

Layer 1: Primary Evidence (Intrinsic Interpretability). LIMEN-AI’s explicit knowledge base and inference traces form the primary evidence layer. They represent the system’s actual reasoning process—not an approximation or post-hoc reconstruction.

Audit Procedure:

1. Developer provides knowledge base file `production_model.limen` and inference trace for the decision under review.

2. Auditor inspects rules: Are formulas semantically valid? Do weights reflect appropriate priorities?
3. Auditor examines trace: Which rules contributed most? Are satisfaction degrees consistent with evidence?
4. Auditor verifies reproducibility: Re-running inference with same KB and evidence yields identical results.

Strength: Ground truth for “why” the system behaves as designed. Provides *a priori* transparency—the system is interpretable by construction.

Limitation: Assumes rules correctly capture domain logic. If the knowledge base itself is flawed (missing rules, incorrect weights), intrinsic explanations will faithfully represent flawed reasoning.

Layer 2: Secondary Validation (Post-Hoc Analysis). Model-agnostic explanation methods (SHAP, LIME) are applied to LIMEN-AI’s inference function, treating it as a black box. The goal is *a posteriori* verification: does the learned behaviour match the design intent?

Audit Procedure:

1. Auditor applies SHAP to LIMEN-AI’s `infer()` function, computing feature importance scores.
2. Compare SHAP values with Layer 1 rule contributions: Do they identify the same features as important?
3. If agreement: confidence in Layer 1 increases (independent validation).
4. If disagreement: investigate potential issues (emergent interactions, rule gaps, adversarial manipulation).

Example: For the query $\mu_Q = 0.87$ with Layer 1 trace showing φ_{23} (Cites rule) contributing 0.43, SHAP analysis might yield:

```
SHAP values: Cites(doc_1337, doc_89) = +0.41
              Relevant(doc_89, case_42) = +0.38
```

The close alignment (0.43 vs. 0.41) independently confirms that the Cites rule is the primary driver, as the intrinsic explanation claims.

Strength: Model-agnostic, detects emergent patterns not obvious from rules alone. Hermosilla et al. (2025) demonstrate that SHAP and LIME provide “complementary strengths” for forensic cybersecurity analysis, with SHAP offering global coherence and LIME providing local fidelity (Hermosilla et al., 2025).

Limitation: Approximations may not perfectly capture true feature importance. Local explanations (LIME) may not generalise globally.

Layer 3: Tertiary Review (Human Expert Validation). Domain experts inspect the rules themselves, independent of any specific inference trace.

Audit Procedure:

1. Domain expert (e.g., legal scholar for contract analysis, cybersecurity analyst for threat detection) reviews knowledge base.
2. Expert assesses: Do rules encode legitimate domain knowledge? Are there missing rules? Are weights reasonable?
3. Expert validates against ground truth: Do rule predictions align with expert judgment on test cases?

Strength: Catches errors in problem formulation, not just implementation. Validates semantic correctness of rules.

Limitation: Subjective, not scalable to large knowledge bases.

Integrated Audit Workflow. The three layers complement one another rather than serving as alternatives:

1. **Pre-deployment:** Layer 3 (expert review) validates knowledge base before deployment.
2. **Operational monitoring:** Layer 1 (intrinsic traces) provides real-time explanations for all decisions.
3. **Post-incident investigation:** Layers 1, 2, and 3 are applied in sequence to suspected errors or adversarial attacks.

The protocol satisfies Article 13(3)(b)(iv)’s requirement for “measures designed to [...] enable users to interpret the system’s output” (plural “measures”). Three complementary interpretation mechanisms ensure robust auditability.

Table 22: Multi-layered audit protocol for LIMEN-AI, showing the role, strength, and limitation of each layer in providing comprehensive interpretability for regulatory compliance. Source: Author.

Layer	Evidence Source	Strength	Limitation
1. Primary	Intrinsic rules + traces	Ground truth, <i>a priori</i> transparency	Assumes correct KB
2. Secondary	SHAP/LIME post-hoc	Independent validation, emergent patterns	Approximations, local
3. Tertiary	Human expert review	Semantic validation, domain knowledge	Subjective, not scalable

Table 22 summarises the protocol. Intrinsic interpretability provides the foundation; post-hoc methods provide independent validation—moving beyond the “intrinsic vs. post-hoc” dichotomy. Recent work in adjacent fields reinforces this stance. Angelov et al. (2025) show that prototype-based networks (ProtoPNet, xDNN) achieve interpretability through similarity to learned prototypes (Angelov et al., 2025). Wiktorowicz & Kluska (2025) demonstrate interpretability-by-design in fuzzy adaptive controllers for safety-critical systems (Wiktorowicz and Kluska, 2025). Across computer vision, control theory, and logic-based AI, explicit symbolic structure offers a compliance foundation that post-hoc explanations alone cannot match.

7.5 Compliance Workflow Patterns

Architectural capabilities only matter if they reach operational practice. Three reusable workflow patterns show how LIMEN-AI’s compliance properties translate into deployment.

7.5.1 Pattern 1: Human-in-the-Loop Decision Support

In this pattern, LIMEN-AI provides recommendations that inform but do not replace human decision-making. The workflow is:

1. **Query formulation:** A user formulates a question about a case or situation.
2. **Inference execution:** LIMEN-AI computes expected truth degrees for relevant queries.

3. **Trace generation:** Structured explanation traces are produced alongside numerical results.
4. **Human review:** The user reviews results and traces, forming an understanding of the reasoning.
5. **Decision:** The user makes a decision, which may accept, reject, or modify the system's recommendation.
6. **Logging:** The query, results, traces, and decision are logged for audit.

Humans retain final decision authority while benefiting from the system's analytical capabilities. Explanation traces enable meaningful review rather than rubber-stamping of opaque outputs.

7.5.2 Pattern 2: Iterative Knowledge Refinement

In this pattern, domain experts iteratively refine the knowledge base based on observed system behaviour. The workflow is:

1. **Initial deployment:** The system is deployed with an initial knowledge base.
2. **Case processing:** Cases are processed, generating recommendations and traces.
3. **Expert review:** Domain experts review cases where the system's reasoning appears incorrect or incomplete.
4. **Knowledge update:** Experts modify rules or weights to correct identified issues.
5. **Validation:** Changes are validated against a test set to ensure they improve overall performance.
6. **Documentation:** All changes are documented with rationale.

Continuous improvement proceeds under human control. Because the rules are explicit, targeted corrections can be made without unintended side effects.

7.5.3 Pattern 3: Audit and Investigation

In this pattern, auditors or investigators use LIMEN-AI’s logging capabilities to review past decisions. The workflow is:

1. **Case identification:** A specific past decision is identified for review.
2. **Log retrieval:** Inference traces from the time of the decision are retrieved.
3. **Reasoning reconstruction:** The auditor examines which rules and facts contributed to the conclusion.
4. **Counterfactual analysis:** The auditor may explore how different inputs would have affected the output.
5. **Findings:** The auditor documents findings about the appropriateness of the decision.

Complete reconstruction of the reasoning behind any past decision is therefore possible, satisfying the traceability requirements.

7.6 Comparison with Black-Box Approaches

A natural question is how LIMEN-AI’s intrinsic transparency stacks up against the post-hoc explanation techniques commonly applied to black-box models.

7.6.1 Post-Hoc Explanation Limitations

Post-hoc methods (LIME, SHAP, attention visualization) approximate rather than reveal the actual computation (*fidelity gap*). They can shift dramatically with small input perturbations (*instability*), capture feature importance but not how features combine logically (*incompleteness*), and may not reproduce across runs (*audit fragility*). Hermosilla et al. (2025) show that SHAP and LIME complement each other in forensic cybersecurity analysis (Hermosilla et al., 2025), yet even in combination they remain approximations—insufficient where regulation demands intrinsic transparency.

7.6.2 LIMEN-AI’s Advantages

LIMEN-AI closes these gaps. Fidelity is perfect because the explanation *is* the reasoning; no separate approximation exists. Stability follows from fixed rules and weights—the same query on the same knowledge base always yields the same trace. Traces record how rules combine, not just which inputs matter, so logical completeness is preserved. Audit reproducibility is deterministic: logging the knowledge base state suffices to reproduce any past decision exactly.

7.6.3 Robustness Against Adversarial Manipulation

Article 15 of the EU AI Act requires that high-risk AI systems be resilient against errors, faults, inconsistencies, and third-party exploitation of vulnerabilities. Most adversarial robustness research targets deep neural networks, but “intrinsically interpretable” models are not immune. Baniecki and Biecek (2025) show that prototype-based networks can be fooled through adversarial prototype manipulation—the model’s reasoning is subverted without changing its interpretable structure, creating a “false sense of security” (Baniecki and Biecek, 2025).

LIMEN-AI faces similar risks. Differentiability of the Łukasiewicz energy function enables efficient learning but also opens an attack surface: an adversary could try to optimise rule weights or input truth assignments to produce malicious outcomes. The key difference from neural black-boxes is that LIMEN-AI’s knowledge representation is explicit—**transparent and auditable knowledge that can always be human-checked and updated.**

In a neural network, adversarial perturbations hide among millions of opaque weights spread across layers. In LIMEN-AI, manipulation of the rule base manifests as *semantically meaningful changes* to explicit logical formulas:

Neural Black-Box Attack: An adversary perturbs weights W_{ij} in layer ℓ by δ such that $f(x; W + \delta) = y_{\text{malicious}}$. The perturbation is *undetectable* without exhaustive testing because individual weight changes have no semantic interpretation.

LIMEN-AI Attack: An adversary modifies rule weight w_i for formula ϕ_i or truth assignment $\nu(A)$ for atom A . The modification is *immediately inspectable*: domain experts can read ϕ_i and assess whether weight w_i is reasonable, or examine whether $\nu(A) = 0.9$ aligns with observed evidence. If a rule suddenly assigns high weight to an implausible implication (e.g., $\text{age}(x, 25) \rightarrow \text{creditRisk}(x, \text{high})$), the

semantic absurdity is apparent.

A **human-checkable knowledge base** provides layered defence. Before deployment, experts can audit every rule and weight—something infeasible for million-parameter neural networks. At runtime, automated consistency checks flag unexpected weight changes or rule additions based on *semantic* anomalies rather than statistical deviation alone.

After an incident, investigators can trace the exact rules behind a suspicious decision and determine whether they were adversarially introduced or legitimately learned (Chapter 4). Future work will add formal weight-robustness verification via robust optimisation and continuous compliance checking through tools like CO2 (Prathyush Turaga et al., 2025).

7.7 Limitations and Considerations

Neurosymbolic transparency comes with trade-offs. Two categories of limitations deserve attention from deployers.

7.7.1 Knowledge Acquisition Challenge

LIMEN-AI’s transparency rests on a well-crafted knowledge base. Building one demands domain expertise and familiarity with the logical formalism. Gaps in coverage lead to uninformed conclusions, and evolving domains require ongoing maintenance. The LLM-based extraction pipeline partially automates construction but does not eliminate the need for expert oversight.

7.7.2 Scalability Considerations

Grounding complexity is polynomial in domain size but exponential in rule arity. Large entity sets increase runtime; high-arity predicates or deeply nested rules can become prohibitive. These constraints inform modelling choices—prefer lower-arity predicates, limit nesting—but do not undermine the transparency properties themselves.

7.8 Empirical Compliance Validation

The mappings above establish that LIMEN-AI *can* comply. The COLIEE evaluation (Section 6.11) shows that it *does*—delivering transparent, oversightable decisions at

scale in a realistic legal application.

7.8.1 Article 13: Transparency Requirements

Article 13(3) demands operational transparency (users understand what the system does) and output interpretability (users understand what specific outputs mean) (European Parliament and Council, 2024). The COLIEE deployment provides evidence for both (Table 23).

Table 23: Empirical evidence from COLIEE deployment demonstrating satisfaction of Article 13(3) transparency requirements. Each row links a specific regulatory obligation to observable system behaviours and measurable outcomes. Source: Author.

Article 13(3) Requirement	LIMEN-AI Mechanism	COLIEE Evidence
(a) Transparent operation	Explicit rule extraction and storage	400 queries processed with visible rule sets
(b) Interpretable outputs	Satisfaction degree computation with fuzzy semantics	100% of rankings include degree values (0.00–1.00)
Output justification	Rule-level attribution in traces	Avg. 4.2 rules per explanation, each with satisfaction degree
Uncertainty communication	Degree-based confidence scores	Entailment scores range 0.00–0.90, reflecting confidence variation

Each of the 400 queries produced a knowledge base snapshot—predicates, ground atoms, weighted rules, and satisfaction degrees—available for inspection, export, and comparison against authoritative legal sources. Experts can read the rules to see what principles the system recognises. Developers can trace behaviour to specific formulas. Regulators can verify alignment with doctrine.

Explanation traces (Figure 46, Chapter 6) demonstrate output interpretability. Each ranking decomposes into individual rule satisfactions that can be examined independently, validated against domain expectations, and compared across candidates. The traces record the actual computation—not a post-hoc approximation—so they are faithful by construction (Rudin, 2019). All 400 queries produced complete traces without degenerate or missing explanations, confirming reliable operation at scale.

7.8.2 Article 14: Human Oversight Capabilities

Article 14 requires that natural persons can fully understand, monitor, and intervene in high-risk systems (European Parliament and Council, 2024). Table 24 shows how the COLIEE deployment demonstrates these capabilities.

Table 24: Empirical evidence from COLIEE deployment demonstrating satisfaction of Article 14 human oversight requirements. The table shows how specific capabilities required by the regulation were operationalised in the case retrieval application. Source: Author.

Article 14 Requirement	LIMEN-AI Capability	COLIEE Evidence
(4)(a) Interpret outputs	Rule-level attribution with satisfaction degrees	Avg. 4.2 rules per trace, each interpretable
(4)(b) Identify anomalies	Outlier detection in satisfaction degrees	12% of cases had ≥ 1 rule with 0.00 degree (anomaly indicator)
(4)(c) Decide not to use	Threshold-based filtering	Users can filter results with score < 0.5
(4)(d) Override output	Modifiable knowledge base	Rules can be added/removed/re-weighted
(4)(e) Interrupt operation	Stateless query processing	Each query independent; no persistent state to manage

Interpretation operates at three levels. At the *summary level*, entailment scores sort cases into highly, moderately, and weakly relevant tiers. At the *rule level*, users see which legal principles drove the ranking. At the *fact level*, they can verify that extracted query facts are accurate. In 8% of queries (32/400), traces revealed weak logical support (satisfaction < 0.2) despite high keyword similarity—exactly the kind of issue that transparent reasoning makes visible.

Override capability (Article 14(4)(c–d)) rests on the modifiable knowledge base. Users can refine rules, add predicates, or adjust weights. A rule too general for a particular legal distinction can be split into finer-grained alternatives, and all subsequent queries will use the refined logic (Floridi et al., 2018).

Limitation awareness (Article 14(2)) surfaces through the score distribution itself. Entailment scores in the COLIEE evaluation ranged from 0.00 to 0.90 (mean 0.42, $\sigma = 0.23$); users naturally see when the system is uncertain, providing a calibration

signal that mitigates automation bias (Goddard et al., 2012).

7.8.3 Comparative Advantage: LIMEN-AI vs. Black-Box Explanations

Table 25 contrasts intrinsic and post-hoc explanation properties observed in the COLIEE deployment.

Table 25: Comparison of explanation properties for LIMEN-AI (intrinsic) vs. BM25 with SHAP (post-hoc). Properties are evaluated based on regulatory requirements and observed behaviour in the COLIEE deployment. Source: Author.

Property	LIMEN-AI (Intrinsic)	BM25 + SHAP (Post-hoc)
Fidelity to actual computation	Perfect (trace = computation)	Approximate (SHAP \approx BM25)
Stability under input perturbation	Stable (deterministic rules)	Variable (depends on perturbation sample)
Logical structure captured	Yes (explicit rules)	No (feature importance scores only)
Audit reproducibility	Perfect (same KB \rightarrow same trace)	Approximate (sampling variance)
Human comprehension	High (legal experts validate rules)	Moderate (feature scores less intuitive)
Regulatory alignment (Articles 13–14)	Direct (explanations <i>are</i> reasoning)	Indirect (explanations <i>about</i> reasoning)

The decisive difference is fidelity. LIMEN-AI’s explanations record the actual computation; SHAP explanations approximate influence through a separate analysis that may not faithfully represent the score. For an auditor investigating a disputed decision, what the system *actually did* matters more than what an approximation suggests. Full explanation coverage across 400 queries confirms reliable intrinsic transparency at scale, whereas post-hoc methods require per-query perturbation sampling that can itself fail or produce unreliable estimates.

7.8.4 Practical Deployment Considerations

Three practical challenges surfaced during the evaluation. The most immediate is query latency: at roughly 30 seconds per query the system suits batch research but needs optimisation for interactive use—through caching, smaller LLMs, or offline pre-computation. A related concern is that, although explanation traces are more interpretable than black-box scores, they still require domain expertise to validate;

oversight personnel should therefore combine technical literacy with subject-matter knowledge. Finally, rule-level attribution could be extended to atom-level granularity for tasks demanding finer analysis. These challenges contextualise the compliance demonstrated above without undermining it.

7.8.5 Summary of Empirical Validation

In the evaluated COLIEE setting, LIMEN-AI demonstrated compliance with Articles 13 and 14: every prediction was accompanied by an explanation trace (100% coverage in this benchmark), confidence scores varied quantifiably across queries to support oversight calibration, and re-running inference on identical inputs produced identical traces—establishing reproducibility within the tested configuration. Generalisation of these properties to other domains and scales requires further empirical validation. The deployment constraints identified (latency, expertise, granularity) are engineering challenges, not architectural shortcomings.

7.9 Summary

LIMEN-AI’s explicit knowledge representation, structured inference traces, and controllable complexity satisfy the transparency (Article 13), human oversight (Article 14), and documentation (Articles 11–12) requirements of the EU AI Act by design rather than by retrofit. Deployment workflow patterns and a multi-layered audit protocol translate these architectural properties into operational compliance. The COLIEE evaluation provides initial evidence that these mechanisms function at benchmark scale—every prediction carried an explanation trace, and repeated runs produced identical outputs. Relative to post-hoc explanation methods applied to black-box systems, LIMEN-AI offers structurally higher fidelity and stability, positioning it as a viable foundation for high-risk AI in domains where accountability is a legal requirement.

8 Discussion and Future Work

LIMEN-AI has now been developed from its mathematical core through inference and induction algorithms to a compliance-ready implementation (Li et al., 2023a). The questions that matter at this stage are what the framework actually achieves, how it compares with competing approaches, and what gaps remain (Alvarado et al., 2023; Gokila and Jansirani, 2024; Pusztaházi et al., 2025; Yang et al., 2020).

8.1 Summary of Contributions

8.1.1 Theoretical Contributions

LIMEN-AI introduces Łukasiewicz fuzzy semantics into Markov Logic. This resolves the tension between expressive weighted first-order rules and gradient-based learning: piecewise linearity and almost-everywhere differentiability follow directly from the choice of t-norm. The formal proofs of piecewise linearity (Theorem 3.3) and loss convexity (Theorem 5.2) anchor the learning algorithms in rigorous mathematics, while gradient Lipschitz continuity (Theorem 5.1) provides the concrete learning-rate bounds that guide practical optimisation. Separately, the convergence analysis for sampling-based inference—variance bounds and statistical consistency of learned weights (Theorem 5.5)—supplies theoretical guarantees that go beyond empirical observation.

8.1.2 Algorithmic Contributions

The inference engine pairs importance and power sampling with structured explanation traces, so every numerical output links back to the logical rules that produced it. Approximate inference becomes both tractable and auditable. Template-based induction exploits the convex optimisation landscape to discover interpretable rules from labelled examples with global-optimality guarantees. An LLM orchestration layer lets users interact in natural language without giving up the explicit logical structure needed for transparency.

8.1.3 Practical Contributions

The open-source `limen-ai` Python library packages these ideas into a documented, tested codebase. Compliance-oriented workflow patterns illustrate integration into

regulated organisational processes, and the design-trade-off discussion offers concrete guidance for deploying LIMEN-AI in new domains.

8.2 Comparison with Related Work

8.2.1 Comparison with Classical MLNs

LIMEN-AI inherits the weighted first-order logic framework of classical MLNs but departs from it in important ways. Classical MLNs count satisfied groundings under Boolean semantics and rely on MCMC or belief propagation over discrete interpretations. LIMEN-AI instead computes continuous satisfaction degrees under Łukasiewicz semantics, sampling over fuzzy interpretations with gradient-guided proposals. This shift unlocks direct gradient-based weight learning, replacing pseudo-likelihood or contrastive divergence. Both frameworks expose explicit logical rules, yet LIMEN-AI goes further by generating structured explanation traces that attribute each conclusion to specific rules and samples.

8.2.2 Comparison with Logic Tensor Networks

Logic Tensor Networks (LTNs) also differentiate through logic, yet they implement predicates as neural networks over entity embeddings and learn semantics end-to-end. LIMEN-AI retains explicit symbolic predicates with fixed Łukasiewicz operations, trading representational flexibility for transparent semantics. On the probabilistic side, LIMEN-AI’s Gibbs distribution gives every output a clear probabilistic reading; LTN loss functions lack such an interpretation. Explaining an LTN decision demands neural-network introspection, whereas a LIMEN-AI decision can be explained by inspecting rules and truth degrees directly.

8.2.3 Comparison with DeepProbLog

DeepProbLog compiles probabilistic logic programs to arithmetic circuits and integrates neural networks as predicates under distribution semantics (probabilities over Boolean worlds). LIMEN-AI follows the opposite inference route—sampling rather than compilation—and operates in a continuous fuzzy space whose probabilistic interpretation derives from the energy function. Neural components can be incorporated through truth functions, but LIMEN-AI privileges explicit symbolic computation over learned perception.

8.2.4 Comparison with Scallop

Scallop provides a general-purpose Datalog-style neurosymbolic language with provenance tracking for gradient flow. LIMEN-AI is narrower in scope—weighted first-order rules under fixed Łukasiewicz semantics—and its explanation traces are designed for human interpretation and regulatory audit, not for general-purpose gradient propagation.

8.3 LIMEN-AI in the Landscape of Interpretable Fuzzy Systems

Fuzzy logic and machine learning have converged rapidly around interpretable AI, especially in domains where transparency carries legal or ethical force (Anuar et al., 2024; Razak et al., 2021b; Shukur et al., 2024). LIMEN-AI’s combination of Łukasiewicz fuzzy semantics with Markov Logic Networks occupies one point in a broader design space of interpretable fuzzy systems (Baimukashev et al., 2024; David et al., 2023; Dubois and Prade, 2023). Understanding the common principles across these systems—and the specific design choices that set them apart—helps clarify what LIMEN-AI adds (Aminoroaya et al., 2025; Lokman et al., 2025; Zheng et al., 2025).

8.3.1 The Interpretability-Accuracy Trade-Off in Deep Fuzzy Systems

A comprehensive survey of deep fuzzy systems (DFS) for regression (Junior et al., 2023) argues that interpretability should be designed in during model development, not bolted on through post-hoc explanations. LIMEN-AI follows this same principle: interpretability by construction, not by approximation.

The survey identifies several architectural families for achieving interpretable deep learning: fuzzy rule-based systems with neural parameter optimisation, neuro-fuzzy networks (ANFIS-style), and hybrid systems where fuzzy logic guides neural feature extraction. LIMEN-AI occupies a distinct niche within this taxonomy: it maintains explicit first-order logical rules (not propositional if-then rules), uses fixed Łukasiewicz semantics (not learnable membership functions), and targets discrete decision support (not continuous regression).

The distinction matters in practice. Many deep fuzzy systems trade semantic

precision for approximation power—membership functions optimised via gradient descent can lose their linguistic interpretability (Ding et al., 2024; Wang and Nishter, 2024). LIMEN-AI inverts that priority: semantic precision is preserved through mechanically-verified Łukasiewicz operations, even at the cost of expressiveness relative to unconstrained neural fuzzy systems.

Measuring interpretability itself is far from straightforward. A participatory design framework for hierarchical fuzzy systems (HFS) (Razak et al., 2021a) engages expert practitioners to define what “interpretable” means in specific contexts, revealing that interpretability spans multiple dimensions: rule readability, semantic consistency, structural transparency, and decision traceability. LIMEN-AI scores well on semantic consistency (fixed Łukasiewicz operations) and decision traceability (explanation traces); hierarchical fuzzy systems may offer advantages in rule compactness for high-dimensional problems.

8.3.2 Bridging Post-Hoc and Intrinsic Explainability

Post-hoc explainability methods (SHAP, LIME) are increasingly being combined with intrinsically interpretable fuzzy systems to create multi-layered audit protocols. SHAP-Rule (Khalyasmaa et al., 2025) exemplifies this convergence: it translates SHAP feature attributions into linguistic fuzzy IF-THEN rules for diagnostic tasks, achieving 89% AUC on industrial predictive maintenance datasets while producing human-readable explanations.

An obvious question arises: if LIMEN-AI is already intrinsically interpretable via weighted rules, what role do post-hoc methods like SHAP play? Khalyasmaa’s results point to a clear answer—SHAP provides instance-level feature attributions that complement rule-level explanations. Applied to LIMEN-AI, this suggests a two-tier audit strategy:

- **Primary Evidence (Intrinsic):** Rule activation traces showing which formulas contributed to a decision and with what satisfaction degrees. This is LIMEN-AI’s native interpretability mechanism.
- **Secondary Validation (Post-Hoc):** SHAP analysis applied to the satisfaction function $\sigma(\phi_i, I)$ to identify which ground atoms most influenced the overall energy. This serves as a consistency check and can reveal emergent patterns not obvious from individual rules.

The idea can be pushed further into counterfactual territory. FLARE (Fuzzy Local Agnostic Rule-Based Explanations) (Fernández et al., 2025) generates both factual and counterfactual explanations for closed-box classifiers by learning local fuzzy decision trees. Factual explanations justify why an instance received a particular classification; counterfactual explanations show what would need to change for a different outcome. LIMEN-AI’s inference traces naturally provide factual explanations (which rules fired, with what weights), but counterfactual generation remains underdeveloped. FLARE-style counterfactual reasoning—“If $\text{hasRole}(x, \text{admin})$ were false, the authorization would fail”—could strengthen LIMEN-AI’s value for contested decisions under Article 14 of the EU AI Act.

An application in a rather different domain reinforces the point. FAS-XAI (Marín Díaz, 2025) combines Fuzzy C-Means clustering, XGBoost classification, and integrated SHAP/LIME explanations for exoplanet candidate vetting, achieving 0.855 ROC-AUC on the Kepler Objects of Interest dataset. Fuzzy memberships quantify ambiguity in borderline cases; SHAP provides global feature importance rankings. For LIMEN-AI, this points to an opportunity: fuzzy memberships in the interpretation space \mathcal{I} (representing uncertainty about ground-atom truth values) could be modelled and communicated to auditors as epistemic uncertainty, kept distinct from the aleatoric uncertainty captured by $P(I; \mathbf{w})$.

8.3.3 Constrained Fuzzy Sets and Semantic Preservation

Maintaining semantic coherence during learning is a persistent difficulty in fuzzy AI. Constrained interval type-2 fuzzy sets (D’Alterio et al., 2021) tackle the problem head-on, preventing unconstrained optimisation from producing footprints of uncertainty (FOU) and embedded sets that drift away from their original concept. A membership function for “high risk,” for instance, might develop a shape after gradient-based tuning that no domain expert would recognise.

LIMEN-AI avoids this problem through a different mechanism: the Łukasiewicz operations ($T_{\mathbb{L}}, S_{\mathbb{L}}, \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}}$) are fixed and mechanically verified against formal definitions in Isabelle/HOL. The knowledge base can grow through inductive rule discovery (Chapter 5), and weights can be learned, but the semantic operators themselves are immutable. This is a form of *semantic locking*: trading expressiveness for guaranteed interpretability.

The trade-off is real. Adaptive neuro-fuzzy systems like ANFIS (Casari et al., 2024) can tune membership functions to fit data more closely, sometimes achieving higher predictive accuracy. LIMEN-AI forgoes that flexibility. In regulated environments where “why did the system decide this?” is a legal requirement, semantic locking provides a defensible answer: “The system computed the Łukasiewicz conjunction of these predicates according to Definition 3.1, verified by `luk_and_valid` in Appendix B.”

8.3.4 Neuro-Symbolic Integration: From Embeddings to Logic Enforcement

How tightly should neural perception be coupled with symbolic constraints? Hè and Apostolaki (Hè and Apostolaki, 2025) offer one answer with *Just-in-Time Logic Enforcement* (LeJIT), which interleaves an SMT solver into a large language model’s inference process to enforce domain-specific constraints during generation. LeJIT avoids the drawbacks of training a model to satisfy constraints (risking overfitting) and of post-processing invalid outputs (wasting computation); instead, it guides token selection step-by-step toward logical consistency.

This approach complements LIMEN-AI’s LLM integration architecture (Chapter 6). LIMEN-AI uses LLMs for rule template instantiation and natural language grounding but does not enforce logical constraints during LLM generation. Integrating a LeJIT-style constraint solver could prevent the LLM from proposing semantically incoherent rule candidates, reducing the burden on the subsequent differentiable scoring phase.

A complementary line of work explores concept similarity within description logic ontologies by combining pre-trained word embeddings (BioWordVec) with formal DL semantics (Racharak, 2021). Embeddings capture statistical co-occurrence patterns from text; DL reasoning captures taxonomic and role relationships in structured knowledge. LIMEN-AI grounds predicates in natural language via LLM-based extraction and so implicitly relies on similar distributional semantics, though the connection is informal. Explicitly modelling predicate similarity with embedding-based metrics could let LIMEN-AI generalise across related predicates—useful in low-data regimes where only a few labelled examples mention a specific predicate.

8.4 Application Domain Validation: Lessons from Fuzzy AI Deployments

Compliance at design time is necessary but not the whole picture; practical utility hinges on performance under real deployment constraints. Recent applications of interpretable fuzzy systems in medicine, industrial diagnostics, environmental monitoring, and critical infrastructure supply concrete lessons for LIMEN-AI’s deployment strategy and highlight where empirical validation is most needed.

8.4.1 Medical Decision Support: Balancing Accuracy and Accountability

Medical AI demands high predictive accuracy alongside clear justification—clinicians face professional liability and regulatory oversight whenever they act on algorithmic recommendations. Fuzzy logic systems have gained traction in this space because they deliver reasonable accuracy together with the interpretability clinicians require.

Attention mechanisms in medical imaging illustrate the interpretability challenge at its sharpest. Fuzzy Attention Rule (FAR) models (Kim and Kwak, 2025) match ResNet-50 accuracy on MRI classification with far fewer parameters, producing pixel-level rule-based attention maps. Unlike Grad-CAM, which often highlights irrelevant regions, FAR focuses on lesion areas by applying fuzzy membership functions and logical operations (AND, OR) at pixel level. The resulting attention maps are intrinsic to the classification decision, not post-hoc approximations.

For LIMEN-AI, this demonstrates the value of *interpretability at multiple resolutions*: global (which rules are active), local (which ground atoms contribute), and sub-symbolic (which pixels/features ground those atoms). LIMEN-AI currently operates at the first two levels but does not address sub-symbolic grounding. Integrating with FAR-style pixel-level fuzzy attention could enable LIMEN-AI to explain not just “patient p has risk factor r ” but “ r was inferred from these specific MRI regions with these fuzzy memberships.”

Multigranular analysis pushes this idea further. The Fuzzy-Guided Multigranular Deep Neural Network (FMDNN) (Ding et al., 2024) extracts features at coarse, medium, and fine granularities for histopathological image classification—mimicking pathologists’ multi-scale diagnostic approach—and uses fuzzy membership functions to describe cell features from multiple perspectives, achieving state-of-the-art performance on multiple public datasets. This multigranular strategy bears directly

on LIMEN-AI’s scalability challenge (Chapter 4, §4.2.3): instead of grounding all formulas at a single resolution, selective refinement for high-stakes decisions paired with coarse grounding for routine cases could improve throughput considerably.

Automated rule generation need not sacrifice interpretability, provided the learning algorithm constrains rule structure. A cascade of fuzzy expert systems for diagnosing obstructive sleep apnea (Casal-Guisande et al., 2023) uses the Wang-Mendel algorithm to generate IF-THEN rules automatically from patient data, achieving AUC values of 0.74–0.88 across 4,400 patients. Each rule has a fixed antecedent format, and fuzzy sets are defined over the entire feature range, maintaining semantic consistency.

This mirrors LIMEN-AI’s template-based induction mechanism (Chapter 5): by constraining the space of learnable rules to predefined templates, semantic interpretability is preserved even when rules are discovered automatically. The clinical validation in Casal-Guisande’s work—rules reviewed by medical experts and found to align with domain knowledge—provides a model for how LIMEN-AI deployments in regulated domains should be validated.

8.4.2 Industrial and Environmental Monitoring: Real-Time Interpretability

Industrial and environmental monitoring adds real-time latency constraints and noisy, incomplete sensor data on top of the interpretability requirement. Energy management sharpens the tension: a hybrid neuro-fuzzy system for load forecasting and adaptive control in smart grids (Wang and Nishter, 2024) must combine neural pattern recognition with fuzzy rule-based control, adapting to fluctuations in renewable energy generation and demand while keeping control decisions interpretable.

Wang and Nishter’s central tension—fast inference versus traceable decisions—applies directly to LIMEN-AI. Importance sampling inference (Chapter 4) offers controllable accuracy-latency trade-offs via the sample count N , but no systematic characterisation of those trade-offs under real-time constraints exists yet. Smart grids, where decisions must occur within milliseconds but may be audited months later, would be an ideal testbed.

Environmental monitoring tells a similar story. Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference Systems (ANFIS) applied to low-cost air quality sensor calibration (Casari et al., 2024) outperform linear regression, random forests, and multilayer perceptrons, but

the decisive advantage is interpretability: the correspondence between detected particulate matter concentrations and fuzzy rules is explicit, letting domain experts validate and adjust the system. This confirms a core LIMEN-AI design principle—in domains where expert oversight is critical, interpretability is a functional requirement, not an optional extra.

Perhaps the clearest illustration of interpretability driving adoption comes from smart agriculture: a fuzzy logic system that monitors soil moisture, temperature, and other parameters to optimise irrigation (Sabrina et al., 2022) succeeded precisely because farmers could understand why each recommendation was made and verify the reasoning against their own experience. The lesson applies equally to LIMEN-AI: *transparency drives trust at least as much as accuracy does.*

8.4.3 Comparative Positioning: Where LIMEN-AI Excels and Where It Struggles

These deployments sharpen the picture of where LIMEN-AI fits best and where alternatives are better suited.

LIMEN-AI is strongest when *relational structure is central*—medical diagnosis with patient-procedure-outcome triples, cybersecurity graphs linking attackers to vulnerabilities and assets, or multi-entity financial transactions—because first-order logic naturally fits such data. It also excels when *regulatory audit is required* (EU AI Act, financial services, clinical trials), since explicit rules and mechanically-verified semantics yield defensible audit trails, and when *knowledge is incrementally refined* over time, as template-based induction preserves the interpretability of earlier rules.

Other approaches win under different pressures. Sampling-based inference may be too slow for *real-time latency* demands (smart grids, autonomous vehicles, high-frequency trading); propositional fuzzy controllers or hardware-accelerated engines are better matched there. *High-dimensional continuous control*—robotics, industrial process regulation—favours fuzzy PID controllers or neural policies over discrete relational reasoning. For *end-to-end learning from raw perception* (images, audio), systems that learn grounding jointly with reasoning (LTN, DeepProbLog, Scallop) avoid the need for pre-grounded predicates.

8.5 Limitations

8.5.1 Expressiveness Limitations

The current formulation omits function symbols, which limits expressiveness relative to full first-order logic. Adding them would complicate grounding substantially, though it remains theoretically feasible. Atoms without explicit truth-degree assignments default to zero—a closed-world assumption that fits many regulatory scenarios but may demand explicit “unknown” modelling in open-world settings. Rule discovery is further bounded by the template library: rules outside the available templates cannot be learned, and broadening coverage increases computational cost.

8.5.2 Scalability Limitations

Energy computation grounds all formulas—polynomial in domain size, but expensive for large domains—and exact alternatives such as grid discretisation incur errors that decrease only as $O(L/k)$ for grid resolution k (Proposition 4.1). Lifted inference could reduce the sampling cost; it is not yet implemented. Importance-sampling variance shrinks slowly with sample count—the sample complexity bound (Theorem 4.5) quantifies this dependence precisely—so high-precision estimates may require many samples and correspondingly longer inference times. Large knowledge bases add a linear factor to energy evaluation. Indexing and caching strategies would help, but they remain future work.

8.5.3 Knowledge Acquisition Limitations

Building an effective knowledge base requires familiarity with both the target domain and the logical formalism—expertise that not every organisation has. The LLM-based extraction pipeline adds another risk: extraction errors can propagate into the knowledge base and go unnoticed without manual review. Assessing whether a knowledge base adequately covers its domain is still an open problem; systematic coverage metrics are needed but do not yet exist.

8.6 Future Research Directions

8.6.1 Theoretical Extensions

A formal characterisation of LIMEN-AI’s expressive power relative to other logical and probabilistic formalisms would sharpen its theoretical positioning. Tighter convergence bounds tailored to specific knowledge-base structures could strengthen the practical guarantees. Complexity lower bounds for inference and learning would delineate fundamental computational limits. Exploring alternative continuous t-norms—product and Gödel, in particular—and their consequences for differentiability and learning could broaden the framework without abandoning its formal underpinnings.

8.6.2 Algorithmic Improvements

Lifted inference for fuzzy semantics is arguably the most impactful algorithmic goal: exploiting domain symmetries could yield order-of-magnitude scalability gains. Adaptive sampling that concentrates effort on high-variance regions would improve estimator efficiency within the same computational budget. Incremental inference—updating results when facts or rules change rather than recomputing from scratch—would suit interactive applications. Parallelising the grounding and sampling stages would better exploit modern multi-core and GPU hardware.

8.6.3 Application Extensions

Temporal operators would let LIMEN-AI reason about event sequences and state transitions, while spatial predicates would open applications involving geographic or geometric constraints. Multi-agent extensions—agents with distinct knowledge bases collaborating under shared rules—could support decentralised decision-making in, e.g., supply-chain or clinical-trial settings. Tighter coupling with neural perception modules (image encoders, language models) would move toward end-to-end neurosymbolic systems that perceive and reason in a single pipeline.

8.6.4 Empirical Validation

Empirical work must keep pace with theoretical development. Systematic evaluation on established benchmarks would position LIMEN-AI relative to competing frame-

works. Targeted case studies in high-stakes domains—cybersecurity, financial risk, legal compliance—would test practical applicability under realistic conditions. User studies with domain experts are needed to assess whether the explanation traces genuinely improve human decision-making. Controlled scalability experiments across varying domain sizes, knowledge-base complexities, and query difficulties would inform deployment sizing.

8.7 Broader Impact

8.7.1 Responsible AI Development

LIMEN-AI pushes back against the assumption that opacity is an inevitable cost of AI capability: an interpretable system *can* be built without abandoning formal rigour. Integrating regulatory requirements at design time shows that compliance need not be retrofitted after deployment. The emphasis on human oversight positions AI as an augmentation of professional judgment rather than a replacement for it.

8.7.2 Limitations of Technical Solutions

Technical transparency is necessary but insufficient on its own. A transparent system can still be misused if organisational processes fail to support proper oversight. Economic incentives may favour opacity or speed over interpretability—pressures no technical artefact can neutralise alone. Traceability in the technical sense does not automatically produce legal or social accountability; governance frameworks must bridge that gap. LIMEN-AI supplies the technical substrate for responsible AI, but realising that potential requires matching commitments at organisational and regulatory levels.

8.8 Chapter Summary

LIMEN-AI is a concrete step toward AI systems that are both capable and accountable—a need that intensifies as automated decisions spread into high-stakes domains. The mathematical foundations, inference and learning algorithms, and compliance-ready implementation developed here provide a working base from which the limitations identified above can be addressed and the research directions pursued.

9 Conclusion

This thesis set out to address a tension that sits at the heart of modern AI deployment: the systems most capable of learning from complex, relational data tend to be the least amenable to human understanding, yet the domains where such learning matters most—law, finance, critical infrastructure—are precisely those where understanding is non-negotiable. With the EU AI Act now in force, that tension has acquired legal weight. I have argued that LIMEN-AI, a reasoning engine built on Neuralized Markov Logic Networks under Łukasiewicz fuzzy semantics, offers a principled resolution. Rather than bolting explanations onto an opaque model after the fact, the framework embeds interpretability into its architecture from the ground up, so that every inference is traceable to explicit logical rules without sacrificing the differentiability needed for gradient-based learning.

The five research questions that structured this work each targeted a distinct facet of that resolution. What follows is a brief account of how each was answered, a consolidated statement of the resulting contributions, and a reflection on the broader implications for the field.

9.1 Answers to the Research Questions

RQ1 asked whether Markov Logic Networks could be formalised under Łukasiewicz fuzzy semantics in a manner that preserves both differentiability and interpretability, and what regularity and convergence properties the resulting energy function would exhibit. Chapter 3 supplied the answer through a complete mathematical framework comprising five key theorems. Theorem 3.2 established that all Łukasiewicz connectives are piecewise linear, and Theorem 3.3 extended this to show that the satisfaction degree of any formula, however deeply nested, remains piecewise linear in the atomic truth values. These two results are what make the entire enterprise work: they guarantee that the energy function (whose properties Theorem 3.1 characterises) admits gradients almost everywhere (Theorem 3.4), and that gradient-based weight learning converges under reasonable assumptions (Theorem 3.5). Differentiability follows as a corollary, not an approximation. To move beyond pen-and-paper assurance, I formalised 55 supporting lemmas and theorems in Isabelle/HOL (Appendix B), providing a level of mechanised verification that is, to my knowledge, unprecedented

in the neurosymbolic AI literature.

RQ2 concerned the design of sampling-based inference algorithms suited to fuzzy truth spaces and the generation of explanation traces that support transparency and audit. Chapter 4 responded with two complementary schemes. Importance sampling (Algorithm 1) handles unimodal energy landscapes efficiently; its variance is bounded by Theorem 4.4, which also yields practical guidance on sample budgets. For the multimodal distributions that arise from richer knowledge bases, power sampling with replica exchange (Algorithm 2) avoids the trapping that plagues single-chain methods; Theorem 4.3 guarantees convergence via detailed balance. Crucially, both algorithms emit structured explanation traces (Algorithm 3) that decompose every query answer into weighted rule contributions—a feature designed to satisfy Article 13 of the EU AI Act, not merely as a desirable add-on but as an integral output of inference.

RQ3 asked how new weighted rules could be learned from labelled examples without collapsing the explicit logical structure that makes the knowledge base interpretable. Chapter 5 introduced a template-based induction mechanism (Algorithm 4) in which candidate rules are generated from syntactic templates encoding patterns such as transitivity, symmetry, and composition. A differentiable scoring function grades each candidate against the training data, and Theorem 5.2 shows that the resulting optimisation landscape is convex—ensuring that gradient descent reliably finds high-quality rules rather than settling into poor local minima. Beam search keeps the procedure tractable by pruning unpromising candidates early. An auxiliary pipeline allows domain experts to propose candidate templates in natural language via large language models; the system then formalises, scores, and ranks these proposals, closing the loop between human intuition and formal validation.

RQ4 posed the practical question: can the theoretical framework be realised in software that demonstrates viability on a real-world task? Chapter 6 answered affirmatively. The open-source `limen-ai` Python library implements the full stack—signature management, knowledge-base construction, tensor-based energy computation via PyTorch, sampling inference, inductive learning, and trace generation—under a modular architecture that mirrors the theoretical structure. Unit tests systematically compare outputs against hand-calculated examples from the theory chapters, and the library was evaluated on the COLIEE legal entailment benchmark, where it achieved a 46% relative precision improvement over the BM25 baseline across 400 queries. Every prediction was accompanied by a logical justification trace, demon-

strating that interpretability and competitive performance are not mutually exclusive in practice.

RQ5 examined the alignment between LIMEN-AI’s technical properties and the requirements of the EU AI Act, together with the workflow patterns needed for compliant deployment. Chapter 7 carried out a systematic mapping of the framework’s capabilities onto Articles 9–15. Explicit weighted rules satisfy Article 13’s transparency mandate; structured explanation traces address Article 14’s human-oversight provisions; and formal verification, combined with serialisable state and structured logging, contributes to the documentation, record-keeping, and robustness obligations of Articles 11, 12, and 15. Reference workflows for cybersecurity anomaly detection, financial risk assessment, and legal contract analysis illustrated how these technical capabilities translate into organisational practice, while also identifying the points at which human procedures must supplement the technical architecture.

9.2 Statement of Contributions

Five contributions emerge from this work, spanning theory, algorithms, implementation, and regulatory analysis. The first is the NMLN formalisation itself (Chapter 3): a comprehensive mathematical framework for Neuralized Markov Logic Networks under Łukasiewicz semantics, anchored by Theorems 3.2–3.5 and verified mechanically through 55 Isabelle/HOL proof certificates, establishing differentiability and convergence properties not previously known for this class of models. The second contribution consists of two inference algorithms—importance sampling (Algorithm 1, Theorem 4.4) and power sampling with replica exchange (Algorithm 2, Theorem 4.3)—together with a formal specification of explanation-trace generation (Algorithm 3) that makes every inference step auditable. Third, the template-based induction mechanism (Algorithm 4) enables structural growth of the knowledge base with provably convex scoring (Theorem 5.2), coupling formal rule discovery with a human-in-the-loop natural-language pipeline. Fourth, the open-source `limen-ai` Python library translates these theoretical constructs into working software whose performance on the COLIEE benchmark provides empirical evidence of practical viability. Fifth, the compliance mapping onto Articles 9–15 of the EU AI Act, accompanied by three reference deployment workflows, bridges the gap between technical capability and regulatory obligation.

9.3 Broader Implications

Taken together, these contributions speak to a question that extends well beyond the specific formalism: is it possible to build AI systems that learn from data, reason under uncertainty, and remain genuinely transparent to the humans who must trust and oversee them? The mainstream answer, implicit in much current practice, is sceptical—deep learning succeeds precisely because it discovers representations that no human would design, and post-hoc methods are the best we can do to peer inside. I have tried to show that this framing presents a false dilemma. The piecewise linearity of Łukasiewicz semantics demonstrates that continuous, differentiable reasoning need not require opaque representations; the knowledge base stays symbolic and inspectable because the mathematics does not demand otherwise.

One implication deserves particular emphasis. At the time of writing, no other neurosymbolic framework offers a worked-out, article-by-article alignment with the EU AI Act. Logic Tensor Networks encode predicates in neural weight matrices that resist human inspection. DeepProbLog compiles logic programmes into arithmetic circuits whose structure no longer resembles the original rules. Scallop tracks provenance but cannot look inside the neural modules that generate its facts. Each of these systems has genuine strengths, and for many applications the trade-offs they make are entirely reasonable. But for high-risk deployments falling within the Act’s scope—credit scoring, hiring, law enforcement, critical infrastructure—the transparency, oversight, and documentation obligations of Articles 9–15 impose constraints that these architectures struggle to meet by design. LIMEN-AI was built with those constraints as first-class requirements, not afterthoughts. The compliance mapping in Chapter 7 is not a post-hoc exercise in regulatory box-ticking; it reflects design decisions taken at every stage, from the choice of logic to the structure of inference traces. As the Act’s enforcement provisions take full effect over the coming years, I expect the demand for architectures that are interpretable by construction, rather than merely explainable by approximation, to grow substantially.

Beyond the regulatory dimension, the thesis contributes to a broader intellectual shift. The prevailing narrative in AI has, for much of the past decade, treated scale as the primary lever of progress: more parameters, more data, more computation. That narrative has delivered extraordinary results, but it has also created systems whose failure modes are difficult to anticipate, diagnose, or correct. LIMEN-AI sits

at the opposite end of the spectrum—a “small reasoning model” in the sense that its behaviour is governed by a compact set of weighted logical rules rather than billions of learned parameters. The system is small not because it is limited, but because its structure is legible: every rule, every weight, every inference step can be examined by a domain expert without specialised interpretability tooling. In domains where decisions must be justified, audited, and occasionally overridden, this legibility is not a weakness but a defining strength.

9.4 Closing Reflection

I began this thesis with a conviction that has only deepened through the work: AI should support human understanding, not circumvent it. That conviction is now codified in European law. What remains is the harder engineering challenge of building systems that honour the principle without sacrificing the capacity to learn from data and reason under uncertainty. LIMEN-AI represents one answer—grounded in formal mathematics, realised in open-source software, and tested against both a benchmark and a regulatory framework. It is not a universal answer; the scalability constraints inherent in logic-based reasoning, the distance still to travel in empirical evaluation, and the rapid evolution of both the field and the regulatory landscape all counsel modesty. But the core demonstration stands: interpretable, compliant, and capable AI is not an aspiration—it is practical, and the tools to build it are available now.

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A LIMEN-AI Code Listings

This annex provides the complete code listings for the LIMEN-AI implementation discussed in Chapter 6. The listings are organised by module, following the library’s architecture. Each listing includes comprehensive documentation and is cross-referenced from the main implementation chapter.

A.1 Module Organisation

```
1 limen/  
2     __init__.py           # Public API exports  
3     core.py              # Core data structures  
4     energy.py            # Energy computation  
5     inference.py         # Sampling-based inference  
6     deduction.py         # Rule-based deduction  
7     induction.py        # Rule learning  
8     orchestrator.py     # LLM integration pipeline  
9     utils.py             # Utility functions  
10    tests/  
11        test_core.py  
12        test_energy.py  
13        test_inference.py  
14        ...
```

Listing 1: LIMEN-AI library module structure.

A.2 Core Data Structures

```
1 @dataclass(frozen=True)  
2 class Predicate:  
3     """A predicate symbol with fixed arity.  
4  
5     Predicates are immutable and hashable, allowing them to serve  
6     as dictionary keys for efficient lookup.  
7     """  
8     name: str  
9     arity: int  
10  
11     def __call__(self, *args: str) -> 'Atom':
```

```

12     """Create an atom by applying this predicate to arguments.
13
14     Args:
15         *args: Constant names to serve as arguments.
16
17     Returns:
18         An Atom instance.
19
20     Raises:
21         ValueError: If wrong number of arguments provided.
22     """
23     if len(args) != self.arity:
24         raise ValueError(
25             f"Predicate {self.name} expects {self.arity} "
26             f"arguments, got {len(args)}"
27         )
28     return Atom(self, tuple(args))
29
30     def __str__(self) -> str:
31         return f"{self.name}/{self.arity}"
32
33
34 @dataclass(frozen=True)
35 class Constant:
36     """A constant symbol representing a domain entity.
37
38     Constants are immutable and hashable for use as dictionary keys
39     .
40     """
41
42     name: str
43
44     def __str__(self) -> str:
45         return self.name

```

Listing 2: Implementation of Predicate and Constant classes using frozen dataclasses.

```

1 @dataclass(frozen=True)
2 class Atom:
3     """A ground atom: a predicate applied to constant arguments.
4
5     Atoms are the basic units of truth assignment. Each atom has

```

```

6     a truth degree in [0, 1] under a given interpretation.
7     """
8     predicate: Predicate
9     arguments: Tuple[str, ...]
10
11     def __post_init__(self):
12         """Validate that argument count matches predicate arity."""
13         if len(self.arguments) != self.predicate.arity:
14             raise ValueError(
15                 f"Atom {self.predicate.name} expects "
16                 f"{self.predicate.arity} arguments"
17             )
18
19     def __str__(self) -> str:
20         """Human-readable string representation."""
21         args = ", ".join(self.arguments)
22         return f"{self.predicate.name}({args})"
23
24     def __repr__(self) -> str:
25         return f"Atom({self.predicate.name}, {self.arguments})"
26
27     def substitute(self, mapping: Dict[str, str]) -> 'Atom':
28         """Apply a variable substitution to create a new atom.
29
30         Args:
31             mapping: Dictionary from variable names to constants.
32
33         Returns:
34             A new Atom with substituted arguments.
35         """
36         new_args = tuple(
37             mapping.get(arg, arg) for arg in self.arguments
38         )
39         return Atom(self.predicate, new_args)

```

Listing 3: Implementation of the Atom class representing ground atomic propositions.

```

1 class FormulaNode(ABC):
2     """Abstract base class for formula syntax tree nodes.
3
4     Each node can evaluate its truth degree under a given

```

```

assignment,
5     in both scalar (Python float) and tensor (PyTorch) forms.
6     """
7
8     @abstractmethod
9     def evaluate(self, assignment: 'TruthAssignment') -> float:
10         """Evaluate the formula under a truth assignment.
11
12         Args:
13             assignment: Mapping from atoms to truth degrees.
14
15         Returns:
16             Truth degree in [0, 1].
17         """
18         pass
19
20     @abstractmethod
21     def evaluate_tensor(
22         self,
23         assignment: 'TensorAssignment'
24     ) -> torch.Tensor:
25         """Tensor-based evaluation for automatic differentiation.
26
27         Args:
28             assignment: Tensor-based truth assignment.
29
30         Returns:
31             Scalar tensor with truth degree.
32         """
33         pass
34
35     @abstractmethod
36     def __str__(self) -> str:
37         """Human-readable formula representation."""
38         pass
39
40
41 class AtomNode(FormulaNode):
42     """Leaf node representing an atomic formula."""
43

```

```

44     def __init__(self, atom: Atom):
45         self.atom = atom
46
47     def evaluate(self, assignment: 'TruthAssignment') -> float:
48         return assignment[self.atom]
49
50     def evaluate_tensor(
51         self,
52         assignment: 'TensorAssignment'
53     ) -> torch.Tensor:
54         return assignment[self.atom]
55
56     def __str__(self) -> str:
57         return str(self.atom)
58
59
60 class NegationNode(FormulaNode):
61     """Lukasiewicz negation:  $\text{neg}(x) = 1 - x$ ."""
62
63     def __init__(self, child: FormulaNode):
64         self.child = child
65
66     def evaluate(self, assignment: 'TruthAssignment') -> float:
67         return 1.0 - self.child.evaluate(assignment)
68
69     def evaluate_tensor(
70         self,
71         assignment: 'TensorAssignment'
72     ) -> torch.Tensor:
73         return 1.0 - self.child.evaluate_tensor(assignment)
74
75     def __str__(self) -> str:
76         return f"NOT({self.child})"
77
78
79 class ConjunctionNode(FormulaNode):
80     """Lukasiewicz conjunction:  $\text{conj}(x,y) = \max(0, x + y - 1)$ ."""
81
82     def __init__(self, left: FormulaNode, right: FormulaNode):
83         self.left = left

```

```

84     self.right = right
85
86     def evaluate(self, assignment: 'TruthAssignment') -> float:
87         l = self.left.evaluate(assignment)
88         r = self.right.evaluate(assignment)
89         return max(0.0, l + r - 1.0)
90
91     def evaluate_tensor(
92         self,
93         assignment: 'TensorAssignment'
94     ) -> torch.Tensor:
95         l = self.left.evaluate_tensor(assignment)
96         r = self.right.evaluate_tensor(assignment)
97         return torch.clamp(l + r - 1.0, min=0.0)
98
99     def __str__(self) -> str:
100         return f"({self.left} AND {self.right})"
101
102
103 class ImplicationNode(FormulaNode):
104     """Lukasiewicz implication:  $\text{impl}(x,y) = \min(1, 1 - x + y)$ ."""
105
106     def __init__(self, antecedent: FormulaNode, consequent:
107 FormulaNode):
108         self.antecedent = antecedent
109         self.consequent = consequent
110
111     def evaluate(self, assignment: 'TruthAssignment') -> float:
112         a = self.antecedent.evaluate(assignment)
113         c = self.consequent.evaluate(assignment)
114         return min(1.0, 1.0 - a + c)
115
116     def evaluate_tensor(
117         self,
118         assignment: 'TensorAssignment'
119     ) -> torch.Tensor:
120         a = self.antecedent.evaluate_tensor(assignment)
121         c = self.consequent.evaluate_tensor(assignment)
122         return torch.clamp(1.0 - a + c, max=1.0)

```

```

123     def __str__(self) -> str:
124         return f"({self.antecedent} -> {self.consequent})"

```

Listing 4: Formula node hierarchy implementing Łukasiewicz operations.

```

1 class TruthAssignment:
2     """A mapping from atoms to truth degrees in [0, 1].
3
4     This class provides the dictionary-based truth assignment used
5     for inspection and non-differentiable computation. For gradient
6     -
7     based learning, use to_tensor_assignment() to convert.
8     """
9     def __init__(self):
10        self._values: Dict[Atom, float] = {}
11        self._default: float = 0.0
12
13    def __getitem__(self, atom: Atom) -> float:
14        """Get truth degree of an atom (default 0.0 if not set)."""
15        return self._values.get(atom, self._default)
16
17    def __setitem__(self, atom: Atom, value: float) -> None:
18        """Set truth degree of an atom.
19
20        Args:
21            atom: The atom to assign.
22            value: Truth degree in [0, 1].
23
24        Raises:
25            ValueError: If value not in [0, 1].
26        """
27        if not 0.0 <= value <= 1.0:
28            raise ValueError(
29                f"Truth degree must be in [0, 1], got {value}"
30            )
31        self._values[atom] = value
32
33    def __contains__(self, atom: Atom) -> bool:
34        """Check if an atom has an explicit truth assignment."""
35        return atom in self._values

```

```

36
37     def __iter__(self):
38         """Iterate over assigned atoms."""
39         return iter(self._values)
40
41     def items(self):
42         """Return (atom, value) pairs."""
43         return self._values.items()
44
45     def to_tensor_assignment(
46         self,
47         atom_index: Dict[Atom, int]
48     ) -> 'TensorAssignment':
49         """Convert to tensor-based assignment for PyTorch.
50
51         Args:
52             atom_index: Mapping from atoms to tensor indices.
53
54         Returns:
55             TensorAssignment with values as PyTorch tensor.
56         """
57         n = len(atom_index)
58         tensor = torch.zeros(n, requires_grad=True)
59
60         # Copy values into tensor
61         for atom, value in self._values.items():
62             if atom in atom_index:
63                 idx = atom_index[atom]
64                 tensor.data[idx] = value
65
66         return TensorAssignment(tensor, atom_index)
67
68     def to_dict(self) -> Dict[str, float]:
69         """Serialize to dictionary for JSON export."""
70         return {str(atom): value for atom, value in self._values.
71 items()}
72
73     @classmethod
74     def from_dict(

```

```

75     data: Dict[str, float],
76     atom_parser: Callable[[str], Atom]
77 ) -> 'TruthAssignment':
78     """Deserialize from dictionary."""
79     assignment = cls()
80     for atom_str, value in data.items():
81         atom = atom_parser(atom_str)
82         assignment[atom] = value
83     return assignment

```

Listing 5: TruthAssignment class mapping atoms to fuzzy truth degrees.

```

1 class KnowledgeBase:
2     """A neuralized Markov logic network knowledge base.
3
4     The knowledge base maintains predicates, constants, weighted
5     formulas, and the current truth assignment. It provides methods
6     for construction, modification, and inspection.
7     """
8
9     def __init__(self, name: str = "default"):
10        self.name = name
11        self.predicates: Dict[str, Predicate] = {}
12        self.constants: Set[str] = set()
13        self.formulas: List[Tuple[FormulaNode, float]] = []
14        self.truth_assignment = TruthAssignment()
15        self._atom_index: Optional[Dict[Atom, int]] = None
16
17    def add_predicate(
18        self,
19        name: str,
20        arity: int
21    ) -> Predicate:
22        """Define a new predicate in the vocabulary.
23
24        Args:
25            name: Predicate name (must be unique).
26            arity: Number of arguments.
27
28        Returns:
29            The created Predicate instance.

```

```

30
31     Raises:
32         ValueError: If predicate name already exists.
33     """
34     if name in self.predicates:
35         raise ValueError(f"Predicate {name} already defined")
36
37     pred = Predicate(name, arity)
38     self.predicates[name] = pred
39     self._invalidate_cache()
40     return pred
41
42 def add_constant(self, name: str) -> None:
43     """Add a constant to the domain."""
44     self.constants.add(name)
45     self._invalidate_cache()
46
47 def add_formula(
48     self,
49     formula: FormulaNode,
50     weight: float
51 ) -> None:
52     """Add a weighted formula to the knowledge base.
53
54     Args:
55         formula: The formula (as a syntax tree).
56         weight: Real-valued weight (can be negative).
57     """
58     self.formulas.append((formula, weight))
59
60 def set_truth(self, atom: Atom, value: float) -> None:
61     """Set the truth degree of a ground atom.
62
63     Args:
64         atom: The atom to assign.
65         value: Truth degree in [0, 1].
66     """
67     # Ensure predicate and constants are registered
68     if atom.predicate.name not in self.predicates:
69         self.predicates[atom.predicate.name] = atom.predicate

```

```

70     for arg in atom.arguments:
71         self.constants.add(arg)
72
73     self.truth_assignment[atom] = value
74
75     def get_atoms(self) -> List[Atom]:
76         """Return all atoms with explicit truth assignments."""
77         return list(self.truth_assignment)
78
79     def get_atom_index(self) -> Dict[Atom, int]:
80         """Get mapping from atoms to indices for tensor operations.
81         """
82         if self._atom_index is None:
83             atoms = self.get_atoms()
84             self._atom_index = {atom: i for i, atom in enumerate(
85 atoms)}
86         return self._atom_index
87
88     def _invalidate_cache(self):
89         """Clear cached computations when KB changes."""
90         self._atom_index = None
91
92     def summary(self) -> str:
93         """Return human-readable summary of knowledge base."""
94         lines = [
95             f"Knowledge Base: {self.name}",
96             f"  Predicates: {len(self.predicates)}",
97             f"  Constants: {len(self.constants)}",
98             f"  Formulas: {len(self.formulas)}",
99             f"  Assigned atoms: {len(list(self.truth_assignment))}"
100         ]
101         return "\n".join(lines)

```

Listing 6: KnowledgeBase class aggregating NMLN components.

A.3 Energy Computation

```

1 def compute_energy(
2     kb: KnowledgeBase,

```

```

3     assignment: Optional[TruthAssignment] = None
4 ) -> float:
5     """Compute the energy of an interpretation.
6
7     Energy is the weighted sum of formula satisfaction degrees:
8         
$$E = \sum_i w_i * [[F_i]]$$

9
10    where  $[[F_i]]$  is the satisfaction degree of formula  $F_i$  under
11    the current truth assignment, computed using Lukasiewicz
12    semantics.
13
14    Args:
15        kb: The knowledge base containing formulas and weights.
16        assignment: Truth assignment (uses kb.truth_assignment if
17        None).
18
19    Returns:
20        Energy as a Python float.
21    """
22
23    if assignment is None:
24        assignment = kb.truth_assignment
25
26    energy = 0.0
27
28    for formula, weight in kb.formulas:
29        satisfaction = formula.evaluate(assignment)
30        energy += weight * satisfaction
31
32    return energy
33
34 def compute_energy_breakdown(
35     kb: KnowledgeBase,
36     assignment: Optional[TruthAssignment] = None
37 ) -> Dict[str, Dict[str, float]]:
38     """Compute energy with per-formula breakdown.
39
40     Returns detailed information about each formula's contribution,
41     useful for debugging and explanation generation.
42
43     Args:

```

```

41     kb: The knowledge base.
42     assignment: Truth assignment (uses kb.truth_assignment if
None).
43
44     Returns:
45         Dictionary with formula string keys and contribution
details.
46     """
47     if assignment is None:
48         assignment = kb.truth_assignment
49
50     breakdown = {}
51     total = 0.0
52
53     for formula, weight in kb.formulas:
54         satisfaction = formula.evaluate(assignment)
55         contribution = weight * satisfaction
56         total += contribution
57
58         breakdown[str(formula)] = {
59             "weight": weight,
60             "satisfaction": satisfaction,
61             "contribution": contribution
62         }
63
64     return {
65         "formulas": breakdown,
66         "total_energy": total
67     }

```

Listing 7: Scalar energy computation using Python floats.

```

1 class TensorAssignment:
2     """Tensor-based truth assignment for PyTorch computation.
3
4     Wraps a PyTorch tensor and provides atom-indexed access,
5     enabling gradient flow through truth value lookups.
6     """
7
8     def __init__(
9         self,

```

```

10     tensor: torch.Tensor,
11     atom_index: Dict[Atom, int]
12 ):
13     self.tensor = tensor
14     self.atom_index = atom_index
15     self._reverse_index = {i: a for a, i in atom_index.items()}
16
17     def __getitem__(self, atom: Atom) -> torch.Tensor:
18         """Get truth degree as a scalar tensor."""
19         if atom not in self.atom_index:
20             return torch.tensor(0.0)
21         idx = self.atom_index[atom]
22         return self.tensor[idx]
23
24
25     def compute_energy_tensor(
26         kb: KnowledgeBase,
27         tensor_assignment: TensorAssignment
28     ) -> torch.Tensor:
29         """Compute energy as a differentiable PyTorch tensor.
30
31         This function enables gradient-based optimization of truth
32         values or formula weights through automatic differentiation.
33
34         Args:
35             kb: The knowledge base.
36             tensor_assignment: Tensor-based truth assignment.
37
38         Returns:
39             Scalar tensor containing the energy value.
40         """
41         energy = torch.tensor(0.0, dtype=torch.float32)
42
43         for formula, weight in kb.formulas:
44             satisfaction = formula.evaluate_tensor(tensor_assignment)
45             energy = energy + weight * satisfaction
46
47         return energy
48
49

```

```

50 def compute_energy_with_grad(
51     kb: KnowledgeBase,
52     truth_tensor: torch.Tensor,
53     atom_index: Dict[Atom, int]
54 ) -> Tuple[torch.Tensor, torch.Tensor]:
55     """Compute energy and its gradient with respect to truth values
56     .
57     Args:
58         kb: The knowledge base.
59         truth_tensor: Tensor of truth values (requires_grad=True).
60         atom_index: Mapping from atoms to tensor indices.
61
62     Returns:
63         Tuple of (energy, gradient) tensors.
64     """
65     truth_tensor = truth_tensor.clone().requires_grad_(True)
66     tensor_assignment = TensorAssignment(truth_tensor, atom_index)
67
68     energy = compute_energy_tensor(kb, tensor_assignment)
69     energy.backward()
70
71     return energy, truth_tensor.grad

```

Listing 8: Tensor-based energy computation for automatic differentiation.

A.4 Inference Module

```

1 class ProposalDistribution(ABC):
2     """Abstract base class for proposal distributions."""
3
4     @abstractmethod
5     def sample(self, kb: KnowledgeBase) -> TruthAssignment:
6         """Draw a sample from the proposal distribution."""
7         pass
8
9     @abstractmethod
10    def log_probability(
11        self,
12        assignment: TruthAssignment,

```

```

13     kb: KnowledgeBase
14 ) -> float:
15     """Compute log probability of an assignment."""
16     pass
17
18
19 class UniformProposal(ProposalDistribution):
20     """Uniform distribution over [0, 1] for each atom."""
21
22     def sample(self, kb: KnowledgeBase) -> TruthAssignment:
23         assignment = TruthAssignment()
24         for atom in kb.get_atoms():
25             assignment[atom] = random.random()
26         return assignment
27
28     def log_probability(
29         self,
30         assignment: TruthAssignment,
31         kb: KnowledgeBase
32     ) -> float:
33         # Uniform on [0,1]^n has density 1, so log density is 0
34         return 0.0
35
36
37 class ImportanceSampler:
38     """Importance sampling for query estimation with traces."""
39
40     def __init__(
41         self,
42         kb: KnowledgeBase,
43         proposal: ProposalDistribution,
44         temperature: float = 1.0
45     ):
46         self.kb = kb
47         self.proposal = proposal
48         self.temperature = temperature
49
50     def estimate(
51         self,
52         query: FormulaNode,

```

```

53     n_samples: int = 100
54 ) -> Tuple[float, 'ExplanationTrace']:
55     """Estimate expected truth degree of a query formula.
56
57     Uses importance sampling to estimate:
58         E_P[[[query]]] = sum_I [[query]](I) * P(I)
59
60     Args:
61         query: Formula to evaluate.
62         n_samples: Number of samples to draw.
63
64     Returns:
65         Tuple of (estimate, explanation_trace).
66     """
67     samples = []
68     log_weights = []
69     query_values = []
70
71     for i in range(n_samples):
72         # Draw from proposal
73         sample = self.proposal.sample(self.kb)
74
75         # Compute importance weight (in log space for stability
76         )
77         target_energy = compute_energy(self.kb, sample)
78         proposal_log_prob = self.proposal.log_probability(
79             sample, self.kb
80         )
81         log_weight = (
82             target_energy / self.temperature -
83             proposal_log_prob
84         )
85
86         # Evaluate query
87         query_value = query.evaluate(sample)
88
89         samples.append(sample)
90         log_weights.append(log_weight)
91         query_values.append(query_value)

```

```

91     # Normalize weights using log-sum-exp for stability
92     max_log_weight = max(log_weights)
93     weights = [
94         math.exp(lw - max_log_weight) for lw in log_weights
95     ]
96     total_weight = sum(weights)
97     normalized_weights = [w / total_weight for w in weights]
98
99     # Compute estimate
100    estimate = sum(
101        w * q for w, q in zip(normalized_weights, query_values)
102    )
103
104    # Build explanation trace
105    trace = self._build_trace(
106        samples, normalized_weights, query_values, query
107    )
108
109    return estimate, trace
110
111    def _build_trace(
112        self,
113        samples: List[TruthAssignment],
114        weights: List[float],
115        query_values: List[float],
116        query: FormulaNode
117    ) -> 'ExplanationTrace':
118        """Construct structured explanation trace."""
119        trace = ExplanationTrace(query_str=str(query))
120
121        for i, (sample, weight, qval) in enumerate(
122            zip(samples, weights, query_values)
123        ):
124            # Compute rule activations for this sample
125            activations = {}
126            for formula, w in self.kb.formulas:
127                sat = formula.evaluate(sample)
128                activations[str(formula)] = {
129                    "satisfaction": sat,
130                    "weighted_contribution": w * sat

```

```

131         }
132
133         record = SampleRecord(
134             index=i,
135             weight=weight,
136             query_value=qval,
137             contribution=weight * qval,
138             rule_activations=activations
139         )
140         trace.add_sample(record)
141
142     return trace

```

Listing 9: Importance sampling implementation with explanation trace generation.

```

1 @dataclass
2 class SampleRecord:
3     """Record of a single sample in importance sampling."""
4     index: int
5     weight: float
6     query_value: float
7     contribution: float
8     rule_activations: Dict[str, Dict[str, float]]
9
10
11 class ExplanationTrace:
12     """Structured trace of the inference process.
13
14     Provides methods for analyzing which samples and rules
15     contributed most to the final estimate.
16     """
17
18     def __init__(self, query_str: str = ""):
19         self.query_str = query_str
20         self.samples: List[SampleRecord] = []
21         self.metadata: Dict[str, Any] = {}
22
23     def add_sample(self, record: SampleRecord) -> None:
24         """Add a sample record to the trace."""
25         self.samples.append(record)
26

```

```

27 def top_contributors(self, n: int = 5) -> List[SampleRecord]:
28     """Return the n samples with highest contributions."""
29     return sorted(
30         self.samples,
31         key=lambda s: abs(s.contribution),
32         reverse=True
33    )[:n]
34
35 def rule_importance(self) -> Dict[str, float]:
36     """Compute aggregate importance of each rule.
37
38     Importance is the weighted sum of absolute contributions
39     across all samples, normalized to sum to 1.
40     """
41     importance: Dict[str, float] = defaultdict(float)
42
43     for sample in self.samples:
44         for rule, activation in sample.rule_activations.items():
45             importance[rule] += (
46                 abs(activation["weighted_contribution"])
47                 * sample.weight
48             )
49
50     # Normalize
51     total = sum(importance.values())
52     if total > 0:
53         for rule in importance:
54             importance[rule] /= total
55
56     return dict(importance)
57
58 def summary(self) -> str:
59     """Generate human-readable summary."""
60     lines = [
61         f"Inference Trace for: {self.query_str}",
62         f" Total samples: {len(self.samples)}",
63         f" Effective sample size: {self._effective_sample_size
64             ().__str__().1f}",
65         ""

```

```

65         "Top contributing samples:",
66     ]
67
68     for record in self.top_contributors(3):
69         lines.append(
70             f" Sample {record.index}: "
71             f"weight={record.weight:.4f}, "
72             f"contribution={record.contribution:.4f}"
73         )
74
75     lines.extend(["", "Most important rules:"])
76     importance = self.rule_importance()
77     for rule, imp in sorted(
78         importance.items(), key=lambda x: -x[1]
79     )[:3]:
80         lines.append(f" {rule}: {imp:.3f}")
81
82     return "\n".join(lines)
83
84     def _effective_sample_size(self) -> float:
85         """Compute effective sample size (ESS)."""
86         weights = [s.weight for s in self.samples]
87         if not weights:
88             return 0.0
89         sum_w = sum(weights)
90         sum_w2 = sum(w**2 for w in weights)
91         if sum_w2 == 0:
92             return 0.0
93         return (sum_w ** 2) / sum_w2
94
95     def to_dict(self) -> Dict[str, Any]:
96         """Serialize trace for JSON export."""
97         return {
98             "query": self.query_str,
99             "n_samples": len(self.samples),
100            "effective_sample_size": self._effective_sample_size(),
101            "top_contributors": [
102                {
103                    "index": s.index,
104                    "weight": s.weight,

```

```

105         "query_value": s.query_value,
106         "contribution": s.contribution
107     }
108     for s in self.top_contributors()
109 ],
110     "rule_importance": self.rule_importance(),
111     "metadata": self.metadata
112 }

```

Listing 10: ExplanationTrace class for structured inference records.

A.5 Orchestration Pipeline

```

1 class LLMClient(ABC):
2     """Abstract interface for LLM interaction."""
3
4     @abstractmethod
5     async def generate(
6         self,
7         prompt: str,
8         max_tokens: int = 1000
9     ) -> str:
10        """Generate text from a prompt."""
11        pass
12
13
14 class LimenPipeline:
15     """High-level orchestration for LIMEN-AI applications.
16
17     Integrates knowledge base management, inference, and natural
18     language interaction through an LLM client.
19     """
20
21     def __init__(
22         self,
23         llm_client: LLMClient,
24         schema: 'SchemaRegistry',
25         kb: KnowledgeBase,
26         callbacks: Optional['PipelineCallbacks'] = None
27     ):

```

```

28     self.llm = llm_client
29     self.schema = schema
30     self.kb = kb
31     self.callbacks = callbacks or PipelineCallbacks()
32
33     # Initialize sub-pipelines
34     self.ingestion = DocumentIngestionPipeline(
35         llm_client=llm_client,
36         schema=schema,
37         kb=kb
38     )
39     self.query_translator = QueryTranslator(
40         llm_client=llm_client,
41         schema=schema
42     )
43     self.response_generator = ResponseGenerator(
44         llm_client=llm_client
45     )
46
47     async def ingest_document(
48         self,
49         text: str,
50         source: str = "unknown"
51     ) -> 'IngestionResult':
52         """Extract facts from a natural language document."""
53         self.callbacks.on_ingestion_start(text, source)
54         result = await self.ingestion.process(text, source)
55         self.callbacks.on_ingestion_complete(result)
56         return result
57
58     async def answer_question(
59         self,
60         question: str,
61         n_samples: int = 100
62     ) -> 'AnswerResult':
63         """Answer a natural language question."""
64         self.callbacks.on_query_start(question)
65
66         # Translate to structured query
67         query = await self.query_translator.translate(question)

```

```

68     self.callbacks.on_query_translated(query)
69
70     # Perform inference
71     sampler = ImportanceSampler(self.kb, UniformProposal())
72     estimate, trace = sampler.estimate(query.formula, n_samples
    )
73
74     # Generate natural language response
75     response = await self.response_generator.generate(
76         question=question,
77         query=query,
78         estimate=estimate,
79         trace=trace
80     )
81
82     result = AnswerResult(
83         question=question,
84         query=query,
85         estimate=estimate,
86         response=response,
87         trace=trace
88     )
89
90     self.callbacks.on_query_complete(result)
91     return result
92
93 def save_state(self, path: str) -> None:
94     """Persist pipeline state to disk."""
95     state = {
96         "schema": self.schema.to_dict(),
97         "kb_name": self.kb.name,
98         "truth_assignment": self.kb.truth_assignment.to_dict(),
99         "formulas": [
100             {"formula": str(f), "weight": w}
101             for f, w in self.kb.formulas
102         ]
103     }
104     with open(path, 'w') as f:
105         json.dump(state, f, indent=2)

```

Listing 11: LimenPipeline class for LLM-integrated orchestration.

```

1 @dataclass
2 class ExtractedFact:
3     """A fact extracted from text by the LLM."""
4     predicate: str
5     arguments: List[str]
6     confidence: float
7     source_chunk: int
8     source_text: str
9
10
11 class DocumentIngestionPipeline:
12     """Extract structured facts from documents using LLM."""
13
14     def __init__(
15         self,
16         llm_client: LLMClient,
17         schema: 'SchemaRegistry',
18         kb: KnowledgeBase,
19         chunk_size: int = 1000,
20         chunk_overlap: int = 100
21     ):
22         self.llm = llm_client
23         self.schema = schema
24         self.kb = kb
25         self.chunk_size = chunk_size
26         self.chunk_overlap = chunk_overlap
27
28     async def process(
29         self,
30         text: str,
31         source: str = "unknown"
32     ) -> 'IngestionResult':
33         """Process a document and extract facts."""
34         chunks = self._chunk_text(text)
35         all_facts: List[ExtractedFact] = []
36         errors: List[str] = []
37
38         for i, chunk in enumerate(chunks):
39             try:
40                 prompt = self._build_extraction_prompt(chunk, i)

```

```

41         response = await self.llm.generate(prompt)
42         facts = self._parse_facts(response, i, chunk)
43         validated = self._validate_facts(facts)
44         all_facts.extend(validated)
45     except Exception as e:
46         errors.append(f"Chunk {i}: {str(e)}")
47
48     # Add validated facts to knowledge base
49     for fact in all_facts:
50         atom = self._fact_to_atom(fact)
51         if atom is not None:
52             self.kb.set_truth(atom, fact.confidence)
53
54     return IngestionResult(
55         source=source,
56         n_chunks=len(chunks),
57         n_facts_extracted=len(all_facts),
58         n_facts_added=len([f for f in all_facts
59                             if self._fact_to_atom(f)]),
60         facts=all_facts,
61         errors=errors
62     )
63
64     def _chunk_text(self, text: str) -> List[str]:
65         """Split text into overlapping chunks."""
66         words = text.split()
67         chunks = []
68         start = 0
69
70         while start < len(words):
71             end = min(start + self.chunk_size, len(words))
72             chunk = " ".join(words[start:end])
73             chunks.append(chunk)
74             start = end - self.chunk_overlap
75             if start >= len(words):
76                 break
77
78         return chunks
79
80     def _build_extraction_prompt(

```

```

81     self,
82     chunk: str,
83     chunk_idx: int
84 ) -> str:
85     """Build prompt for LLM fact extraction."""
86     schema_desc = self.schema.describe()
87     return f"""Extract facts from the text below.
88 Available predicates:
89 {schema_desc}
90
91 Text (chunk {chunk_idx}):
92 {chunk}
93
94 Output JSON array of facts:"""

```

Listing 12: Document ingestion pipeline for fact extraction.

```

1 @dataclass
2 class PredicateInfo:
3     """Information about a predicate in the schema."""
4     name: str
5     arity: int
6     argument_types: List[str]
7     description: str
8
9
10 class SchemaRegistry:
11     """Registry of available predicates for fact extraction."""
12
13     def __init__(self):
14         self._predicates: Dict[str, PredicateInfo] = {}
15
16     def register(
17         self,
18         name: str,
19         arity: int,
20         argument_types: List[str],
21         description: str
22     ) -> None:
23         """Register a predicate in the schema."""
24         if len(argument_types) != arity:

```

```

25         raise ValueError(
26             f"argument_types length must match arity"
27         )
28
29     self._predicates[name] = PredicateInfo(
30         name=name,
31         arity=arity,
32         argument_types=argument_types,
33         description=description
34     )
35
36     def is_valid_predicate(self, name: str) -> bool:
37         """Check if a predicate name is registered."""
38         return name in self._predicates
39
40     def get_predicate(self, name: str) -> Optional[PredicateInfo]:
41         """Get predicate information."""
42         return self._predicates.get(name)
43
44     def describe(self) -> str:
45         """Generate schema description for LLM prompts."""
46         lines = []
47         for name, info in self._predicates.items():
48             args = ", ".join(f"{t}" for t in info.argument_types)
49             lines.append(f"- {name}({args}): {info.description}")
50         return "\n".join(lines)
51
52     def to_dict(self) -> Dict[str, Any]:
53         """Serialize schema for persistence."""
54         return {
55             name: {
56                 "arity": info.arity,
57                 "argument_types": info.argument_types,
58                 "description": info.description
59             }
60             for name, info in self._predicates.items()
61         }

```

Listing 13: SchemaRegistry for predicate vocabulary management.

A.6 Testing and Quality Assurance

```
1 class TestLukasiewiczOperations:
2     """Unit tests verifying Lukasiewicz operation properties."""
3
4     def test_negation_involution(self):
5         """Verify that negation is an involution: neg(neg(x)) = x."""
6         """
7         for x in [0.0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0]:
8             result = 1.0 - (1.0 - x)
9             assert abs(result - x) < 1e-10
10
11        def test_negation_bounds(self):
12            """Verify negation stays in [0, 1]."""
13            for x in [0.0, 0.5, 1.0]:
14                result = 1.0 - x
15                assert 0.0 <= result <= 1.0
16
17        def test_conjunction_identity(self):
18            """Verify conjunction with 1 is identity: x AND 1 = x."""
19            for x in [0.0, 0.3, 0.7, 1.0]:
20                result = max(0.0, x + 1.0 - 1.0)
21                assert abs(result - x) < 1e-10
22
23        def test_conjunction_annihilator(self):
24            """Verify conjunction with 0 is 0: x AND 0 = 0."""
25            for x in [0.0, 0.5, 1.0]:
26                result = max(0.0, x + 0.0 - 1.0)
27                assert result == 0.0
28
29        def test_implication_tautology(self):
30            """Verify x -> x = 1 for all x."""
31            for x in [0.0, 0.3, 0.7, 1.0]:
32                result = min(1.0, 1.0 - x + x)
33                assert result == 1.0
34
35 class TestEnergyComputation:
36     """Tests for energy function computation."""
37
```

```

38     def test_empty_kb_zero_energy(self):
39         """Empty KB has zero energy."""
40         kb = KnowledgeBase()
41         assignment = TruthAssignment()
42         energy = compute_energy(kb, assignment)
43         assert energy == 0.0
44
45     def test_positive_weight_increases_with_satisfaction(self):
46         """Higher satisfaction increases energy for positive weight
47         ."""
48         kb = KnowledgeBase()
49         p = kb.add_predicate("p", 1)
50         kb.add_constant("a")
51         atom = p("a")
52
53         formula = AtomNode(atom)
54         kb.add_formula(formula, weight=2.0)
55
56         # Low satisfaction
57         kb.set_truth(atom, 0.2)
58         low_energy = compute_energy(kb)
59
60         # High satisfaction
61         kb.set_truth(atom, 0.8)
62         high_energy = compute_energy(kb)
63
64         assert high_energy > low_energy

```

Listing 14: Unit tests for Łukasiewicz operations.

```

1 name: CI
2
3 on:
4   push:
5     branches: [main, develop]
6   pull_request:
7     branches: [main]
8
9 jobs:
10  test:
11    runs-on: ubuntu-latest

```

```

12 strategy:
13     matrix:
14         python-version: ['3.9', '3.10', '3.11']
15
16     steps:
17     - uses: actions/checkout@v4
18
19     - name: Set up Python
20       uses: actions/setup-python@v5
21       with:
22         python-version: ${ matrix.python-version }
23
24     - name: Install dependencies
25       run: pip install -e ".[dev]"
26
27     - name: Type checking
28       run: mypy limen --strict
29
30     - name: Linting
31       run: flake8 limen tests
32
33     - name: Run tests
34       run: pytest tests/ -v --cov=limen --cov-report=xml
35
36 publish:
37     needs: test
38     if: startsWith(github.ref, 'refs/tags/v')
39     runs-on: ubuntu-latest
40
41     steps:
42     - uses: actions/checkout@v4
43     - name: Build package
44       run: pip install build && python -m build
45     - name: Publish to PyPI
46       uses: pypa/gh-action-pypi-publish@release/v1

```

Listing 15: GitHub Actions workflow for CI/CD.

A.7 Package Configuration and Usage

```

1 [project]
2 name = "limen-ai"
3 version = "0.3.0"
4 description = "LIMEN-AI: Lukasiewicz Interpretable Markov Engine"
5 readme = "README.md"
6 license = {text = "AGPLv3"}
7 authors = [
8     {name = "Enrico Zanardo"}
9 ]
10 keywords = [
11     "markov-logic", "fuzzy-logic",
12     "interpretable-ai", "neural-symbolic"
13 ]
14 dependencies = ["torch>=2.0.0"]
15 requires-python = ">=3.9"
16
17 [project.optional-dependencies]
18 dev = [
19     "pytest>=7.0",
20     "pytest-asyncio>=0.21",
21     "mypy>=1.0",
22     "black>=23.0",
23 ]
24
25 [build-system]
26 requires = ["setuptools>=61.0"]
27 build-backend = "setuptools.build_meta"

```

Listing 16: Package configuration in pyproject.toml.

```

1 pip install limen-ai

```

Listing 17: Installing LIMEN-AI from PyPI.

```

1 from limen import KnowledgeBase, compute_energy
2 from limen.core import AtomNode, ImplicationNode
3
4 # Create knowledge base
5 kb = KnowledgeBase(name="example")
6
7 # Define predicates
8 connected = kb.add_predicate("connected", 2)

```

```

9 reachable = kb.add_predicate("reachable", 2)
10
11 # Add domain constants
12 for node in ["a", "b", "c"]:
13     kb.add_constant(node)
14
15 # Set observed facts
16 kb.set_truth(connected("a", "b"), 0.9)
17 kb.set_truth(connected("b", "c"), 0.8)
18 kb.set_truth(reachable("a", "b"), 0.9)
19
20 # Add a weighted rule
21 rule = ImplicationNode(
22     AtomNode(connected("a", "b")),
23     AtomNode(reachable("a", "b"))
24 )
25 kb.add_formula(rule, weight=2.0)
26
27 # Compute energy
28 energy = compute_energy(kb)
29 print(f"Energy: {energy:.4f}")

```

Listing 18: Basic usage example demonstrating KB construction and energy computation.

```

1 from limen import KnowledgeBase
2 from limen.core import ImplicationNode, AtomNode
3
4 # Start with basic knowledge
5 kb = KnowledgeBase(name="network_security")
6 connected = kb.add_predicate("connected", 2)
7 vulnerable = kb.add_predicate("vulnerable", 1)
8 compromised = kb.add_predicate("compromised", 1)
9
10 # Initial facts
11 kb.set_truth(connected("server1", "server2"), 0.95)
12 kb.set_truth(vulnerable("server1"), 0.8)
13
14 # Later: add more facts as they are discovered
15 kb.add_constant("server3")
16 kb.set_truth(connected("server2", "server3"), 0.9)

```

```

17
18 # Add rules based on domain expertise
19 rule1 = ImplicationNode(
20     AtomNode(vulnerable("server1")),
21     AtomNode(compromised("server1"))
22 )
23 kb.add_formula(rule1, weight=1.5)

```

Listing 19: Incremental knowledge base construction pattern.

```

1 class NeurosymbolicInducer:
2     """Neurosymbolic hybrid ILP using LLM proposal + gradient
3     tuning.
4
5     Achieves ~3x10^5 speedup over traditional template-based ILP by
6     :
7     1. Using LLM to propose semantically meaningful rules (O(1) vs
8     O(p^3))
9     2. Validating rules against KB facts (O(rxn) pruning)
10    3. Optimizing weights via differentiable Łukasiewicz ops (O(rxt
11    ))
12    """
13
14    def __init__(
15        self,
16        kb: KnowledgeBase,
17        llm_client: LLMClient,
18        domain_context: str = "general",
19        learning_rate: float = 0.05,
20        train_steps: int = 100,
21        min_support: int = 2,
22        device: str = "cuda"
23    ):
24        self.kb = kb
25        self.llm_client = llm_client
26        self.domain_context = domain_context
27        self.learning_rate = learning_rate
28        self.train_steps = train_steps
29        self.min_support = min_support
30        self.device = device

```

```

28     def _llm_propose_rules(
29         self,
30         target_predicate: str,
31         n_proposals: int = 5
32     ) -> List[Dict]:
33         """Step 1: Ask LLM to propose semantically meaningful rules
34         .
35
36         Complexity: O(1) LLM call vs O(p^3) template generation.
37         For 460 predicates: 1 call vs 97,336,000 templates!
38         """
39         prompt = f"""Domain: {self.domain_context}
40 Target predicate: {target_predicate}
41
42 Task: Suggest {n_proposals} plausible causal rules where
43 {target_predicate} is the consequent. Use predicates from:
44 {'', '}.join(p.name for p in self.kb.predicates.values())}
45
46 Format: antecedent1(X) AND antecedent2(X,Y) -> {target_predicate}(Y
47         )"""
48
49         response = self.llm_client.generate(prompt)
50         return self._parse_rule_proposals(response)

```

Listing 20: Neurosymbolic Hybrid ILP: Step 1 - LLM Semantic Proposal for meaningful rule generation.

```

1     def _validate_rules(
2         self,
3         proposed_rules: List[Dict],
4         assignment: TruthAssignment
5     ) -> List[Dict]:
6         """Step 2: Filter rules based on KB fact support.
7
8         Complexity: O(r × n) where r=rules (5-10), n=facts
9         (100-1000).
10        Total: ~500-10,000 checks vs 1.9 billion for templates.
11        """
12        validated = []

```

```

13     for rule in proposed_rules:
14         body_predicates = {ant["pred"] for ant in rule["body"]}
15
16         # Count matching facts
17         support = sum(
18             1 for atom in assignment.values.keys()
19             if atom.predicate.name in body_predicates
20         ) // len(body_predicates)
21
22         if support >= self.min_support:
23             validated.append(rule)
24
25     return validated

```

Listing 21: Neurosymbolic Hybrid ILP: Step 2 - Data-driven validation to prevent hallucinations.

```

1     def _optimize_weights(
2         self,
3         validated_rules: List[Dict],
4         assignment: TruthAssignment
5     ) -> List[LearnedRule]:
6         """Step 3: Optimize rule weights via gradient descent.
7
8         Complexity:  $O(r \times t)$  where  $r=5-10$ ,  $t=100$ .
9         Total: ~500-1000 gradient steps vs 1.9 billion operations!
10        """
11         import torch
12         import torch.nn as nn
13
14         # Convert to FormulaNode trees
15         formulas = [self._rule_to_formula(r) for r in
validated_rules]
16
17         # Learnable weights
18         weights = nn.ParameterList([
19             nn.Parameter(torch.tensor([1.0]))
20             for _ in formulas
21         ])
22
23         optimizer = torch.optim.Adam(weights, lr=self.learning_rate

```

```

)
24     tensor_assign = assignment.to_tensor_assignment()
25
26     # Training loop (100 steps, not billions!)
27     for step in range(self.train_steps):
28         optimizer.zero_grad()
29         loss = 0.0
30
31         for i, formula in enumerate(formulas):
32             sat = formula.evaluate_tensor(tensor_assign)
33             w = torch.sigmoid(weights[i])
34             loss -= w * sat # Maximize satisfaction
35
36         loss.backward()
37         optimizer.step()
38
39     return [
40         LearnedRule(formula=f, weight=torch.sigmoid(w).item())
41         for f, w in zip(formulas, weights)
42         if torch.sigmoid(w).item() > 0.1
43     ]

```

Listing 22: Neurosymbolic Hybrid ILP: Step 3 - Differentiable weight optimization via gradient descent.

```

1 def make_decision_with_explanation(
2     kb: KnowledgeBase,
3     query: FormulaNode,
4     threshold: float = 0.5,
5     n_samples: int = 200
6 ) -> Dict[str, Any]:
7     """Make a decision with full explanation."""
8     sampler = ImportanceSampler(kb, UniformProposal())
9     estimate, trace = sampler.estimate(query, n_samples)
10
11     decision = "APPROVE" if estimate >= threshold else "DENY"
12
13     explanation = {
14         "decision": decision,
15         "confidence": estimate,
16         "threshold": threshold,

```

```

17     "query": str(query),
18     "effective_sample_size": trace._effective_sample_size(),
19     "supporting_rules": []
20 }
21
22 # Identify contributing rules
23 importance = trace.rule_importance()
24 for rule, imp in sorted(importance.items(), key=lambda x: -x
25 [1])[:5]:
26     if imp > 0.1:
27         explanation["supporting_rules"].append({
28             "rule": rule, "importance": imp
29         })
30 return explanation

```

Listing 23: Decision support pattern with explanation generation.

B Formal Verification of Łukasiewicz Logic

An Isabelle/HOL formalisation mechanically verifies the mathematical claims underpinning LIMEN-AI. Across four theory files (~ 650 lines of definitions and proofs), 55 theorems cover Łukasiewicz operations, formula semantics, energy-function properties, and piecewise linearity—all machine-checked against Chapter 3.

B.1 Introduction to Formal Methods in AI Systems

B.1.1 The Assurance Gap in Modern AI

Modern AI systems are overwhelmingly empirical artefacts, probed through benchmarks, adversarial testing, and statistical sampling. These methods have driven rapid progress, but they leave an assurance gap—*no finite test suite can guarantee correctness on all possible inputs*. Deployed failures (autonomous-vehicle crashes, biased hiring algorithms, financial trading anomalies) routinely trace back to corner cases that escaped validation. In safety-critical domains—medical diagnosis, legal reasoning, financial risk assessment—empirical validation alone may fall short of what regulators and domain experts demand.

Formal verification closes this gap by using mathematical logic to *prove* properties for *all* inputs. A theorem accepted by a proof checker holds with mathematical certainty, independent of sampling bias or statistical significance. Two obstacles have historically limited its uptake in AI. The more fundamental is that most AI systems are defined operationally (as trained parameters) rather than declaratively (as specifications), leaving nothing clean to verify. Even when a specification does exist, state-space explosion in model checking and the expertise cost of interactive theorem proving restrict verification to small, critical subsystems.

B.1.2 Why LIMEN-AI is Uniquely Amenable to Formal Verification

LIMEN-AI is simultaneously a neural system (optimised via gradient descent) and a symbolic system (defined by explicit logical rules). This duality makes formal verification both *feasible* and *valuable*.

The symbolic component—a knowledge base of weighted first-order formulas evaluated under Łukasiewicz semantics—has a clean mathematical specification that predates the implementation. Its operations (t-norm, t-conorm, negation, implication)

are closed-form algebraic expressions (e.g., $\max(0, a + b - 1)$), and its semantics (formula evaluation, ground satisfaction, energy computation) are compositional: the meaning of a complex formula is determined recursively from the meanings of its sub-formulas. Compositionality is what enables formal reasoning here—properties can be proved by structural induction on formulas, without reasoning about the entire state space at once.

Many of the properties worth verifying are *local*: they concern individual operations or small compositions, not global system-level invariants involving millions of parameters. For example:

- **Well-formedness:** Do Łukasiewicz operations map truth degrees in $[0, 1]$ to truth degrees in $[0, 1]$? This is a property of the operation definitions alone, independent of any particular knowledge base or interpretation.
- **Commutativity:** Is $a \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} b = b \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} a$ for all $a, b \in [0, 1]$? This is a simple algebraic identity that can be verified by expanding the definitions and applying arithmetic reasoning.
- **De Morgan laws:** Does $\neg_{\mathbb{L}}(a \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} b) = (\neg_{\mathbb{L}} a) \vee_{\mathbb{L}} (\neg_{\mathbb{L}} b)$ hold for all truth degrees? Again, this is a property of the operation definitions, provable by case analysis on the regions of the piecewise linear functions.

These properties are *universal*: they must hold for all possible inputs. Testing can build confidence—sampling one million random pairs (a, b) and checking commutativity, for instance—but it cannot deliver certainty. Formal verification proves properties for the uncountably infinite set of all truth-degree pairs, ruling out corner-case violations entirely.

B.1.3 The Role of Isabelle/HOL

Isabelle/HOL (Higher-Order Logic) is a general-purpose proof assistant developed at the University of Cambridge and Technical University of Munich. It provides a formal language for stating mathematical definitions and theorems, and a proof engine for mechanically checking that proposed proofs are logically valid. Isabelle has been used to verify a wide range of critical systems, including:

- The seL4 microkernel: a formally verified operating system kernel with end-to-end correctness guarantees from implementation to hardware.

- Cryptographic protocols: proofs of security properties for key exchange algorithms, digital signature schemes, and blockchain consensus protocols.
- Mathematical theorems: mechanised versions of major results in number theory, real analysis, and abstract algebra, including portions of the Kepler conjecture proof.

Isabelle offers three complementary advantages for this work. *Definitional transparency*: every definition is explicit and unambiguous—the Łukasiewicz AND operation, for instance, is specified precisely as:

```
definition luk_and :: "truth_degree => truth_degree => truth_degree"
  where "luk_and a b = max 0 (min 1 (a + b - 1))"
```

leaving no room for implementation drift. *Mechanical proof checking*: claiming a theorem such as `luk_and_commutative` requires supplying a sequence of inference steps, each justified by axioms or earlier results; if Isabelle accepts the proof, correctness is guaranteed with no possibility of subtle error. *Proof automation*: Sledgehammer translates goals to external SAT/SMT solvers and reconstructs proofs inside Isabelle, discharging routine obligations automatically. The 55 theorems here took roughly two days of interactive development.

B.1.4 Scope and Limitations of the Formalisation

The scope is limited to the *mathematical core* of LIMEN-AI: Łukasiewicz logic operations, formula-evaluation semantics, and energy-function properties. The formalisation does *not* cover the Python implementation in `src/limen/`, the learning algorithms (gradient descent, sampling), or application-level reasoning (case law retrieval, anomaly detection).

This boundary reflects a deliberate engineering trade-off. Verifying the mathematical definitions provides the strongest possible assurance for the theoretical claims in Chapter 3. If commutativity is proved for the Łukasiewicz operations, then any correct implementation must exhibit commutativity—otherwise it deviates from the specification. The formalisation therefore doubles as a *specification* against which the implementation can be validated.

Extending verification to the implementation would require a different approach: Isabelle’s code extraction (generating verified OCaml or Haskell from Isabelle defini-

tions) or a program-verification framework such as Why3 or Dafny for the Python code. Both routes are feasible future work but fall outside the present thesis.

Verifying the learning algorithms would demand reasoning about probabilistic and numerical properties—convergence of stochastic gradient descent, floating-point arithmetic, numerical stability—topics that remain active research areas in formal methods.

Even within these bounds, the formalisation certifies that LIMEN-AI’s *logical substrate* is mathematically sound. The 55 verified theorems serve as a specification against which implementation bugs can be diagnosed: any empirical behaviour inconsistent with a theorem must originate in the code, not the mathematics.

B.1.5 Significance for Regulatory Compliance

The formalisation carries direct regulatory weight. Article 13 of the EU AI Act (Chapter 7) demands transparency “appropriate to enable deployers to interpret the system’s output.” The Isabelle theories function as machine-readable documentation that regulators, auditors, or domain experts can inspect to see exactly how formulas are evaluated and energy computed. Article 15 requires validated accuracy and robustness. The well-formedness theorems (`luk_and_valid`, `satisfaction_valid`) prove that the logical core cannot produce truth degrees outside $[0, 1]$ regardless of inputs. The monotonicity theorems (`luk_and_monotonic_left`) guarantee stable, predictable behaviour under perturbations: slightly raising an input truth degree can only raise (or leave unchanged) the satisfaction of a conjunction, never lower it.

B.2 Primer on Isabelle/HOL for Non-Experts

The primer below covers enough Isabelle/HOL background to read the theorems in Sections B.3 and B.4; it is not a comprehensive tutorial.

B.2.1 The Logic: Higher-Order Logic (HOL)

Isabelle/HOL is based on *higher-order logic*, a powerful formal system that extends first-order predicate logic with the ability to quantify over functions and predicates. In HOL, functions are first-class citizens: they can be passed as arguments, returned as results, and reasoned about using the same logical machinery as ordinary values.

The basic building blocks of HOL include:

Types: Every term in Isabelle has a type, which describes the kind of mathematical object it represents. Common types include:

- `bool`: The type of Boolean truth values (`True` and `False`).
- `nat`: The type of natural numbers $(0, 1, 2, \dots)$.
- `real`: The type of real numbers.
- `a => b`: The type of functions from `a` to `b`.
- `a * b`: The type of pairs with components of types `a` and `b`.
- `a list`: The type of lists with elements of type `a`.

For LIMEN-AI, we define a custom type `truth_degree` as a synonym for `real`, representing fuzzy truth values:

```
type_synonym truth_degree = real
```

This synonym improves readability by making the intended semantics explicit.

Terms: Terms are expressions built from variables, constants, function applications, and lambda abstractions. Examples:

- `0`, `1`, `2.5`: Literal numbers.
- `a + b`: Function application (addition applied to `a` and `b`).
- `max 0 (a + b - 1)`: Nested function application.
- `$\lambda x. x + 1$` : Lambda abstraction (anonymous function incrementing its argument).

Formulas: Formulas are terms of type `bool`. They can be combined using logical connectives:

- `$\neg P$` : Negation.
- `$P \wedge Q$` : Conjunction.
- `$P \vee Q$` : Disjunction.
- `$P \longrightarrow Q$` : Implication.
- `$P \longleftrightarrow Q$` : Bi-implication (equivalence).

- $\forall x.$ $P(x)$: Universal quantification.
- $\exists x.$ $P(x)$: Existential quantification.

Note: The logical connectives ($\wedge, \vee, \longrightarrow$) in Isabelle are *meta-logical* operators on Boolean values, distinct from the Łukasiewicz fuzzy logic operations ($\wedge_{\mathbb{L}}, \vee_{\mathbb{L}}, \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}}$) that we define and reason about.

B.2.2 Definitions and Theorems

Mathematical knowledge in Isabelle is built through a sequence of *definitions* (introducing new constants or types) and *theorems* (stating properties that have been proven).

Definitions. A definition introduces a new constant by specifying its meaning in terms of previously defined concepts. For example, the Łukasiewicz AND operation is defined as:

```
definition luk_and :: "truth_degree => truth_degree => truth_degree"
  (infixl "□L" 70)
  where "luk_and a b ≡ max 0 (min 1 (a + b - 1))"
```

Breaking this down:

- **definition:** Keyword indicating a new definition.
- **luk_and:** Name of the new constant.
- **:: "truth_degree => truth_degree => truth_degree":** Type signature (a function taking two truth degrees and returning a truth degree).
- **(infixl "□_L" 70):** Optional infix notation with precedence 70 (higher precedence = tighter binding).
- **where "luk_and a b ≡ ...":** The defining equation. The symbol \equiv is meta-logical equality (definitional equality).

After this definition, `luk_and a b` and `max 0 (min 1 (a + b - 1))` are interchangeable—they denote the same mathematical object by definition.

Theorems. A theorem (or lemma, which is synonymous in Isabelle) states a property that we claim to be true and intend to prove. For example:

```
lemma luk_and_commutative:
  assumes "valid_truth a" "valid_truth b"
  shows "luk_and a b = luk_and b a"
```

Breaking this down:

- `lemma`: Keyword indicating a theorem statement.
- `luk_and_commutative`: Name of the theorem (for later reference).
- `assumes`: Preconditions (hypotheses) that we assume to hold. Here, we assume that `a` and `b` are valid truth degrees (i.e., in the interval $[0, 1]$).
- `shows`: The conclusion that we aim to prove, given the assumptions.

After stating the theorem, we must provide a *proof*. Proofs in Isabelle are written in Isar (Intelligible Semi-Automated Reasoning), a structured proof language designed for human readability.

B.2.3 Proof Structure in Isar

Isar proofs consist of a sequence of proof steps, each justified by a tactic or a previously proven theorem. A typical structure is:

```
proof -
  <proof steps>
qed
```

Within the proof, we can use various tactics:

- `by simp`: Automatically simplify using rewrite rules.
- `by auto`: Try various proof search strategies automatically.
- `by (simp add: thm1 thm2)`: Simplify using specific theorems `thm1` and `thm2`.
- `unfolding def1 def2`: Expand definitions `def1` and `def2` before proceeding.
- `have "..."`: `<proof>`: Prove an intermediate fact.
- `show "..."`: `<proof>`: Prove the goal statement.

For example, a simple proof of commutativity might look like:

```
lemma luk_and_commutative:
  assumes "valid_truth a" "valid_truth b"
  shows "luk_and a b = luk_and b a"
  unfolding luk_and_def using assms by simp
```

This proof unfolds the definition of `luk_and`, applies the assumptions (using `assms`), and then simplifies (by `simp`). The simplifier recognises that `max` and `min` are commutative, completing the proof automatically.

B.2.4 Key Isabelle Concepts for LIMEN-AI

Type Synonyms. We use `type_synonym` to create readable aliases:

```
type_synonym truth_degree = real
type_synonym atom_id = nat
type_synonym weight = real
```

These do not introduce new types (in the sense of abstract data types); they are merely abbreviations that improve code readability.

Predicates for Validity. We define a predicate `valid_truth` to express the constraint that a truth degree must be in $[0, 1]$:

```
definition valid_truth :: "truth_degree => bool"
  where "valid_truth a  $\equiv$   $0 \leq a \wedge a \leq 1$ "
```

Many of our theorems assume `valid_truth a` as a precondition, reflecting the fact that Łukasiewicz operations are defined for truth degrees, not arbitrary real numbers.

Inductive Datatypes. We define the syntax of formulas using an inductive datatype:

```
datatype formula =
  Atom atom_id
| Neg formula
| And formula formula
| Or formula formula
| Implies formula formula
```

This defines `formula` as a tree structure, where leaves are atoms (identified by natural numbers) and internal nodes are logical connectives. This inductive structure

enables proofs by structural induction: to prove a property $P(\varphi)$ for all formulas φ , we prove it for atoms (base case) and show that if it holds for sub-formulas, it holds for compound formulas (inductive case).

Recursive Functions. We define formula evaluation recursively:

```
fun satisfaction :: "interp => formula => truth_degree"
  (infix "⊨" 50)
  where
    "I ⊨ (Atom a) = I a"
  | "I ⊨ (Neg φ) = luk_not (I ⊨ φ)"
  | "I ⊨ (And φ ψ) = luk_and (I ⊨ φ) (I ⊨ ψ)"
  | "I ⊨ (Or φ ψ) = luk_or (I ⊨ φ) (I ⊨ ψ)"
  | "I ⊨ (Implies φ ψ) = luk_implies (I ⊨ φ) (I ⊨ ψ)"
```

Here, `fun` declares a recursive function, and the five clauses handle the five constructors of the `formula` datatype. The notation $I \models \varphi$ (pronounced "I satisfies phi") matches the standard logical notation from Chapter 3.

B.2.5 Proof Automation and Sledgehammer

One of Isabelle's most powerful features is Sledgehammer, an automated proof search tool. When stuck on a proof goal, we can invoke Sledgehammer, which translates the goal into formats understood by external automated theorem provers (ATPs) and satisfiability modulo theories (SMT) solvers. If one of these tools finds a proof, Sledgehammer reconstructs the proof within Isabelle, providing a certificate that can be independently checked.

For many of the theorems in the LIMEN-AI formalisation, Sledgehammer was able to discharge the proof obligations automatically, reducing the human effort required. This is particularly effective for algebraic properties (commutativity, associativity) and routine case analyses (checking that a piecewise function is well-defined in all regions).

Some theorems still require human guidance—either because the reasoning is too subtle for the ATPs, or because the proof hinges on a specific sequence of intermediate steps that automated tools do not discover. In those cases, structured Isar proofs are written by hand, with Sledgehammer filling in routine sub-goals.

B.3 Overview of the Formalisation

Four Isabelle theory files make up the formalisation, layered to mirror the mathematical framework.

B.3.1 Theory 1: Fundamental Operations

Purpose. This theory defines the four basic Łukasiewicz operations (negation, conjunction, disjunction, implication) and establishes their fundamental properties: well-formedness (preservation of the $[0, 1]$ interval) and boundary behaviour (interaction with the constants 0 and 1).

Key Definitions.

- `valid_truth`: Predicate constraining truth degrees to $[0, 1]$.

$$\text{valid_truth}(a) \equiv 0 \leq a \wedge a \leq 1$$

- `luk_not`: Łukasiewicz negation.

$$\neg_{\mathbb{L}} a = 1 - a$$

- `luk_and`: Łukasiewicz t-norm (conjunction).

$$a \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} b = \max(0, \min(1, a + b - 1))$$

- `luk_or`: Łukasiewicz t-conorm (disjunction).

$$a \vee_{\mathbb{L}} b = \min(1, \max(0, a + b))$$

- `luk_implies`: Łukasiewicz implication.

$$a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b = \min(1, \max(0, 1 - a + b))$$

Note: The additional $\min(1, \dots)$ and $\max(0, \dots)$ wrappers in the definitions ensure that results are always clamped to $[0, 1]$, even if intermediate calculations exceed

the interval (which can happen due to floating-point rounding in the Isabelle real number model).

Key Theorems (19 total). Well-formedness (4 theorems):

- `luk_not_valid`: $\text{valid_truth}(a) \implies \text{valid_truth}(\neg_{\mathbb{L}} a)$
- `luk_and_valid`: $\text{valid_truth}(a) \wedge \text{valid_truth}(b) \implies \text{valid_truth}(a \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} b)$
- `luk_or_valid`: $\text{valid_truth}(a) \wedge \text{valid_truth}(b) \implies \text{valid_truth}(a \vee_{\mathbb{L}} b)$
- `luk_implies_valid`: $\text{valid_truth}(a) \wedge \text{valid_truth}(b) \implies \text{valid_truth}(a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b)$

These theorems guarantee that Łukasiewicz operations cannot produce invalid outputs when given valid inputs, ensuring type safety.

Boundary conditions (11 theorems):

- `luk_and_zero_left`: $\text{valid_truth}(a) \implies 0 \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} a = 0$
- `luk_and_one_left`: $\text{valid_truth}(a) \implies 1 \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} a = a$
- `luk_or_zero_left`: $\text{valid_truth}(a) \implies 0 \vee_{\mathbb{L}} a = a$
- `luk_or_one_left`: $\text{valid_truth}(a) \implies 1 \vee_{\mathbb{L}} a = 1$
- `luk_not_involutive`: $\text{valid_truth}(a) \implies \neg_{\mathbb{L}}(\neg_{\mathbb{L}} a) = a$
- `luk_implies_reflexive`: $\text{valid_truth}(a) \implies a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} a = 1$
- `luk_implies_one_right`: $\text{valid_truth}(a) \implies a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} 1 = 1$
- (4 additional boundary theorems for edge cases)

These theorems characterise the behaviour of operations at the boundaries of the truth degree interval, ensuring alignment with classical Boolean logic (where 0 represents false and 1 represents true).

Involutivity and reflexivity (4 theorems):

- Double negation cancels.
- Implication is reflexive.
- Implications with constant consequents.

Proof Techniques. Most proofs in this theory are straightforward. Well-formedness is proven by unfolding definitions and applying arithmetic reasoning about inequalities (if $a, b \in [0, 1]$, then $\max(0, a+b-1) \in [0, 1]$). Boundary conditions are proven by substituting the boundary value (e.g., $a = 0$) and simplifying.

B.3.2 Theory 2: Algebraic Laws

Purpose. Here the algebraic structure of Łukasiewicz logic is established: commutativity, associativity, monotonicity, and De Morgan laws. These properties underpin formula manipulation (e.g., normalisation) and reasoning about how the energy function behaves under perturbations.

Key Theorems (16 total). Commutativity (2 theorems):

- `luk_and_commutative`: $a \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} b = b \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} a$
- `luk_or_commutative`: $a \vee_{\mathbb{L}} b = b \vee_{\mathbb{L}} a$

Associativity (2 theorems):

- `luk_and_associative`: $(a \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} b) \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} c = a \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} (b \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} c)$
- `luk_or_associative`: $(a \vee_{\mathbb{L}} b) \vee_{\mathbb{L}} c = a \vee_{\mathbb{L}} (b \vee_{\mathbb{L}} c)$

Monotonicity (7 theorems):

- `luk_and_monotonic_left`: $a_1 \leq a_2 \implies a_1 \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} b \leq a_2 \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} b$
- `luk_and_monotonic_right`: (similar for right argument)
- `luk_or_monotonic_left/right`: (similar for disjunction)
- `luk_not_antimonotonic`: $a_1 \leq a_2 \implies \neg_{\mathbb{L}} a_2 \leq \neg_{\mathbb{L}} a_1$
- `luk_implies_antimonotonic_left`: $a_1 \leq a_2 \implies a_2 \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b \leq a_1 \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b$
- `luk_implies_monotonic_right`: $b_1 \leq b_2 \implies a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b_1 \leq a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b_2$

Monotonicity matters directly for gradient-based learning: raising an atom's truth degree can only raise (or leave unchanged) the satisfaction of formulas built from that atom via conjunction or disjunction.

De Morgan laws (2 theorems):

- `luk_demorgan_and`: $\neg_{\mathbb{L}}(a \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} b) = (\neg_{\mathbb{L}} a) \vee_{\mathbb{L}} (\neg_{\mathbb{L}} b)$
- `luk_demorgan_or`: $\neg_{\mathbb{L}}(a \vee_{\mathbb{L}} b) = (\neg_{\mathbb{L}} a) \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} (\neg_{\mathbb{L}} b)$

Implication properties (3 theorems):

- `luk_implies_via_or`: $a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b = (\neg_{\mathbb{L}} a) \vee_{\mathbb{L}} b$
- `luk_modus_ponens`: $a = 1 \wedge a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b = 1 \implies b = 1$
- `luk_implies_transitive`: $a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b = 1 \wedge b \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} c = 1 \implies a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} c = 1$

Proof Techniques. Commutativity and De Morgan laws are proven by unfolding definitions and applying algebraic simplification. Associativity requires case analysis on the regions of the piecewise linear functions (e.g., when is $a + b - 1 > 0$?). Monotonicity is proven by arithmetic reasoning over inequalities, using the fact that max and min preserve order.

B.3.3 Theory 3: Semantics and Energy

Purpose. This theory formalises first-order formula semantics under Łukasiewicz interpretation, defines the satisfaction-degree function, and establishes energy-function properties. It connects the atomic operations (Theories 1–2) with the formula-level reasoning that LIMEN-AI requires.

Key Definitions.

- `interp`: Type of fuzzy interpretations (functions from atom IDs to truth degrees).

`type_synonym interp = atom_id \Rightarrow truth_degree`

- `valid_interp`: Predicate ensuring all assigned truth degrees are in $[0, 1]$.
- `formula`: Inductive datatype for formulas.
- `satisfaction`: Recursive function computing the satisfaction degree of a formula under an interpretation.
- `equiv`: Semantic equivalence (two formulas are equivalent if they have the same satisfaction degree under all interpretations).

- **energy**: The energy function for a list of weighted formulas.

$$\text{energy}(I, [(\varphi_1, w_1), \dots, (\varphi_n, w_n)]) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot (I \models \varphi_i)$$

Key Theorems (15 total). Well-formedness of satisfaction (1 theorem):

- **satisfaction_valid**: $\text{valid_interp}(I) \implies \text{valid_truth}(I \models \varphi)$

This theorem ensures that formula evaluation cannot produce invalid truth degrees, providing type safety at the formula level.

Satisfaction computation (definitional equations from the recursive `fun satisfaction` declaration):

- **satisfaction_Atom**: $I \models \text{Atom}(a) = I(a)$
- **satisfaction_Not**: $I \models \neg\varphi = 1 - (I \models \varphi)$
- **satisfaction_And**: $I \models (\varphi \wedge \psi) = \max(0, (I \models \varphi) + (I \models \psi) - 1)$
- **satisfaction_Or**: $I \models (\varphi \vee \psi) = \min(1, (I \models \varphi) + (I \models \psi))$
- **satisfaction_Implies**: $I \models (\varphi \rightarrow \psi) = \min(1, 1 - (I \models \varphi) + (I \models \psi))$

These five equations are definitional: they follow directly from the recursive function definition and are not counted among the proven theorems.

Equivalence relation (3 theorems):

- **equiv_reflexive**: $\varphi \equiv_{\mathbb{L}} \varphi$
- **equiv_symmetric**: $\varphi \equiv_{\mathbb{L}} \psi \implies \psi \equiv_{\mathbb{L}} \varphi$
- **equiv_transitive**: $\varphi \equiv_{\mathbb{L}} \psi \wedge \psi \equiv_{\mathbb{L}} \chi \implies \varphi \equiv_{\mathbb{L}} \chi$

Formula-level laws (4 theorems):

- **demorgan_and_formula**: $\neg(\varphi \wedge \psi) \equiv_{\mathbb{L}} (\neg\varphi) \vee (\neg\psi)$
- **demorgan_or_formula**: $\neg(\varphi \vee \psi) \equiv_{\mathbb{L}} (\neg\varphi) \wedge (\neg\psi)$
- **double_negation_formula**: $\neg(\neg\varphi) \equiv_{\mathbb{L}} \varphi$
- **implies_via_or_formula**: $\varphi \rightarrow \psi \equiv_{\mathbb{L}} (\neg\varphi) \vee \psi$

These lift the operation-level laws to the formula level, enabling formula transformations during normalisation.

Energy function properties (7 lemmas):

- **energy_linear**: $\text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F}_1 @ \mathcal{F}_2) = \text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F}_1) + \text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F}_2)$
(Concatenating formula lists sums their energies.)
- **energy_scaling**: $\text{energy}(I, \text{map } (\lambda(\varphi, w).(\varphi, c \cdot w)) \mathcal{F}) = c \cdot \text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F})$
(Scaling all weights scales the total energy.)
- **energy_full_satisfaction**: $(\forall(\varphi, w) \in \mathcal{F}. I \models \varphi = 1) \implies \text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F}) = \sum w$
(If all formulas are fully satisfied, energy equals the sum of weights.)
- **abs_mult_le**: $|w| \leq W \wedge 0 \leq x \leq 1 \implies |w \cdot x| \leq W$
(Helper lemma bounding the contribution of a single weighted truth degree.)
- **energy_bounded**: $(\forall(\varphi, w) \in \mathcal{F}. |w| \leq W) \implies |\text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F})| \leq |\mathcal{F}| \cdot W$
(Energy is bounded by the number of formulas times the maximum weight.)
- **energy_nonneg**: $(\forall(\varphi, w) \in \mathcal{F}. w \geq 0) \implies \text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F}) \geq 0$
(Non-negative weights yield non-negative energy.)
- **energy_equiv**: $\varphi \equiv_{\mathcal{L}} \psi \implies \text{energy}(I, [(\varphi, w)]) = \text{energy}(I, [(\psi, w)])$
(Equivalent formulas contribute identical energy.)

These properties formalise the claims in Chapter 3 about the energy function’s linearity (Theorem 3.1) and its suitability for gradient-based optimisation.

Proof Techniques. Formula-level proofs use structural induction on the `formula` datatype. Energy function proofs use list induction on the list of weighted formulas, combined with arithmetic reasoning about sums and products.

B.3.4 Theory 4: Piecewise Linearity (`Piecewise_Linearity.thy`)

Purpose. This theory formalises the piecewise linearity of the individual Łukasiewicz connectives, directly verifying Theorem 3.2 of Chapter 3. Unlike the algebraic properties in Theories 1–3, piecewise linearity is a structural result specific to LIMEN-AI’s choice of semantics: it establishes that each connective decomposes into

at most two affine regions separated by a single hyperplane boundary, underpinning the differentiability corollaries used for gradient-based learning.

Definition.

- `piecewise_linear_2`: A function f is *piecewise linear with threshold c* if there exist coefficients a_1, b_1, a_2, b_2 such that $f(x) = a_1x + b_1$ for $x \leq c$ and $f(x) = a_2x + b_2$ for $x > c$.

Key Theorems (5 total).

- `luk_and_piecewise`: For fixed $b \in [0, 1]$, λa . $a \sqcap_{\mathbb{L}} b$ is piecewise linear with threshold $1 - b$. Below the threshold: 0; above: $a + b - 1$.
- `luk_or_piecewise`: For fixed $b \in [0, 1]$, λa . $a \sqcup_{\mathbb{L}} b$ is piecewise linear with threshold $1 - b$. Below: $a + b$; above: 1.
- `luk_not_piecewise`: Negation λa . $\neg_{\mathbb{L}} a = 1 - a$ is globally linear, hence trivially piecewise linear with any threshold.
- `luk_implies_piecewise`: For fixed $b \in [0, 1]$, λa . $a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b$ is piecewise linear with threshold b . Below: 1; above: $1 - a + b$.
- `luk_operations_piecewise_linear`: A summary theorem establishing that all four connectives satisfy the piecewise-linearity property.

Significance. These theorems verify the base case of Theorem 3.2 mechanically. The inductive extension to compound formulas (Theorem 3.3) remains a paper proof; its base case—that each connective is piecewise linear—is now machine-checked, eliminating the possibility of an error in the algebraic decomposition that would invalidate the inductive argument.

Proof Techniques. Each proof proceeds by case analysis on the `max/min` breakpoint, using Isabelle’s real arithmetic automation to establish the affine coefficients in each region. The proofs are short (3–5 lines each) because the `auto` and `simp` tactics handle the arithmetic directly.

B.3.5 Summary: 55 Theorems Across 4 Theories

The complete formalisation consists of:

- **Theory 1:** 19 theorems (operations and boundaries)
- **Theory 2:** 16 theorems (algebraic laws)
- **Theory 3:** 15 theorems (formulas and energy)
- **Theory 4:** 5 theorems (piecewise linearity)
- **Total:** 55 mechanically verified theorems

All theorems have been checked by Isabelle’s proof engine. The formalisation can be built from source using:

```
cd thesis/formal/  
isabelle build -D .
```

The theories are publicly available and can be inspected, modified, or extended by future researchers.

B.4 Selected Proof Walkthroughs

Six representative proofs are walked through below, covering well-formedness, commutativity, De Morgan laws, energy linearity, associativity, and monotonicity. Each walkthrough pairs the Isabelle script with a natural-language explanation so that readers without Isabelle experience can follow the reasoning.

B.4.1 Proof 1: Well-Formedness of Conjunction

```
lemma luk_and_valid:  
  assumes "valid_truth a" "valid_truth b"  
  shows "valid_truth (luk_and a b)"
```

Informal Proof Sketch. We must show that if $a, b \in [0, 1]$, then $\max(0, \min(1, a + b - 1)) \in [0, 1]$.

Let $s = a + b - 1$. Since $a, b \in [0, 1]$, we have $-1 \leq s \leq 1$.

Case 1: $s \leq 0$. Then $\min(1, s) = s \leq 0$, so $\max(0, \min(1, s)) = 0 \in [0, 1]$.

Case 2: $0 < s \leq 1$. Then $\min(1, s) = s$, so $\max(0, \min(1, s)) = s \in (0, 1] \subseteq [0, 1]$.

Case 3: $s > 1$. This is impossible since $s = a + b - 1 \leq 1 + 1 - 1 = 1$ when $a, b \leq 1$.

Thus, in all cases, $\max(0, \min(1, s)) \in [0, 1]$.

```
proof -
  have "0 ≤ a" "a ≤ 1" "0 ≤ b" "b ≤ 1"
    using assms unfolding valid_truth_def by auto
  have "a + b - 1 ≤ 1"
    using 'a ≤ 1' 'b ≤ 1' by simp
  have "luk_and a b = max 0 (min 1 (a + b - 1))"
    unfolding luk_and_def by simp
  also have "... ≥ 0"
    by simp
  also have "max 0 (min 1 (a + b - 1)) ≤ 1"
    using 'a + b - 1 ≤ 1' by simp
  finally show ?thesis
    unfolding valid_truth_def by simp
qed
```

Explanation. The proof begins by extracting the four inequalities ($0 \leq a \leq 1$, $0 \leq b \leq 1$) from the assumptions. It then unfolds the definition of `luk_and`, obtaining the expression $\max(0, \min(1, a + b - 1))$. The proof establishes that this expression is ≥ 0 (trivially, since $\max(0, x) \geq 0$ for any x) and ≤ 1 (using the fact that $a + b - 1 \leq 1$, hence $\min(1, a + b - 1) \leq 1$, and $\max(0, y) \leq 1$ when $y \leq 1$). Combining these, the result follows by the definition of `valid_truth`.

Isabelle's simplifier completes the proof automatically once the definitions are unfolded. The case analysis in the informal sketch above is handled implicitly by the simplifier's reasoning about `max` and `min`.

B.4.2 Proof 2: Commutativity of Conjunction

```
lemma luk_and_commutative:
  assumes "valid_truth a" "valid_truth b"
  shows "luk_and a b = luk_and b a"
```

Informal Proof Sketch. By definition, $a \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} b = \max(0, \min(1, a + b - 1))$ and $b \wedge_{\mathbb{L}} a = \max(0, \min(1, b + a - 1))$. Since addition is commutative ($a + b = b + a$), the two expressions are identical.

```
unfolding luk_and_def using assms by simp
```

Explanation. This is a one-line proof. After unfolding the definition of `luk_and`, Isabelle’s simplifier recognises that $a + b = b + a$ (addition is commutative), and the proof is complete. The assumptions `valid_truth a` and `valid_truth b` are not explicitly needed for this proof (commutativity holds for all real numbers, not just truth degrees), but we include them for consistency with other theorems.

Simple algebraic properties like this one are discharged by Isabelle’s automation with no human effort.

B.4.3 Proof 3: De Morgan Law for Conjunction

```
lemma luk_demorgan_and:
  assumes "valid_truth a" "valid_truth b"
  shows "luk_not (luk_and a b) = luk_or (luk_not a) (luk_not b)"
```

Informal Proof Sketch. We must show that $1 - \max(0, \min(1, a + b - 1)) = \min(1, \max(0, (1 - a) + (1 - b)))$.

Let $s = a + b - 1$ and $t = (1 - a) + (1 - b) = 2 - a - b = 1 - s$. We need to show:

$$1 - \max(0, \min(1, s)) = \min(1, \max(0, 1 - s))$$

Case 1: $s \leq 0$. Then $\max(0, \min(1, s)) = 0$, so $\text{LHS} = 1 - 0 = 1$. Also, $1 - s \geq 1$, so $\max(0, 1 - s) \geq 1$, hence $\min(1, \max(0, 1 - s)) = 1$. $\text{LHS} = \text{RHS}$.

Case 2: $0 < s \leq 1$. Then $\max(0, \min(1, s)) = s$, so $\text{LHS} = 1 - s$. Also, $0 \leq 1 - s < 1$, so $\max(0, 1 - s) = 1 - s$, hence $\min(1, \max(0, 1 - s)) = 1 - s$. $\text{LHS} = \text{RHS}$.

Case 3: $s > 1$. Impossible since $s = a + b - 1 \leq 1$ for $a, b \in [0, 1]$.

Thus, the law holds in all cases.

```

proof -
  have "0 ≤ a" "a ≤ 1" "0 ≤ b" "b ≤ 1"
    using assms unfolding valid_truth_def by auto
  have "luk_not (luk_and a b) = 1 - max 0 (min 1 (a + b - 1))"
    unfolding luk_not_def luk_and_def by simp
  also have "luk_or (luk_not a) (luk_not b) = min 1 (max 0 ((1-a) + (1-b)))"
    unfolding luk_or_def luk_not_def by simp
  also have "(1-a) + (1-b) = 2 - (a + b)"
    by simp
  also have "1 - max 0 (min 1 (a + b - 1)) = min 1 (max 0 (2 - (a + b)))"
    using '0 ≤ a' 'a ≤ 1' '0 ≤ b' 'b ≤ 1'
    by (simp add: max_def min_def)
  finally show ?thesis
    by simp
qed

```

Explanation. The proof unfolds all definitions, obtaining explicit arithmetic expressions. It then simplifies $(1-a)+(1-b)$ to $2-(a+b)$. The key step is the equational reasoning showing that $1 - \max(0, \min(1, a + b - 1)) = \min(1, \max(0, 2 - (a + b)))$. This is proven by case analysis on the relative magnitudes of $a + b - 1$ and 1, using the definitions of max and min. Isabelle’s simplifier handles this case analysis automatically when provided with the bounds $0 \leq a, b \leq 1$.

The final `by simp` step collapses the simplified expressions on both sides, confirming their equality.

B.4.4 Proof 4: Energy Linearity

```

lemma energy_linear:
  assumes "valid_interp I"
  shows "energy I (F1 @ F2) = energy I F1 + energy I F2"

```

Here, F1 and F2 are lists of weighted formulas, and @ denotes list concatenation.

Informal Proof Sketch. The energy function is defined as:

$$\text{energy}(I, [(\varphi_1, w_1), \dots, (\varphi_n, w_n)]) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot (I \models \varphi_i)$$

Concatenating two lists of formulas corresponds to summing their energy contributions:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F}_1 @ \mathcal{F}_2) &= \sum_{(\varphi, w) \in \mathcal{F}_1 @ \mathcal{F}_2} w \cdot (I \models \varphi) \\
&= \sum_{(\varphi, w) \in \mathcal{F}_1} w \cdot (I \models \varphi) + \sum_{(\varphi, w) \in \mathcal{F}_2} w \cdot (I \models \varphi) \\
&= \text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F}_1) + \text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F}_2)
\end{aligned}$$

This is a standard property of sums over concatenated lists.

```

proof (induction F1)
  case Nil
  show ?case by simp
next
  case (Cons f F1')
  obtain  $\varphi$  w where "f = ( $\varphi$ , w)" by (cases f) auto
  have "energy I (( $\varphi$ , w) # F1' @ F2) = w * (I  $\models$   $\varphi$ ) + energy I (F1' @ F2)"
    unfolding energy_def by simp
  also have "... = w * (I  $\models$   $\varphi$ ) + energy I F1' + energy I F2"
    using Cons.IH by simp
  also have "... = energy I (( $\varphi$ , w) # F1') + energy I F2"
    unfolding energy_def by simp
  finally show ?case
    using 'f = ( $\varphi$ , w)' by simp
qed

```

Explanation. The proof proceeds by induction on the structure of the list F1.

Base case (F1 = Nil): $\text{energy}(I, [] @ \mathcal{F}_2) = \text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F}_2) = 0 + \text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F}_2) = \text{energy}(I, []) + \text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F}_2)$. This holds trivially since the energy of an empty list is 0.

Inductive case (F1 = (φ , w) :: F1'): Assume the property holds for F1'.

We must show it holds for $(\varphi, w) :: F1'$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{energy}(I, ((\varphi, w) :: \mathcal{F}'_1) @ \mathcal{F}_2) &= w \cdot (I \models \varphi) + \text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F}'_1 @ \mathcal{F}_2) \quad (\text{definition of energy}) \\
&= w \cdot (I \models \varphi) + \text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F}'_1) + \text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F}_2) \quad (\text{induction hypothesis}) \\
&= \text{energy}(I, (\varphi, w) :: \mathcal{F}'_1) + \text{energy}(I, \mathcal{F}_2) \quad (\text{definition of energy})
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, the property holds by induction.

This proof demonstrates structural induction on lists, a common technique in Isabelle. The induction hypothesis (that the property holds for the tail of the list) is used to establish the property for the full list.

B.4.5 Proof 5: Associativity of Conjunction

```
lemma luk_and_associative:
```

```
  assumes "valid_truth a" "valid_truth b" "valid_truth c"
  shows "luk_and (luk_and a b) c = luk_and a (luk_and b c)"
```

Informal Proof Sketch. We must show that $(a \wedge_E b) \wedge_E c = a \wedge_E (b \wedge_E c)$ for all $a, b, c \in [0, 1]$.

By definition:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{LHS} &= \max(0, \min(1, \max(0, \min(1, a + b - 1)) + c - 1)) \\
\text{RHS} &= \max(0, \min(1, a + \max(0, \min(1, b + c - 1)) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

The proof requires careful case analysis on the intermediate values. Let $s_1 = a + b - 1$ and $s_2 = b + c - 1$. We distinguish cases based on whether s_1 and s_2 are positive or negative.

Case 1: $s_1 \leq 0$ and $s_2 \leq 0$. Then $\max(0, \min(1, s_1)) = 0$ and $\max(0, \min(1, s_2)) = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{LHS} &= \max(0, \min(1, 0 + c - 1)) = \max(0, \min(1, c - 1)) = 0 \quad (\text{since } c \leq 1) \\
\text{RHS} &= \max(0, \min(1, a + 0 - 1)) = \max(0, \min(1, a - 1)) = 0 \quad (\text{since } a \leq 1)
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\text{LHS} = \text{RHS} = 0$.

Case 2: $s_1 > 0$ and $s_2 > 0$. Then $a + b > 1$ and $b + c > 1$.

Sub-case 2a: $s_1 \leq 1$ and $s_2 \leq 1$. Then $\max(0, \min(1, s_1)) = s_1$ and $\max(0, \min(1, s_2)) = s_2$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LHS} &= \max(0, \min(1, s_1 + c - 1)) = \max(0, \min(1, (a + b - 1) + c - 1)) \\ &= \max(0, \min(1, a + b + c - 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{RHS} &= \max(0, \min(1, a + s_2 - 1)) = \max(0, \min(1, a + (b + c - 1) - 1)) \\ &= \max(0, \min(1, a + b + c - 2)) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\text{LHS} = \text{RHS}$.

Sub-case 2b: $s_1 > 1$. Then $a + b > 2$, which implies $a, b > 1 - \epsilon$ for some $\epsilon < 0.5$. In this case, $\min(1, s_1) = 1$, so:

$$\text{LHS} = \max(0, \min(1, 1 + c - 1)) = \max(0, \min(1, c)) = c$$

Similarly, if $s_2 > 1$, RHS simplifies. The full case analysis shows that both sides equal $a + b + c - 2$ (clamped to $[0, 1]$) in all cases.

The remaining cases (mixed signs of s_1, s_2) follow similar reasoning. The key insight is that the nested max and min operations "telescope" due to the associativity of addition: $(a + b) + c = a + (b + c)$.

proof -

```
have "0 ≤ a" "a ≤ 1" "0 ≤ b" "b ≤ 1" "0 ≤ c" "c ≤ 1"
```

```
using assms unfolding valid_truth_def by auto
```

```
have lhs: "luk_and (luk_and a b) c = max 0 (min 1 (max 0 (min 1 (a + b - 1)) + c - 1))"
```

```
unfolding luk_and_def by simp
```

```
have rhs: "luk_and a (luk_and b c) = max 0 (min 1 (a + max 0 (min 1 (b + c - 1)) - 1))"
```

```
unfolding luk_and_def by simp
```

```
show ?thesis
```

```
proof (cases "a + b ≤ 1")
```

```

case True
then have "max 0 (min 1 (a + b - 1)) = 0"
  using '0 ≤ a' '0 ≤ b' by (simp add: max_def min_def)
show ?thesis
proof (cases "b + c ≤ 1")
  case True
  then have "max 0 (min 1 (b + c - 1)) = 0"
    using '0 ≤ b' '0 ≤ c' by (simp add: max_def min_def)
  show ?thesis
    using lhs rhs 'max 0 (min 1 (a + b - 1)) = 0' 'max 0 (min 1 (b + c - 1))
= 0'
      'a ≤ 1' 'c ≤ 1'
    by (simp add: max_def min_def)
next
  case False
  then have "a + b ≤ 1" "b + c > 1"
    using 'a + b ≤ 1' by simp_all
  have "a + b + c - 2 ≤ a + 1 + c - 2"
    using 'b ≤ 1' by simp
  show ?thesis
    using lhs rhs 'a + b ≤ 1' 'b + c > 1' '0 ≤ a' 'a ≤ 1' '0 ≤ b' 'b ≤ 1'
'0 ≤ c' 'c ≤ 1'
    by (simp add: max_def min_def)
qed
next
  case False
  then have "a + b > 1"
    by simp
  show ?thesis
  proof (cases "b + c ≤ 1")
    case True
    show ?thesis
      using lhs rhs 'a + b > 1' 'b + c ≤ 1' '0 ≤ a' 'a ≤ 1' '0 ≤ b' 'b ≤ 1'
'0 ≤ c' 'c ≤ 1'
      by (simp add: max_def min_def)
  next
    case False
    then have "a + b > 1" "b + c > 1"
      using 'a + b > 1' by simp_all
    have "max 0 (min 1 (a + b - 1)) = min 1 (a + b - 1)"

```

```

    using 'a + b > 1' by (simp add: max_def)
  have "max 0 (min 1 (b + c - 1)) = min 1 (b + c - 1)"
    using 'b + c > 1' by (simp add: max_def)
  show ?thesis
    using lhs rhs 'a + b > 1' 'b + c > 1' '0 ≤ a' 'a ≤ 1' '0 ≤ b' 'b ≤ 1'
    '0 ≤ c' 'c ≤ 1'
    by (simp add: max_def min_def)
qed
qed
qed

```

Explanation. This proof is more involved than the previous examples, requiring explicit case analysis on whether $a + b \leq 1$ and $b + c \leq 1$. The proof is structured as nested case distinctions, mirroring the informal sketch.

In each branch, the simplifier is guided by explicitly unfolding the definitions of max and min and applying arithmetic reasoning. The key steps are:

1. Expanding the definitions of `luk_and` twice (once for each nested application).
2. Distinguishing four cases based on the signs of $a + b - 1$ and $b + c - 1$.
3. In each case, simplifying the nested max and min operations to show that both sides reduce to the same expression (either 0, or $a + b + c - 2$, clamped to $[0, 1]$).

Even properties that feel "obviously true" by algebraic intuition require explicit case-by-case reasoning in formal verification. The payoff is an exhaustive check—there is no possibility of a missed corner case.

B.4.6 Proof 6: Monotonicity of Implication

```

lemma luk_implies_monotonic_right:
  assumes "valid_truth a" "valid_truth b1" "valid_truth b2" "b1 ≤ b2"
  shows "luk_implies a b1 ≤ luk_implies a b2"

```

Informal Proof Sketch. We must show that if $b_1 \leq b_2$, then $a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b_1 \leq a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b_2$.

By definition, $a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b = \min(1, \max(0, 1 - a + b))$. Let $s_1 = 1 - a + b_1$ and $s_2 = 1 - a + b_2$. Since $b_1 \leq b_2$, we have $s_1 \leq s_2$.

Case 1: $s_1, s_2 \geq 1$. Then $\min(1, \max(0, s_1)) = 1$ and $\min(1, \max(0, s_2)) = 1$, so the inequality holds trivially.

Case 2: $s_1, s_2 \leq 0$. Then $\min(1, \max(0, s_i)) = 0$ for $i = 1, 2$, so again the inequality holds.

Case 3: $s_1 \leq 0 < s_2 < 1$. Then $a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b_1 = 0 \leq s_2 = a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b_2$.

Case 4: $0 < s_1 < s_2 < 1$. Then $a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b_1 = s_1 \leq s_2 = a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b_2$ by the assumption $s_1 \leq s_2$.

Case 5: $0 < s_1 < 1 \leq s_2$. Then $a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b_1 = s_1 < 1 = a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b_2$.

In all cases, $a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b_1 \leq a \rightarrow_{\mathbb{L}} b_2$.

proof -

```

have "0 ≤ a" "a ≤ 1" "0 ≤ b1" "b1 ≤ 1" "0 ≤ b2" "b2 ≤ 1"
  using assms unfolding valid_truth_def by auto

have "1 - a + b1 ≤ 1 - a + b2"
  using 'b1 ≤ b2' by simp

have "luk_implies a b1 = min 1 (max 0 (1 - a + b1))"
  unfolding luk_implies_def by simp
also have "... ≤ min 1 (max 0 (1 - a + b2))"
  using '1 - a + b1 ≤ 1 - a + b2'
  by (simp add: max_def min_def)
also have "... = luk_implies a b2"
  unfolding luk_implies_def by simp
finally show ?thesis .
qed

```

Explanation. This proof is more direct than the associativity proof. It unfolds the definition of `luk_implies`, obtaining the expression $\min(1, \max(0, 1 - a + b))$. It then uses the fact that `max` and `min` are monotonic functions: if $x \leq y$, then $\max(0, x) \leq \max(0, y)$ and $\min(1, x) \leq \min(1, y)$. Applying these monotonicity properties to $1 - a + b_1 \leq 1 - a + b_2$ (which follows from $b_1 \leq b_2$), we obtain the desired inequality.

The Isabelle simplifier handles the monotonicity reasoning automatically when provided with the definitions of `max` and `min`. The proof is essentially a straightforward application of order-theoretic reasoning.

Significance for Gradient-Based Learning. Monotonicity theorems like this one are essential for understanding the behaviour of gradient-based optimisation in LIMEN-AI. The theorem states that increasing the truth degree of the consequent of an implication can only increase (or leave unchanged) the satisfaction of the implication. This ensures that the gradient of the energy function with respect to consequent atoms is non-negative, preventing pathological situations where improving the satisfaction of a consequent would paradoxically decrease the overall energy.

In the context of the COLIEE benchmark (Chapter 6), monotonicity guarantees that if we increase the "relevance" of a candidate document, the satisfaction of implication rules linking premises to relevance conclusions will not decrease, aligning with the intuitive expectation that "more relevant is better."

B.4.7 Summary of Proof Techniques

The recurring techniques across these six proofs are: definitional unfolding followed by simplifier-driven algebra (`luk_and_valid`, `commutativity`); case analysis on piecewise regions (`luk_demorgan_and`, `associativity`); structural induction over datatypes (`energy_linear`); order-theoretic monotonicity reasoning (implication monotonicity); and pervasive use of Isabelle's built-in real-number arithmetic. Routine sub-goals were typically dispatched by `by simp` or `by auto`, with human effort reserved for the high-level proof skeleton. None of these techniques is specific to LIMEN-AI; they transfer to other neurosymbolic systems with comparably clean mathematical specifications.

B.5 Implications and Future Extensions

The formalisation covers the mathematical core. Extending it further would raise assurance progressively.

B.5.1 Extending Coverage to the Implementation

The mathematical definitions and properties are verified, but the Python implementation in `src/limen/` is not. Three routes could bridge this gap. Isabelle's *code extraction* generates verified OCaml or Haskell from definitions; extracting the Łukasiewicz operations, formula evaluation, and energy function and wrapping the result with Python bindings would yield provably correct core components within

the Python ecosystem. *Refinement proofs* could alternatively show that the Python code computes the same results as the Isabelle specification modulo floating-point rounding, though formalising floating-point arithmetic is non-trivial. A lighter-weight option is *property-based testing via QuickCheck*: Isabelle can generate thousands of random test cases from verified theorems (e.g., 10,000 pairs $(a, b) \in [0, 1]^2$ for commutativity), exportable into the Python CI/CD pipeline for regression testing.

Each route involves trade-offs. Code extraction requires definitions that satisfy executability criteria and must bridge the gap between Isabelle’s abstract reals and machine floating-point. QuickCheck provides empirical confidence rather than certainty, with corner-case coverage depending on the test distribution. Refinement proofs demand the greatest formalisation effort but offer the strongest guarantees. Combining QuickCheck-based regression testing (low effort, immediate value) with selective code extraction for performance-critical paths (moderate effort, high assurance) is likely the most pragmatic path forward.

B.5.2 Verifying Learning Algorithms

The convergence theorem (Theorem 3.5 in Chapter 3) is stated informally. A future extension could formalise stochastic gradient descent in Isabelle, proving convergence under the Robbins–Monro conditions. The required formalisations would include:

- Sequences and limits.
- Probability distributions and expectations (using Isabelle’s `Probability` library).
- The concavity of the log-likelihood.
- The Robbins-Monro convergence theorem.

Such a result would provide end-to-end assurance for the learning process, not only the logic layer.

B.5.3 Formalising Inference Algorithms

The sampling algorithms (Gibbs sampling, Metropolis–Hastings, power tempering) of Chapter 4 have probabilistic correctness properties—e.g., that the Markov chain converges to the target distribution. Formalising them in Isabelle would require:

- Markov chain theory (stationary distributions, detailed balance, ergodicity).
- Measure-theoretic probability (to handle continuous state spaces).
- Proofs that the sampling update rules satisfy detailed balance.

A significant undertaking, but one that would establish theoretical soundness for the inference algorithms beyond empirical evidence alone.

B.5.4 Integration with Other Proof Assistants

Other proof assistants—Coq, Lean, Agda—bring different strengths. Coq has strong support for dependent types and constructive mathematics; Lean has an active community formalising mathematics and is designed for ease of use. Future work could port the LIMEN-AI formalisation to one of these systems, or establish interoperability between proof assistants to reuse verified libraries.

Concretely, Coq’s `Coquelicot` library provides formalised real analysis (limits, derivatives, integrals), and its `Ltac2` tactic language offers more flexible automation than `Isar`; porting would also open Coq’s verified-compilation ecosystem. Lean’s `mathlib` library exceeds one million lines of formalised mathematics, and Lean 4’s metaprogramming support lends itself to generating proofs from domain-specific patterns. Agda’s dependent types enable more abstract formulations, though the community is smaller for numerical work. Porting—or establishing translation via a framework such as `Dedukti`—would add cross-checking confidence, since bugs in one proof assistant are unlikely to recur in another.

B.5.5 Verification of End-to-End System Properties

The most ambitious extension would verify end-to-end system properties spanning multiple components (logic layer, learning algorithm, inference algorithm, application-level reasoning). Examples include:

Soundness of case law retrieval. Prove that if the LIMEN-AI re-ranker outputs document d as relevant to query q , then d satisfies certain logical criteria (e.g., it cites cases relevant to q , or it addresses legal issues present in q). This would require formalising the legal reasoning domain (case law precedents, legal concepts, citation relationships) and proving that the knowledge base rules correctly capture legal expertise.

Such a proof would have the form:

$$\forall q, d. \text{rank}(d, q) > \theta \longrightarrow \exists \text{formula } \varphi \in \mathcal{K}. \varphi \text{ justifies relevance of } d \text{ to } q$$

This property ensures that every high-ranking result has an explicit logical justification grounded in the knowledge base—precisely the transparency requirement of EU AI Act Article 13.

Robustness to adversarial inputs. Prove that small perturbations to atom truth degrees result in small changes to the energy function, ensuring that the system is not brittle. Formally, this is a Lipschitz continuity property:

$$\forall I_1, I_2, \mathbf{w}. \|I_1 - I_2\|_\infty \leq \epsilon \longrightarrow |E(I_1; \mathbf{w}) - E(I_2; \mathbf{w})| \leq L \cdot \epsilon$$

where L is the Lipschitz constant.

For LIMEN-AI, L is bounded by the sum of absolute weights: $L \leq \sum_i |w_i|$. This follows from the linearity and boundedness of the energy function (Theorem 3.1). Formalising and proving this property would provide a quantitative robustness guarantee: small errors in input features (due to sensor noise, measurement uncertainty, or adversarial perturbations) cannot cause large swings in predictions.

Privacy preservation. If interpretations contain sensitive data (e.g., user profiles, financial records), prove that the system satisfies differential privacy guarantees: an adversary observing the system’s outputs cannot infer the presence or absence of a particular individual’s data. Differential privacy is a well-established framework with existing Isabelle formalisations (e.g., in the `Differential_Privacy` AFP entry).

For LIMEN-AI, one would prove that the inference algorithms (e.g., noisy gradient descent for weight learning) satisfy (ϵ, δ) -differential privacy: the probability distribution over outputs changes by at most a factor e^ϵ (plus δ) when a single individual’s data is added or removed from the training set.

Such proofs would require formalising domain ontologies (legal concepts, cybersecurity threats) and may depend on real-world assumptions—e.g., that training data is representative—that are themselves hard to verify. End-to-end properties may also be undecidable or intractable for realistic system sizes. Even partial results, though, would raise assurance enough that regulatory compliance can be demonstrated by

construction rather than by empirical evidence alone.

B.5.6 Roadmap for Future Formalisation Work

A plausible phased roadmap would proceed as follows. Phase 1 (6–12 months): integrate QuickCheck-based property testing into the Python CI/CD pipeline. Phase 2 (1–2 years): extract the core Łukasiewicz operations into verified code, wrapped with Python bindings. Phase 3 (2–3 years): formalise stochastic gradient descent convergence under realistic assumptions (mini-batch sampling, momentum). Phase 4 (3+ years, research frontier): end-to-end soundness and robustness proofs spanning the full pipeline from knowledge-base design to prediction output. Each phase delivers standalone value while preparing the ground for the next.

B.6 Summary

The 55 mechanically checked theorems—covering well-formedness ($[0, 1]$ preservation), algebraic laws (commutativity, associativity, monotonicity, De Morgan), semantic correctness of formula evaluation, energy-function properties (linearity, boundedness, scaling), and piecewise linearity—serve three roles at once: a specification for the implementation, a transparency artefact for regulatory compliance, and a foundation for future extensions. They underpin every mathematical claim in Chapter 3 and provide assurance that empirical testing alone cannot match.